

publisher.agency
Finland

October, 2023

No 4

Helsinki, Finland
5-6.10.2023

International
Scientific
Conference

Academics and Science Reviews Materials

UDC 001.1

P 97

Publisher.agency : Proceedings of the 4th International Scientific Conference «Academics and Science Reviews Materials» (October 5-6, 2023). Helsinki, Finland, 2023. 239p

ISBN 978-0-9706-3041-4

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.8419476

Editor: Sari Selänne, Professor, University of Helsinki

International Editorial Board:

Petri Huusko

Professor, Åbo Akademi University

Seija Turunen

Professor, University of Turku

Olavi Korpela

Professor, University of Jyväskylä

Mikko Ruonakoski

Professor, University of Oulu

Daniel Luiro

Professor, University of Vaasa

Eetu Granroth

Professor, University of Lapland

Leevi Tuominen

Professor, University of Eastern Finland

Tarja Laitinen

Professor, Aalto University

Janne Kontkanen

Professor, Tampere University

Tiina Tikkala

Professor, Arcada University of Applied Sciences

Juhani Mäkinen

Professor, Diaconia University of Applied Science

Olavi Mella

Professor, University of Eastern Finland

Lily Kontkanen

Professor, Seinajoki University of Applied Sciences

Eeva Selänne

Professor, Lut University

editor@publisher.agency

<https://publisher.agency/>

Table of Contents

Philosophical Sciences

ABOUT PHILOSOPHICAL AND AESTHETIC PROBLEMS OF ARTISTIC CREATIVITY	6
---	---

KANKULOVA ASEM BOKAIKHANOVA

Economic Sciences

THE IMPACT OF INFLATIONARY PROCESSES ON THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF KAZAKHSTAN	11
--	----

*ASSYLBEKOV AMANBAY
ASSYLBEKOVA BAYAN*

THE EXPERIENCE OF WASTE MANAGEMENT IN THE FOOD INDUSTRY OF AZERBAIJAN	21
---	----

EMIN HUSEYNOV

THE MAIN DIRECTIONS OF SMALL BUSINESS SUPPORT BY THE STATE	28
--	----

*GARACAYEVA LALA RAMIZ
YUSIBOVA SABRIN AZER
HASANOVA AYGUN AYDIN
ALLAHVERDIYEV ALADDIN VUSAL*

FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN STIMULATING URBANISATION PROCESSES	33
--	----

*DIGEL IVAN
KOPBOSSINOVA ALUA*

ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ ИНТЕРНЕТ-МАРКЕТИНГА В ЦЕЛЯХ ПРИВЛЕЧЕНИЯ ПЕРСПЕКТИВНЫХ СТУДЕНТОВ	41
--	----

КУРМАНГАЛИЕВ АСЛАН САНЖАРОВИЧ

ПРОДВИЖЕНИЕ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ УСЛУГ ВУЗОВ ЧЕРЕЗ САЙТЫ И СОЦИАЛЬНЫЕ СЕТИ	48
---	----

КУРМАНГАЛИЕВ АСЛАН САНЖАРОВИЧ

ACCOUNTING SYMMETRIES ON DIVIDEND POLITICS BY APPLICATIONS OF ACCOUNTING METHODOLOGY OF EDGEWORTH BOX	56
---	----

MIGUEL ANGEL PÉREZ BENEDITO

МАРКЕТИНГОВЫЙ ПОДХОД К ПОВЫШЕНИЮ ЛОЯЛЬНОСТИ ПОТРЕБИТЕЛЕЙ В ИНДУСТРИИ ГОСТЕПРИИМСТВА	63
---	----

МУРАТ БАЛЖАН

ЖИЗНЕННЫЙ ЦИКЛ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ: ЭМПИРИЧЕСКИЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ И ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ПОДХОДЫ	66
---	----

САДЫКОВ АСХАТ САБЕРЖАНОВИЧ

Literature

ҚАЗІРГІ ҚАЗАҚ ПРОЗАСЫНДАҒЫ 1920-30 ЖЫЛДАРДЫҢ АШАРШЫЛЫҚ СУРЕТТЕРІ: КӨРКЕМДІК ПЕН ТАРИХТЫҢ АҚТАҢДАҚТАРЫ	70
---	----

*БИСЕК ЖАНГЕЛДИ
АКБУЛАТОВ А.А.*

AZƏRBAYCAN DİLİNİN İNKİŞAF TARİXİNDƏN	75
---	----

ABDULLAYEVA SƏMINƏ SABİR QIZI

Philological Sciences

ANTROPONİM VƏ ONUN DİL SİSTEMİNDƏ YERİ	79
--	----

ƏLİYEVƏ GÜNEL

NƏZƏRİ VƏ TƏTBİQİ DİLÇİLİK	81
----------------------------------	----

ƏSƏDOVA SEVİNC SABİR QIZI

DİALEKTOLOGİYAMIZIN MAHİR TƏDQIQATÇISI - Həsən Mirzəyev	83
---	----

GÜLNARƏ MƏMMƏDZADƏ

EDUCATION IS THE FUTURE OF THE NATION	87
---	----

ƏHMƏDOVA SEVİNC İSLAM Q.

HEYDƏR ƏLİYEV VƏ ƏDƏBİYYATIMIZ	90
--------------------------------------	----

ŞƏFƏQ ƏZİZOVA

ON THE CAUSES OF ARCHAICATION	95
-------------------------------------	----

ARZU KARIMOVA

ЯЗЫКОВЫЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ТЕКСТА ПУБЛИЦИСТИЧЕСКОГО СТИЛЯ	98
---	----

АБИЕВ БАХЫТЖАН МЫРЗАХМЕТОВИЧ

ЕСЕНҒАЛИ РАУШАНОВ ШЫҒАРМАЛАРЫНЫҢ КӨРКЕМДІК, ТАНЫМДЫҚ ЕРЕКШЕЛІКТЕРІ	108
--	-----

*ҒАЙНЕДЕН ӘСЕЛХАНЫМ ЕРСІНҚЫЗЫ
МУТИЕВ ЗИНУЛЛА ЖАҚСЫЛЫКОВИЧ*

ФАРИЗА ОҢҒАРСЫНОВА ПОЭЗИЯСЫНДАҒЫ 'ӘЙЕЛ' БОЛМЫСЫ	112
---	-----

*БАТЫРБЕК НУРЖАУСЫН МЕҢДІБЕКҚЫЗЫ
МУТИЕВ ЗИНУЛЛА ЖАҚСЫЛЫКОВИЧ*

Historical Sciences

HEYDAR ALIYEV'S STATE CONCERN FOR AZERBAIJANI SPORTS	117
--	-----

TƏRANƏ AĞARZA QIZI HƏMZƏBƏYOVA

THE COLONIAL CHARACTER OF SOVIET STATEHOOD IN KAZAKHSTAN: THE SYSTEM OF GOVERNANCE	120
--	-----

ABIL YERKIN

KUZEMBAYULY AMANZHOL

WHAT IS THE CONCEPT OF PATRIOTISM?	125
<i>RÖVŞƏN ZAKİR OĞLU QULİYEV</i>	
Pedagogical Sciences	
SPORT IS THE FOUNDATION OF HEALTH	127
<i>ŞAHƏDDİN ASLAN OĞLU NƏRİMANOV</i>	
МОДЕРНИЗАЦИЯ НАУЧНЫХ СТУДЕНЧЕСКИХ КОНФЕРЕНЦИЙ, КАК ФАКТОР ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЗАИНТЕРЕСОВАННОСТИ СТУДЕНТОВ ВУЗов Республики КАЗАХСТАН К НАУЧНО-ИССЛЕДОВАТЕЛЬСКОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ	129
<i>БОРИСОВ А.А. БАШИРОВ А.В. ХАНОВ Т.А.</i>	
STUDENTS IN THE TEACHING OF LITERARY LANGUAGE NORMS ENSURING COGNITIVE ACTIVITY	133
<i>SEVDA İSLAM GİZİ ABBASOVA</i>	
ЦИФРЛЫҚ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАР НЕГІЗІНДЕ БІЛІМ АЛУШЫЛАРДЫҢ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТУАЛДЫҚ ҚАБІЛЕТІН ДАМУ ТУДЫҢ ТИІМДІ ӘДІСТЕРІ	136
<i>СМАҒУЛ БОТАКӨЗ ҚЫТАЙБАЙҚЫЗЫ</i>	
МЕТОДОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ ЕСТЕСТВЕННО-НАУЧНОЙ ГРАМОТНОСТИ УЧАЩИХСЯ В СООТВЕТСТВИИ С ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯМИ PISA В КАЗАХСТАНЕ.....	141
<i>ЖУМАГУЛОВА ҚАЛАМҒЫР АБЖАППРОВНА МАЙМАТАЕВА АСИЯ ДҮЙСЕНГАЛИЕВНА АМАНБАЕВА МАХАБАТ БАТЫРГАЛИЕВНА</i>	
ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ЗАДАНИЙ PISA НА УРОКАХ ХИМИИ ДЛЯ РАЗВИТИЯ ЧИТАТЕЛЬСКОЙ, ЕСТЕСТВЕННОНАУЧНОЙ ГРАМОТНОСТИ ШКОЛЬНИКОВ	145
<i>ГАЛЫМОВА НУРЖАНАР ГАЙСАТҚЫЗЫ МУКАТАЕВА ЖАЗИРА САГАТБЕКОВНА</i>	
Legal Sciences	
DOMESTIC CORRUPTION IN KAZAKHSTAN	149
<i>BİBIGÜL MAIOROVA</i>	
INTERPLAY OF INTERNATIONAL POLITICAL ECONOMY WITH AUTHORITARIAN REGIMES IN CENTRAL ASIA.....	153
<i>TEMİRGALİYEV YELDOS</i>	
Art History	
MÜASİR AZƏRBAYCAN MƏDƏNİYYƏTİNİN QURUCUSU	162
<i>SEYFULLAYEVA AYNUR TAHİR QIZI</i>	
Geological and Mineralogical Sciences	
DIRECT-PROSPECTING METHODS OF SATELLITE AND PHOTO IMAGES FREQUENCY-RESONANCE PROCESSING: POSSIBILITY OF APPLICATION FOR NATURAL HYDROGEN ACCUMULATIONS SEARCHING IN SPAIN	165
<i>MYKOLA YAKYMCHUK IGNAT KORCHAGIN</i>	
Technical Sciences	
THERMODYNAMICS OF SOME PHYSICAL AND CHEMICAL TRANSFORMATIONS IN POLYPHASE CERAMIC MATERIALS.....	188
<i>M. KULBEK D. BAIMOLDA E. DZHAKSIGELDINOVA G. ZHEXENBAYEVA N. AYTAN</i>	
THE NEED FOR DEVELOPING NEW TECHNOLOGIES USING CYBER-PHYSICAL SYSTEMS TO CREATE SMART FACTORIES. SYSTEMS AND INDICATORS IN KAZAKHSTAN'S INDUSTRY 4.0	197
<i>BEKET BAIGANOV</i>	
Chemical Sciences	
SYNTHESIS OF BIFUNCTIONAL CATALYSTS BASED ON MESOPOROUS ALUMINOSILICATES FOR HYDROAROMATIZATION OF MODEL COMPOUNDS	202
<i>ABDRASSILOVA ALBINA VASSILINA GULZIRA</i>	
Sociological Sciences	
DETERMINING GENDER IDENTITY AMONG BENEFICIARIES OF THE CENTER 'TEN QOGAM'	204
<i>ERKEZHAN MARAT ABAY AJDAROV AIZHAN SHABDENOVA</i>	

Medical Sciences

SKIN TOXICITY IN CHEMOTHERAPY AND ONCOLOGICAL DISEASES	213
<i>TOLYBEKOVA A.A.</i>	
<i>BAIKENZHEYEVA A.A.</i>	
ORGANIZATION OF HEMATOLOGICAL CARE IN THE REPUBLIC OF KAZAKHSTAN	219
<i>ARMAN KHOZHAYEV</i>	
<i>RAMIL VALIYEV</i>	
<i>МАКПАЛ СУЛТАН</i>	
<i>ZHUMABEK TASSYBEKOV</i>	
<i>MEIRKUL ZHUMABAIEVA</i>	
<i>AINUR RYSPEKKYZY</i>	
<i>YERLAN AMANGELDINOV</i>	
<i>RAUAN ASSYLBEK</i>	

Pharmaceutical Sciences

ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЕ ЧИСЛЕННЫХ ПОКАЗАТЕЛЕЙ СЫРЬЯ <i>VICIA NARBONENSIS</i> L.	223
<i>Т.А. ГАДЖИБЕЙЛИ</i>	
<i>Д.С. ГАФАРОВА</i>	
<i>Г.Р. ЗЕЙНАЛОВА</i>	

Biological Sciences

ВЛИЯНИЕ УСЛОВИЙ РАЗМОРАЖИВАНИЯ НА ПОКАЗАТЕЛИ ВСХОЖЕСТИ И ЭНЕРГИИ ПРОРАСТАНИЯ СЕМЯН ПОЛЫНИ ГЛАДКОЙ ЛЕКАРСТВЕННОГО	225
<i>А.М. МУРАТОВА</i>	

Veterinary Sciences

ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ ИЗМЕНЕНИЯ СПРОСА ВЛАДЕЛЬЦЕВ ДОМАШНИХ ЖИВОТНЫХ НА УСЛУГИ ПО УЧЕТУ ПИТОМЦЕВ	229
<i>БАУРЖАНОВА АСЕЛЬ БАУРЖАНОВНА</i>	

Physical and Mathematical Sciences

СПЕКТРЫ КОМБИНАЦИОННОГО РАССЕЯНИЯ ИОННО-ОБЛУЧЕННЫХ МОНОКРИСТАЛЛОВ GGG.....	233
<i>GULNARA ARALBAYEVA</i>	
<i>ZHAKYR KARIPBAYEV</i>	
<i>ANATOLI POPOV</i>	
<i>KUAT KUMARBEKOV</i>	

Culturology

THE ART OF KAZAKHSTAN AND THE CREATIVE INDUSTRY.....	236
<i>MUSSABAYEV KUAT</i>	

Philosophical Sciences

ABOUT PHILOSOPHICAL AND AESTHETIC PROBLEMS OF ARTISTIC CREATIVITY

Kankulova Asem Bokaikhanovna

Master of Philosophy, Department of General Educational Disciplines, Academy named after Barimbek Beisenov, Karaganda, Republic of Kazakhstan

Annotation: In the article, the author draws attention to one of the “eternal” problems of aesthetics - the problem of artistic Sense, which was introduced into the circle of philosophical problems in the Enlightenment. The author shows the relevance of this problem in the modern world. Having summarized the analyzed works of the most famous philosophers, thinkers, psychologists, cultural scientists in the consideration of this criterion from C. Montesquieu, A. Shaftesbury, C. Hume, G. Hegel to H. Ortega y Gasset, G. Gadamer and others. In the article by the author the philosophical idea of 20th century aesthetics about the transformation of the “sublime”, “high” in art into the art of everyday life of the 20th century is supported. The article focuses on the need to study the place and role of aesthetic Sense in the everyday culture of the 20th century. The author agrees with the conclusion of modern the culturologist and the philosopher that the mechanisms for the implementation of aesthetic Sense as a person’s creative exploration of the world have changed significantly in modern conditions.

Keywords: philosophy, aesthetics, mass society, progress, culture, art, classical aesthetics, non-classical aesthetics.

“The form of our perception is completely random, but if we were created differently, we would feel differently. If our body had more than one organ of Sense (sense)... our understanding of poetry would change” [1].

The question of aesthetic Sense, closely connected with our everyday life, problems of artistic creativity, theory and practice of aesthetics, is a traditional topic and at the same time not distinguished by terminological clarity. We propose an attempt to look not for differences, but for agreement in those different points of view that have been expressed in the history of philosophy and aesthetics. Firstly, even the simple consolidation of the concept of “aesthetic Sense” occurs only in the 17th century and at that time this term meant:

- a special, specific ability of a person to realize his aesthetic experience;
- the ability to realize aesthetic harmony of human communication with the world;
- the ability to identify the aesthetic value of any object.

Secondly, for a very long time in the science and metaphysics that made their way in the 16th-17th centuries, the concept of aesthetic Sense was associated with the physical understanding of man, his physiology, biological, animal nature. It is noteworthy that the concept of “Sense” (*gusto*) in the aesthetic sense first appeared in the seventeenth-century Spanish Writer B. Grasian in his work “Oracle in your pocket” [2]. It is from this work and this time that this term begins to widely enter the circle of philosophical problems widely and comprehensively discussed by French and English enlighteners: Montesquieu, Rousseau, Diderot, Helvetius, Shaftesbury. It is noteworthy that in this era the concept of *bon ton* dominated (the French word “*bon ton*” - good Sense) and it denoted the ability to live in a special space, where everything is subordinated to the good Sense of life. It is amazing, but it is a fact that even if a person from high society (aristocrat)

committed a crime before the law, it was not considered terrible. It was considered terrible in society if a person did something that was contrary to good aesthetic sense.

However, the Age of Enlightenment should not be understood so narrowly: works, historical and cultural events, understanding of nature, everything that was aesthetically revealed to man at the turn of the 17th-18th centuries was broad and multifaceted and required a scientific need to discuss the problem of a single criterion of artistic sense.

At the beginning of its development, the Age of Enlightenment was distinguished by the desire to understand Sense based on its sensual nature. Voltaire even wrote the work "Sense" for the "Philosophical Dictionary", in which he points out that Sense as the ability to "recognize food" is associated with Sense as "the sense of beauty and error in all arts." Along with the presence of an etymological connection between them, Voltaire points out the commonality of these feelings: immediacy and non-discursiveness. Another thinker of this era, C. Montesquieu, joined the discussion about their nature in his book "Spirit of laws".

Another approach to the problem of Sense was proposed by the English philosopher E. Burke, who was a convinced sensualist and approached the problem of man biologically. He considered the psychological properties of a person to be unchangeable, and aesthetic ideas to arise on the basis of a sense of self-preservation and a sense of sociability. In his work "A Philosophical Inquiry into the Origin of Our Ideas of the Sublime and the Beautiful" he states: "what is called Sense is not a simple concept, but it is composed of the perception of the primary pleasures of the senses, the secondary pleasures of the imagination and from the conclusions of the mind regarding the various relations between them, as well as regarding human passions, morals and actions" [3]. It is from these elements that Sense arises. The philosopher expresses doubt about the view of aesthetic judgment as instantaneous, momentary, Sense is like instinct. For example, a person is able to change his mind after using his mind, i.e. The first impression deceives a person. This is what Burke wrote about this: "...Sense (whatever it is) is improved in exactly the same way as our faculty of judgment, namely, by the extension of our knowledge, close attention to the subject, and frequent exercise."

The classification of Sense was continued by another educator, D. Diderot, who suggested that Sense consists of a special combination of three components:

- sensory perception;
- rational idea;
- emotions of experience.

Diderot wrote about sensory perception: "Deprive a sound of any secondary moral idea, and you deprive it of beauty. Keep some image on the surface of your eye so that the resulting impression does not touch either your mind or your heart, and there will be nothing beautiful in this impression." Diderot even tried to give an analysis of the genesis of Sense, which he considered in its relationship with human biological needs. And the French thinker's conclusion is that Sense appears when a person goes beyond the limits of physical necessity: "Nature requires what is necessary. Sense requires that what is necessary be endowed with an additional quality that makes it pleasant for us" [4]. This interpretation is characterized not by the opposition of different sides of Sense (sensual and rational, utilitarian and disinterested), but by their combination in some kind of interaction. The search for a dialectical moment in aesthetics is generally indicative of Diderot.

For Diderot, "Sense is the ease acquired by repeated experiences with which you perceive the true and good," "art reproduces nature; Sense determines the choice of what is reproduced" [4]. At the same time, Sense was a developing concept, dependent on social relations, socially determined.

The discussion about the problem of Sense in aesthetics receives its logical conclusion in the philosophy of I. Kant, in his work "Critique of the Power of Judgment," which occupies a special

position in the history of aesthetic thought. It is in this work that Kant carries out a critical rethinking of the aesthetic views of the Enlightenment and thereby determines the prospects for the formation of modern aesthetic theory.

The philosophical merit of Kant and his critical analysis of “pure” (theoretical) reason lies in substantiating the activity of the subject in the process of cognition. For the first time, thanks to Kant, human consciousness is considered as an activity that constructs objects and relationships between them, as a result of which a world of phenomena arises. A different picture of reality emerges, replacing the world for a person as it exists on its own, which brings together the ideological positions of I. Kant and C. Hume.

At the same time, despite the similarity of the positions of the two named great thinkers and philosophers, Kant believed that truth is not a purely subjective content of consciousness, because the acquired knowledge allows for its practical use. Kant thus poses the problem of the essence of true knowledge in a new way. Kant understands knowledge as a synthesis of sensibility and reason in the activity of imagination and, therefore, a unified subject-conceptual knowledge arises.

In his logic of philosophical reasoning, Kant completely innovatively poses the question of comprehending beauty as the main category of aesthetics: not what should be an object that can be called beautiful, but what should be the ability of the subject so that beauty can be revealed to him. Kant's work “Analyst of the Beautiful” therefore represents a definition of beauty through the basic characteristics of aesthetic judgment, i.e. sense.

Let's consider Kant's understanding of beauty: beauty is an object of taste as the ability to judge on the basis of pleasure, free from any interest, which the philosopher calls “favor.” This is his first definition of beauty. Kant gives the second definition of beauty through the characteristic of the judgment of taste ‘by quantity’, i.e. according to the degree of universality of aesthetic judgment. This is what he writes: “What is beautiful is what everyone likes without a concept” [5].

At the same time, it is worth noting that aesthetic reflection has a subjective purpose for Kant: to preserve the very state of the play of imagination and reason, to set in motion the cognitive abilities and thereby initiate the act of cognition and the desire to establish a connection between the world of nature and the world of freedom. And here is another definition of beauty that Kant gives through the category of taste: “according to modality,” i.e. according to the degree of necessity of pleasure from the subject of judgment. Since aesthetic judgment is carried out with the participation of the transcendental abilities of imagination and reason, the state of pleasure from their play and combinations also has universality, is a “general feeling”: “Beauty is a form of purposiveness of an object, since it is perceived in it without the idea of a goal” [5].

Unlike other thinkers, Kant calls this state not a motivation for aesthetic judgment, but the basis of the process of reflection, indicating that the judgment of taste has taken place: “What is beautiful is that which is known without the medium of a concept as an object of necessary pleasure.” [5].

It was the great philosopher Kant who first defined pleasure from aesthetic reflection as a necessary characteristic of taste. According to Kant, beauty is the objective layer of the surrounding world, which is perceived by the subject of aesthetic judgment when it corresponds to the basic parameters of taste. Contemplation of beauty causes aesthetic reflection to strive towards the world of moral meanings, but does not achieve them, therefore, according to Kant, there is another aesthetic sphere where reflective judgment seems to close the connection between nature and moral freedom. And this is expressed by the category of aesthetics “sublime”, “high”.

This main problem of taste - its subjective-objective nature, was intuitively understood by almost all thinkers who wrote about taste as a criterion for assessing beauty. The only problem was to express this understanding through discourse. If we are historically objective, then from

the height of time we have the right to criticize Kant's position, which, although he came closest to resolving it among all philosophers, still did not do it completely - he was able to express an understanding of taste through an understanding of the objective boundaries of understanding as such.

Today, the focus of aesthetics is on two phenomena: the totality of all phenomena, processes, relationships designated as aesthetic, i.e. the aesthetic itself as such, the second phenomenon is art in its essential foundations. Consequently, the problem of taste is analyzed through the experience of communication with both everyday aesthetic values and artistic ones, since the aesthetic has always been the essence of art, insofar as the study of the problem of taste is concentrated around the concept of artistic taste - a personality trait formed and developed in the process of contact with art.

In the famous work "Dehumanization of Art" X. Ortega y Gasset noted that art should be more aimed at presenting relationships, "everything that is interesting in human existence" [6]. According to Ortega y Gasset, the subject of the new art - art that is called "non-objective" - is "pure" ideas, contemplated intellectually.

Currently, the understanding of aesthetic taste is based on the everyday world as "familiar and close", which is directly experienced by the individual. The problem of taste is especially acute in the culture of postmodernism in the context of the urgent tasks of forming a person's personal sense of self and self-affirmation. In the situation of blurring the value structure, characteristic of postmodernism, and the loss of criteria for social and spiritual orientation, the need for the formation of special sensitivity to life and cultural diversity increases. The manifestation of the aesthetic in everyday life is the subject of the study of aesthetics. The aesthetics of everyday life developed by the end of the 70s. XX century. The institutionalization of this trend is happening before our eyes, as they say.

The main attention of scientists is concentrated around the traditional issue of the relationship between art and life, as well as problems of applied art, design, and aesthetic design of the subject-spatial environment. Such relatively young scientific directions as semiotics of history and semiotics of culture (R. Barth, G. Knabe, Y. Lotman, U. Eco, etc.) also turn to the topic of everyday life. Within these areas, for example, the problems of multilingualism in everyday life are posed, and both the semantics of spoken language and "body languages" are studied.

Thanks to the book by J. Huizinga "Autumn of the Middle Ages", as well as some art historical, semiotic, aesthetic studies of the late twentieth century. (Yu. Lotman, H. Lech, etc.), a circle of main themes of everyday aesthetics was formed, namely:

- aesthetic feelings that a person experiences in everyday life, including the feeling of love;
- standards of appearance;
- cosmetics;
- costume;
- ritualized forms of communication: festive meals, loving courtship;
- thing-objective environment of human habitation.

When discussing the phenomenon of mass culture in the context of the problem of aesthetic taste, one should turn to the consideration of the "elite culture" of the early 20th century, namely to the avant-garde movements that declared themselves in a similar way. Today, these movements, which had as their intention to oppose themselves to mass culture, have in many ways already found themselves within the framework of the latter: the classical avant-garde is a collection of heterogeneous and differently significant artistic movements. Modernism accepts the basic values of traditional art, but is engaged in updating artistic means in solving the so-called eternal problems of art. Avant-garde, on the contrary, creates another art, renewing not its means, but the object of art itself. The emergence of avant-garde movements, with their sharp rejection of tradition and the desire for total novelty, became the answer to the question of the directions

for the further development of art and culture in general. Meanwhile, a categorical rejection of the classical traditional heritage is only one of the possible answers. It seems that one of the most important conditions for recognizing the category of aesthetic taste as viable is the presence of a generally valid hierarchy of assessments and rankings. The presence of a generally accepted hierarchy of evaluation cultivates in a person and society the ability and at the same time the need for selection, preserving the best and cutting out the unsuitable, i.e. forms qualities that are the most important conditions for the development of culture. In addition, in the absence of a ranking system of assessments, a problem arises in determining the achievements of genius. If mass culture flourishes beautifully without brilliant guesses, in its space such a problem is not posed and simply does not matter, the importance is the satisfaction of the interests of the broad masses and the resulting commercial success, then high culture exists in constant development and in what can be called ascension from the existing highest level, as an upward movement - she lives on the creations of geniuses.

An analysis of the historical evolution of the functioning of aesthetic taste in the culture of everyday life gives grounds to consider it a mechanism that promotes the activation of the entire axiosphere of a person in the process of life, stimulating his sensory ability to aesthetically evaluate the world around him, determining the aesthetic positions and value guidelines of the individual and influencing the organization of a person's life world. Thus, the current significance of the problem of aesthetic taste is revealed not only as a category of theoretical aesthetics and art history, but also as a socio-cultural phenomenon and a category of applied aesthetics. Consequently, the theoretical study of taste should become the subject of interdisciplinary research in the humanities, social sciences, and psychological sciences. Aesthetic taste is also included in the field of problems of project activity in such subject areas as modern industrial design, fashion, marketing communications systems, environmental aesthetics, aesthetic medicine, etc.

The study of the functioning of aesthetic taste in the structures of everyday life seems promising in connection with the emergence of new value priorities, norms, and life models.

List of sources for the article:

1. Montesquieu S. Experience on Sense (aesthetic sense). <http://etika/problema-vkusa-kak-odna-tsentrallyih-estetike-55796.html>
2. Gracian B. Oracle in your pocket. <http://etika/problema-vkusa-kak-odna-tsentrallyih-estetike-55798.html>
3. E. Burke. A Philosophical Inquiry into the Origin of Our Ideas of the Sublime and the Beautiful. <http://etika/problema-vkusa-kak-odna-tsentrallyih-estetike-55799.html>
4. Diderot D. Salons. <https://coollib.com/b/639888-deni-didro-salonyi-tom-1/readp>
5. Kant I. The Critique of Judgement. – M.: Publishing house AST. – 2020. – 145 p.
6. Ortega y Gasset H. Dehumanization of art. – M.: Publishing house AST. Series Philosophy. Psychology. – 2020. – 192 p.

Economic Sciences

УДК 336.7, 338.47

SCSTI: 06.73.35

JEL Code O11, O47

The impact of inflationary processes on the socio-economic development of Kazakhstan

Assylbekov Amanbay

NARXOZ University, Almaty, Kazakhstan

Assylbekova Bayan

Kenzhegali Sagadiyev University of International Business, Almaty, Kazakhstan

Abstract

In this paper, the issues of the influence of inflationary processes on the socio-economic development of Kazakhstan are considered. As a result of the study, interesting results were obtained.

In particular, frequently cited and used price indices: for consumer goods, foodstuffs, etc.; in fact, they do not have a significant impact on the socio-economic development of the state. As a result of the study, significant relationships were established between the socio-economic development of Kazakhstan and two inflation indices: the price index for imported products and the price index for construction.

Per capita income, unemployment rate, GDP, foreign direct investment, export and import volumes, budget deficits at various levels, and other criteria are related to the prices of imported products. For the most part, these relationships are statistically significant and negative. For example, the part of the per capita income dispersion explained by the price index for imported products was 49%. Measures taken by the state aimed at import substitution have not yet given the desired result. The same nature of relations, without any special differences, has developed between the price index in construction and the criteria for the country's economic development.

In our opinion, a new paradigm of managing inflationary processes is required.

Key words: inflation, correlation and regression analysis, statistical significance, correlation matrix and data matrix, price index, socio-economic development.

Methodology: correlation and regression analysis.

Tools: R platform, RStudio interface, user package (library) "corrtable".

1. INTRODUCTION

The Republic of Kazakhstan aims to be among the 30 leading countries of the world by 2050. Some steps have already been taken towards this goal, however, if Kazakhstan is to achieve growth rates that bring living standards closer to those of more developed Western countries, a number of serious structural problems will need to be addressed. It is especially important to overcome the excessive dependence of the economy on the export of hydrocarbon raw materials, as well as a thorough reform of the public administration system. The fundamental characteristics

of the modern economy of Kazakhstan include the underdevelopment and imperfection of market institutions. Only effective institutions can ensure the successful use of economic growth factors and increase the stability of the country's socio-economic system. (NB RK Monetary Policy Report, February 2023)

Their development contributes to the creation of positive motivation for entrepreneurial and innovative activities, savings and investments. In this regard, the central strategic task of Kazakhstan is a fundamental change in the institutional environment in the context of modernization, aimed at creating an effective market mechanism for the distribution of resources and produced goods. At the same time, a special role in the transformation of the economic system belongs to the state, as the main subject of institutional design and construction, which has the resource to adopt formal laws. The strengthening of its system-forming role and the implementation of a competent macroeconomic and socio-economic policy contribute to new positive shifts in the development of the national economy and an increase in the standard of living of the population. Inflationary processes, despite relative stabilization, are formed at a high level due to stable domestic demand, restructuring of logistics and production chains, stimulating fiscal policy, as well as high and unstable inflationary expectations. Monthly inflation rates, despite the slowdown, continue to form above the historical average. Estimates of inflationary expectations of the population indicate that the current inflationary background continues to be perceived highly by the population. A clear downward trend has not yet been formed. This creates an obstacle to a rapid slowdown in inflation.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Works and empirical studies are devoted to determining the relationship between social factors and various industries, expressed through the gross domestic product (GDP) indicator. The GDP indicator is not limited to sustainability and social well-being, it also includes human development, economic structure, international trade (import and export), investment and other social factors. According to Aganbegyan A.G. (2015) investment affects economic growth in two ways. Firstly, the transition to accelerated investments, for example, to their annual increase by 10%, already in the process of investing causes the development of industries involved in this, provides additional work for design and engineering organizations, builders, equipment manufacturers, banking and finance, foreign trade in the case of using foreign equipment, etc. Secondly, investments have the greatest effect after a number of years, on average after 3–5 years, when the new capacities being created come into operation and begin to produce products, and every year more and more as the development of capacities and development of these industries. On the basis of new technology and the use of the most advanced equipment, labor productivity increases several times, energy and material consumption are significantly reduced, its quality is sharply improved, it becomes possible to produce new products that are in demand, and exports are growing. According to the research conducted by Raimbekova Zh.S. et al. (2018) the growth of the total share of transport in fixed assets indicates an unfavorable trend towards an increase in the level of unit logistics costs in Kazakhstan, reduced to a unit of GDP. To a certain extent, this can be explained by the raw material orientation of the Kazakh economy and its growth. Specific costs for the transportation of raw materials are higher than those for high-tech finished products and services. According to the World Bank, population growth and urbanization will increase the demand for food, even as natural capital is being depleted and climate change is affecting food production. According to the forecast of socio-economic development of Kazakhstan for 2023-2027 and draft laws on the formation of the republican budget for 2023-2025, the average annual real size of Kazakhstan's GDP under this scenario will be 3.9%, including 4% in 2023. At the same time, exports are expected to grow in all major sectors of the economy (primeminister.kz, 2023). According to the report of the National Bank of the Republic of

Kazakhstan, annual inflation in February 2023 amounted to 21.3% (in January - 20.7%). Prices for food products over the year increased by 26.2% (in January - 25.7%), for non-food products - by 20.5% (in January - 20.2%), for paid services - by 15.0% (in January - 14.2%). To obtain a realistic and accurate forecast and analysis of inflation, certain technical requirements must be met. For example, a sufficiently large amount of data must be available, and appropriate models must be developed to predict and analyze inflation. The study of inflation and its sources in the economy is important because it plays a significant role in shaping the monetary policy pursued by the central bank. A study by the International Monetary Fund (Loungani & Swagel, 2001) found that the sources of inflation in developing countries are not homogeneous and vary by continent. In particular, it is noted that the drivers of inflation in African and Asian countries differ, as most of the latter tend to have lower or moderate levels of average inflation. The study also showed that fiscal factors, which are reflected in money supply growth, exchange rate peg adjustments in response to oil or non-oil commodity price shocks, have a significant impact. (Islam E. et al., 2022). Forecasting local inflation with global inflation examines a range of inflation forecasting models and argues that current economic models are poorly suited to inflation forecasts in emerging markets (Duncan & Martínez-García, 2015).

Zhanshanlo et al. conducted an analysis of inflationary processes for the period 1992-2014. in Kazakhstan, where a discrete model of the emergence and development of inflation was studied. Based on this model, a formula was derived that links inflation, money supply growth rates and economic growth with the regulatory aspects of the exchange rate. Inflation management involves the use of a set of measures that allow, to a certain extent, to combine price growth with income stabilization (Janshanlo, R., Andybaeva, G. and Beysenbaeva, A., 2015).

The decline in oil prices causes a reduction in industrial production, and negative changes in oil prices have a greater impact than positive ones, which is a risk factor for Kazakhstan's macroeconomic performance. In order to promote economic growth and sustainable development in Kazakhstan, the income that is generated from oil revenues should be invested in both the agro-industrial sector and social infrastructure such as education and healthcare. (N Kose, S Baimaganbetov, 2015)

In a study by Akhmedyarova A, (2022), housing preferences determine fluctuations in housing price consumption. Productivity disruptions have contributed greatly to explaining output and employment. Interest rate fluctuations are mainly explained by government spending performance.

There was a break in general, food and non-food inflation at the end of 2015 when the National Bank of Kazakhstan announced a change in the monetary policy regime (Tolepbergen, A. 2022).

Aydın, C., Esen, Ö., & Bayrak, M. (2016). conducted a study looking at the impact of inflation on economic growth in five transition republics (Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, and Turkmenistan) by analyzing dynamic panel data based on a threshold. The results of the study show that there is a non-linear relationship between inflation and growth rates; The threshold for the impact of inflation on economic growth is 7.97%, and an inflation rate above this threshold has a negative impact on economic growth, while an inflation rate below this threshold has a positive effect on economic growth. These results show that high inflation will have a significant impact on economic growth. In this regard, it is important to achieve sustainable growth, which plays a decisive role in improving the effectiveness of the ongoing monetary policy and ensuring stability.

The National Bank sets the official refinancing rate depending on the situation on the money market and the level of inflation. Thus, the refinancing rate remains positive in real terms as inflation rises. An increase in the interest rate tightens monetary policy, hindering access to credit and, as a result, slowing down investment. These measures cause a reduction in the

components of GDP, a deterioration in the situation on the labor market. (Dufrenot, G., Ospanova, A. and Sand-Zantman, A., 2014).

The question of whether inflation and its uncertainty have a positive or negative impact on economic growth has been the subject of extensive research, primarily because of its policy relevance. The main goal of macroeconomic policy is to stimulate growth and keep inflation low. It is generally recognized that high and unsustainable inflation is detrimental to economic growth and entails social security costs. However, with few exceptions, the empirical study has separately considered the impact of inflation and inflationary uncertainty on economic growth. The question of how the two aspects of inflation jointly affect economic growth remains unanswered, especially in developing countries where high inflation rates often prevail. Moreover, it is widely recognized that the rate of inflation is closely related to inflationary uncertainty, both empirically and theoretically. These two factors are known to have different effects on economic growth, which together can either increase or decrease the net effect of inflation on economic growth. The main motive of this study is to determine the impact of inflationary processes on the socio-economic development of Kazakhstan.

3. ANALYSIS

In this study, as inflation criteria, for the period from 2001 to 2021. 13 following indexes are chosen:

- consumer price index (at the end of the period, as a percentage of December of the previous year),
- food price index,
- price index for non-food products,
- price index for paid services for the population,
- price index of enterprises producing industrial products (goods, services) (at the end of the period, as a percentage of December of the previous year),
- price index for the purchase of products for industrial purposes by industrial enterprises (at the end of the period, as a percentage of December of the previous year),
- price index in construction (at the end of the period, as a percentage of December of the previous year),
- Producer price index of agricultural products (at the end of the period, as a percentage of December of the previous year),
- index of tariffs for the transportation of goods by all modes of transport (at the end of the period, as a percentage of December of the previous year),
- index of tariffs for postal and courier services for legal entities (at the end of the period, as a percentage of December of the previous year),
- index of tariffs for communication services for legal entities (at the end of the period, as a percentage of December of the previous year),
- price index of export deliveries of goods, products (at the end of the period, as a percentage of December of the previous year),
- price index of import receipts of goods, products (at the end of the period, as a percentage of December of the previous year).

The list did not include two indices: the price index for forestry products and services (at the end of the period, as a percentage of December of the previous year) and the price index for fisheries and fish farming products (at the end of the period, as a percentage of December of the previous year).

These indices began to be published in 2010. The correlation analysis carried out over this period showed the absence of statistically significant relationships between these indices and the

criteria of socioeconomic development. This situation could arise, among other things, due to a lack of observations. For this reason, these indices were excluded from the overall analysis.

As criteria for socio-economic development, the following were chosen: average per capita monetary income of the population, unemployment rate, wages, GDP, etc. There are 37 criteria in total, the list is attached (Appendix 1).

Correlation analysis was carried out on the R platform, using the *'correlation_matrix(...)'* function from the *'corrtable'* user library. Compared to the base function *'cor(...)'*, the function we used not only creates a correlation matrix, but also assigns a degree of statistical significance to each expression. Significance code values have the following interpretation: ***-probability of the null hypothesis is 0, **-probability of the null hypothesis is 0.001, and *-probability of the null hypothesis is 0.01. The absence of codes means that the resulting expression is not statistically significant. The calculation results are partially shown in Table 1. Full correlation table *index.cor2001-2021.csv*. attached.

It is interesting to note that the so often mentioned price indices for consumer, food and non-food products do not have statistically significant links with the criteria of socio-economic development.

As we can see, a systematic, statistically significant relationship with the criteria of socio-economic development was found in only two indices - the price index in construction and the price index of imported goods. At the same time, the impact of import prices is more significant than construction prices.

If we start with the most significant dependencies, then we should emphasize the negative impact of import prices on the average per capita nominal cash income of the population in dollars. They also negatively affect wages, GDP in dollars, and investments in fixed assets to the same extent.

With less probability, but quite significantly, it can be argued that the growth of import prices leads to an increase in unemployment of all forms, the number of people with incomes below the subsistence level; decrease in exports, imports and inflow of foreign investments. In our assumption, the rise in import prices is a criterion for external inflation.

With regard to prices in construction, first of all, it should be noted that the rise in prices in construction does not correlate with the rise in import prices. Therefore, construction can be considered as a source of domestic inflation. Secondly, the argument that prices in construction are a direct consequence of prices for imported components is not confirmed. In our opinion, the financial bubble in construction is filling up, and dependence on imports fills the bubble partially.

Table 1 Correlation analysis results

	Price index for services for the population	Construction price index	Tariffs for commun. services for legal entities	Price index for imported products
Per capita income, tenge	-0.396	-0.494*	0.009	-0.38
Income per capita, USD	0.088	-0.298	-0.294	-0.701***
The share of the population with incomes below the subsistence level in %	-0.1	0.358	0.277	0.635**
Employed population as % of the previous year	0.048	0.619**	0.502*	0.512*
Unemployment rate in %	0.108	0.475*	0.257	0.601**
Youth unemployment rate 15 24 years in percent	0.041	0.43	0.246	0.616**
Youth unemployment rate 15 28 years in percent	0.149	0.487*	0.21	0.576**
Long-term unemployment rate in percent	-0.093	0.405	0.357	0.561**
Average monthly salary of one employee tenge	-0.375	-0.488*	-0.015	-0.383
Average monthly salary per employee USD	0.158	-0.258	-0.344	-0.696***
Gross domestic product by production method million tg	-0.423	-0.492*	0.023	-0.37
Gross domestic product by production method USD million	-0.037	-0.36	-0.249	-0.684***
Gross domestic product by production method per capita tg	-0.404	-0.491*	0.006	-0.398
Gross domestic product by production method per capita USD	0.052	-0.308	-0.291	-0.697***
Investments in fixed assets mln tg	-0.4	-0.506*	0.022	-0.379
Investments in fixed capital USD mln	0.204	-0.242	-0.319	-0.676***
Manufacturing industry mln tenge	-0.384	-0.434*	0.019	-0.279
Gross output of agricultural services mln tenge	-0.411	-0.481*	0.007	-0.341
Volume of communication services mln tenge	-0.264	-0.479*	-0.095	-0.521*
Trade turnover in foreign currency export mln USD	0.197	-0.119	-0.345	-0.593**
Trade turnover in foreign currency import mln USD	0.156	-0.265	-0.35	-0.611**
State budget, revenue mln. tenge	-0.397	-0.479*	0.016	-0.353
State budget, expenses million tenge	-0.409	-0.499*	0.019	-0.351
Deficit (surplus) of state. budget million tenge	0.345	0.499*	0.015	0.356
Deficit (surplus) of state. budget as a percentage of GDP	0.077	0.363	0.073	0.521*
Republican budget, revenue million tenge	-0.4	-0.488*	0.014	-0.362
Republican budget, costs million tenge	-0.414	-0.501*	0.02	-0.358
Deficit (surplus) rep. budget million tenge	0.333	0.454*	0.03	0.377
Deficit (surplus) rep. budget as a percentage of GDP	0.026	0.325	0.109	0.540*
Local budget, revenue million tenge	-0.361	-0.481*	-0.012	-0.361
Local budget, costs million tenge	-0.375	-0.503*	-0.011	-0.346
Deficit (surplus) local. budget million tenge	0.363	0.604**	-0.06	0.174
Deficit (surplus) local. budget as a percentage of GDP	0.376	0.475*	0.005	0.113
Foreign direct investment inflow US\$ mln	0.095	-0.156	-0.24	-0.570**
Average annual US dollar exchange rate	-0.563**	-0.480*	0.173	-0.122

Source: Compiled by the author based on the data from the Bureau of National Statistics (2022)

Figure 1 shows the dependence of the average per capita nominal income of the population in US dollars on the price index of import receipts of goods and products. Graphical representation does not give the exact nature of the relationship between inflation and the criteria for socio-economic development. The connection can be either linear or non-linear. To clarify the nature of statistically significant dependencies, we conduct a regression analysis.

Figure 1 Dependence of average per capita nominal income of the population
 Source: Compiled by the author

Applying a parametric approach, we initially assume that the dependences are linear and fit a linear regression to our data:

$$\text{Income per capita, USD} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 * (\text{Price index for imported products})$$

Platform Code R:

```
lm.fit=lm(Income per capita, USD ~ Price index for imported products)
```

We obtain the following characteristics of the linear model:

```
summary(lm.fit)
```

Call:

```
lm(formula = Income per capita, USD ~ Price index for imported products)
```

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-147.23	-64.56	17.97	46.78	109.74

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	1077.171	198.434	5.428	3.08e-05 ***
Price index for imported products	-7.740	1.806	-4.286	0.000399 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 73.11 on 19 degrees of freedom
 Multiple R-squared: 0.4916, Adjusted R-squared: 0.4648

F-statistic: 18.37 on 1 and 19 DF, p-value: 0.0003988

The obtained characteristics of linear regression indicate its statistical significance and suitability for a quantitative description of the relationship between predictor and response.

It is possible that a non-linear model will be better suited to the nature of the relationship than a linear model. We tested this hypothesis with the help of polynomial regression in 3 degrees:

$$\text{Income per capita, USD} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 * (\text{Price index for imported products}) + \beta_2 * (\text{Price index for imported products})^2 + \beta_3 * (\text{Price index for imported products})^3$$

Platform Code R:

```
lm.fit3=lm(Income per capita, USD ~poly(Price index for imported products,3))
```

We obtain the following characteristics of the polynomial model:

```
summary(lm.fit3)
```

Call:

```
lm(formula = Income per capita, USD ~poly(Price index for imported products, 3))
```

Residuals:

```
    Min     1Q  Median     3Q     Max
-146.048 -16.746  4.184  40.631 113.231
```

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	229.40	15.52	14.780	3.91e-11 ***
poly(Price index for imported products, 3)1	-313.36	71.13	-4.406	0.000386 ***
poly(Price index for imported products, 3)2	-95.99	71.13	-1.350	0.194830
poly(Price index for imported products)3	79.63	71.13	1.120	0.278468

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 71.13 on 17 degrees of freedom

Multiple R-squared: 0.5695, Adjusted R-squared: 0.4935

F-statistic: 7.495 on 3 and 17 DF, p-value: 0.002084

Polynomials of the second, third degree and the corresponding coefficients were not statistically significant. Consequently, the linear model better reflects the dependence of socio-economic development criteria on inflation. The full working code of the program is given in Appendix 3.

We also made the assumption that import prices are closely related to the US dollar exchange rate. Which would be quite natural and understandable. But we did not find a stable, significant dependence, which is the subject of more careful consideration.

We believe that the list of predictors should be supplemented by the balance of payments of the state. This is especially true for exports and imports of services, where a negative balance persists for a long time.

In terms of methodology, in order to clarify the structure of inflation, we would like to supplement the work with "Principal Component Analysis (PCA)". To reduce the dimension of the composition of predictors, we propose to conduct a LACCO analysis based on an alternative selection methodology.

In addition, the studies proposed in addition, in our opinion, can significantly supplement information about the nature of inflation in our country, its impact on socio-economic development and help in the synthesis of a new management paradigm.

CONCLUSIONS

Commonly cited and used price indices: for consumer goods, foodstuffs, etc.; in fact, they do not have a significant impact on the socio-economic development of Kazakhstan.

Of the entire complex of inflationary predictors: a systematic, statistically significant relationship with the criteria of socio-economic development was found in only two indices - the price index in construction and the price index of imported goods. At the same time, the impact of import prices is more significant than construction prices. We believe that these indices require special attention and management.

In construction, it is necessary to take preventive measures in order to prevent the further growth of the financial bubble.

The relationships between predictors and responses are linear.

We propose to supplement our work with new research, which can significantly supplement information about the nature of inflation in our country, its impact on socio-economic development and help in the synthesis of a new management paradigm.

References

- 1 Monetary Policy Report, February 2023 NB RK Official website of the National Bank of the Republic of Kazakhstan. <https://www.nationalbank.kz/>
- 2 Aganbegyan A. G. Six steps necessary for the resumption of socio-economic growth and overcoming stagnation, recession and stagflation // Money and credit. – 2015. – no. 2. - S. 7-13.
- 3 Raimbekov Zh. S. et al. Current trends in the development of the logistics system in Kazakhstan // economics and modern management: in search of a new model of innovative development. – 2018. – p. 116-129.
- 4 Official information resource of the Prime Minister of the Republic of Kazakhstan. <https://primeminister.kz/> was accessed on April 8, 2023.
- 5 Islam E. et al. Dynamic Factor Model of Inflation for Kazakhstan. – 2022. – no. 2022-4.6
- 6 Duncan, R., & Martínez-García, E. (2015). Forecasting local inflation with global inflation: When economic theory meets the facts. *Available at SSRN 2589712*.
- 7 Janshanlo, R., Andybaeva, G., & Beysenbaeva, A. (2015). Methodological aspects of inflation management by example of Kazakhstan. *Economic Annals-XXI*.
- 8 Nezir, K. Ö. S. E., & Baimaganbetov, S. (2015). The asymmetric impact of oil price shocks on Kazakhstan macroeconomic dynamics: A structural vector autoregression approach. *International Journal of Energy Economics and Policy*, 5(4), 1058-1064.
- 9 Akhmedyarova, A. (2022). *Housing market dynamics in Kazakhstan: An estimated DSGE model* (No. 19). NAC Analytica, Nazarbayev University.
- 10 Tolepbergen, A. (2022). A study of inflation persistence in Kazakhstan: what has changed?. *Macroeconomics and Finance in Emerging Market Economies*, 1-20.
- 11 Aydın, C., Esen, Ö., & Bayrak, M. (2016). Inflation and economic growth: A dynamic panel threshold analysis for Turkish Republics in transition process. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 229, 196-205.
- 12 Dufrénot, G., Ospanova, A., & Sand-Zantman, A. (2014). A small macro econometric model for Kazakhstan: a retrospective of alternative economic policies undertaken during the transition process. *Economic Change and Restructuring*, 47, 1-39.
- 13 Agambayeva, S. , A. Algozhina, S. Khakimzhanov, B. Konurbaeva, E. Kucherenko, I. Talhanbaeva, N. Turekhanova, V. Tutushkin, R. Shagiakhmetova, and S. Shaih (2010): “KMOD The

Structural Macroeconomic Model of Kazakhstan.” Economic Review, 1, National Bank of Kazakhstan.

14 Berg, A., P. Karam, and D. Laxton (2006): “*Practical Model-Based Monetary Policy Analysis – A How-To Guide.*” *IMF Working Paper WP/06/81, International Monetary Fund.*

15 Bergholt, D., V. H. Larsen, and m. Seneca (2017): “*Business Cycles in an Oil Economy.*” *BIS Working Paper No 618, Bank for International Settlements.*

16 Epstein, N. and R. Portillo (2014): “*Monetary Policy in Hybrid Regimes: The Case of Kazakhstan.*” *IMF Working Paper WP/14/108, International Monetary Fund.*

17 Hamann, F., J. Bejarano, D. Rodríguez, and P. Restrepo-Echavarría (2016): “*Monetary Policy in an Oil-Exporting Economy.*” *Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis Review, Third Quarter 2016.*

18 Melek, N. C., M. Plante, and M. K. Yücel (2017): “*The U.S. Shale Oil Boom, the Oil Export Ban, and the Economy: A General Equilibrium Analysis.*” *Research Working Paper 17-10, Federal Reserve Bank of Kansas City*

19 Kilian, L. (2005), *The effects of exogenous oil supply shocks on output and inflation: Evidence from the G7 countries.* Centre for Economic Policy Research. Discussion Paper, No. 5404.

20 Korhonen, L., Mehrotra, A. (2009), *Real exchange rate, output and oil: Case of four large energy producers.* Bank of Finland. Institute for Economies in Transition. Discussion Papers, 6/2009.

21 Kuralbayeva, K., Kutan, M.A., Wyzan, M.L. (2001), *Is Kazakhstan vulnerable to the Dutch disease?* ZEI Working Paper. No. B 29-2001.

22 Kutan, A.M., Wyzan, M.L. (2005), *Explaining the real exchange rate in Kazakhstan, 1996-2003: Is Kazakhstan vulnerable to the Dutch disease?* *Economic Systems, 29, 242-255.*

The experience of waste management in the food industry of Azerbaijan

Emin Huseynov

Azerbaijan Technological University, Department of Management

Abstract

Food waste management is a pressing research area aligning with green economic principles. This article examines Azerbaijan's approach to food waste management, focusing on statistical data and methods. Through statistical analysis, it highlights trends and challenges in the country's food industry waste management. The article explores theoretical and practical strategies, from policy frameworks to waste reduction and sustainable disposal methods. By studying Azerbaijan's experience, this research contributes to the global discourse on sustainable food waste management.

Keywords: Waste management, food industry, food policy, green economics, food waste management.

Introduction

In the contemporary landscape of our ever-evolving world, characterized by technological leaps and profound societal changes, human evolution has given birth to a rich tapestry of new academic disciplines and areas of inquiry. Amid this burgeoning diversity of knowledge, the imperative of sustainability has risen to prominent importance. As we approached the close of the 20th century, the principles of green economics emerged as a transformative departure from conventional economic ideologies. This paradigm shift extended far beyond the traditional pursuit of economic gain. It laid the foundation for a profound shift in perspective, recognizing the intricate and inseparable link between economic systems and the fragile ecological balance of our planet. Green economics championed the notion that sustainable economic growth must coexist harmoniously with responsible environmental stewardship. With the formulation of innovative global strategies, an eco-economic political pathway started to take shape on the world stage. This path, rooted in a holistic approach that integrates economic, social, and environmental dimensions, sought to guide us towards a more sustainable and equitable future. The investigation and management of food waste represent a pivotal facet of research within the realm of green economy and the pursuit of a sustainable future.

Material and Methods

In this context, waste management emerges as a pivotal element in shaping a sustainable and resilient future for our planet and the well-being of generations to come. In their scholarly investigation, Duque-Acevedo and colleagues (2020) systematically elucidated the evolutionary characteristics inherent to the food waste management process, concurrently exploring plausible alternative conceptual frameworks. Concurrently, Hasanov's (2023) scholarly contribution on the subject of waste management proves valuable for adopting a comprehensive and generalized approach to addressing this issue. To ensure that the research remained firmly rooted in the specifics of Azerbaijan's context, data regarding the food industry and waste within the country were meticulously sourced from the official platforms of the State Statistics Committee, various executive government organisations, and respected media organizations. This approach allowed for a tailored examination of the economic and environmental landscape unique to Azerbaijan.

Results and Discussion

On the ecologically fragile Absheron Peninsula, the Azerbaijani government set priority in 2006 to reduce domestic waste and pollution from oil and gas extraction. After the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan signed the "Comprehensive Action Plan for the Improvement of the Environmental Situation in the Republic of Azerbaijan for 2006-2010" on September 28, 2006, a new agenda was created to alter the country's current solid waste management practice. Within the framework of the project, with the help of the World Bank, 800,000 people of Baku now have greater access to daily garbage collection services, and the scope of waste collection has expanded by 19% from 2008 to 79% and 6345 new garbage cans were installed in 5 districts of Baku and 1973 new collection points were created in order to expand the coverage (Ibrahimova, 2023). The President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Mr. Ilham Aliyev, established "Tamiz Shaheer" Open Joint Stock Company by executive order dated August 6, 2008, "On improving the management of household waste in the city of Baku," and by executive order dated June 22, 2021 and "On household waste on the improvement of management," with the executive order dated July 2, 2022, expanding the scope of activities of "Tamiz Shaheer" OJSC, collecting, transporting, placing an order to the "Tamiz Shehar" OJSC it was given (Tamizshahar, 2023).

According to the State Statistics Committee, in 2022, 3,985,000 tons of waste were generated across the country, of which 802,000 tons were reused and neutralized. The amount of waste per person was 395 kg. (Stat, 2023). As it can be seen from the statistics, the problem of domestic waste is important, and in the future it is necessary to expand the platform related to these works. The problem is global in scope. On a global scale, the majority of waste is disposed of in open spaces or in landfills. 8 percent of garbage is dumped in sanitary landfills with landfill gas collecting systems, and 37% of waste is disposed of in landfills in one way or another. 33 percent of waste is dumped in landfills, 19 percent is recycled or composted, and 11 percent is burned off for final disposal. High and upper-middle-income countries almost solely have access to adequate waste disposal or treatment, such as controlled landfills or more stringently controlled facilities (World Bank, 2023).

	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
The amount of generated production and consumption waste.	2896.1	3256.0	3452.3	3778.2	3985.1
Per capita, kg.	295	329	346	377	395
Amount of used, neutralized production and consumption waste.	848.3	713.4	792.1	1563.1	801.9
Per capita, kg.	85	72	79	156	79

Figure 1. Generation, use and disposal of waste in Azerbaijan (thousand tons).

Source: Stat.gov.az.

Efficient waste management holds paramount significance within the context of Azerbaijan's eco-economic landscape. In addition to economic considerations, adhering to principles aligned with stringent environmental standards remains a pivotal focal point. The intricate tapestry of waste management in Azerbaijan entails a multifaceted approach that encompasses various stages, each contributing to the overarching goal of responsible waste handling. Beginning with the initial collection and segregation of waste materials, the process then proceeds to waste processing, where recyclable and non-recyclable materials are sorted, treated, and prepared for further utilization or disposal. This commitment to thorough processing not only

optimizes resource recovery but also minimizes the environmental footprint. Finally, the emphasis extends to efficient disposal methods, ensuring that residual waste is managed in a manner that safeguards both the local environment and public health. Consequently, this comprehensive approach to waste management underscores Azerbaijan's dedication to sustainable development, simultaneously fostering a cleaner environment and supporting its burgeoning eco-economic aspirations.

At the core of waste management in Azerbaijan lies a robust foundation built upon waste processing and its intricate array of processes. This fundamental approach serves as the cornerstone of the strategy to tackle the growing challenges posed by waste generation and environmental sustainability. Waste processing in Azerbaijan involves a series of operations designed to extract the maximum value from waste materials while minimizing their environmental impact. By prioritizing waste processing and its associated processes, countries not only minimize the environmental burden of waste but also harnesses valuable resources, contributes to energy production, and promotes sustainable practices. This approach exemplifies the nation's commitment to balancing economic growth with environmental stewardship in its waste management endeavors. During collection and segregation, waste is initially gathered from various sources, including households, businesses, and industrial facilities, where it is carefully separated into categories like recyclables, organic matter, and non-recyclables. This crucial sorting process at its outset significantly streamlines subsequent processing and recycling efforts. In the recycling and material recovery phase, recyclable materials such as paper, plastics, metals, and glass undergo precise sorting and processing procedures, involving techniques like shredding, melting, and refining. These processes are instrumental in extracting valuable resources from recyclables, thereby reducing the demand for virgin resources and promoting sustainability through the creation of new products.

Figure 2. Waste management and its various processes in Azerbaijan.

Source: Author.

The processing of food waste holds significant importance due to both its large volume and environmental implications. Food waste processing involves techniques like composting and anaerobic digestion, which transform discarded food materials into valuable resources such as compost and biogas. These methods mitigate the environmental impact of food waste while supporting sustainable waste management practices.

In Azerbaijan, food waste management primarily focuses on recycling and energy production as the key processes. These approaches enable the responsible disposal of food waste while also harnessing its potential for resource recovery and green energy generation. In general, food products (44%) are the main of solid domestic waste.

Figure 3. The main food waste processing.

Source: Author.

Recycling begins at the household level, emphasizing the importance of reusing items instead of discarding them needlessly. This practice entails finding new uses for used products, contributing to the overall recycling effort (Organika, 2023).

Recycling is a multifaceted process that offers a wide range of significant benefits to both society and the environment. These advantages include:

- **Brings Economic Profit:** Recycling fosters economic growth by creating job opportunities in collection, processing, and manufacturing industries. It also reduces the need to extract and process raw materials, thereby lowering production costs for various goods. Additionally, the sale of recycled materials generates revenue for individuals and businesses.
- **Environmental Preservation:** One of the most prominent benefits of recycling is its positive impact on the environment. By diverting waste from landfills and incineration, recycling helps reduce pollution, greenhouse gas emissions, and the depletion of natural resources. This, in turn, contributes to cleaner air, water, and land, promoting overall environmental health and biodiversity.
- **Waste Reduction:** Recycling plays a pivotal role in diminishing the volume of waste sent to landfills. By reusing and repurposing materials, less waste accumulates in disposal sites, extending their lifespan and mitigating the associated environmental and health hazards.
- **Energy Conservation:** Recycling conserves energy compared to the production of goods from raw materials. Processing recycled materials typically requires less energy, reducing the carbon footprint and lessening the demand for fossil fuels. This energy efficiency is especially crucial in the context of combatting climate change.
- **Resource Preservation:** Recycling alleviates the pressure on ecosystems and habitats by reducing the need to extract virgin raw materials. This protects natural landscapes, conserves biodiversity, and helps maintain fragile ecosystems.

Waste management represents a burgeoning field in Azerbaijan, and with proper organization and investment, the country has the potential to secure a foothold in the recycling

industry's raw materials market. By prioritizing efficient waste collection, recycling, and resource recovery practices, Azerbaijan can not only reduce its reliance on virgin raw materials but also position itself as a regional leader in sustainable waste management, fostering economic growth and environmental sustainability (Abizade, 2022).

Within the realm of solid waste management in the food industry, certain materials are notably well-suited for swift and effective recycling processes. Aluminum, glass, and paper products emerge as top contenders due to their inherent recyclability and relatively low levels of contamination.

- **Aluminum:** Aluminum is a standout material for rapid recycling. It possesses the remarkable quality of retaining its properties when recycled, making it highly desirable for manufacturers. Within the food industry, aluminum is commonly employed in the form of cans, foils, and various packaging materials. Recycling aluminum not only conserves substantial energy but also lessens the demand for bauxite ore mining and refining, the primary source of aluminum production. This significantly reduces greenhouse gas emissions and the overall environmental footprint linked to aluminum manufacturing.

- **Glass:** Glass containers, frequently used for packaging in the food industry, such as bottles and jars, are exceptionally conducive to recycling. The process entails crushing and melting the glass to create fresh containers or other glass products. Glass recycling is known for its efficiency and can be repeated indefinitely without compromising quality. This sustainable practice not only conserves natural resources but also reduces energy consumption. Manufacturing glass from recycled materials consumes notably less energy compared to using raw materials, contributing to energy efficiency and environmental preservation.

- **Paper Products:** Paper and cardboard are prominent packaging materials in the food industry. These materials can be promptly recycled into new paper and cardboard products. Recycling paper not only safeguards trees but also diminishes water and energy usage. Moreover, it decreases air pollution associated with paper production. The relatively low levels of contamination found in paper and cardboard packaging facilitate their recycling, making it an eco-friendly choice.

Efficiently recycling these materials from the food industry aligns with overarching environmental sustainability objectives. It curtails landfill-bound waste, preserves precious resources, and mitigates the carbon footprint tied to the production of fresh materials. Furthermore, it fosters the principles of a circular economy, where materials are continually repurposed and reused, thereby contributing to a more eco-conscious and resource-efficient food industry.

The Balakhani household waste plant, a cornerstone of Azerbaijan's waste management efforts, was inaugurated on November 3, 2009, with President Ilham Aliyev leading the initiative (President, 2012). This significant facility plays a crucial role in processing diverse waste types, embodying Azerbaijan's commitment to responsible waste management and environmental preservation. The Balakhani waste plant possesses the capability to process 200,000 tons of waste annually, with an average daily intake of approximately 300-350 tons. Any waste unsuitable for sorting undergoes separation and is directed to the incineration plant, where its volume is reduced by a factor of ten. The incineration facility is designed to handle 500,000 tons of waste yearly, concurrently generating electricity. Approximately 180 million kilowatt-hours of electricity are produced through this process, with 30 million kilowatt-hours allocated for the plant's internal operations, making it entirely self-sufficient in terms of electricity supply. The surplus 155 million kilowatt-hours of energy are distributed to the general populace, with the capacity to fully power a city of up to 300,000 residents (Azinform, 2016).

Figure 4. Balakhani Waste Factory.

Photo Source: <https://president.az/az/articles/view/6874>

The incineration of waste demands the utilization of contemporary technological methods to ensure its efficiency and minimize adverse consequences. Without proper planning and measures in place, waste incineration can indeed pose significant environmental hazards. These detrimental effects encompass the emission of harmful gases, acidic components, smoke, and noxious odors into the atmosphere. To address these concerns and mitigate environmental harm, it is imperative to construct rational, state-of-the-art waste treatment facilities that adhere to modern technological standards.

In 2021, solid household waste constituted 68.3 percent of the total waste in Azerbaijan, while various types of waste generated by industrial enterprises accounted for 31.7 percent. Among these, 78.3 percent were transported to landfills for disposal, 21.3 percent were utilized for energy generation, and a minimal 0.4 percent were sold domestically (Stat, 2022).

Figure 5. Use of 2581.2 thousand tons of solid household waste in 2021.

Source: Stat.gov.az

Waste plays a significant role in the production of green energy, a facet of the energy landscape that is growing in paramount importance on a global scale. The share of energy derived from waste in Azerbaijan's burgeoning green energy sector is progressively on the rise. In fact,

thanks to the innovative utilization of household waste, there has been a noticeable decrease of 193.2 million kWh, representing a reduction of 3.7 percent in electricity production compared to the figures from 2020. This exemplifies the nation's commitment to both environmental sustainability and the advancement of renewable energy sources, positioning Azerbaijan as a notable player in the global transition towards a more eco-conscious energy future.

Conclusion

In summary, the Azerbaijani government's initiatives to address waste management and environmental challenges on the Absheron Peninsula, dating back to 2006, have led to substantial improvements in solid waste management practices. Efforts, including improved garbage collection services, expanded coverage, and infrastructure development, have positively impacted the lives of the population in Baku. Globally, waste management remains a critical issue, with a significant proportion of waste ending up in open spaces or landfills, underscoring the importance of responsible waste management practices. Azerbaijan's focus on food waste management, recycling, and energy production, as well as the operation of the Balakhani household waste plant, exemplifies the country's commitment to sustainable waste management and environmental preservation.

References

- Abizade, N. (2022). Waste management in Azerbaijan and future developments. <http://dspace.unive.it/handle/10579/21698>
- Azinforum (2016). Balaxanı Bərk Məişət Tullantılarının Çeşidlənməsi zavodundan – REPORTAJ. <https://azinforum.az/media/balaxani-b%C9%99rk-m%C9%99is%C9%99t-tullantilarinin-cesidl%C9%99nm%C9%99si-zavodundan-reportaj/>
- Duque-Acevedo, M., Belmonte-Ureña, L. J., Cortés-García, F. J., & Camacho-Ferre, F. (2020). Agricultural waste: Review of the evolution, approaches and perspectives on alternative uses. *Global Ecology and Conservation*, 22, e00902. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gecco.2020.e00902>
- Ibrahimova, A. (2023). DAVAMLI İNKİŞAFDA EKOLOJİ AMİLLƏR: AZƏRBAYCANDA BƏRK MƏİŞƏT TULLANTILARININ EMALI. IDI. <https://idi-aze.org/files/pdf/2023-05-19/zlkPvv51Tx8bnVvBis1ssUZLo2dq9aiEHsPWkBir.pdf>
- Organika (2023). Təkrar emal. <https://www.organika.az/tekrar-emalin-ehemiyyeti>
- President.az (2012). İlham Əliyev Bakı bərk məişət tullantılarının yandırılması zavodunun açılışında iştirak etmişdir. <https://president.az/az/articles/view/6875>
- Ramil Həsənov (2023). TULLANTILARIN İDARƏ EDİLMƏSİ VƏ TƏKRAR EMALI: ÜMUMİ BAXIŞ. İPƏK YOLU, No.3, 2023, səh.35-40.
- Stat (2022). 2021-ci ildə tullantıların hərəkəti haqqında. <https://stat.gov.az/news/index.php?id=5197&lang=az>
- Stat (2023). Source environment. Stat.gov.az https://stat.gov.az/source/environment/az/011_1.xls
- Tamizshahar (2023). Haqqımızda. <https://tamizshahar.az/az/haqqimizda>
- World Bank (2023). Trends in Solid Waste Management. <https://datatopics.worldbank.org/what-a-waste/trends-in-solid-waste-management.html>

The main directions of small business support by the state

Garacayeva Lala Ramiz

University of Technology of Azerbaijan, Ganja, Azerbaijan

Yusibova Sabrin Azer

University of Technology of Azerbaijan, Ganja, Azerbaijan

Hasanova Aygun Aydin

University of Technology of Azerbaijan, Ganja, Azerbaijan

Allahverdiyev Aladdin Vusal

Azerbaijan State Agrarian University

Summary: The financial capabilities of small and medium-sized enterprises, the structure of financing sources, have an important impact on their economic and investment activity. At present, a system of public and private international financial assistance to small and medium entrepreneurs is operating in Azerbaijan. During the years of independence, certain positive experience was collected in the field of financial assistance to small and medium-sized enterprises. However, despite all this, small and medium-sized entrepreneurs, who play an important role in the country's economy due to their potential, have limited use of financial resources. This limitation also manifests itself in obtaining long and short-term loans. One of the important tasks that need to be solved in Azerbaijan is the activation of the investment activity of small and medium entrepreneurs and the expansion of opportunities to attract financial resources to this section.

Keywords: small business, state budget, credit resources, investment.

The lack of opportunities for small and medium-sized entrepreneurs to collect their own money, limited opportunities to allocate funds to this sector from the state budget, high interest rates for their own credit resources of commercial banks, including credit resources of international and foreign financial institutions, difficulties in guaranteeing and collateral make financing of small and medium-sized businesses difficult. .

It should be noted that among the factors influencing the development of small and medium-sized entrepreneurs in Azerbaijan, financial factors had the weakest impact during the entire period of the transition to the market economy. On the one hand, this can be explained by the limitation of financial resources, on the other hand, it can be explained by the inefficient use and non-repayment of loans. The main sources of financing the activities of small and medium-sized businesses are state budget funds, credit resources of commercial banks, credit lines of international and foreign banks and financial institutions.

Two mechanisms of state financial assistance to small and medium entrepreneurs have been established in Azerbaijan. The first mechanism is providing credit concessions in the form of subsidies to farms. Through this mechanism, it was ensured that the percentage of the loans received by the farms from the commercial banks was paid instead of the farmers at the expense of the budget funds. The second mechanism is the implementation of investment assistance to small businesses. For this purpose, it is planned to allocate funds from the state budget. These funds are directed to investment projects in the priority directions of entrepreneurship in the form of preferential long-term loans based on competition. However, the difficulties of entrepreneurial

activity in the field of production in the republic and the issue of credit guarantee do not allow full use of these sources of financial resources for small and medium entrepreneurs. Commercial banks are an important source of financing for small and medium-sized businesses. In recent times, the share of long-term loans in the structure of loans allocated in this direction has increased. This has had a significant impact on the development of small and medium enterprises.

Difficulties in the financial situation of small and medium-sized businesses have also been one of the factors that have a negative impact on their development. The research shows that the high real interest rate, the weak development of the financial market and banking structure, the low turnover rate of various components of the money supply, the lack of flexible and efficient interaction mechanism between the financial sphere and the real production sectors, etc. is one of the important factors that determine its increase. The main factors that make it difficult for small and medium-sized entrepreneurs to widely use bank loans are the caution of banks due to the high risk of lending to small and medium-sized businesses, the limitation of collateral security opportunities for small and medium-sized entrepreneurs, the high interest rate of loans, and the lack of experience of entrepreneurs that will attract the interest of banks. It can be attributed to the inability to prepare a plan, the entrepreneurs not having the necessary information about credit sources and conditions.

Commercial banks provide financial assistance to small and medium entrepreneurs by providing loans together with international and foreign financial institutions within the framework of development programs of small and medium enterprises in Azerbaijan. At present, loans from the International Finance Corporation and the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development are available for the private banks of Azerbaijan. The volume of the credit line of the International Finance Corporation amounts to 3.4 million US dollars and is aimed at expanding, modernizing business for small and medium-sized entrepreneurs, financing the working capital of the trade department. The volume of the credit line of the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development is 20 million US dollars. It is intended for state-owned enterprises that are in the stage of creation of enterprises, privatization. The loan is directed to the purchase of equipment, working capital, financing of the trade department to open, expand and modernize the business. International organizations and financial institutions implement various programs that benefit small and medium-sized businesses. Some of them provide training and technical assistance to financial institutions in order to expand their development and lending opportunities. Others provide direct assistance to small and medium-sized businesses.

Credit lines for 6 exemplary farms, a macrocredit scheme sponsored by the United States Agency for International Development, a humanitarian office of the European Union for internally displaced persons, as well as a microcredit program for the development of agriculture and other programs are operating in Azerbaijan. As it can be seen, there are a number of domestic and foreign organizations engaged in the financing of small and medium enterprises in the republic. The amount of financial resources that can be used in the small and medium business sector cannot be considered sufficient compared to their needs, not used. The mechanism of distribution and use of these resources is not adapted to the characteristics of small and medium entrepreneurs, especially those who have just started their entrepreneurial activities. Therefore, it is important to adapt the financial service market to the needs of small and medium-sized entrepreneurs and increase the stimulating role of financial resources.

From the examination of the possibilities of using the financial resources of small and medium enterprises, it can be concluded that a number of measures should be taken for them to use the available financial resources on a large scale. In the state budget, full use of the funds provided for investment assistance to small businesses and credit concessions to farms should be ensured. On the one hand, this will increase the level of providing financial resources to small and medium entrepreneurs, and on the other hand, it will increase the amount of financial resources

of this source. Because the funds directed to small and medium entrepreneurs from the budget do not return, they are given to small businesses again. Thus, the funds used for small and medium enterprises every year are almost in addition to the funds allocated from the budget. In order to make full use of the budget funds, the mechanism of its use should be simplified, it would be appropriate to direct a part of these funds to entrepreneurial activity in priority areas, and the other part to entrepreneurial activity in all areas. The annual interest rate of the loan directed to priority areas can be kept at the current level, while the annual interest rate of the loan directed to other areas can be set at the level of the Central Bank's interest rate.

Budget funds are a favorable source of finance for small and medium-sized entrepreneurs in the Republic (both in terms of interest rate and duration), and the lack of full use of this source has a negative impact on the development of small and medium-sized entrepreneurs. In order to increase the role of commercial banks in meeting the financial needs of small and medium-sized entrepreneurs, it is important to give certain tax incentives to banks that provide loans to small and medium-sized entrepreneurs, to take other stimulating measures, to create bank activists in the regions of the republic, and to increase their experience of working with small and medium-sized entrepreneurs. The issue of loan security has a significant impact on the ability of small and medium-sized businesses to get loans from banks. Small and medium-sized entrepreneurs do not have or have little property to pledge for a loan, which prevents banks from lending to them. Therefore, it is appropriate to create a mechanism for providing loans to small and medium entrepreneurs in the republic.

The possibility of establishing a state bank specialized in small and medium entrepreneurs should also be studied. Credit lines allocated by international and foreign financial institutions for small and medium-sized entrepreneurs are usually provided through commercial banks. Here, the problems related to banks arise again, the interest rate of loans from foreign sources is also high, the obligations taken by banks to financial institutions that open credit lines prompt them to approach lending more cautiously and, as a result, limit the opportunities for small and medium-sized entrepreneurs to use international and foreign financial resources. Therefore, new financial mechanisms and tools should be created to expand the opportunities for small and medium-sized entrepreneurs to use the financial resources of international organizations and foreign financial institutions.

In the current period, the importance of microcredit mechanisms has increased in the countries of the world. Microcredit has proven its importance in attracting small enterprises and a wide segment of the population to entrepreneurial activity and their active participation in the development of the economy. Despite the increase in the number of small businesses in the Republic, and the population's interest in entrepreneurial activity, many of them do not have savings and need a small amount of credit to start their activities. The simplicity of the microcredit scheme ensures their widespread use of this credit. Because it is not necessary to prepare many documents, the procedure of getting a loan is free from bureaucratic obstacles. Therefore, it would be appropriate to take measures in the field of creating microcredit schemes in the republic.

The use of non-commercial alternatives to the small business financial services market can also play an important role. World experience shows that the establishment of a self-help system for small entrepreneurs, that is, mutual financial aid institutions, can play an important role in meeting their need for small loans. For this purpose, Credit Unions are being established in Azerbaijan, and their number has reached 100. On the one hand, the importance of Credit Unions is explained by the creation of mutual lending opportunities, on the other hand, it creates the opportunity to attract loans for its members from other financial institutions based on this collective guarantee. Expanding the opportunities of small and medium-sized entrepreneurs to use financial resources requires a change in the attitude of entrepreneurs and the population as a whole to credit. Every borrower should know that taking a loan in the market economy is a big

risk. When taking a loan, its effective use should be carefully analyzed based on the business plan, all possible risks should be identified and appropriate precautions should be taken.

Thus, as can be seen from the research, "the tasks defined in the State Aid Program for small and medium enterprises in the Republic of Azerbaijan have been mostly fulfilled. In our country, the legal base of small and medium entrepreneurship (SME) has been created and developed, significant progress has been made in the field of entrepreneurship regulation. Structures that provide education, information and consulting services to SMEs have been expanded and their activities have been strengthened, necessary steps have been taken in the direction of the formation of financial support mechanisms for SMEs, reduction of the tax burden for entrepreneurs, and strengthening of the stimulating role of the tax system. Purposeful measures have been taken in the field of the formation of the mechanism for the protection of the rights and legal interests of entrepreneurs. In order to prevent illegal interference in entrepreneurial activities and to eliminate unreasonable inspections, the implementation of the "Control Manual" has been started. The activity of the regional infrastructures of KOS has expanded. Significant results have been achieved in the direction of the formation of social and professional knowledge of entrepreneurs. Cooperation with international regional and national organizations of foreign countries has been expanded in the field of SME development. In addition, the opportunities created by the macroeconomic stability prevailing in the country's economy have not been fully used for the purposes of accelerating the development of SMEs. The number of people engaged in entrepreneurial activity is less than the available opportunities. Although the private sector has a high specific weight in the country's economy, enterprises with strategically important structure-forming potential are still underdeveloped in this section. The impact of the SME sector on strengthening the country's export potential and improving its structure is limited. The current level of regional development of the entrepreneur does not correspond to the existing potential of the country. So, now 70 percent of SME enterprises are concentrated in Baku city and its surroundings. Relations between domestic producers are developing poorly, and the cooperation and integration of large enterprises into SMEs has not reached the necessary level. Accelerating the development of SMEs in Azerbaijan, as in the world experience, forming an efficient market economy system of this sector and adapting it to the international economic environment, solving the economic and social problems of the region expanding its role in the solution is one of the leading directions of the state's economic policy. For this purpose, the framework of state aid measures for the development of the SME sector is expanded and their targeting is strengthened.

The role of the small business sector in the economy, the laws of its formation, its current situation and development prospects and problems in the country were investigated and the following important results were obtained: One of the main factors of creating a perfect market environment in the transition to new economic relations is the formation and development of entrepreneurship. There is no unified opinion on the concept of development of entrepreneurial activity in scientific literature. When studying the economic nature of entrepreneurship, it is appropriate to start with the study of the ethnology of this word itself and its stages of development.

Various indicators are used to characterize the activity of small and medium-sized businesses, in particular, investment activity and financial status. In other words, the complex analysis of the indicator system of statistics of small and medium-sized enterprises allows to comprehensively characterize the situation of economic entities and the demand for funds, as well as to predict the financial strategy in the market economy. The research shows that small and medium-sized business in the Republic of Azerbaijan has formed its own potential. In other words, the current level of development of small and medium-sized entrepreneurship corresponds to the initial stage of the formation of a market-type economy and is still far from the full realization of

its potential opportunities. At the same time, despite the inefficiency of its sectoral structure, during the period of economic reforms in the country, there was a positive trend in the development process of small and medium enterprises.

Literature

1. Azerbaijan small entrepreneurship, Sada publishing house, Baku, 2015
2. Social and economic indicators of the Republic of Azerbaijan, ADSK, "Seda" publishing house, 2015
3. A. O. Bainov, I. N. Shapkin "Small entrepreneurship". Moscow 2003
4. N.K. Syropolis. Management of financial business. Moscow. 2002
5. www.stat.gov.az

Foreign experience in stimulating urbanisation processes

Digel Ivan

Researcher, RSE “Institute of economics” Science Committee of the Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Republic of Kazakhstan

Kopbossynova Alua

Junior Researcher, RSE “Institute of economics” Science Committee of the Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Republic of Kazakhstan

Annotation

This article explores the promotion of urbanisation and urban development using the example of cities in Europe and Asia. It discusses key aspects of urban development such as smart cities, green infrastructure, environmental sustainability, public spaces and inclusive urban planning. The main objective of this article is to provide a comprehensive analysis of strategies and best practices for stimulating urbanisation through improving the quality and efficiency of urban services, and developing public spaces as multifunctional facilities that not only serve recreational purposes but also promote community cohesion, cultural expression and economic vitality. The authors emphasise the importance of infrastructure development, resource management and participatory urban planning. The article also emphasises the need to invest in the training and development of urban development actors and provides recommendations for improving urban planning and development strategies in Kazakhstan based on global experience.

The article was prepared as part of the implementation of the GF project “Organizational and economic mechanism of managed urbanization in the post-pandemic period” (IRN: AP09260795).

Key words: urbanization, urban development, smart cities, green infrastructure, environmental sustainability, public spaces.

Urbanization, as the process of population movement from rural areas to cities, has been a defining trend for the past several centuries. Historically, the attractiveness of cities has been driven by the promise of better economic opportunities, an improved quality of life, and access to amenities. As industrialization took root, cities became hubs for job concentration, particularly in factories, which only accelerated their growth.

Urbanization not only increases population density but also brings about changes in the socio-economic and cultural structure of society. Cities often become melting pots of diversity, fostering innovation, cultural exchange, and economic growth. According to the World Bank, cities occupy only 3% of the Earth's land area but account for 80% of the global GDP [1]. This underscores the economic power and significance of urban areas.

However, along with the advantages of urbanization come challenges. Rapid and unplanned urban growth can lead to infrastructure overload, housing shortages, and environmental degradation. The proliferation of informal settlements or slums in many growing cities is evidence of the need for planned urban development. The role of urban services becomes paramount. They are not just conveniences but crucial components that define the quality of urban life. Well-designed and efficiently managed urban services and public spaces can alleviate many issues arising from rapid urbanization, making cities more livable, resilient, and sustainable.

They become key elements in shaping the urban fabric, extending beyond mere infrastructure components and influencing the socio-cultural and economic viability of cities.

Urban services, including communal services such as water supply, electricity supply, waste disposal, and transportation, are an integral part of the daily functioning of cities. Efficient urban services ensure the uninterrupted operation of a city, promoting economic growth and an improved quality of life. For instance, a reliable public transportation system not only provides mobility but also reduces traffic congestion and environmental pollution.

Public spaces, possessing cultural, aesthetic, historical, and even utilitarian qualities, complement and enhance the quality of these services [2]. At the same time, public places, including parks and squares, serve as community hubs, facilitating interaction and community cohesion. There is evidence of the crucial role of public spaces in integrating industry and the city and reimagining public services [3]. These spaces are essential for cultural events, public gatherings, and recreational activities, improving the quality of life. There is also evidence that the proper development of public spaces can improve the environmental conditions of cities and contribute to sustainable development [4]. As cities continue to grow, strategic development and management of their growth become of paramount importance.

The history of urbanization is rich and diverse: cities around the world have employed various methods and strategies over centuries to promote growth, sustainability, and the improvement of their residents' quality of life. Several historical and traditional methods of urbanization stand out, reflecting the socio-cultural, economic, and environmental contexts of different eras and regions.

Morphological Evolution. One of the primary pathways for urban growth is morphological evolution, where the spatial structure and design of cities change over time “naturally”, based on the needs and activities of the inhabitants. This path is deeply intertwined with the historical trajectory of urban development: urban spaces evolve, reflecting changing needs and aspirations of its residents. For example, cities like Famagusta have been studied to understand their spatial growth using tools such as GIS, revealing patterns of human activity and movement within urban spaces [5]. This is the most challenging path of urbanization to control, as it implies indirect management through stimulating desirable activities by residents. A variation of this path is **linear expansion**, where some cities have grown along trade routes or rivers, vital transportation arteries. This allowed cities to remain connected to crucial trade and transportation networks, fostering economic growth and cultural exchange [6]. Another variation is **concentric growth**, where cities expand outward in concentric circles from a central point, often an important landmark or trading center. This kept the city core dynamic and accessible, while new developments expanded beyond its boundaries [7].

Harmonization with the Environment. Traditional urbanization in many cities, especially in China, emphasized harmonizing urban development with the natural environment. Cities were developed to maintain a balance between built spaces and natural landscapes, ensuring sustainability and ecological balance. The historic city of Pingyao serves as an example of this approach, where urban planning focused on the spatial connection between urban areas and their natural surroundings [8]. This path requires a certain level of planning as it necessitates a deliberate consideration of the interaction between urban space and the surrounding natural environment.

Development Planning implies the presence of centralized authority that intentionally shapes urban space to achieve specific goals. There are several variations of this approach. **Grid-based planning** is a common one, where urban districts are laid out in a grid-like pattern (not necessarily rectangular). This planning method was a distinctive feature of several ancient civilizations, including the Indus Valley and ancient Greece. It allowed for efficient land use, easy navigation, and systematic expansion [9]. Another method of planned expansion is the **creation of**

satellite cities. These are cities built around another city, supporting its economy. This approach enabled the creation of multiple “small cores” of cities around a major city, reducing population concentration and infrastructure burden [10]. There was also the method of **creating urban corridors** in regions where the landscape did not permit uniform expansion, especially in areas with dense vegetation or complex terrain. This approach facilitated communication between different parts of the city, ensuring smooth movement and trade [11].

Essentially, historical and traditional methods of urbanization demonstrate how cities developed almost “from scratch”. They underscore the importance of understanding the past to inform modern urban development strategies. However, these methods may not be well-suited for use in contemporary urbanization conditions, as they often involved the creation of entirely new cities or a lack of sufficient control over urban development. In current circumstances, such approaches can lead to “false urbanization” and other problems associated with uncontrolled urban growth [12].

In the modern era, urbanization is influenced by technological advancements, changing societal needs, and a heightened focus on environmental sustainability. As cities continue to grow and develop, contemporary methods of urbanization have emerged, offering innovative solutions to urban development challenges. Urban planning is a complex, multifaceted task that requires a harmonious blend of technological innovations, ecological sustainability, and social inclusivity. This is why modern urbanization methods typically combine several approaches, with the main ones outlined below.

Modern urbanization recognizes the importance of preserving cultural heritage while ensuring sustainability. In Asian cities like Penang, Hanoi, Shanghai, and Tokyo, **comprehensive revitalization** strategies have been adopted to revive old urban areas and preserve their unique character. These strategies prioritize the preservation of urban heritage while also creating environmental conditions conducive to the quality of life for residents. Striking a balance between heritage preservation and modernization, especially in the context of tourism, is a key focus of these efforts [13].

The rapid expansion of cities worldwide underscores the importance of **developing green infrastructure.** For example, Seoul has adopted a policy that places special emphasis on the development of parks and green spaces. Integrating greenery into urban planning increases the likelihood that cities will be more resilient to environmental risks [14]. Green spaces help mitigate the intensity of urban heat islands, enhance biodiversity, provide recreational areas for residents, and contribute to the overall aesthetic appeal of urban areas. Moreover, green infrastructure plays a significant role in addressing pressing environmental issues, ensuring urban sustainability, and improving the overall quality of life for city dwellers [15].

This approach effectively complements **scenario modeling for sustainable development.** In the face of urbanization challenges and water shortages, particularly in semi-arid regions, scenario modeling has become a vital tool in urban planning. This method allows urban planners to shape and visualize dynamic city development scenarios. By adapting to the challenges of urbanization through scenario modeling, cities can effectively safeguard themselves against unpredictable risks [16].

The rapid growth and transformation of cities necessitate the implementation of **spatial modeling** for urban planning. This method enables planners to understand factors contributing to informal development and propose innovative solutions for sustainability. Spatial modeling, such as the Integrated Planning Model (IPM), provides a framework that integrates urban development factors, offering valuable insights for urban planners and policymakers [17].

Modern urbanization methods reflect a holistic approach to urban development. By integrating technological advancements, environmental considerations, and societal needs, these methods ensure that cities are not only functional but also sustainable, resilient, and adaptable to

future challenges. The urban environment of the 21st century is undergoing profound changes, driven by multifaceted issues and opportunities.

At the forefront of urban innovation is the concept of the “smart city”. While not entirely new, this concept has evolved significantly in its application. The transition from earlier smart city concepts to the more advanced “Smart City 3.0” model represents a significant development in urban development ideas. Unlike older concepts primarily focused on the integration of technologies into urban spaces, “Smart City 3.0” is centered around local communities. This model emphasizes the importance of improving the quality of life, fostering the formation and development of local communities, and facilitating collaborative decision-making processes in urban planning. Consequently, the concept highlights the need to create urban spaces that are not only technologically advanced but also socially inclusive and responsive to the needs of their residents [18].

In an era characterized by rapid mobility, understanding the movements of urban populations is of paramount importance. Access to data on mobile phone usage provides urban planners with a new tool for assessing the concentration and movements of urban populations. This information allows for informed decisions related to infrastructure development, the provision of public services, and urban zoning. By understanding where people move, gather, and live, cities can optimize their resources, ensuring the efficient distribution of urban services and accessibility for all [19].

To understand the methods of stimulating urbanization, it is instructive to delve into the experience of European cities that have long been at the forefront of innovative urban planning and the development of public spaces. From their experience, valuable knowledge can be gained on how to design, manage, and integrate public spaces into the urban fabric to promote community development.

European cities are actively exploring the impact of autonomous vehicles on urban development. The integration of autonomous road vehicles into passenger transport presents both opportunities and challenges for urban planners. While these vehicles have the potential to revolutionize mobility, their impact on location choices, land use organization, and infrastructure design is substantial. Cities like Amsterdam and Stockholm are already considering the spatial consequences of autonomous vehicles, emphasizing the need for adaptive urban planning that can account for these technological advancements while ensuring sustainable urban development [20].

Some cities are increasingly recognizing the interplay between climate change, health, and the quality of urban spaces. In particular, innovative initiatives aimed at creating a sustainable urban environment that can mitigate the adverse effects of climate change while improving public health have emerged in cities such as Barcelona, Paris, and several other major cities. The planning and design of public spaces in these cities are geared towards reducing greenhouse gas emissions, improving air quality, and promoting social cohesion [21]. An unconventional but effective approach to the development of public spaces can be observed in Scandinavian cities like Oslo and Copenhagen, as well as in several other cities in Northern Europe [22]. These cities re-imagine certain unconventional spaces (such as cemeteries and industrial areas) as multifunctional public spaces.

Cities located along riverbanks or large bodies of water are actively developing waterfront development strategies in light of climate change. These projects not only enhance the aesthetic appeal of municipal areas but also increase the city's resilience to flooding and other climate change-related issues. The transformation of urban waterfronts in these cities serves as evidence of the potential for design interventions to address complex urban challenges [23].

The experience of stimulating urbanization in European cities demonstrates a prioritization of sustainability, inclusivity, and adaptability over rigid planning. Drawing on the experience of

European cities and their approach to public spaces, it is equally instructive to study the experiences of their Asian “counterparts”. The Asian continent, with its diverse cultures, rapid urbanization, and unique challenges, offers a rich source of knowledge. While these cities share some commonalities with their European counterparts, they also exhibit different approaches depending on their socio-cultural, economic, and environmental contexts.

China's path to urbanization reflects its transformative socio-economic policies. The country's approach to urban development is more planned and centralized, as there was a pressing need to control the explosive growth of cities [24]. Key features of stimulating urbanization in China include an unprecedented speed and scale of urbanization, where China could not rely on the experiences of, for instance, European cities. This is compounded by the fact that land ownership structure in China differs from that in Europe: all land belongs to the state and is managed by its officials. Those who demonstrate high economic growth and development in their assigned territories may advance in the administrative hierarchy. However, the quality of urbanization in China varies by region, with eastern regions often outpacing central and western regions. Administrative levels further influence the trajectory of urbanization, with regions enjoying greater administrative autonomy often demonstrating more successful urban development.

Rapid urbanization in Asian cities is giving rise to serious public health challenges. Cities such as Dhaka, Hanoi, and Pokhara are grappling with these issues, aiming to incorporate healthcare considerations into urban planning. While healthcare often competes with other priorities, these cities emphasize the importance of evidence-based healthcare planning. Accessibility and quality of data, especially regarding disadvantaged populations, play a crucial role in shaping healthcare policies and measures [25]. The COVID-19 pandemic has heightened attention to informal settlements and the problems they create. The spread of the virus and subsequent public health measures have had a profound impact on the lives and livelihoods of slum dwellers. This crisis underscores the need to rethink urban planning approaches that combine slum control principles with modern urban development strategies [26].

Global experiences in stimulating urbanization demonstrate a multitude of different paths that can be successfully (or unsuccessfully) combined. Kazakhstan, with its unique socio-cultural and geographical landscape, can benefit from these ideas. The experiences of European and Asian cities can be successfully adapted to meet the specific needs and aspirations of urban development in Kazakhstan. Several directions can be highlighted to stimulate urban development in the Republic:

1. Embrace the paradigms of “smart cities” with a localized approach. The “smart city 3.0” model focuses on community-oriented urban development. For Kazakh cities like Almaty and Nur-Sultan, it is crucial to ensure that technological advancements in urban planning consider local needs, promote community involvement, and enhance overall quality of life.

2. Prioritize green infrastructure and environmental sustainability. Kazakhstan should emphasize the integration of green infrastructure into urban spaces through centralized urban planning methods. Beyond aesthetics, parks, greenery, and natural features should be regarded as vital components that contribute to biodiversity conservation, alleviate environmental issues, and enhance the overall urban experience.

3. Reimagine traditional urban spaces. Kazakhstan can explore innovative ways to utilize its underutilized urban spaces. Historical sites, industrial zones, and cultural landmarks can be reimaged to promote community interaction, cultural exchange, and improved urban living.

4. Focus on inclusive urban planning: Urban spaces in Kazakhstan should be designed to be inclusive and accessible. Streets and public areas should be designed to accommodate all residents, promote social cohesion, and ensure safety and accessibility for everyone.

5. Strengthen infrastructure development. Infrastructure serves as the foundation of urban development. Kazakhstan should give priority to the development of reliable transportation networks, efficient waste management systems, and energy supply. Modern infrastructure can enhance mobility, ensure sustainability, and improve the overall quality of urban life.

6. Efficient resource management. As urban centers grow, efficient resource management becomes paramount. Kazakhstan should adopt integrated resource management strategies that optimize water, energy, and other essential resources. This not only ensures sustainability but also reduces costs and enhances the resilience of urban centers.

7. Facilitating collaborative urban planning. Joint efforts involving government institutions, private enterprises, and local communities can ensure holistic urban planning. Such partnerships can guarantee that urban strategies are comprehensive, inclusive, and aligned with broader national development goals.

8. Investing in capacity building and training. To address the complexities of modern urban development, it is crucial to invest in capacity building. Urban planners, policymakers, and stakeholders need to be equipped with the necessary skills and knowledge, facilitated through training programs and seminars.

9. Establishing monitoring and evaluation mechanisms. To assess the effectiveness of urban initiatives, reliable monitoring and evaluation systems must be established. These systems can provide feedback, enabling continuous improvement of urban planning and development strategies.

Research into urbanization processes with a focus on urban services and public spaces has provided a comprehensive understanding of the multifaceted nature of urban development. Drawing from global experiences, especially in European and Asian cities, the research has identified several key conclusions that are of paramount importance for the development of cities in Kazakhstan.

There is a need for technology integration tailored to local needs. The significance of green infrastructure has become a recurring theme, emphasizing its role in biodiversity conservation, mitigating environmental issues, and enhancing the urban experience. Traditional urban spaces, when reimagined, can become vibrant hubs of public interaction and cultural exchange. Furthermore, the importance of inclusive urban planning has been underscored, emphasizing the need for urban spaces that are accessible, safe, and meet the needs of all residents.

Infrastructure development and resource management have been identified as key areas for the future of Kazakhstan's cities. Reliable transportation networks, efficient waste management systems, and robust energy grids can significantly improve the quality of urban life. Simultaneously, effective resource management, particularly for water and energy resources, will be crucial for ensuring the sustainability and resilience of urban centers.

LIST OF SOURCES

1. Urban Development. Overview. // World Bank. – 2022. – URL: <https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/urbandevelopment/overview>

2. Stojanovski T. Urban design and public transportation–public spaces, visual proximity and Transit-Oriented Development (TOD) //Journal of Urban Design. – 2020. – Vol. 25. – No. 1. – pp. 134-154.

3. Keskinok H. Ç. Urban planning experience of Turkey in the 1930s. // ODTÜ Mimarlık Fakültesi Dergisi. – 2010. – Vol. 27. – No2. – pp. 173-188.

4. Wang H., Pei Z. Urban green corridors analysis for a rapid urbanization city exemplified in Gaoyou City, Jiangsu //Forests. – 2020. – Vol. 11. – No. 12. – pp. 1374.

5. Atakara C., Allahmoradi M. Investigating the urban spatial growth by using space syntax and GIS—a case study of famagusta city //ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information. – 2021. – Vol. 10. – №. 10. – pp. 638.
6. Liu J., Zhan J., Deng X. Spatio-temporal patterns and driving forces of urban land expansion in China during the economic reform era //AMBIO: a journal of the human environment. – 2005. – Vol. 34. – №. 6. – pp. 450-455.
7. Blumenfeld H. On the concentric-circle theory of urban growth //Land Economics. – 1949. – Vol. 25. – №. 2. – pp. 209-212.
8. Li X. et al. Traditional thoughts and modern development of the historical urban landscape in China: Lessons learned from the example of Pingyao historical city //Land. – 2022. – Vol. 11. – №. 2. – pp. 247.
9. Ross E., Bigon L. The urban grid and entangled planning cultures in Senegal //Planning Perspectives. – 2018.
10. Vertinskaya T., Bogdanovich A., Bulko O. Conceptual model of development of Minsk satellite cities. – Litres, 2022. (Published in Russian)
11. Zhang Y. et al. Urban development trend analysis and spatial simulation based on time series remote sensing data: A case study of Jinan, China //Plos one. – 2021. – Vol. 16. – №. 10. – pp. e0257776.
12. Maneshin, S. Yu., Orlov, E. V., & Sergeeva, E. A. The impact of false urbanization on city residents //Journal of sociological research. – 2020. – Vol. 5. – №. 4. – pp. 25-28. (Published in Russian)
13. Sing T. Y., Yoh S. Rehabilitation Methods and Revitalization Strategies in the Old Inner-City Areas of Rapid Growth Cities in Asia A comparison of four cities: Penang, Hanoi, Shanghai, and Tokyo //Urban and Regional Planning Review. – 2016. – Vol. 3. – pp. 1-20.
14. Choi J., Kim G. History of Seoul’s parks and green space policies: Focusing on policy changes in urban development //Land. – 2022. – Vol. 11. – №. 4. – pp. 474.
15. Danilina N., Tsurenkova K., Berkovich V. Evaluating urban green public spaces: The case study of Krasnodar region cities, Russia //Sustainability. – 2021. – Vol. 13. – №. 24. – pp. 14059.
16. Hanoon S. K. et al. Using scenario modelling for adapting to urbanization and water scarcity: Towards a sustainable city in semi-arid areas //Periodicals of Engineering and Natural Sciences. – 2022. – Vol. 10. – №. 1. – pp. 518-532.
17. Aldeek Z. A. O., Mistarihi M. Z. Towards a modern design of undeveloped city using a spatial modelling analysis; a case study of Irbid City in Jordan //International Journal of Sustainable Development and Planning. – 2020. – Vol. 15. – №. 4. – pp. 547-557.
18. Szarek-Iwaniuk P., Senetra A. Access to ICT in Poland and the co-creation of urban space in the process of modern social participation in a smart city—A case study //Sustainability. – 2020. – Vol. 12. – №. 5. – pp. 2136.
19. Yang J. et al. Challenges of using mobile phone signalling data to estimate urban population density: towards smart cities and sustainable urban development //Indoor and Built Environment. – 2020. – Vol. 29. – №. 2. – pp. 147-150.
20. Gavanas N. Autonomous road vehicles: Challenges for urban planning in European cities //Urban Science. – 2019. – Vol. 3. – №. 2. – pp. 61.
21. Orsetti E. et al. Building resilient cities: climate change and health interlinkages in the planning of public spaces //International journal of environmental research and public health. – 2022. – Vol. 19. – №. 3. – pp. 1355.
22. Grabalov P., Nordh H. The future of urban cemeteries as public spaces: Insights from Oslo and Copenhagen //Planning Theory & Practice. – 2022. – Vol. 23. – №. 1. – pp. 81-98.

23. Dal Cin F., Hooimeijer F., Matos Silva M. Planning the urban waterfront transformation, from infrastructures to public space design in a sea-level rise scenario: The european union prize for contemporary architecture case //Water. – 2021. – Vol. 13. – №. 2. – pp. 218.

24. Singh R. B. (ed.). Urban development challenges, risks and resilience in Asian mega cities. – Tokyo : Springer, 2015. – pp. 2020-2025.

25. Mirzoev T. et al. Is evidence-informed urban health planning a myth or reality? Lessons from a qualitative assessment in three Asian cities //Health policy and planning. – 2019. – Vol. 34. – №. 10. – pp. 773-783.

26. Patel A., Shah P. Rethinking slums, cities, and urban planning: lessons from the COVID-19 pandemic //Cities & Health. – 2021. – Vol. 5. – №. sup1. – pp. S145-S147.

Применение интернет-маркетинга в целях привлечения перспективных студентов

Курмангалиев Аслан Санжарович

Студент университета Туран, магистратура 2 курс, Алматы

Научный Руководитель: Розакова Дина Ибрагимовна

Абстракт

В статье обосновывается необходимость более активного применения интернет-маркетинга в сфере высшего образования Казахстана. Определены основные этапы развития интернет-маркетинга и интернет-маркетинга образовательных услуг, в частности, а также представлен обзор практик применения инструментов интернет-маркетинга высшими учебными заведениями ряда зарубежных стран. В заключении сформулированы выводы и предложения по использованию интернет-маркетинга казахстанскими вузами.

Ключевые слова: интернет-маркетинг, высшее образование, перспективный студент

Введение

Онлайн присутствие важно в деле привлечения идеального клиента [1]. В сфере высшего образования данная задача решается посредством применения интернет-маркетинга образовательных услуг, а идеальным клиентом является абитуриент, который лидирует по результатам вступительных тестирований или экзаменов и принимает решение о выборе вуза (перспективный студент).

Стартовавшее с 1970х годов развитие интернет-технологий способствовало развитию интернет-маркетинга в сфере высшего образования и проведению исследований в данной области [2-5]. Данное направление в маркетинговой деятельности казахстанских вузов является новым и слабо изученным. Обзор литературы по изучаемой теме показывает, что в сравнении с вузами зарубежных стран казахстанские вузы уступают в части использования инструментов интернет-маркетинга.

Целью данной статьи является формирование предложений по более активному использованию интернет-маркетинга вузами страны, что будет способствовать повышению их конкурентоспособности на рынке образовательных услуг. В первой части статьи обосновывается актуальность проблемы применения интернет-маркетинга в сфере высшего образования Казахстана, во второй – представлен обзор по основным этапам развития интернет-маркетинга и практикам зарубежных вузов по успешному продвижению образовательных услуг в интернете. Заключительная часть статьи содержит выводы и предложения.

Актуальность внедрения интернет-маркетинга в сфере высшего образования

Сохранению спроса на высшее образование способствует общепринятое восприятие о возможностях более выгодного трудоустройства выпускников вузов [6]. Данные Бюро национальной статистики подтверждают справедливость этого утверждения. Согласно опросу 2022 года (апрель месяц), заработная плата работников с высшим образованием в стране была выше заработной платы работников со средним образованием более чем в 1,8

раза (337 222 и 182 563 тенге, соответственно). Однако, востребованность образовательных услуг вузов зависит и от демографических факторов; в условиях сокращения числа абитуриентов конкуренция среди вузов за перспективных студентов усиливается [6-7]. Сравнение численности принятых и обучающихся студентов в динамике за 2000-2022 годы показывает, что за последние два десятилетия наметилась тенденция сокращения (см. Рисунок 1), которая может быть преодолена при устойчивых темпах роста численности молодежи, людей в возрасте от 16 до 35 лет – целевой аудитории вузов.

Рисунок 1. Прием и численность студентов вузов в Казахстане за 2000-2022 годы

* График составлен автором по данным Бюро национальной статистики Агентства по стратегическому планированию и реформам Республики Казахстан. <https://stat.gov.kz/>

Изменения количества вузов (фактор предложения) также влияют на конкуренцию на рынке образовательных услуг. Число вузов в Казахстане, по данным Бюро национальной статистики, сократилось со 170 в 2000 году до 116 в 2022 году. По классической теории маркетинга, уменьшение количества продавцов (в нашем случае – вузов, как поставщиков образовательных услуг) ведет к ослаблению конкуренции. Но наблюдаемое сокращение числа казахстанских вузов связано с ужесточением требований, предъявляемых к образовательной деятельности [8], а образовательные услуги продолжают оказываться в конкурентной среде, так как рынок представлен более 100 организациями. Конкуренция по фактору предложения также не будет ослабевать в связи с инициативами по открытию в стране филиалов зарубежных вузов. Например, открытие в городе Алматы филиала британского Университета Де Монсфорд Лестер, передача Северо-Казахстанского университета им. М. Козыбаева в доверительное управление Университету Аризоны, а также планы по открытию филиалов Национального исследовательского ядерного университета

«МИФИ», Российского государственного университета нефти и газа им. И. М. Губкина, Московского государственного технического университета им. Н. Э. Баумана [8].

Наряду с формированием спроса и повышением конкурентоспособности, интернет-маркетинг должен способствовать получению прибыли [9]. Поэтому актуализацию внедрения интернет-маркетинга можно объяснить и необходимостью решения задачи повышения экономической выгоды образовательных услуг в стране. В 2022 году, по данным Бюро национальной статистики, текущие расходы организаций высшего и послевузовского образования превысили текущие доходы на 41,4 млрд. тенге (убыток), что в 3,4 раза больше размера убытка 2020 года.

Наконец, к вышеперечисленным причинам необходимости актуализации интернет-маркетинга в сфере высшего образования можно добавить и достижения Казахстана в части обеспечения доступа населения к интернету, рост числа активных пользователей сети интернет, а также повышение уровня цифровой грамотности населения [10-11]. В наши дни решения о выборе вузов все чаще принимаются через изучение информации, размещаемой на различных онлайн-платформах, социальных сетях и поисковых системах [5]. Кроме того, сегодняшние клиенты вузов – перспективные студенты, как представители поколения Z, и их родители – благодаря интернету и новым цифровым технологиям лучше осведомлены и, поэтому, более требовательны к процессу получения высшего образования [5, 12].

Развитие и применение инструментов интернет-маркетинга вузами

Интернет-маркетинг и интернет-маркетинг образовательных услуг, в частности, являются предметом исследований ряда авторов. По мнению Горохова М.М., Докучаева Д. Е. и Трефиловой А.Д., интернет-маркетинг (веб-маркетинг, онлайн-маркетинг) возник «на стыке маркетинга и информационных технологий» [9]. С момента первого применения интернет-технологии в 1969 году, а именно – создания экспериментальной сети передачи информации по заданию Департамента обороны США, интернет (web) и, параллельно, интернет-маркетинг (marketing) перешли от первой к третьей стадии развития:

- 1) Web 1.0 и Marketing 1.0 – использование вебсайтов для размещения информации об организации;
- 2) Web 2.0 и Marketing 2.0 – целевое привлечение и удержание клиентов через их участие в формировании контента размещаемой в сети информации, развитие социальных сетей;
- 3) Web 3.0 и Marketing 3.0 – формирующееся направление, в основе которого лежит идея развития Семантической паутины, в которой вебсайты и приложения будут способны обрабатывать огромный поток информации, размещаемой в глобальной сети [2].

Активное развитие интернет-маркетинга объясняется возможностью привлекать и удерживать клиентов через интернет-ресурсы, решая одновременно задачу повышения экономической выгоды деятельности организации. Постоянная связь с клиентами (интерактивность), выделение целевого сегмента (таргетирование), быстрое привлечение покупателей (веб-аналитика), исследование действий клиентов (трекинг) позволили интернет-маркетингу закрепиться в качестве эффективного способа продвижения товаров и услуг [9, 13]. Фактором успеха интернет-маркетинга является также и позитивное восприятие клиентов. Методы интернет-маркетинга работают, потому что клиенты считают их легкими в применении, практичными и эффективными в изучении нового материала [14].

Интернет-маркетинг образовательных услуг возник и развивался в западных странах с опережением в сравнении с нашей страной, что объясняется более ранним применением и более быстрым освоением сети интернет. Например, все американские вузы присутствовали в интернете уже к 1997 году, что со временем позволило студентам перейти

от традиционных способов знакомства с вузами (визиты и рекламные брошюры) к получению необходимой информации через интернет; более 40% вузов использовали интернет для приема студентов; многие вузы стали практиковать проведения онлайн-курсов [15]. Главным преимуществом присутствия вузов в интернете – в контексте теории маркетинга – *создать и сохранить клиента* – стала возможность долгосрочной вовлеченности клиентов; т.е., взаимодействие с перспективными студентами стало осуществляться с момента первой коммуникации, в течение всего процесса обучения и до послевузовского периода [4, 15].

Сегодня продвижение образовательных услуг вуза в интернете может осуществляться с применением следующих инструментов:

- 1) поисковая оптимизация (search engine optimization, SEO), нацеленная на повышение посещаемости сайта вуза через размещение сайта на приоритетных местах в поисковых системах;
- 2) контекстная реклама (search engine advertising, SEA) – рекламирование продвигаемой услуги в зависимости от запроса перспективного студента;
- 3) медийная реклама – размещение в интернете статичной или интерактивной информации о продвигаемой услуге;
- 4) социальный интернет-маркетинг (social media marketing, SMM) – продвижение образовательной услуги в социальных сетях и усиливает лояльность целевой аудитории к продвигаемой услуге;
- 5) вирусный маркетинг, нацеленный на повышение осведомленности о продвигаемой услуге в социальных сетях;
- 6) интернет PR, используемый для освещения деятельности вуза на официальных интернет-ресурсах авторитетных средств массовой информации;
- 7) партнерский маркетинг – предполагает продвижение образовательной услуги через интернет-ресурсы аффилированных организаций [9].

Результативность инструментов интернет-маркетинга доказана практикой многих зарубежных вузов. Например, порядка 160 студентов поступило в один из факультетов Российского экономического университета имени Г. В. Плеханова в результате применения контекстной рекламы; техника SEO успешно применяется Московским государственным университетом имени М. В. Ломоносова, что подтверждается первым местом данного университета в поисковой системе Yandex при использовании слов поиска «рейтинг самого известного вуза России»; рост числа абитуриентов Северо-центрального университета на 25% за счет использования рекламы и целевых страниц [5, 16].

Еще одним подтверждением выгоды интернет-маркетинга образовательных услуг стала быстрая адаптация вузов в ответ на ограничительные меры, которые по всему миру предпринимались в 2020-2021 годах для предотвращения распространения коронавирусной инфекции. К примеру, многие зарубежные вузы стали практиковать проведение интерактивных туров по кампусам, видеоконференций, виртуальных мероприятий, интернет-выставок [17]. А использование программ дистанционного обучения и открытых образовательных платформ – что предполагает повышения уровня присутствия вуза в сети Интернет – признаны практиками, рекомендуемыми ЮНЕСКО [18].

Интернет-маркетинг в сфере образования Казахстана, как и в большинстве стран СНГ, стал фрагментарно применяться с 2000х годов [19-20]; однако, данное направление в маркетинговой стратегии казахстанских вузов остается слабо развитым. По мнению Зарубиной В.Р., Зарубина М. Ю. и Васильчук Е.В., в нашей стране инструменты интернет-продвижения образовательных услуг применяются не в полной мере и это отрицательно сказывается на конкурентоспособности вузов [21]. Эта ситуация требует принятия мер по более активному использованию интернет-маркетинга казахстанскими вузами.

Выводы и предложения

Наблюдаемая в динамике последних двух десятилетий тенденция сокращения численности принятых и обучающихся в казахстанских вузах студентов, инициативы по открытию филиалов зарубежных вузов, убыточность деятельности вузов, а также предпочтения перспективных студентов требуют более активного использования интернет-маркетинга в сфере высшего образования в стране.

При формировании маркетинговой стратегии вузы должны учитывать, что с точки зрения перспективных студентов, преимущества интернет-маркетинга заключаются в возможности быстрого доступа к необходимой информации и налаживании полезных коммуникаций с вузом. Этого можно достичь, если активнее использовать более широкий спектр инструментов интернет-маркетинга. Активное использование интернет-маркетинга должно предполагать лучшую видимость вуза в поисковых системах, продвижения бренда вуза в интернете (создание креативных брендовых материалов), использование методов e-коммерции, маркетинговых исследований и e-обучения, проведение рекламных компаний в социальных сетях, образовательных интернет-выставок и интернет-конференций.

Список использованной литературы

1. Kolyandov, S., & Radev, R. Internet Marketing: Modern Advertising Models for Reaching New Customers. *Trakia Journal of Sciences*, 19(1), pp 122-129, 2021. doi:10.15547/tjs.2021.s.01.017
2. Лукичева Т. А., Лезина Т. А. Эволюция интернет-маркетинга: от публикации сайта до маркетинга социальных медиа (Social Media Marketing) // *Экономика и управление*. – 2011. – №. 11 (73). – С. 87-92.
3. Байкова И. А., Канафьева В. В. Исследование эффективности продвижения образовательных услуг инструментами интернет-маркетинга // *Петербургский экономический журнал*. – 2021. – №. 1. – С. 60-77.
4. McCoy, J. C. A Comparison of Internet Marketing Methods Utilized by Higher Education Institutions. Thesis. University of Arkansas, 2011. UMI Number: 3469336
5. Рувенный И. Я., Касимова Э. Р., Кузнецова Е. В. Продвижение вуза в интернет-пространстве // *Менеджмент и маркетинг в различных сферах деятельности: сборник научных трудов/ под ред. И. Я. Рувенного; Уфимский государственный авиационный технический университет – Уфа: УГАТУ, 2021. – 164 с.*
6. Kisiołek A. The internet as an element of marketing strategies of polish universities during recent years [Online] // *Economic Processes Management: International Scientific E-Journal*. 2015. № 4. Available: http://epm.fem.sumdu.edu.ua/download/2015_4/2015_4_10.pdf
7. T. Wu, V. Naidoo (eds.). The Role of International Marketing in Higher Education. Chapter 1 in *International Marketing of Higher Education*, 2016. doi 10.1057/978-1-137-54291-5_1
8. Бурангулов Э. Р. Государственная политика в сфере высшего образования в современном Казахстане: особенности и тенденции развития // *Каспийский регион: политика, экономика, культура*. – 2023. – №. 1 (74). – С. 64-67.
9. Горохов М. М., Докучаев Д. Е., Трефилова А. Д. Интернет-маркетинг: стратегия и виды // *Социально-экономическое управление: теория и практика*. – 2019. - № 1(36). – С. 21-24.
10. Беузова А. А., Алишеров А. А. Особенности интернет-маркетинга в сфере высшего образования: управленческие и финансовые аспекты // *Финансовое просвещение*. – 2021. – С. 201-208.
11. Уразбаева Г. Т. Цифровизация образования: основные понятия и проблемы // *Понятийный аппарат педагогики и образования*. – 2023. – С. 280-288.
12. Николаев В. К. Экспорт образования в вузах России в условиях новой реальности // *Высшее образование в России*. – 2022. – №. 2. – С. 149-166.
13. Дьячкова Е. Н. Интернет-маркетинг как инновационное направление современной концепции маркетинга // *Белгородский экономический вестник*. – 2014. – №. 4. – С. 128-138.
14. Aravinthan, M. M., & Stanley, T. S. Assessing the Impact of Present Internet-based Digital Marketing on Both Consumers and Businesses. *International Management Review*, 19, 2023.
15. Kittle, B., & Ciba, D. Using College Web Sites for Student Recruitment: A Relationship Marketing Study. *Journal of Marketing for Higher Education*, 11(3), 2001.
16. Соколова Е.В., Копытовских А.В. Маркетинг в сфере высшего образования. Менеджмент и маркетинг: современное состояние, технологии и тенденции развития: сборник научных статей [Электронный ресурс] / отв. ред. Е. А. Ильина, Г. Л. Белов. – Чебоксары: Чуваш. гос. пед. ун-т, 2021. – 256 с.
17. Gregory, J. 10 ways students search colleges today—and how to adapt. February, 2014. <https://universitybusiness.com>

18. Сейтбаткалова А., Мукан С., Таменова С. Анализ цифровых платформ обучения университетов: отечественный и зарубежный опыт // *Central Asian Economic Review*. – 2021. – №. 2. – С. 169-179.
19. Ачкасова О. Г. Образовательный маркетинг вуза на этапе цифровой трансформации высшего образования // *Профессиональное образование в России и за рубежом*. – 2020. – №. 4 (40). – С. 54-60.
20. Ebzeeva Yu.N., Gishkaeva L.N. Improving the Competitiveness of Education in Russia at the International Level. *Logos et Praxis*, 2023, vol. 22, no. 1, pp. 62-72. (in Russian). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.15688/lp.jvolsu.2023.1.8>
21. Зарубина В. Р., Зарубин М. Ю., Васильчук Е. В. Продвижение образовательных услуг вуза в условиях цифровизации // *Вестник университета «Туран»*. – 2022. – №. 4. – С. 300-310.

Продвижение образовательных услуг вузов через сайты и социальные сети

Курмангалиев Аслан Санжарович

Студент университета Туран, магистратура 2 курс, Алматы

Научный Руководитель: Розакова Дина Ибрагимовна

Абстракт

В статье – на основе обзора результатов исследований зарубежных и казахстанских авторов – определены тренды и пробелы в области изучения практики применения сайтов и социальных сетей казахстанскими вузами. Представлены результаты оценки использования сайтов и социальных сетей шестью наиболее видимыми в интернете вузами страны. По итогам обзора литературы и оценки обосновывается необходимость проведения большего числа исследований, посвященных использованию эффективных техник интернет-маркетинга в сфере высшего образования в Казахстане.

Ключевые слова: интернет-маркетинг, сайт, социальные сети, высшие учебные заведения (вузы)

Введение

Сайты и социальные сети становятся наиболее востребованными и эффективными инструментами интернет-маркетинга в сфере высшего образования, которые применяются для формирования спроса на образовательные услуги – удержания посетителей сайтов и подписчиков сетей и их перехода в статус потребителей услуг, т.е. будущих студентов вузов. Доступ населения к интернету (17,3 млн. человек или 89,2% населения страны) и резкий рост числа пользователей социальных сетей с преобладанием в среди них доли молодежи (см. Рисунок 1) – потенциальных клиентов казахстанских вузов – обуславливают необходимость активного внедрения новых и эффективных техник продвижения образовательных услуг через сайты и социальные сети.

Рисунок 1. Объем и возрастной портрет аудитории социальных сетей в Казахстане

* График составлен автором по данным Инновационного digital-хаба Wunder Digital. <https://digitalbusiness.kz/2023-05-23/proniknovenie-interneta-v-kazahstane>

Активное использование сайтов и социальных сетей вузами и перспективными студентами стало трендом; эти инструменты интернет-маркетинга в высшем образовании используются для привлечения перспективных студентов, поддержания коммуникаций со всеми заинтересованными лицами, повышения комфортности образовательного процесса, продвижения имиджа вуза [1-7]. Обзор литературы по изучаемой теме показывает, что применение сайтов и социальных сетей в сфере высшего образования в Казахстане является малоизученным [8-11]. Поэтому целью данной статьи является оценка использования сайтов и официальных страниц в социальных сетях вузами нашей страны и формирование предложений по будущим исследованиям, которые будут содействовать эффективному использованию инструментов интернет-маркетинга в сфере высшего образования. В первой части статьи представлены результаты обзора литературы по изучаемой теме, во второй – дана оценка практики казахстанских вузов по использованию сайтов и социальных сетей (на примере шести наиболее видимых в интернете вузов). Заключительная часть статьи содержит выводы и предложения.

Обзор литературы

Использование сайтов и социальных сетей в качестве инструментов интернет-маркетинга в сфере высшего образования является одним из популярных направлений современных исследований. Цели и предмет этих исследований обновлялись с развитием новых интернет-технологий; 1990-ые годы – активное продвижение сайтов, 2000ые – поисковых систем, 2010-ые – социальных сетей [12].

Киттл Б. и Сиба Д., в рамках исследования применения американскими вузами сайтов для привлечения студентов, проанализировали контент сайтов 228 американских вузов о процедурах приема, преподавательском составе и турах (посещение вузов в формате дня открытых дверей). Согласно выводам авторов, университеты и колледжи в полной мере реализуют интерактивный потенциал интернета, создавая и поддерживая с перспективными студентами эффективные двусторонние коммуникации через свои сайты [2]. Поисковые системы и выход через них на сайты вузов стали активно использоваться перспективными студентами для выбора подходящего вуза, а вузы, в свою очередь, стали использовать сайты для приема студентов; к 2010 году 99% американских вузов через свои сайты предоставляли клиентам возможность онлайн подачи заявок на поступление, 76% – возможность онлайн регистрации на прохождение курсов по программе обучения [13]. Исследование официальных страниц пяти топовых вузов – *Массачусетский технологический институт, Гарвардский университет, Кембриджский университет, Стэнфордский университет, Калифорнийский технологический институт* – в Instagram показало, что данная платформа стала основным средством получения информации, общения и взаимодействия между вузами и пользователями сети [14].

Активное использование сайтов и социальных сетей – тренды, характерные и для российского рынка образовательных услуг. Первые сайты (сайты-визитки) российских вузов трансформировались в крупные информационные порталы, на которых размещается информация, необходимая для всех заинтересованных лиц – абитуриенты и их родители, государственные органы, работодатели [4, 15]. По мнению Керн К.Е., сайт является эффективным способом взаимодействия между университетом и его клиентами, а наличие сайта на иностранном языке повышает конкурентоспособность вуза на международном рынке образовательных услуг [16]. Николаев В.К. отмечает, что социальные сети стали главной площадкой для общения с потенциальными студентами; российские вузы используют Twitter для размещения информации о науке, Instagram и TikTok – историй о жизни студентов, Facebook – об образовательных программах [17]. Опрос 110 студентов Новгородского государственного университета имени Ярослава Мудрого в возрасте 18-25

лет, проведенный Дониной И.А. и Шайдоровой Н.А., показал, что самыми популярными социальными сетями среди респондентов являются VKontakte и Instagram; по мнению авторов, социальные сети имеют большой потенциал для реализации маркетинговой стратегии вуза [4].

Несколько исследований по изучаемой теме проведено казахстанскими специалистами [8-11]. На основе анализа цифрового профиля вузов на сайтах и контент-анализа социальных сетей Конопьянова Г.А., Байкенов Ж.Е., Мамбетказиев А.Е. и Мухамбетова З.С. определили, что сайты и социальные сети являются основными средствами цифровой медиакommunikации вузов в Казахстане, а наиболее востребованными платформами – Instagram и Facebook [8]. По оценкам Зарубиной В.Р., Зарубина М. Ю. и Васильчук Е.В., основным источником трафика на сайт является прямой трафик с компьютеров (Евразийский национальный исследовательский университет имени Л.Н. Гумилева – 49%, Казахский национальный университет имени аль-Фараби – 40%), тогда как трафик с социальных сетей составляет менее 3% [9]. Авторы по результатам сравнительного (компаративного) анализа сетевого трафика делают вывод о недоиспользовании источников трафика на сайты вузов и предлагают применение специального алгоритма онлайн продвижения образовательных услуг [9].

Как показывает обзор литературы, в отличие от зарубежных стран, в нашей стране применение сайтов и социальных сетей для продвижения образовательных услуг является все еще слабо изученным и этот пробел может обострить проблему отставания в применении эффективных инструментов интернет-маркетинга в сфере высшего образования.

Методология и результаты оценки

Оценка применения сайтов и социальных сетей как инструмента интернет-маркетинга в сфере высшего образования проведена на примере шести казахстанских вузов. Выбор вузов осуществлен следующим образом. В поисковых системах Google и Yandex с применением ключевых слов «казахстанские вузы» были отобраны следующие наиболее часто встречающиеся вузы (видимость вуза в интернете):

- 1) Казахский национальный университет имени аль-Фараби (КазНУ);
- 2) Евразийский национальный исследовательский университет имени Л.Н. Гумилева (ЕНУ);
- 3) Казахский национальный аграрный исследовательский университет (КазНАИУ);
- 4) Казахский национальный исследовательский технический университет им. К.И. Сатпаева (КазНТИУ);
- 5) Южно-казахстанский государственный университет имени М. Ауезова (ЮКГУ);
- 6) Казахский педагогический университет имени Абая (КазНПУ).

Присутствие (видимость) вуза в интернете оценено с применением техники SEO (*search engine optimization, поисковая оптимизация*); для поиска использовано словосочетание «лучший вуз Казахстана». Использование сайта оценено посредством выборочного изучения информации, размещенной на сайтах отобранных вузов в августе 2023 года; изучена информация о вузе, условиях приема и обучения, а также о предлагаемых способах коммуникации с вузом. Информация оценивалась по способам размещения: использование текстового формата, визуализированных материалов, видеороликов и аудиозаписей (например, подкасты), техник прямой коммуникации (например, боты). Использование социальных сетей оценивалось посредством наличия официальной страницы вуза в социальных сетях, количества подписчиков, а также числа размещаемых материалов (публикации, видеоролики, фотоматериалы и др.).

По результатам SEO, из шести отобранных вузов в системе Google лидирует КазНУ, в системе Yandex – ЕНУ (см. Рисунок 1).

Рисунок 1. Результаты оценки лучшей видимости вуза в поисковых системах

* Скриншот сделан автором по данным поиска в Google 24 августа 2023 года.

По применению сайтов, КазНУ лидирует, так как использует наиболее эффективные и удобные форматы размещения информации, а сайт КазНАИУ уступает пяти вузам, так как использует форматы размещения информации с минимальной визуализацией; все шесть вузов не используют подкасты и техники прямой коммуникации (см. Таблицу 1).

Таблица 1. Результаты оценки использования сайтов

	Контент сайта (способы размещения информации о вузе, приеме студентов, условиях обучения и контактах с вузом)
КазНУ	Текстовый и визуализированный форматы сбалансированы; активное использование видеороликов; использование специальных (удобных) вкладок для информации по условиям поступления и обучения. Подкасты и техники прямой коммуникации не используются.
ЕНУ	Преобладает текстовый формат, использование инфографиков и презентаций; использование видеороликов; размещена информация по условиям поступления и обучения. Подкасты и техники прямой коммуникации не используются.
КазНАИУ	Преобладает текстовый формат, неактивное использование инфографиков; неактивное использование видеороликов; размещены общие сведения по условиям приема.
КазНИТУ	Текстовый и визуализированный форматы сбалансированы; активное использование видеороликов; использование 3D тура по университету. Подкасты и техники прямой коммуникации не используются.
ЮКГУ	Текстовый формат преобладает, фрагментарная визуализация; использование видеороликов; использование вкладок для информации по условиям поступления и обучения. Подкасты и техники прямой коммуникации не используются.
КазНПУ	Преобладает текстовый формат, фрагментарная визуализация; неактивное использование видеороликов; размещены общие сведения по условиям приема. Подкасты и техники прямой коммуникации не используются.

* Составлено автором по результатам изучения контента сайтов, 20-24 августа 2023 года.

По результатам оценки использования социальных сетей, первые три места распределились следующим образом – КазНУ, ЕНУ и ЮКГУ (см. Таблицу 2).

Таблица 2. Результаты оценки использования социальных сетей

	КазНУ	ЕНУ	КазНАИУ	КазНИТУ	ЮКГУ	КазНПУ
Присутствие в поисковых системах*						
Google	2	3	2	3	0	0
Yandex	3	3	3	0	2	2
Ссылки на социальные сети, размещенные на вебсайте вуза	Facebook Instagram YouTube Telegram TikTok VKontakte	Facebook Instagram YouTube Telegram TikTok	Facebook Instagram YouTube TikTok	Facebook Instagram YouTube VKontakte	Facebook Instagram YouTube Telegram TikTok VKontakte Twitter	Facebook YouTube Telegram VKontakte
Основные показатели по социальным сетям						
Facebook	1,3 тыс. подписчиков	3,2 тыс. подписчиков	3,9 тыс. подписчиков	2,4 тыс. подписчиков	2 тыс. подписчиков	621 подписчик
Instagram	30,4 тыс. подписчиков 3436 публикаций	34,7 тыс. подписчиков 1978 публикаций	11,4 тыс. подписчиков 799 публикаций	31,1 тыс. подписчиков 4376 публикаций	25 тыс. подписчиков 4307 публикаций	-
YouTube	46,7 тыс. подписчиков 1,7 тыс. видео	6,92 тыс. подписчиков 1,7 тыс. видео	97 подписчиков 78 видео	2,65 тыс. подписчиков 257 видео	5,45 тыс. подписчиков 554 видео	3,58 тыс. подписчиков 1,6 тыс. видео
Telegram	3672 подписчиков 3,81 тыс. фото 150 видео 2087 ссылок 5 файлов	6,48 тыс. подписчиков 1,83 тыс. фото 147 видео 801 ссылка 83 файла	-	-	364 подписчика 10,69 тыс. фото 399 видео 443 ссылки 1 файл	4,2 тыс. подписчиков 1000 фото 140 видео 1245 ссылок 32 файла
TikTok	1383 подписчиков 16,2 тыс. лайков	2601 подписчик 206 тыс. лайков	1984 подписчика 61,2 тыс. лайков	-	840 подписчиков 10,7 тыс. лайков	-
VKontakte	142 участника	-	-	6815 участников	2490 участников	-

* Первые 4 страницы результатов поиска по словам «казахстанские вузы», 20-22 августа 2023 года.

** Составлено автором.

Выводы и предложения

Сайты и социальные сети являются наиболее востребованными и эффективными инструментами интернет-маркетинга в сфере высшего образования во многих странах, чему способствует доступ к сети интернет и высокая активность молодежи в социальных сетях. Как показали результаты оценки практик шести казахстанских вузов, сайты и социальные сети и в нашей стране активно используются вузами для размещения информации, которая необходима для принятия решения о поступлении в вуз. Однако, в изученной области существуют определенные пробелы. Например, недостаточное использование техник SEO, отставание в использовании удобных форматов размещения информации, а также небольшая аудитория подписчиков официальных страниц вузов в социальных сетях в сравнении с общим числом пользователей сети интернет и социальных сетей в стране. Результаты оценки совпали с результатами предыдущих исследований о повышении роли сайтов и социальных сетей во взаимодействии между вузами и их клиентами, а также о пробелах в практике использования интернет-технологий в сфере высшего образования [8-11, 18].

Проведенная работа имеет ряд ограничений. Оценка проведена на примере шести вузов, тогда как в стране функционирует 116 вузов [19]. Не оценивалось содержание информации, размещаемой на сайтах и в социальных сетях вузов. Кроме того, оценка проведена автором и является субъективной. Поэтому предлагается оценить использование сайтов и социальных сетей посредством проведения опроса среди пользователей (абитуриенты и студенты). Полезным также может быть контент-анализ сайтов и публикаций вузов в социальных сайтах, а также изучение содержания форума пользователей. По примеру зарубежных стран предлагается изучить влияние инструментов интернет-маркетинга (сайты, социальные сети и др.) на имидж (популярность) вуза, процессы приема студентов, качество образовательного процесса и трудоустройства выпускников вузов. Эти исследования будут содействовать более эффективному интернет-продвижению услуг казахстанских вузов и повышению их конкурентоспособности.

Список использованной литературы

1. Popa, A. L. Understanding Students Needs for a More Effective Online Marketing in the Higher Education System, Annals of Faculty of Economics, University of Oradea, Faculty of Economics, vol. 1(1), 2015.
2. Kittle, B., & Ciba, D. Using College Web Sites for Student Recruitment: A Relationship Marketing Study. Journal of Marketing for Higher Education, 11(3), 2001.
3. Ванчикова А. Б., Кокшарова А. С. Место интернет-маркетинга образовательных услуг в маркетинговой деятельности университета // Вестник Забайкальского государственного университета. – 2016. – Т. 22. – №. 11. – С. 102-108.
4. Донина И. А., Шайдорова Н. А. Потенциал социальных сетей в реализации интернет-маркетинга образовательной организации // Проблемы современного педагогического образования. – 2018. – №. 58-2. – С. 75-79.
5. Олехова И. П., Лузикова С. Н., Нефедьева В. С. Выявление эффективных маркетинговых стратегий и инструментов в сфере высшего образования (на основе анализа контента интернет-презентации вузов) // Ekonomické trendy. – 2016. – №. 4. – С. 33-38.
6. Рувенный И. Я., Касимова Э. Р., Кузнецова Е. В. Продвижение вуза в интернет-пространстве // Менеджмент и маркетинг в различных сферах деятельности: сборник научных трудов/ под ред. И. Я. Рувенного; Уфимский государственный авиационный технический университет – Уфа: УГАТУ, 2021. – 164 с.

7. Шевченко Д. А. Интернет-маркетинг вуза: новые принципы клиентоориентированного маркетинга // Практический маркетинг. – 2014. – №. 8 (210). – С. 15-21.
8. Конопьянова Г.А., Байкенов Ж.Е., Мамбетказиев А.Е., Мухамбетова З.С. Анализ использования сетевых инструментов в продвижении образовательных услуг вуза // Экономика: стратегия и практика. – 2023. – Т. 18(2). – №. 2. – С. 107-122.
9. Зарубина В. Р., Зарубин М. Ю., Васильчук Е. В. Продвижение образовательных услуг вуза в условиях цифровизации // Вестник университета «Туран». – 2022. – №. 4. – С. 300-310.
10. Сейтбаткалова А., Мукан С., Таменова С. Анализ цифровых платформ обучения университетов: отечественный и зарубежный опыт //Central Asian Economic Review. – 2021. – №. 2. – С. 169-179.
11. Жумабаева Ч. Н., Бримкулов У. Н. Социальные сети, цифровые образовательные ресурсы и гаджеты в учебном процессе: мнение студентов Кыргызстана и Казахстана //Международный журнал экспериментального образования. – 2019. – №. 1. – С. 5-10.
12. Лукичева Т. А., Лезина Т. А. Эволюция интернет-маркетинга: от публикации сайта до маркетинга социальных медиа (Social Media Marketing) // Экономика и управление. – 2011. – №. 11 (73). – С. 87-92.
13. McCoy, J. C. A Comparison of Internet Marketing Methods Utilized by Higher Education Institutions. Thesis. University of Arkansas, 2011. UMI Number: 3469336
14. Quijada, M., Munoz, P., Corrons, A., & Olmo-Arriaga, J. Engaging students through social media. Findings for the top five universities in the world, Journal of Marketing for Higher Education, 32:2, 197-214, 2022. doi: 10.1080/08841241.2020.1841069
15. Соболева Т. Н. Интернет-маркетинг образовательных услуг //Междисциплинарный диалог: современные тенденции в общественных, гуманитарных, естественных и технических науках. – 2014. – №. 1. – С. 148-155.
16. Керн К. Е. Интернет-маркетинг образовательных услуг ВУЗа как инструмент привлечения китайских студентов (на примере Томского государственного университета) // Вопросы истории, археологии, политических наук и регионоведения. – 2017. – Т. 2. – №12. – С. 27-31.
17. Николаев В. К. Экспорт образования в вузах России в условиях новой реальности // Высшее образование в России. – 2022. – №. 2. – С. 149-166.
18. Минажева Г.С., Садырова М.С. Пути повышения конкурентоспособности высших учебных заведений Казахстана // Journal of Educational Sciences. – 2019. – Т. 59. – №. 2. – С. 68-83.
19. Официальный сайт Бюро национальной статистики Агентства по стратегическому планированию и реформам Республики Казахстан. <https://stat.gov.kz/>

Accounting symmetries on dividend politics by applications of accounting methodology of Edgeworth box

Miguel Angel Pérez Benedito

PhD. Senior Lecture in Economics and Business Sciences, Universidad de Valencia (Spain)

Abstract

The relationship between the remuneration for shareholders and self-financing policies for the continued activity of companies are criteria that play a main role in the management responsibility of companies. The manuscript analyzes the evolution of dividends paid during 2014 to 2022 by two banks and their respective accounting symmetries with central banks. The Basel international regulatory framework for banks, Brexit, and the COVID-19 pandemic justify this analysis to support the validity of the accounting methodology development. The visual contrasts of symmetries explain the different strategies carried out to overcome this compulsive period. The accounting utility functions, Tier I, and Capital ratio are indicators contrasted with the relationship between the dividend paid divided by reserves for getting conclusion of this research.

INTRODUCTION

The accounting methodology visually represents on an Edgeworth box the situation of an entity based on four variables such as results of operations, variations in economic assets, variations in net financial positions, and monetary savings (Perez, 2020a, 202b). Considering accounting records are making decisions, the financial statements are their synthesis and include three economic, financial, and monetary value criteria. The assessment of variables has included the culture of the geographical location where the entities carry out their activities and the banks have them included in their transactions. So that, same financial regulations of their activities have different effects on their financial statements.

The hypothesis of this work is ratios are not enough to obtain a conclusion on the management of values recorded in a system of accounts because they are a combination of three values taken in pair and opposite them a position on an Edgeworth is a combination of three values taken in threes. Additionally, ratios do not admit gaps to confirm the hypothesis evaluated according to cultural environment. Consequently, it is possible to be contrasting variables that do not have the same canonical base in a Euclidean space because the scenario can change.

The scenarios for the application of ratios and accounting standards based on them is desirable, but the other thing is to achieve them. So that, the cultural factors include in accounting transactions limit actions of banks. This work evaluates banking activity in an alternative way and visually brings the knowledge of banking activity closer to anyone interested in knowing its activity. The Edgeworth box is a laboratory where the visual position adopted by a banking entity is measured after transforming the accounting variables of interest into the applied methodology. These variables are deduced from the dynamic behavior of banks and they are prevented from containing values belonging to past transactions.

THE LABORATORY OF EDGEWORTH BOX.

The comparison by difference of economic and financial transactions allows obtaining four variables. The capacity or need for financing is the effect of the differences between the inputs and products of banking activity. The difference between the result of economic operations (RoEO) and the economic asset not placed on the market (VoEA) is identified with the difference between

financial position of the banking entity (NFP) minus the value of the monetary saving (MS) not placed on the market such as loans or credits. The analytic expression is as follows:

$$\text{RoEO} - \text{VoEA} = \text{NFP} - \text{MS} \quad (1)$$

Where:

RoEO is Results of Economic Operations or Cash flow Economic.

VoEA is Variations of Economic Assets

NFP is Net Financial Positions

MS is Monetary Saving or Cash Flow Monetary.

The accounting equation obtained by transpositions of before variable is:

$$\text{VoAE} + \text{NFP} = \text{MS} + \text{RoEO} \quad (2)$$

This expression is applied on financial statements of Deutsh Bank and Barclays Bank as well as their respective Central Banks, Deutsche Bundesbank and Bank of England. The positions in an Edgeworth box are obtained by fallow transformation:

$$\text{AVi} = (\text{Xi} - \text{Xo})/\Sigma$$

Where:

AVi is accounting variables includes in Edgeworth box.

Xi is accounting variables expression 1 and 2

Xo is maximum minus value of variations variables of expression 1 and 2 multiplied by minus tow (-2).

Σ is sum of assets and liabilities of expression 2 for each year.

The Edgeworth boxes for Deutsche Bank AG (DB) and Deutsche Bundesbank (DBB) are on figure 1 and for Barclays Bank PLC (BB) and Bank of England (BoE) are on figure 2. According to equation 2 sum of assets and liabilities sum 100%. The assets are VoEA and NFP, so liabilities are RoEO and MS. The relative positions for Central Banks are marked by cross and commercial banks by fish (\diamond) for Deutsche Bank (DB) and a bread (\circ) for Barclays Bank (BB).

Figure 1. Germany DB

Figure 2. England BB

The colors in figures 1 and 2 are related with level of economic and financial risk. So, red, and green colors are high and low levels risk on making decisions, respectively. The zones with color blue are positions that will worsen and improve the activity of the entities. The measuring positions on

figures require consider an economic and financial criterion, according to nature of accounting variables in expression 1.

The indicator L and G measure financial and economic nature of position by fallow expressions.

$$L = \text{NFP/RoEO} - \text{VoEA/MS} \quad (3)$$

$$G = \text{VoEA/RoEO} - \text{NFP/MS} \quad (4)$$

The measure of significance by L and G indicators:

- The indicator L measures financial activity of banks and contrasts how many time the RoEO allows lending credits corrected by level of guarantees from economic assets (VoEA) respect to monetary saving (MS).
- The G indicator measures the economic activity of banks by contrasting how many times the assets (VoEA) contain the RoEO minus the application of the monetary result (MS) in contracting credits. Alternative criteria, how many times the banking activity (NFP/MS) is guaranteed by economic assets (VoEA/RoEO).

The results of Table 1 and Table 2 correspond to banking activity of German and England banks.

L ^{ADB}	G ^{ADB}	Year	L ^{DBB}	G ^{DBB}
-0,012292	-0,001193	2022 ^{C&B}	-0,615769	0,004265
-0,024349	-0,014465	2021 ^{C&D}	0,439709	-0,012317
-0,060809	0,000737	2020 ^{B&A}	1,314559	0,052911
0,139441	0,007996	2019 ^{A&B}	-0,291660	0,033284
-0,118280	-0,004247	2018 ^{C&D}	0,074288	-0,008222
0,072569	0,002567	2017 ^{A&A}	0,787473	0,020451
-0,270391	-0,001901	2016 ^{C&A}	0,511640	0,016697
-0,199839	0,003127	2015 ^{B&A}	0,313135	-0,029591
-0,377146	-0,031165	2014 ^{C&C}	-0,293036	-0,009755
-0,076291	0,013743	2013 ^{B&A}	1,010330	0,171356

L ^{BB}	G ^{BB}	Year	L ^{BoE}	G ^{BoE}
-0,110104	-0,004950	2022 ^{C&B}	-1,130857	0,024407
-0,058209	0,012837	2021 ^{B&A}	0,629771	0,000748
0,358080	-0,023199	2020 ^{D&D}	1,456015	-0,000043
-0,040347	-0,017137	2019 ^{C&B}	-0,151291	0,001801
-1,458842	-0,026740	2018 ^{C&C}	-0,116265	-0,007129
0,539047	-0,276188	2017 ^{D&A}	0,593472	0,000615
-1,046578	0,320017	2016 ^{B&A}	0,252324	0,004936
-0,831099	-0,040146	2015 ^{C&C}	-0,226262	-0,000338
-0,820950	0,155997	2014 ^{B^C}	-0,168224	-0,000066
0,313272	-0,012759	2013 ^{D&A}	1,683106	0,003840

Tables 1 and 2 have letters assigned to years – column year- and represent the risk levels of the commercial and central banks in that year. The letter A and C have relation on low high levels of risk, which have assigned blue and red colors, respectively. The letter B has relation on medium levels of risk (green color) as well as letter D. Nevertheless, the zone B has the side of RoEO and

represents an entry on financial risk, the zone D has the side of MS and represents an exit on financial risk.

The financial situation improves when L is positive ($L > 0$) and this is greater than G ($L > G$), both the L and G indicators must be positive. According to these criteria, there was a conflictive situation for German banks in 2014 and for English banks in 2015 and 2018 because both central and commercial banks were in C zones in those years.

EVOLUTION OF BANKING ACTIVITY

The positions of banks are on cartesian axes in figure 3 and 4 according to respective tables 1 and 2. The relative position of L and G indicates that they differ depending on the adopted value of X_0 . However, the G/L ratio will be the same because it maintains its value independent of the measurement criterion, its relative position does not change, so G/L is also a measure of control over the refutation of the steps taken to obtain them.

Figure 3: L and G indicator for Germany Banks

Figure 4: L and G indicators for England Banks

The positions L (x-axis) and G (y-axis) indicators on Cartesian axes of figures 3 and 4 are their rotation from figures 1 and 2, respectively. Their location on Euclidean space allows contrast them with other ones that have the same criterion of reference, a cartesian canonical base. So that, the assessment of banking activity includes the contrasting L and G indicator between Basile ratios (Tier I, Capital requirements) and politics of dividend payment. The evolution of banking activity is on figures 5 and 6 for German and England banks, respectively. The discontinued lines have the secondary y-axis as reference, and they are indicators of accounting methodology applied and politic of payment of dividends.

Figure 5. Evolution of Deutsche Bank

Figure 6. Evolution of Barclays PLC

The evolution of indicator Div/Res (●) represents payment of dividend respect to reserve generated and have same evolution. The maintaining investor interest and banking activity with alternative ways for contrasted banks. This indicator increases/decreases according to the financial accounting indicator L from 2014 to 2017. Banks are highly regulated in this period and their Tier I indicators increase according to their respective positions or locations in the Edgeworth box, but their policies are different. The commercial and central banks of Germany are in zones A\A and the English banks in zones D\A of their respective Edgeworth box, in tables 1 and 2 of the previous section in 2017. So, Deutsche Bank prefer continued their activity with a $G > 0$ and Barclays Bank prefer maintain positions of investor with a $G < 0$.

These strategies allow the improving requirement of Basile for Deutsche Bank by increasing L more than G ($L > G$) and do not pay dividend in 2019 and 2020, its selection is for the maintaining the activity. The Barclays Bank pays dividends decreasing L respect to G ($L < G$) indicator. The observing figure 3 and 4 at 2022 both entities are on zone C but on different location in Edgeworth box. Consequently, their respective indicators Tier I have different evolution. The next section explains this alternative way of behavior.

THE ACCOUNTING SYMETRIES: COMERCIAL AND CENTRAL BANKS.

The Central Banks condition the behavior of local banks due to their commitment to the monetary policy of the countries. The accounting symmetries can explain above behavior of banks. The figures 7s and 8s are accounting symmetries between commercial banks and respective central banks. The visual representations are very explicit, and they explain level of collaboration on activities of banks.

The extensions and contractions of symmetries axes have relevance. The extensions of axes explain the less financial or economic dependency between commercial banks and central banks. Taking on account the banking activity is lending credit according to the management of monetary saving and later transforms monetary value into financial and economic values. So that, the financial

contractions of German and England banks in 2014 (figures 7.3) and 2017 (figure 8.2) are hard regulations with effects on their activities. These are effects to overcome financial crisis on different cultures o economies.

The above behavior suggests the extension of G axes supposes increasing their economic guarantees for maintaining their activities and L axes have more contraction. There is freedom to economic investments and contractions on lending credits. The decision of Central Banks condition financial activity of commercial Banks. The effect of this scenery are payments of dividends for maintaining interest of investors. The dividends of Deutsche Bank in 2015, 2019 and 2020 are zero and their figures have extended axes G then more axes L. The behavior of Barclays Bank have same situation in 2014, 2016, 2017 and 2020.

The accounting symmetries have not same measure on axes, because their visual perception take relevance on measure of figures. According to result of visual observations the contractions and extensions of axes can be measure and allow the obtaining an accounting utility criterion.

The dispersion of symmetries and locations of banking positions on Euclidean space (figure 3 and 4) are related to other variables that also measure banking activity. The proposed measure of accounting utility is multiplying radians by module of the symmetry, which is the extension/dispersion of relative banking positions, and not their Euclidean distance. This uniform measure could allow contrasting the collaboration between banks and their individual activity, and so considering the assessing of banking decisions by Theory of Game for next random scenarios. The contrasts on politics of collaboration represented on figures 10 and 11 are complemented by other variables as Basel indicators (Tier I) and dividend politics Div/Res). The figure 9s are respective symmetries of German and England banks on figure 7s and 8s of above section.

The greatest dispersions of accounting utility functions in 2013 (figure 9) and 2017 (10) are hard regulations of banking activity (figure 9.10 and 9.11), when extension of G axes is biggest than L axes. According to evolutionary of series commercial banks pay dividends when utilities functions are next from 2017, when L high than G ($L > G$) and Tier I increases on respective cultures of countries.

CONCLUSION

The accounting methodology explains the banking activity by visual graphics in respective sections. The perception of figures has relation on real success of regulations and accounting variables of figures are contrasted on those ones obtained from other sources of information. The refutations of estimation models in conflict period can be admits and so alternative form to estimations short term are admitted over conditions their adjustment to real situations researched. The cause-effect relations are contrasted by accounting methodology of manuscript, and so the Accounting is an economic or social-economic science more than other alternative considerations.

BIBLIOGRAPHY. (no application)

Perez-Benedito, MA. (2020a). A Propósito de Margarita Salas: Genética, Comportamiento Socio-Económico y Simetrías Contables. Encuentros Multidisciplinares 22(64):1-7. http://www.encuentros-multidisciplinares.org/revista-64/Indice_n%C2%BA_64_2020.htm
 Perez-Benedito, MA. (202b). Accounting Symmetries on Indonesian Entities by Applying the Edgeworth’s Box. June 2020Economics and Business 3(2):795-810Follow journal. DOI: 10.31014/aior.1992.03.02.238

УДК 004

Маркетинговый подход к повышению лояльности потребителей в индустрии гостеприимства

Мурат Балжан

Университет «Туран», Магистрант ОП «Маркетинг»

Индустрия гостеприимства является высококонкурентным рынком, и лояльность потребителей является решающим фактором ее успеха. Это исследование направлено на изучение маркетинговых стратегий, которые могут быть использованы для повышения лояльности потребителей в индустрии гостеприимства. Исследование сосредоточено на обзоре литературы и анализе тематических исследований для выявления эффективных маркетинговых подходов, которые использовались в отрасли. В высококонкурентной индустрии гостеприимства лояльность клиентов имеет важное значение для успеха бизнеса. В этой статье мы исследуем маркетинговый подход к повышению лояльности клиентов в индустрии гостеприимства. В статье представлен обзор материалов и методов, используемых в исследовании, а также основные выводы и обсуждение.

С развитием социально-экономических процессов в современном мире отельная индустрия обязана уделять серьёзное внимание собственному развитию и повышению конкурентоспособности, чтобы оставаться на передовой позиции в условиях жёсткой рыночной конкуренции. Отели должны всегда следить за изменениями на рынке и потребительскими требованиями, ориентироваться на потребности рынка и разрабатывать научно обоснованные маркетинговые стратегии, соответствующие реальной ситуации на рынке. Книга "Управление маркетингом в гостиничной индустрии и его практика" является профессиональным учебным пособием по управлению туризмом и гостиничным делом, которое органично объединяет основные принципы маркетинга с практикой управления гостиничными предприятиями. В ней учтены последние практические и теоретические результаты исследований маркетинга как на национальном, так и на мировом уровнях. На основе теории маркетинга и анализа текущих тенденций в гостиничной индустрии, в книге детально анализируются маркетинговые концепции, маркетинговое планирование, методы маркетинга, маркетинговые стратегии и маркетинговое управление, уделяя внимание как теоретическим аспектам, так и практическим вопросам. Книга "Управление маркетингом в гостиничной индустрии и его практика" является важным средством помощи читателям в освоении ключевых и сложных аспектов управления маркетингом в гостиничной индустрии. Работа помогает читателям увидеть основные аспекты и трудности в данной области, и предоставляет ценную поддержку в решении этих вопросов. Управление маркетингом в гостиничной индустрии имеет важное значение.

В современном обществе успешное управление маркетингом играет ключевую роль в обеспечении устойчивого развития отельного бизнеса. Во-первых, качество управления непосредственно влияет на основную конкурентоспособность отелей. На фоне активного экономического роста в рыночной экономике в Казахстане туристическая индустрия получила импульс, что привело к появлению разнообразных типов и масштабов отелей и увеличило конкуренцию в сфере гостиничного бизнеса. Поэтому отели должны продолжать уделять

серьёзное внимание управлению, глубоко анализировать психологические особенности потребителей, тесно связывать предлагаемые продукты и услуги отелей с потребностями рынка, чтобы эффективно расширять клиентскую базу и повышать экономическую эффективность отелей. Во-вторых, управление отелем может эффективно снижать операционные затраты, оптимизировать распределение ресурсов и обеспечивать всестороннее повышение экономической эффективности отелей. Использование маркетинговых стратегий для управления отелем позволяет мобилизовать сотрудников отеля, клиентов и другие ресурсы, интегрировать их в обслуживание отелей. Управление отелем с использованием маркетинговых стратегий может включать в себя разработку рекламных маркетинговых стратегий, стратегий продвижения продуктов, стратегий ценообразования и стратегий культуры бренда, что помогает улучшить уровень удовлетворённости потребителей отеля. Наконец, управление отелем включает в себя внутренние потребности прибыльности в новой среде, что также является ключевой задачей.

Гостиничная индустрия - это прибыльная отрасль, поэтому управление отелем необходимо совмещать с маркетинговыми стратегиями, чтобы глубоко анализировать психологию потребителей, связать продукты и услуги управления отелями с потребностями рынка, расширить клиентскую базу и увеличить экономический доход отелей. Тем не менее, мы также должны четко понимать, что ни один отель, независимо от его размера, уровня обслуживания и уровня оборудования, не может удовлетворить все потребительские потребности. Кроме того, гостиничный рынок постоянно расширяется, конкуренты увеличиваются, а потребительские требования постоянно меняются и растут, поэтому отель зачастую оказывается в пассивной позиции и трудно точно определить свою собственную позицию для развития. Поэтому отели должны выбирать аудиторию, которая им подходит, и разрабатывать научно обоснованные маркетинговые стратегии. В первую очередь, необходимо правильно определить целевую аудиторию. Правильные маркетинговые стратегии позволяют анализировать и позиционировать текущих и потенциальных клиентов отелей, чтобы помочь отелям понять их целевую аудиторию, узнать о жизненных привычках, требованиях к услугам отелей, интересах в других областях и многом другом. Таким образом, отели могут повысить качество обслуживания отелей. Во-вторых, нужно правильно определить имидж отеля. Правильные маркетинговые стратегии позволяют отелям чётко определить собственный имидж, убедиться, что отель правильно позиционирован среди целевой аудитории, и понять, в какой точке находится отель в сердцах потребителей в настоящее время, чтобы понимать, какие области нуждаются в изменениях и улучшениях. Наконец, маркетинговое управление отелем заключается в разработке научно обоснованных маркетинговых планов для повышения экономической эффективности отелей. Правильное маркетинговое планирование позволяет фокусировать внимание на текущих и потенциальных клиентах отелей, а также разрабатывать эффективные стратегии и планы для своевременной информированности о динамике развития отелей, стимулировать потенциальное любопытство потребителей и увеличивать поток клиентов в отели. В связи с этим управление маркетингом в отрасли гостиничного бизнеса имеет большое значение, и разработка научно обоснованных маркетинговых стратегий становится ключевой задачей. Во-первых, необходимо разработать научно обоснованную рекламную стратегию. На данный момент большинство отелей предоставляют примерно одинаковые услуги, различия могут наблюдаться только в качестве и уровне услуги. Отсутствие индивидуальности услуг делает важным выделение особенностей отеля в рекламной стратегии, проведение таргетированной рекламы и разработку стратегий дифференциации, чтобы подчеркнуть собственные преимущества. Во-вторых, нужно иметь разумную PR-

стратегию. Разумная PR-стратегия позволяет оптимизировать использование различных социальных ресурсов, разрабатывать эффективные стратегии и планы, чтобы создать положительное впечатление о себе. Отелю нужно хорошо вести сбор и управление информацией о клиентах, устанавливать долгосрочные и дружеские отношения с клиентами, предоставлять всесторонние и индивидуализированные услуги. В то же время необходимо проводить регулярные визиты клиентов, анализировать психологию потребителей, чтобы удовлетворить потребности клиентов и разработать планы, способствующие привлечению потенциальных клиентов. Наконец, управление маркетингом отеля включает в себя внутренние потребности в доходности в новых условиях, что также является ключевым элементом. Гостиничная индустрия - это прибыльная отрасль, поэтому маркетинговое управление отелями необходимо для анализа психологии потребителей, связывания предоставляемых отелями продуктов и услуг с потребностями рынка, расширения клиентской базы и увеличения экономического дохода отелей.

Однако мы также должны четко понимать, что ни один отель, независимо от его размера, уровня обслуживания и оборудования, не может удовлетворить все потребительские потребности. Кроме того, рынок гостиничных услуг постоянно расширяется, конкуренты увеличиваются, а потребительские требования постоянно меняются и растут, поэтому отель зачастую оказывается в пассивной позиции и трудно точно определить свою собственную позицию для развития. Поэтому отели должны выбирать аудиторию, которая им подходит, и разрабатывать научно обоснованные маркетинговые стратегии. В первую очередь, необходимо правильно определить целевую аудиторию. Правильные маркетинговые стратегии позволяют анализировать и позиционировать текущих и потенциальных клиентов отелей, чтобы помочь отелям понять их целевую аудиторию, узнать о жизненных привычках, требованиях к услугам отелей, интересах в других областях и многом другом. Таким образом, отели могут повысить качество обслуживания отелей. Во-вторых, нужно правильно определить имидж отеля. Правильные маркетинговые стратегии позволяют отелям четко определить собственный имидж, убедиться, что отель правильно позиционирован среди целевой аудитории, и понять, в какой точке находится отель в сердцах потребителей в настоящее время, чтобы понимать, какие области нуждаются в изменениях и улучшениях. Наконец, маркетинговое управление отелем заключается в разработке научно обоснованных маркетинговых планов для повышения экономической эффективности отелей. Правильное маркетинговое планирование позволяет фокусировать внимание на текущих и потенциальных клиентах отелей, а также разрабатывать эффективные стратегии и планы для своевременной информированности о динамике развития отелей, стимулировать потенциальное любопытство потребителей и увеличивать поток клиентов в отели.

Литература

Позднеев О. И. Роль рекламы на предприятиях индустрии гостеприимства // Вестник науки и образования № .С. 73

Туватова В. Е. Перспективы использования средств маркетинга в ресторанном бизнесе // Маркетинг, 2011. №1.

С Туватова В. Е. Методы инновационного маркетинга в ресторанном бизнесе // Маркетинг в России и за рубежом, No 3. С. 55

Туватова В. Е. Проблемы и перспективы повышения качества услуг в гостиничном бизнесе // Маркетинг в России и за рубежом, No 3. С. 76

ЖИЗНЕННЫЙ ЦИКЛ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ: ЭМПИРИЧЕСКИЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ И ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ПОДХОДЫ

Садыков Асхат Сабержанович

Докторант DBA, Алматы Менеджмент Университет, Республика Казахстан, г. Алматы

ORGANIZATION LIFE CYCLE: EMPIRICAL RESEARCH AND THEORETICAL APPROACHES

Sadykov Askhat

Doctoral student of Business Administration,
Almaty Management University (Almaty, Kazakhstan)

В последние годы можно отметить растущий интерес со стороны ученых и практиков казахстанского бизнеса к проблемам развития организации на разных стадиях ее жизненного цикла. Ряд публикаций — как в научных, так и в деловых журналах — свидетельствует о многообразии подходов к исследованию этого феномена. Выступления доктора И. Адизеса в ведущих российских и казахстанских школах бизнеса вызвали колоссальный интерес аудитории к его модели жизненного цикла корпорации. Триумфальное шествие идей Адизеса сопровождается переводом и публикацией его книг, которые почти сразу становятся бестселлерами. В то же время концепцию Адизеса довольно сложно отнести к строгим научным исследованиям, скорее это консалтинговый инструмент, позволяющий диагностировать проблемы организации и проводить организационные изменения для их преодоления. Очевидно, что, помимо изучения и восприятия популярных концепций в теории жизненного цикла организаций (ЖЦО), требуются серьезные научные исследования, направленные на выявление специфики развития казахстанских компаний. Представляется, что изучение имеющегося опыта проведения подобных исследований за рубежом является актуальным и своевременным для казахстанской науки.

Концепция жизненного цикла организации: подходы к изучению.

Концепция ЖЦО, основанная на биологической аналогии с жизненным циклом живого организма, развивается на протяжении последних нескольких десятилетий. Основное назначение концепции — объяснение изменений, которые происходят в организации с течением времени. К настоящему времени ученые разработали и представили довольно большое количество моделей ЖЦО, однако до сих пор между различными исследователями нет единого мнения относительно количества стадий и подхода к их определению. Представляется, что причины подобного многообразия можно обнаружить в выбираемых учеными объектах исследований.

Например, одна из первых моделей ЖЦО была посвящена жизненному циклу правительственной организации, дальнейшие исследования были направлены на создание моделей жизненного цикла как коммерческих, так и некоммерческих организаций и посвящены анализу стадий и их связи с происходящими организационными процессами. Некоторые исследования были сфокусированы на определении общей модели технологических изменений, которая влияла на стадии организационного жизненного цикла, изучении организационной культуры и ее роли в предпринимательской активности во время создания и развития новых организаций, анализе вновь созданных организаций, изучении организационной эффективности. Меняющиеся приоритеты топ-менеджеров на

разных стадиях жизненного цикла становились предметом сразу нескольких исследований: [Churchill, Lewis, 1983; Dodge, Fullerton, Robbins, 1994; Kazanjian, 1988; Smith, Mitchell, Summer, 1985]. Жизненный цикл промышленных предприятий был центром исследования в течение нескольких десятилетий [Grimm, Smith, 1997; Miles, Snow, Sharfman, 1993], в последние годы все более пристальное внимание стало уделяться особенностям формирования жизненного цикла малых и средних предприятий [Kiriri, 2002; Masurel, van Montfort, 2006]. Кроме того, концепция ЖЦО выступала в качестве предмета анализа при изучении издательского дела [Hall, 1976], закономерностей развития университетов [Levine, 1978; Cyert, 1978; Cameron, Whetten, Kim, 1987] и для исследования больниц [D'Aunno, Zuckerman, 1987], агентства космических исследований NASA [McCurdy, 1991] и голливудской киностудии [Miller, Shamsie, 2001].

Более ранняя литература по жизненным циклам организации носила скорее теоретический, нежели эмпирический характер, и исследователи сильно расходились в оценке количества стадий или этапов ЖЦО. Например, некоторые авторы предлагали модели из трех стадий [Downs, 1967; Scott, 1976; Katz, Kahn, 1978], другие считали, что стадий должно быть четыре [Lyden, 1975], есть модели, содержащие пять и более стадий, например, модель Грейнера состоит из пяти стадий [Грейнер, 2002], модель Торберта содержит девять стадий [Torbert, 1974] и модель Адизеса — десять стадий [Adizes, 1989]. Разные авторы делают акцент на различном наборе уникальных характеристик каждой стадии их моделей. Однако, независимо от количества стадий, в выводах исследователей есть общее. Во-первых, последовательность стадий является закономерной. Во-вторых, каждая стадия — следствие предыдущей, и вернуться назад не очень просто. В-третьих, все модели рассматривают довольно широкий спектр организационных характеристик и переменных [Gupta, Chin, 1994].

Некоторые ученые подвергают сомнению наличие закономерностей в развитии организации на основе лонгитюдных исследований конкретных организаций [Kimberly, Miles, 1980; Lester, Parnell, 1999; Lodahl, Mitchell, 1980; Miller, Friesen, 1984; Tichy, 1980]. Результаты показывают, что в жизни организации существует скорее неопределенность, а не детерминизм развития [Miller, Friesen, 1984]. Таким образом, можно сказать, что жизненный цикл — это в большей степени собирательная интерпретация топ-менеджеров внутренней среды организации. Большинство фирм не переходят непреклонно от одной стадии развития к другой в традиционном биологическом смысле [Lester, Parnell, 2002; Miller, Friesen, 1984; Lester, Parnell, Carraher, 2003].

Стадия жизненного цикла представляет собой широкий набор различных характеристик организационной деятельности [Dodge, Fullerton, Robbins, 1994; Hanks et al., 1993; Quinn, Cameron, 1983]. Таким образом, ключ к пониманию того, что представляет собой стадия ЖЦО, лежит в том, чтобы осознать, как эти характеристики изменяются во времени. Например, некоторые исследования демонстрируют, что топ-менеджеры обращают больше внимания на внешние проблемы на ранних стадиях цикла жизни и внутренних проблемах на стадиях роста и зрелости [Dodge, Robbins, 1992]. Кроме того, организация способна не только оставаться довольно продолжительное время на одной и той же стадии развития [Miller, Friesen, 1984], но и возвращаться на более ранние стадии [Drazin, Kazanjian, 1990] или банкротиться на ранних стадиях, иногда быстро продвигаясь к стадии упадка и смерти [Churchill, Lewis, 1983]. К настоящему времени можно четко выделить два подхода к исследованиям жизненных циклов организаций. Первый подход носит исключительно эмпирический характер и включает в себя исследования с применением количественных методов, изучение конкретных кейсов или лонгитюдные наблюдения. В большинстве своем эти исследования отличаются друг от друга объектами изучения, или типами организаций. Второй подход, менее многочисленный, предполагает применение концепции ЖЦО с целью

ее интеграции с другими областями исследований организаций и менеджмента. В данном случае концепция жизненного цикла используется для объяснения изменений того или иного явления по мере становления и развития организации. В настоящей хрестоматии представлены оба подхода, и, на наш взгляд, выбранные статьи позволяют получить полное представление об особенностях каждого направления исследований.

Эмпирическое исследование стадий роста высокотехнологичных организаций

Предлагаемая вниманию читателей статья С. Хэнкса, К. Уотсона, Э. Янсена и Г. Чандлера «Уточнение структуры жизненного цикла: таксономическое исследование конфигураций стадий роста в высокотехнологичных организациях» является одной из наиболее цитируемых в литературных обзорах исследований, посвященных концепции ЖЦО. Статья представляет значительный интерес для казахстанской научной аудитории по двум причинам. Во-первых, авторы провели один из наиболее подробных анализов теории жизненного цикла организации, сопоставив десять моделей ЖЦО с точки зрения количества стадий и характеристик каждой стадии. Несмотря на то что статья была опубликована в 1993 г., ничего подобного в более поздних исследованиях выполнено не было. По сути, авторам удалось обобщить всю имеющуюся литературу и разработанные к тому времени модели. Несомненной их заслугой является также прием, который они используют для сравнительного анализа десяти моделей, — создание обобщенной модели ЖЦО для выделения общих, повторяющихся характеристик и особенностей каждой модели.

Во-вторых, в статье была представлена уникальная методология проведения эмпирических исследований, которая продемонстрирована на примере 126 компаний из высокотехнологичных отраслей. Уникальность методологии заключается в том, что она позволяет не только выделить определенное количество стадий в жизненном цикле организации, но и проверить обоснованность самой концепции ЖЦО. Основным вкладом авторов данной статьи в развитие теории жизненного цикла организаций является разработанная методология эмпирического исследования, которая дает возможность протестировать гипотезу о существовании закономерностей в развитии организации в виде предсказуемой модели ЖЦО. В работе выделены восемь специфических переменных организационной среды, которые, изменяясь с течением времени, являются индикаторами перехода организации с одной стадии на другую. В результате анализа эмпирических данных была разработана модель ЖЦО для высокотехнологичных фирм, включающая в себя четыре стадии развития. Представляется, что данная статья заслуживает внимания со стороны казахстанских исследователей не только по вышеуказанным причинам. Это — классический образец научной статьи, содержащей эмпирическое исследование и включающей все необходимые элементы. Кроме того, предложенная методология может быть использована для проведения аналогичных исследований на казахстанских материалах.

Теория заинтересованных сторон с точки зрения жизненного цикла организации

Статья И. Джавахара и Г. МакЛафлина «К дескриптивной теории заинтересованных сторон: подход с точки зрения жизненного цикла организации» относится к более многочисленному направлению в теории ЖЦО — использованию концепции для анализа конкретного феномена в жизни организации. Например, уже упоминавшееся исследование приоритетов топ-менеджеров на разных стадиях жизненного цикла [Smith, Mitchell, Summer, 1985], изучение специфики распределения власти в зависимости от стадии ЖЦО [Mintzberg, 1984], изменение политик и стратегии на протяжении жизненного цикла организации [Gray, Ariss, 1985; Gupta, Chin, 1992] и др. Обычная логика подобных исследований такова: авторы берут за основу существующую модель ЖЦО (в большинстве случаев четырех- или пятиэтапную), описывают выбранную организационную проблему или характеристику и

затем анализируют процесс изменений этой проблемы по мере движения организации по стадиям жизненного цикла.

В рассматриваемой статье предпринята довольно удачная попытка создания дескриптивной теории стейкхолдеров на основе теоретических знаний и результатов эмпирических исследований по теории ресурсной зависимости, теории перспектив и моделей жизненного цикла организации. Представленная теория позволяет увидеть, что на любой стадии ЖЦО одни заинтересованные стороны будут важнее других благодаря своей возможности удовлетворять основные потребности организации и на разных стадиях ЖЦО компания должна использовать разные стратегии взаимодействия с каждой отдельной заинтересованной стороной.

Данная статья является в большей степени постановочной, так как четыре выдвинутые гипотезы относительно принятия решений и стратегии взаимодействия организации с заинтересованными сторонами на разных стадиях жизненного цикла не проверены эмпирически. В то же время автор довольно подробно описывают методологию эмпирической проверки теоретических предположений. Указанная методология позволяет не только определить стадию ЖЦО, но и измерить восприятие угроз и решений о распределении ресурсов, которым обладают лица, принимающие эти решения, и распознать стратегии, которые применяются при взаимодействии с заинтересованными сторонами. Данная статья, безусловно, является актуальной с точки зрения современной теории и практики менеджмента и вносит существенный вклад в теорию заинтересованных лиц, так как объясняет изменения значимости заинтересованных сторон для организации по мере ее развития и расширяет границы современного представления о стратегии управления заинтересованными сторонами.

Для казахстанского читателя статья будет полезна как в плане развития будущих исследований, так и с методологической точки зрения. Статья содержат оригинальные подходы к проведению научных исследований в области теории жизненного цикла организации, которые могут лечь в основу методологий эмпирических исследований на казахстанских данных.

Список литературы:

1. Адизес И. 2006. Как преодолеть кризисы менеджмента: диагностика и решение управленческих проблем. СПб.: Стокгольмская школа экономики в Санкт-Петербурге.
2. Адизес И. 2007. Управление жизненным циклом корпорации. СПб.: Питер.
3. Грейнер Л. Е. 2002. Эволюция и революция в процессе роста организаций. Вестник С.-Петербургского ун-та. Сер. Менеджмент (4): 76–92.
4. Железняк Т. 2001. Какая она, ваша компания? Персонал-Микс (2): 63–71.
5. Ивашковская И. В., Константинов Г. Н., Филонович С. Р. 2004. Становление корпорации в контексте жизненного цикла организации. Российский журнал менеджмента 2 (4): 19–34.
6. Кушелевич Е., Филонович С. 2004. Модели жизненных циклов организаций. В сб.: Виханский О. С., Наумова А. И. (ред.). Менеджмент: век XX — век XXI. М.: Экономика; 304–321.
7. Семенов И. 2001. Стадии развития организации. Управление персоналом (9): 62–71.
8. Филонович С. Р. 2001. Чем болеют компании. Секрет фирмы (11): 56–58.
9. Широкова Г., Меркурьева И., Серова О. 2006. Особенности формирования жизненных циклов российских компаний (эмпирический анализ). Российский журнал менеджмента 4 (3): 3–26.

Literature

ӘОЖ: 821.512.122

Қазіргі қазақ прозасындағы 1920-30 жылдардың ашаршылық суреттері: көркемдік пен тарихтың ақтаңдақтары

Бисек Жангелді

Қазақ тілі мен әдебиеті БББ 2-курс магистранты

Акбулатов А.А.

М.Өтемісов атындағы БҚУ доценті, PhD доктор, ғылыми жетекші

Түйін: Мақалада қазіргі қазақ прозасындағы тарихи тақырыптың бірі ашаршылық жылдар қарастырылады. Тарихи тақырып пен көркем шындықты бейнелеу жолдары сараланады. Көркем образдарды жасаудағы авторлық концепциялар астары, ұлттық трагедияның себебі мен салдары нақты көркем шығармалар арқылы талданып көрсетіледі.

Кілт сөздер: қазақ прозасы, ашаршылық жылдар, тарихи тақырып, көркемдік шындық, образ.

Изображение голодомора 1920-30 годов в современной казахской прозе: истины литературы и истории

Бисек Жангельді,

магистрант 2 курса , обучающийся по ОП “Казахский язык и литература”.

Научный руководитель:

А.А.Акбулатов, доцент ЗКУ ,доктор PhD

Резюме: В статье рассматривается одна из значимых тем в истории казахского народа- годы голода в Казахстане. В работе анализируются методы и приемы воплощения исторической действительности и художественного изображения. На реальных примерах из художественных произведений исследуются замысел авторов в создании художественных образов,причины и страшные последствия национальной трагедии.

Ключевые слова: казахская проза, голодные годы, историческая тема,художественная реальность,образ.

Images of the famine of the 1920s-30s in contemporary Kazakh prose: the truths of art and history

Bisek Jangeldi

2nd year master’s student of Kazakh language and literature education program

Akbulatov A.A.

Docent of M. Utemisov WKU, PhD doctor, scientific supervisor

Summary: The article deals with the years of famine, one of the historical topics in contemporary Kazakh prose. Ways of depicting historical subject and artistic reality are differentiated. The prerequisites for the author's concepts in creating artistic images, the causes and consequences of the national tragedy are analyzed through real works of art.

Keywords: Kazakh prose, famine years, historical subject, artistic reality, image.

Жаңа заман, жаңа ғасыр әдебиеттің даму процесін зерделейтін оның ғылымына да жаңаша талаптар, заман биігінен сараптау қажеттігін алға тартты. Тәуелсіздік бүгінгі таңдағы қоғамтану ғылымдарының ақтаңдақтарын қопара зерттеп, тың деректер мен пікірлерді толықтыра зерттеп, бүгінгі жас ұрпақтың талғамына қатысты ұлттық құндылықтарды қалыптастыруға қажетті маңызды идеологиялық мұраларды зерттеп, зерделеуге аса мән беруді басты мұрат етеді. Бұл өз кезегінде қоғамдық сананы жаңғыртып, руханияттың сұранысына жауап беретін әдебиет тарихының түрлі кезеңдерінде жабық болған, игерілмеген тақырыптардың қайта түлеуіне, халық санасында жаңғыруына да мол мүмкіндік туғызды.

Тәуелсіз ел атанған сәтте рухани ұлттық мұраларды саралап, бүгінгі уақыт биігінен бағалағанда кешегі тоталитарлық тәртіп аясындағы идеологиялық қағида, тұжырымдармен, олар әкелген зардаптармен тығыз байланыста алып қарастырудың маңызы зор екені белгілі.

Сондай кеңес кезінде тұмшаланған ұлттық тақырыптардың бірі - отаршылдық ниетпен қасақана ұйымдастырылған, отызыншы жылдардың басында халық басына төтеден түсірілген ауыр нәубет – аштық туралы шындық [1,415]. Осы тұрғыдан келсек, әдебиет өз дәуірінің, оқиғаның дәлелі болатын деректер пен тарихи тұжырымдарың көркем сөзбен салынған жалпақ жұртқа, оқырманға арналған ұлттық руханияттың көзі деуге болады. Әр дәуірдің тарихы сол заманға сай түсіндірілсе, бірақ уақыт өте келе кейбір құндылықтар өзгеріске ұшырап отырғандықтан, ол қайта ойлау мен түсіндіру әдісіне айналады. Қазақ ақын-жазушылары қазақ тарихындағы әрбір қайғы-қасіретке ешқашан бей-жай қарамаған, соның ішінде ашаршылық көптеген көркем шығармаларының тақырыбына айналдырды. Заманның әрбір өткелдерін басынан өткізе отырып, қазақ қаламгерлері ұлттық трагедиясыны қабырғаларын қайыстыра отырып, суреттеуге ден қойып келеді. Бұл жеке жазушының шығармашылық зертханасы болса да, көпшілік оқырман қауымның менімен ұласып, трагедияға толы ұлттық тарихтың шынайылығын ашып көрсеткен көркемдік өрнектер деуге болады.

Бұл тақырыпта жазылған қазақ прозасының көрнекті туындыларының қатарындағы Ғ.Мүсіреповтың «Шұғыла», Б.Майлиннің «Күлпәш» әңгімелері сонау кеңестік заманның өзінде жазылса, кейінгі жылдардағы Ш.Мұртазаның «Тортай шалдың есегі» әңгімесі, Адам Меекебаевтың «Қазына сыры» (1994), Смағұл Елеубайдың «Ақбоз үй», Кәкімжан Қазыбаевтың «Сұрапыл», Гүлсара Дәулетқызы Райымқұлованың «Үзілме, Үміт» романдары тәуелсіздік жылдары жарық көріп, кеңестік кезеңде айтуға мүмкіндік берілмеген тарихи ақтаңдақтарды терең зерделеуге мүмкіндік туды.

Ашаршылық тақырыбы қазақ тарихшылары мен жазушыларын ғана емес, әлемдік деңгейде қызығушылық туғызып отыр. Сондай еңбектердің бір-екеуіне тоқталып өтсек, неміс ғалымы Киндлер Роберттің «Сталиндік көшпенділер. Қазақстан билігі және ашаршылық» (ауд. Ө.Ахмет, 2023) [2] кітабын, сондай-ақ шет елде тұрып жатса да, әлемнің назарын қазақ даласындағы өткен зұлмат жылдардың трагедиясына аударған Едіге Мағауиннің құрастыруымен шыққан «Сары кітап. Қазақ ашаршылығы – 1931-1933 жылдар: Көз көрген естеліктер» (2020) [3] еңбегін атап өтуге болады. Екі кітапта да сол замандағы тірі куәгерлер мен тарихи құжаттардың ізі мен естеліктері негізінде жазылған.

Неміс ғалымы Киндлер Роберт аталған кітабында тарихи деректерді кеңінен пайдаланған. Ресей, Қазақстан, Еуропа архивтерінің құжаттарын кеңінен ақтарып, сонымен қатар сол кезеңге байланысты туған әдеби көркем мұраларды да мәліметтер ретінде қарыстырған. 1917-1950 жылдар аралығындағы қазақ ұлтының қаралы трагедиялық ғұмырының кең понораммасын жасаған ғалым Киндлер Роберт: «Қазақстанда 1930 жылдың

бас кезінен басталған ашаршылық ұлттық трагедия болып саналады. Бір жарым миллионнан астам адам ажал құшты, миллиондаған адам жер-суын тастай қашып, босқынға айналды.

Ашаршылық қашып құтыла алмайтын шарасыздықтан келген жоқ, Иосиф Сталин жетекшілігімен Кеңес басшылығы қабылдаған шешімдердің салдарынан туындады. Ұжымдастыру және мал-мүлікті тәркілеу, оған қоса көшпенділерді күштеп отырықшы ету әрекеті халықты қайыршыға айналдырды. Соған қарамастан ұжымшарлар мен шарулардың мемлекет алдындағы міндеттемелері өте жоғары болды. Соның кесірінен адамдар ең соңғы күнкөріс көзінен айырылды. Адам тағдырының мемлекет үшін еш құны болмағандықтан, олар аштық пен індеттен қара шыбынша жаппай қырылды. Өз кітабымда мен осындай саясат жүргізуге алып келген себептердің мәнін түсіндіруге тырыстым. Сонымен бірге аштықтың осындай ауыр сипатта кең құлаш жайып кетуіне әкімшіл-әміршіл билік жүйесінің барлық деңгейде елдің аман қалуына мүмкіндік беретіндей оң шешімдер қабылданғанын да атап көрсеттім» [2,5], - дейді. Кеңестік кезеңдегі қазақ тарихына қатысты неміс ғалымының қазіргі уақыттағы қазақ тарихнамасы туралы тұжырымындарынан біршама ойды аңғаруға болады.

Халыққа теңдік, жақсылық береміз деген социализм сұмдығы Ғ.Мүсіреповтың «Шұғыла» (1933) әңгімесінде астарлы символикамен ашылады. «Асыра сілтеу болмасын, аша тұяқ қалмасын» деген үкімет саясаты қазақтың күнкөрісі малынан тігерге тұяқ қалдырмай түгел алып қояды. Халық аштыққа, жаппай қырылуға ұшырайды. Осы жайды жазушы ашық жазбағанымен, аштықтың себебін, кінәлі басшылықты астармен бейнелейді. Елді тентіретіп, алдының аштықтан өлуіне себепкер болғандардың бірі – Дәулетбек піркәншік пен оның әйелінің топастығын, сұрқиялығын суреттейді. Алғашқы жоғарыда аталған шығармаларында 20-30 жылдардағы халық өмірінің шынайы шындығын берген түбегейлі тартысты ойнақы әзілмен, жарасымды қалжыңмен, ұлттық нақышпен дәл суреттеуін шеберлік үлгісі деуге болады.

Шерхан Мұртазаның «Тортай шалдың есегі» атты әңгімесінде тарихта өшпес із қалдырған, миллиондаған жазықсыз жандардың қаны төгілген кешегі өткен Ұлы Отан соғысы деген атауға ие зұлмат тұсында қазақ халқы басынан өткерген шырғалаң сәттер суреттеледі. Қаламгердің бұдан басқа да «Сол бір күз», «Ақсай мен Көксай», «Бойтұмар», «Айырбас», «Жүз жылдық жара», «Интернат наны», «Қасқырдың тарамысы» атты әңгімелерінде соғыс жылдарындағы ауыл өмірі сан қырынан бейнеленген болатын. Бір есекке бола жиырма бес жылға сотталған Тортай шалды баласы Нұртай Кеңес одағының батыры болып келген соң, қорыққанынан әкім қаралар айдалған жерінен алдырады. Осындай келеңсіз оқиғаларды суреттей отырып, дүйім елде болып жатқан «асыра сілтеу болмасын, аша тұяқ қалмасын» деп ұрандаған елдің жайын көрсетеді.

Көлемді роман жанрындағы туындыларға шолу жасасақ, Адам Мекебаевтың «Қазына сыры» романы сонау жылдардағы ұлт трагедиясын ашуда дәстүрлі тарихи тақырыпты өзінше басқа қырынан ашып, жанрлық тұрғыдан шым-шытырық оқиға толы авантюралы сюжетті алға тартып, адамзат баласының басына түскен нәубеттегі адамның адамшылық келбеті мен бірге ішкі азғындық-малұғындық образын ашып көрсетіп, терең психологиялық портреттерді көз алдымызға әкеледі.

Романның сюжеті Сатыбалды байдың кәмпеске уақытында бас сауғалап қашқанда көміп кеткен қазына байлығына қатысты аңыздармен байланысты сюжеттік желілер оқырманды түрлі психологиялық ауыр сезім-күйлерге түсіреді.

Аталған романның басталуы да ерекше басталып, оқырман санасын психологиялық тұрғыдан шымырлатып өтеді. «Ол бүгіннен қалмай баласы мен әйелінің, сосын өзінің аштан өлетінін білді» [4,3], - деген жалғыз ауыз сөйлемнен басталып, лирикалық шегіністермен өткен тарихи кезеңдерді баяндап өтеді.

Романдағы тарихи уақыт хроникасы 1928, 1929 жылдардағы байлардың мал-мүлкін тәркілеу, асыра сілтеу саясаты, ұжымдастыру, мал шаруашылығымен айналысқан ұлттың күн

көріс кәсібінен жасанды түрде ажырату т.б. сол кездегі тарихи шешімдердің трагедиясына тоқталады. Сол арқылы романның орталық кейіпкері писарь Түктібайдың отбасына ене бастаған аштық тауқыметінің алғашқы зардаптарын суреттеуінен қалың елдің басындағы тұрмыс тауқыметін баяндап, ол аждаһаның құрығы ұзын екенін, одан жуық арада құтылудың жолы көрінбейтінін автор сездіреді.

Автор бас кейіпкерді антиморальдық әрекеттер үстінде суреттеп, аштықтың әртүрлі әлеуметтік психологиялық астарына үңіліп, салдары көрсетілген. Романның өзіндік түйер ойы ретінде тамақ таппай ашығу мен аштықтан гөрі, қоғамдық өмірдегі адамшылықтан айырылу әлде қайда қауыпті, әлде қайда қорқынышты екенін айтып өткен абзал.

Көркем шығармада әуелі адамдығыбар кейіпкер, кейін келе бұзылады. Бай болмаса да, жан сақтарлық азын-шоғын малы тәркіленіп, бай-құлақ болып танылған ол түрмеге тоғытылады. Ондан пара беріп шыққанымен, бір бүлінген дүние шыр айналдырып, өмірі өмір болмайды. Әйелі Сырға мен жалғыз тұяғы Ердәулет аштықтан жан тапсырады.

Билік үкіметі қазақ даласында кіші Қазан төңкерісін жасаймыз деп өзеуресе, ауылдағы шолақ белсенді, қараңғы қара таяқтар қит етсе, «контра» деп, бай мен кедей деп ажыратпастан, «түгін түтеткен шаңырақтың ошағының отын өшірмей тынбайды» [4,7]. Міне, осындай азғындықтардың ортасында жүріп Түктібайдың да өмір үшін жанталасып, теріс бағыттарға түсуінің алғышарттары қалыптасады. Сыртқы ортадағы түрлі жағдайларды өзінше топшылап, аштықтан өзегі талған жанның ішкі ниетінде бір қара дақ, фэлсафа өсіп шығады. Бұл сол кездегі кеңестік биліктің жалған ұрандары мен адамға көрсеткен қорлықтары еді. «Бұл заман қолында билігі бар, әмірін өткізе алатындардың заманы, - деген тұжырым жасайды ол. – Белсенділер сияқты біреуді қорқытсаң ғана алақаныңа бірдеңе тамады. Әйтпесе көрген күнің қараң, құрып кетесің» [4,9], - деген Түктібайдың миының түпкірінде осындай бір фэлсафа оянады. Осы әрекеттерін жүзеге асырып, қорқытып күн көру керек деген ойын жүзеге асырып Өмірбайдың жалғыз сиырын сойғызып, енді бірінің қолындағы астығын тартып алса, Сатыбалды байдың алтын қазына қоймасының жасырылған жерін айтпадың деп Қабыш деген кедейді айбалтамен өлімші етеді. Оның әйелі Мәдинаны балаларыңмен бірге аштықтан құтқарамын деген желеумен масқараға ұшыратады. Сөйтіп қойынын алтынға толтырып, тайып тұрады.

Бұл роман туралы Ғалым Ш.Елеуенов: «Романда аштықтың әртүрлі әлеуметтік салдары көрсетілген. Шовинизмнің де үскірік аязы аз тітірентпейді. Кеңес өкіметі жарлы-жақыбайларды жарылқайды дегенге алданған бұрынғы белсенді Жиенқұл: ашығу апатын «балшайбектердің өздері қазақ халқын қасақана құрту үшін жасап жатыр ма деп қауіптенем» дейді. Аштықта қазақ халқының жартысына дейін қырылғанын еске алсақ, мұндай қорытынды шындыққа қайшы келмейді. Мекебаев романы аштық қазақ ұлтының санын ғана кемітіп қоймағанына назар тіктіреді. Халықтың қасиетін де аз жоғалтпаған. Ел ішін безбүйрек белсенділер шаңдатты. Түктібайдай тітіркенбей еске алмайтын залым сұрқияларды қоздатты» [1,417], - деп бағалайды.

Мақаламызды қорытындылай келсек, тарихымыздағы 1920-30 жылдардың ашаршылық ең қаралы, қасіретті жылдар ретінде халық жадында өшпестей із қалдырды. Адамзат баласының тарихындағы түрлі табиғи апаттардан бөлек, саяси жүйенің құрбаны ретінде тұтас ұлттардың жер бетінен жойылып, не болмаса, ел, жерін тастап әлемнің түпкір-түпкіріне босқындыққа ұшыруы бүгінгі заман биігінен қарасақ, тек ұлттық проблема ғана емес, әлемдік адами проблема деуге болады. Ал, қазақ ақын-жазушылар өз ұлтының тағдырындағы қасіретті кезеңдерді көркем суреттеу арқылы ұлттың мұң-мұқтажын әдебиеттің өзегіне айналдырып, кейінгі ұрпаққа рухани тағылымды мұра ретінде мәнін ашып жеткізеді.

Пайдаланылған әдебиеттер:

1. Қазақ романы: өткені мен бүгіні: Ұжымдық монография. – Алматы: «Алматы баспа үйі», 2009. – 644 б.
2. Киндлер Роберт. Сталиндік көшпенділер. Қазақстан билігі және ашаршылық / Роберт Киндлер [ауд. Ө.Ахмет]. – Астана: Фолиант, 2023. – 432 б.
3. Мағауин Едіге. Сары кітап. Қазақ ашаршылығы – 1931-1933 жылдар: Көз көрген естеліктер / Құрастырған, баспаға әзірлеген: Мағауин Едіге. – Алматы: «BRK Press», 2020. – 317 б.
4. Мекебаев А. Қазына сыры. Алматы: ҚР Жоғарғы кеңесінің баспаханасы, 1994.

AZƏRBAYCAN DİLİNİN İNKİŞAF TARİXİNDƏN

Abdullayeva Səminə Sabir qızı

Azərbaycan Dövlət Pedaqoji Universtet

Açar sözlər: Azərbaycan dili, Dilin tarixi, Dövlətçilik, Dilə münasibət

Key words: Azerbaijani language, History of the language, Statehood, Attitude towards the language

Dilin cəmiyyətdəki mövqeyi dövlətçiliklə birbaşa bağlıdır. Dövlətçilik, həmçinin dilin dayacağıdır, hərəkətverici qüvvəsidir və cəmiyyətdəki nüfuzunun təminatçısıdır. Dilin müstəqil inkişafı, zənginləşməsi və nüfuzu bilavasitə dövlətçiliklə bağlı olduğu üçün dil dövlətçiliyin ən aparıcı atributlarından biri hesab olunur. Dövlətçilik zəminində dilin cəmiyyətdəki rolu artır, informasiya imkanları genişlənir. Yeni anlayışların ifadəsində daxili imkanlar aparıcı yer tutur. Onun strukturu inkişaf edir, informasiyaların intensiv çatdırılması prosesinə uyğun olaraq yeni ifadə vasitələri sözlər, sözdüzəldici vasitələr, söz birləşmələri və cümlə tipləri formalaşır. Dövlətçiliyin uzun dövrlər ərzində mövcudluğu şifahi və yazılı dil arasındakı vəhdəti yaxşılaşdırır və sabitləşmə yaradır. Dövlətçilik olmadığı təqdirdə nə yaxşılaşmadan, nə də sabitləşmədən söhbət açmaq mümkündür.

Dil dövlətçiliklə müşayiət edildikdə onun ifadə imkanları artdığı üçün nüfuzu da qat-qat artır. Odur ki, dövlətçiliklə müşayiət oluna dildən başqa dillərə sözlər daha çox keçməyə başlayır. Dövlətçilik olmadıqda isə dilin nüfuzu azalır, sözyaratma qabiliyyəti zəifləyir, təsir və təzyiqlərə daha çox məruz qalır. Yeni anlayışların ifadəsində daxili imkanların rolu azaldığı üçün məcburi şəkildə nüfuzlu dillərdən hazır ifadə vasitələri almalı olur. Belə olduqda isə dildə kənar elementlər çoxalır, onun ümumişlək səviyyəsi aşağı düşür. Dil dövlətçiliklə müşayiət olunmadıqda geniş informasiya imkanlarını itirməklə adi məişət dili səviyyəsində qalır. Bu isə onun tədricən cəmiyyətdəki mövqeyini itirilməsinə səbəb olur.

Dil insan cəmiyyətində elə bir güclü, elə bir mühüm, elə bir vacib informasiya vasitəsidir ki, o təkə bu gün üçün gərəkli deyildir. Dil elə bir qüdrətli vasitədir ki, o keçmiş bu günə, bu günə gələcəyə çatdırır. Ona görə də dil qorunmalıdır, yaşadılmalıdır. Dildə qaydalar elə təyin olunmalıdır ki, yüz il, beş yüz il, min il bundan sonra da informasiyalar gələcək nəsllə maneəsiz çatdırıla bilsin. Dilin hamı üçün anlaşılıqlı olan normalarını yaratmaq və qorumaq lazımdır ki, gələcək nəsillər çətlik çəkmədən onu başa düşə bilsinlər.

Dilin dövlətçiliyə münasibəti, məhz onun uzunömürlü olmasından ibarətdir. Dil bütün əsillər tərəfindən qorunmalı, cilalanmalı və daha çox daxili imkanlar hesabına zənginləşdirilməlidir.

Dilin çox anlaşılıqlı olması üçün onun müvafiq normalarının yaranması və sabitləşməsi zəruri problemlərdən biridir. Dil normaları nə qədər sabitləşmiş olsa da o qədər də uzun ömürlü olur. Dil normaları nə qədər uzun ömürlüdürsə, onun informasiya imkanları da o qədər çoxdur.

Azərbaycan dili mövcud olduğu tarixi dövrlər ərzində həm zəngin inkişaf mərhələləri keçmiş, həm də müəyyən vaxtlarda çox ciddi təsir və təzyiqlərə məruz qalmışdır. Azərbaycan dilinin zəngin sözdüzəldici və sözdəyişdirici vasitələrə malik olması, şəkilçi sistemində çox ciddi bir ardıcılığın formalaşması, sözyaratma prosesində az sözlə çoxlu mənaların ifadə edilməsi, söz sırasında özünəməxsus qanunauyğun ardıcılığın mövcudluğu və s. onu göstərir ki, bu dil ən qədimlərdə ictimai həyatda böyük nüfuzə malik bir informasiya vasitəsi olmuşdur. İctimai həyatda fəal mövqeyə malik olan dil isə, şübhəsiz, güclü dövlətçiliyi olan xalqın informasiya vasitəsi kimi fəaliyyət göstərmişdir. Lakin müəyyən zaman mərhələlərində Azərbaycan dili güclü təzyiq və

təsirlərə də məruz qalmışdır. Bu təzyiq və təsirlər nəticəsində vahid norma pozulmuş, öz yerini ixtiyari səviyyədəki üslublara vermişdir. Məsələn, qədim və zəngin ənənələri olan «Kitabi-Dədə Qorqud» dastalarında təcəssüm tapan Azərbaycan dilinin yazılı mənbələri barədə hələ XIII əsrə qədər heç bir məlumat əldə edilməmişdir. Azərbaycan dilindəki ilk yazılı mənbə kimi, hələlik İzzəddin Həsənoğlunun qəzəlinə istinad edilir. Qəzəlin hər bir beytinin birinci misrası bu gün çox aydın başa düşülür. İkinci misra isə ərəb-fars tərkibləri ilə yükləndiyindən çətin anlaşılır. Həsənoğluda sonrakı dövrdə də yazılı ədəbiyyatımızın dilində klassik ənənələr aparıcı yer tutur. Odur ki, bu gün mədəniyyət xəzinəmizə əvəzsiz töhfələr vermiş Nəsiminin, Füzulinin, Qövsü Təbrizinin və bir çox dahi sənətkarlarımızın əsərlərinin aydın başa düşülməsi çətinlik yaradır. Ona görə həmin mənbələr çətin başa düşülür ki, onlar ümumxalq dili normalarından uzaqlaşmışdı.

Azərbaycan dilində ərəb-fars elementlərinin ixtiyari işlənməsi hələ XIX əsrin əvvəllərinə qədər (xüsusən, 30-cu illərə kimi) davam etmişdir. Bununla birlikdə, XIX əsrin birinci yarısında, Rusiyanın Azərbaycan torpaqlarını işğal etməsindən sonra (1813-1828-ci illər) dilimizə ixtiyari şəkildə rus sözləri daxil olmağa başlamışdır. Bu isə onsuz da vahid norma əsasında işlənməyən yazılı dilə yeni bir pərakəndəlik gətirdi. Ümumxalq danışq dilində isə rus dilinə məxsus sözlərin interferensiya səciyyəli elementləri daxil olmağa başlamışdı. Beləliklə, həm şifahi və həm də yazılı dildə norma fərqlənməsi getdikcə artmağa başlamışdı. Azərbaycan dilinin şifahi və yazılı qolları arasında çoxlu fərqlər yarandığına görə, eləcə də yazılı dildə vahid, sabit norma müəyyənləşdirilə bilmədiyinə görə, hətta, 1918-ci ildə yaranmış Azərbaycan Xalq Cümhuriyyətində rəsmi dövlət işləri rus dilində aparılırdı. Bunu nəzərə alaraq Cümhuriyyət 1918-ci il iyunun 27-də, hələ hökumət Gəncədə fəaliyyət göstərərəkən dövlət dili barədə bir qərar qəbul edildi. Ancaq qərar da Azərbaycan dili yox, türk dili adı işlənməmişdi. Qərar hökumət tərəfindən elə edildi, lakin parlamentdə bu məsələ qaldırılmadığından həll edilməmiş də qaldı. Qərarın dil haqqındakı bəndində belə deyilir: «Türk dili dövlət dili qəbul olunsun. Dövlət idarələrinə, məhkəmə və inzibati orqanlara, habelə, sair vəzifələrə bu dili bilənlər gələcəkdə hökumət müəssisələrində rus dilinin işlədilməsinə ixtiyar verilsin».

Azərbaycan Xalq Cümhuriyyəti süquta uğrayandan sonra da bir müddət dövlət dilinin adı türk dili kimi işlənməkdə davam etdi. 1935-ci ildə yalnız bir təsadüf nəticəsində türk dili adı Azərbaycan dili adı ilə əvəz olundu. O təsadüf bundan ibarət idi ki, 1935-ci ildə İ.V.Stalin Kremlə Azərbaycan ümayəndələrini qəbul edərkən aqronom Kremlyayevaya belə bir sual vermişdi: «Siz Azərbaycan dilini bilirsinizmi?». Bundan sonra mətbuatda türk dili adı əvəzinə Azərbaycan dili işlədilməyə başlamışdır.

Azərbaycan dilinin, hətta, respublika daxilində dövlət dili kimi işlədilməsi mərkəzi hökumət üçün maraqlı deyildi. Yalnız o zaman Azərbaycan Respublikasının rəhbəri olan Heydər Əliyevin təşəbbüsü ilə 1978-ci il Konstitusiyasında Azərbaycan dili dövlət dili kimi rəsmiləşdirilmişdir. Konstitusiyanın 73-cü maddəsində göstərilir: «Azərbaycan Sovet Sosialist Respublikasının dövlət dili Azərbaycan dilidir». Bu o zamanlara təsadüf edirdi ki, sovet dövlətində formaca milli, məzmunca sosialist mədəniyyətinin çox güclü təbliğatı gedirdi. Formaca milli, məzmunca sosialist mədəniyyətinin dili, şübhəsiz ki, rus dili olmalı idi. Ona görə də bu konsepsiya bir milli dil kimi Azərbaycan dilinin yayılması, genişlənməsi və zənginləşməsi qarşısında ciddi çətinliklər yaradırdı.

Azərbaycan dilinin dövlət dili adlandırılması o zaman üçün böyük hadisə idi. Dövlət dili odur ki, elmi, texniki, sosial, iqtisadi nailiyyətlər bu dildə ifadə olunsun. Bu dil rəsmi, diplomatik və hüquqi sənədlərin dili kimi işlədilsin. Bu dil inzibati orqanlar sahəsində, eləcə də hərbi işlərdə istifadə olunsun. Bu dil ölkə daxilində bütün sahələri təmin edə bilsin, həm də respublikanın nailiyyətləri bu dillə dünyaya çıxarılsın.

Dövlət dili anlayışı əslində dərin bir anlayışdır. Sovet dövründə ona görə mərkəzi hökumətdəki rəhbərlər buna reaksiya verə bilmədilər ki, həmin dövrdə elə bir çoxları dövlət dilini ədəbi dil kimi başa düşürdü. Heydər Əliyev isə bu ifadəni strateji məqsədlə işlədirdi. Həqiqətən, Azərbaycan müstəqil dövlət olduqda sonra bu strateji məqsəd həyata keçdi. Azərbaycan dili indi

bütün sahələr üzrə inkişaf edərək öz nailiyyətlərini özü dünyaya çıxmaq əzmindədir. Heydər Əliyev belə bir zamanda ana dilinə qayğı barədə düşünürdü, dilin inkişafı prespektivlərini müəyyən edərək mütəxəssislərin qarşısında konkret vəzifələr qoyurdu. Yazılı və şifahi dil arasında yaxınlığa nail olunması sabitləşmiş normalara malik dilin formalaşmasında mühüm amil olduğuna görə nitq mədəniyyətinin inkişaf etdirilməsi zəruri bir məsələ kimi qarşıda dururdu. Məhz o zaman Heydər Əliyev dövlət dili barəsində düşünərkən dövlət dilinin formalaşmasında nitq mədəniyyətini onun təməli hesab edirdi.

Heydər Əliyevin ana dilinin tətbiqi və inkişaf etdirilməsi barədəki fikirləri, kəlamları bu gün bizim təsəvvürümüzdə aforizm kimi canlanır. Heydər Əliyev dilin mənəvi, tərbiyəvi, ideoloji xarakter daşdığını aşağıdakı kimi müdrik kəlamlarda ifadə etmişdir: «Hər bir xalqın milliliyini, mənəvi dəyərlərini yaşadan, inkişaf etdirən onun dilidir», «Hər bir xalq öz dili ilə yaranır. Ancaq xalqın dilini yaşatmaq, inkişaf etdirmək və dünya mədəniyyəti səviyyəsində qaldırmaq xalqın qabaqcıl adamlarının, elm, bilik xadimlərinin fəaliyyəti nəticəsində mümkün olur».

Heydər Əliyev həmişə, hər zaman ana dilimiz olan müqəddəs Azərbaycan dilinə böyük hörmətlə yanaşmış və ona biganə yanaşmağın, etinasız qalmağın, xüsusən də onun adının kimsə tərəfindən dəyişdirilməsinin qətiyyənlə yolverilməz olduğunu göstərmişdir.

RESUME

The state language is a necessary information mechanism regulated by statehood. If there is statehood, we can talk about the development, formation and internal norms of the language. The support, structure and legal base of the language that develops it meaningfully is statehood. This means that if there is no statehood, there is no state language. Statehood In the absence of a language, it is deprived of a legal basis. Also, There are many differences in the information space where the language exists.

The conditions of independent statehood are a fertile ground for multi-fold revitalization of the flexible mechanism of our mother tongue and expansion of its functions. As our independent statehood flourishes, our mother tongue will also be enriched and will successfully overcome all the obstacles in front of it to enter the world arena.

By promoting the mother tongue as the state language, Heydar Aliyev saw the independence, freedom, and sovereignty of Azerbaijan behind it. Life proved that Heydar Aliyev assessed the future correctly and correctly.

Today, the task is to achieve the implementation of Heydar Aliyev's program in the development of the mother tongue at the level of the state language.

The state language is an important field of activity for every nation for its existence. However, there are independent states in the world that do not have a program to develop the state language. Therefore, the activity of the national language in such states is limited to covering internal information.

Ədəbiyyat siyahısı

1. Axundov A. Ümumi dilçilik. Bakı, Maarif, 1979.
2. Azərbaycan dilinin orfoepiya sözlüyü. Bakı, 1982.
3. Abdullayev N. Nitq mədəniyyətinin əsasları. Bakı, Elm və təhsil, 2013.
4. Bayramov Akif, Məhərrəmov Ziyəddin, Mustafa İskəndərzadə. "Azərbaycan dili və nitq mədəniyyəti". Bakı, "ULU", 2015.
5. Dəmirçizadə Ə. Müasir Azərbaycan dili. Bakı, Maarif, 1972.
6. Dəmirçizadə Ə. Azərbaycan ədəbi dilinin tarixi. Bakı, Maarif, 1979.
7. Əfəndizadə Ə. Orfoqrafiya, orfoepiya, qrammatika lüğəti. Bakı, Maarif, 1983.
8. Əzizov E. Azərbaycan dilinin tarixi dialektologiyası. Bakı, Elm və təhsil, 2016
9. Quluzadə Gülsəda. Nitq mədəniyyəti. Nitqin yığcamlığı üzərində iş. Təhsil Problemləri. 5 May, 2014.

Philological Sciences

Antroponim və onun dil sistemində yeri

Əliyeva Günel

ADPU, XDM, ingilis dili müəllimi

Açar sözlər: antroponim, universal, leksika, semantik.

Bütün dillərin adlar sistemində ümumi və xüsusi adlar universal semantik sistem yaradır. Adların adlandırma xarakterinə görə qarşılaşdırılmasına antik filosofların, o cümlədən Frakiyalı Dionisinin (e.ə.II əsr) işlərində rast gəlinir.

Ötən əsrin əvvəllərində Böyük Britaniyada Evelen, Leslie, Robin adlarının oğlanlara verilməsi geniş yayılmışdır. Bu adın qızlara qoyulması halları çoxaldıqdan sonra oğlan adı kimi onlar az istifadə edilir. İngilis dilində cins kateqoriyası olmadığından bu dilin apelyativ leksikasında cinsi fərqləndirmə sözləri azdır. Rus dilində isə morfoloji əlamət adda cinsi ifadə edir. Bu dildə qadın və kişi adları arasında dəqiq sərhəd vardır. Hər iki cins üçün eyni olan adlarda da fərqləndirmə məntiqi izahını tapır: Aleksandr-Aleksandra. İngilis dilində isə eyni adın həm kişiyə, həm də qadına verilməsi halları çoxdur. Bu hal hətta bədii əsərlərdə də qeyd alınır. D.Lodcun "Nise Work" romanında Robin/Robun adını qızın daşması hadisələrin inkişafında aparıcı xətt olur.

İngilis antroponimikasındakı adların bir qisminin yaşı da təqribən təyin etməsi özünü göstərir. S.Pinker yazır: *"Amerika oxucularının əksəriyyəti Murray adının daşıyıcısı barədə onun 60-dan yuxarı yaşının olması, orta sinfə mənsubluğu haqqında müəyyən qənaətə gəlirlər"* [1, s.13]. Müəllif bundan sonra göstərir ki, Edna, Ethel, Bertha – yaşlı, Susan, Nangy, Debra – orta yaşlı, Cenifer, Amanda, Heather – yaş 30-u aşmış qadınların, İsabella, Madison, Olivia – qızların adlarıdır. Kişilərdə isə, adlar dayanıqlıdır. Bütün dövrlərdə Robert, David, Michael, Cohn, Cames həm oğlan, həm də kişi adları olmuşdur [1, s.312].

C.Millə görə, konnotasiyadan məhrum olan yeganə predmet adları xüsusi adlardır. Xüsusi adlar heç bir mənaya malik deyildir. O.Yespersen bu fikirlə razılaşmır, xüsusi adda lüğəvi mənə axtarmağı düzgün saymır, kontekstual mənaya diqqəti cəlb edir. Adın konkret situasiyada necə tələffüz olunması, yazılması və kontekstual mənasını araşdırmağın vacibliyini qeyd edərək yazır: *"Söz hər bir ayrıca cümlədə kontekstdən və situasiyadan irəli gələn müəyyən mənə daşır"* [2, s.71].

V.A.Nikonova görə, xüsusi ad adlandıraraq fərdiləşdirir, ümumi isimlər növü cinsdən ayırır [3, s. 89].

Hər bir dilin onomastik sahəsində nüvə konstituenti antroponimlərdir. Bura rəsmi şəxs adları (tam), ev (qısa, hipokoristik), kiçiltmə-əzizləmə (diminutiv-meliorativ), böyüdücü-təhqiredici (arqumentativ-neyrativ) formalar, ikinci və sonrakı adlar, ata adları, baba adları, andronimlər, qinekonimlər, patronimlər, soyadlar, ikinci familiyalar, ləqəblər, təxəllüslər, küçə familiyaları və s. aiddir. Antroponim fondu (antroponimlər toplusu) öz tərkibinə görə rəngarəngdir. Dilə aid bütün adların siyahısı məhduddur. Ona görə bir ad yalnız bir adama verilmir [4, s.29]. Hər bir linqvokulturoloji cəmiyyət müxtəlif adlardan istifadə edir və həmin adlarda öz mədəniyyətinə aid mənaları gerçəkləşdirir.

Antroponimlərin bütün növləri ümumi funksional əlamətlərlə birləşir. Əlamətlər adamı adlandırmaq və ona müraciət etmək üçün istifadə olunur. Antroponim növləri arasında yalnız şəxs adı denotatı maksimum fərdiləşdirir. Digər növlər fakultativ olub xalqın tarixi-mədəni ənənələri ilə uyğunlaşır, etnokulturoloji diaxroniyada fərqlənir. Şəxs adları nisbətən sərbəst seçilir. Seçimdə müəyyən məcburilik ayrı-ayrı birliklərə aid vacib xüsusiyyətləri saxlamaqla bağlıdır. Məsələn, Çin ənənəsinə görə, müsəlman və xristian adlarının müəyyən siyahıdan seçilməsi, müsbət mənəli ümumi isimlərdən düzəltmə, müsbət semantikali sözlərdən düzəltmək isə bütüpərəstlikdən irəli

gəlmişdir. Familiya və ata adları törəmədir, qohumluq əlaqələri ilə bağlıdır. Ləqəb, təxəllüs, əsas deyil, əlavə adlardır. Etnodil birliyinin üzvlərinin əksəriyyətinin ləqəb və təxəllüsü olmur. Ləqəb, küçə adları, andronim, genikonimlər fərdə kənardan verilir, onun daşıyıcısı ilə ünsiyyətdə işləyə bilər. Təxəllüs və kriptonimləri fərd özü seçir.

Hind-Avropa dillərinin hər birinin öz antroponim sistemi vardır. Onların etimologiyasını müəyyənləşdirmək bu sistemlərin tarixi təkamülünə işıq salır.

A.A.Beletski belə hesab edir ki, şərq slavyan antroponimiyasının tarixi mənbəyi Vizantiya dövrü adlarının yunan sistemidir. Təbii ki, slavyan və skandinav antroponimiyası ilə bağlı adlar da ümumi sistemə daxildir (Vladimir, Vsevolod, Yaroslav, Olqa, İqor və s.). Antroponimlərlə ümumi adlar arasındakı bu cür fərqlər mədəniyyətlərin qarşılıqlı əlaqəsini, mürəkkəb mədəni təkamülü göstərir [5, s.78].

Antroponimik sistemdə milli, beynəlmiləl və alınma adlar bir-birinə qarışa bilər. Ruslarda yunan və latın adlarının tərcüməsi prosesində müəyyən antroponimlər yaranmışdır. Məsələn, Fides-Vera, Spes-Nadejda, Caritas-Löbov, Kliment-Tixomir, Fedor-Boqodar və s.

Müxtəlif xalqların antroponimik sisteminin öyrənilməsi prosesində aydın olmuşdur ki, bu sistemlər təkadıllıqdan çoxadlılığa doğru inkişaf etmişdir. Birüzvlü adlar daha qədimdir.

Antroponimik sistemin bir fərdə aid vahidlərindən müraciət zamanı istifadə edilməsi ayrı-ayrı xalqlarda fərqlidir. Antroponim növləri onların sayı, işlənmə ardıcılığı diaxronik dəyişkənliyə malikdir.

Ədəbiyyat siyahısı:

1. Pinker, S. The stuff of thought. / S.Pinker. –Penguin Books, – 2008. – 499 p.
2. Есперсен, О. Философия грамматики. / О.Есперсен. – М.: Изд-во Эдиториал УРСС, – 2002. – 404 с
3. Никонов, В.А. Имя и общество. / В.А.Никонов. – М.: Наука, – 1974. – 278 с.
4. Карасик, В.И. Язык социального статуса. / В.И.Карасик. – М.: Ин-т языкознания, РАН; Волгор. Гос. Пед. Ин-т, – 1992
5. Андреева, К.А. Лингвоцветовая картина мира в поэзии Д.Г.Лоурена // Проблемы лингвистики и методики преподавания иностранных языков. – Тюмень: Изд-во ТГУ, – 2002. – с. 3-9

NƏZƏRİ VƏ TƏTBİQİ DİLÇİLİK

Əsədova Sevinc Sabir qızı

ADPU, XDM, ingilis dili müəllimi, dissertant

XÜLASƏ

Dilçiliyin nəzəri və tətbiqi sahələrinin biri digəri üçün zəruridir. Məsələn, müasir dövrdə dil haqqında elmin sahəsi kimi tətbiqi dilçilik dilçiliyin ümumnəzəri əsasları ilə bağlı olub, ondan asılıdır. Dilçiliyin bu iki sahəsi bir-birini tamamlayır. Nəzəri dilçiliyin əsrlər boyu inkişafı əsasında onun bir sıra şöbələri yaranıb müəyyənləşmişdir. Belə müstəqil şöbələr təxminən bunlardır: fonetika, leksikologiya, onomalogiya, frazeologiya, semasiologiya, etimologiya, derivatologiya, morfologiya, sintaksis. Bu şöbələrin hər birinin özünə aid mövzusu, məqsədi və tarixi vardır. Tətbiqi dilçiliyin bir sıra şöbələri formalaşmışdır. Bunlardan ən başlıcaları aşağıdakılardır: qrafika, orfoqrafiya, orfoepiya, leksikoqrafiya və linqvotərcüməşünaslıq [3].

Açar sözlər: *dilçilik, nəzəri, tətbiqi, fonetika, praktik*

Key words: *linguistics, theoretical, practical, phonetics, applied*

Tədqiqatçıların nəzəri və tətbiqi dilçilik sahəsində əldə etdikləri nailiyyətləri genişləndirmək, həmçinin səhvləri aradan qaldırmaq kimi məsələlər dilçilik elmi ilə bağlı irəli sürülən fikir, fərziyyə və nəzəriyyələri tədqiq etmək üçün vacibdir. Habelə bu elmin tarixinin öyrənilməsi müasir dövr üçün də əhəmiyyətlidir. Dilçiliklə bağlı olaraq elmdə bir sıra anlayış və bunlara aid terminlər meydana çıxmışdır. Bu anlayışlar müxtəlif səbəb və məqsəddən irəli gəlmişdir; məsələn, tədqiqat sahəsinə görə “nəzəri dilçilik”, “tətbiqi dilçilik”; ideya-fəlsəfi əsasına görə “materialist dilçilik”, “idealist dilçilik”; ölkələrə görə “Azərbaycan dilçiliyi”, “yapon dilçiliyi”; xalqa görə “hind dilçiliyi”, “ərəb dilçiliyi”; qitələrə görə “Avropa dilçiliyi”, “Amerika dilçiliyi”; qütblərə görə “Qərb dilçiliyi”, “Şərq dilçiliyi”; elmin inkişaf tarixinə görə “klassik dilçilik”, “ənənəvi dilçilik”, “qədim dilçilik”, “müasir dilçilik” və s. Dilçiliyin sahələri problemi ilə dilçilər çoxdan maraqlanmışlar. Buna görə də dilçilik elmində həmin problemə müəyyən dərəcədə toxunulmuş, bu və ya digər şəkildə fikir söylənilmişdir. Rus alimlərindən V.A.Boqoroditski özünün 1915-ci ildə çap olunmuş “Ümumi dilçiliyə dair mühazirələr” adlı əsərində dilçiliyi iki sahəyə ayıraraq demişdir: “*Dilçilik, hər şeydən əvvəl, saf və tətbiqiyyə bölünür*” [1]. Dilçilik həm tətbiqi, həm də nəzəri elmdir. Bu cəhətə görə onun iki geniş sahəsi mövcuddur. Bunlardan biri nəzəri dilçilik sahəsi adlanır. Dilçiliyin nəzəri və tətbiqi aspektdə inkişafı heç də bunun iki elm olduğunu göstərmir. Lakin təəssüflə qeyd edilməlidir ki, bəzi elmi ədəbiyyatlarda dilçiliyin bu sahələrinin hər birinin ayrıca müstəqil elm hesab edildiyi fikirlərinə də rast gəlmək olur. Dilçiliyin tətbiqi və nəzəri sahələrinin fərqləndirilməsinin, bunlar arasında şərti də olsa, sərhədin müəyyənləşdirilməsinin xüsusi elmi əhəmiyyəti vardır. Bu sahələrin hər birinin özünəməxsus müəyyən tədqiqat mövzuları və problemləri mövcuddur. Dilçilik elminin tətbiqi adlanan sahəsi nəzəri dilçilikdən onunla fərqlənir ki, burada dillə bağlı olan əməli məsələlər həll edilir. Bundan əlavə, tətbiqi dilçilik dilin praktik öyrənilməsi üçün üsullar və vasitələr hazırlayır. Ayrı-ayrı elmlərin tarixi göstərir ki, elmin başlanğıc dövründə tətbiqi, əməli məsələlər ilk planda dayanır və zəruri hesab olunur, lakin sonralar elmin nəzəri sahəsi təşəkkül tapır. Belə bir cəhət tamamilə dilçilik elminə də aiddir. Tətbiqi dilçiliyin kökləri çox qədimlərdə insan cəmiyyətinin yazı yaratmaq kimi zəruri əməli tələbləri ilə bağlı olmuşdur. Get-gedə əməli tələblər daha da artmış, yeni-yeni məsələlər qarşıya çıxmışdır. İnsanlar yazı yaratmaqla əlaqədar xalq təfəkkürünün nailiyyətlərini mühafizə edib saxlamaq imkanı əldə etmişlər. Yaradılmış bədii əsərlərə kommentariyalar yazmağa başlamışlar və sair. Dilçiliyin tətbiqi sahəsinə alimlər xüsusi qiymət vermişlər. Bunun əhəmiyyətindən görkəmli dilçilərdən Boduen de Kurtene hələ XIX əsrin 70-ci illərində Peterburq Universitetində mühazirə oxuduğu zaman geniş bəhs etmişdir. XX əsr dilçiliyində, o cümlədən ölkəmizdə tətbiqi dilçiliyə dövlət əhəmiyyətli

məsələlərin həlli baxımından yanaşılmışdır. İndi başqa elm sahələrində olduğu kimi, dilçilikdə də tədqiqatın tətbiqi istiqamətinə daha çox meyil göstərilir və bu məqsədlə tətbiqi dilçiliyə aid əsərlərin nəşrinə geniş yer verilir. Dilçiliyin hər iki sahəsi arasında qarşılıqlı əlaqə mövcuddur. Möhkəm və müntəzəm qarşılıqlı əlaqə əsasında bu sahələr məhsuldar şəkildə inkişaf edə bilər. *“Əgər bunlar arasında əlaqə pozulsa, nəzəriyyə sxolastikaya, təcrübə isə vulqar empirizmə çevrilər”* [2].

ƏDƏBİYYAT SİYAHISI

1. Хрестоматия по истории русского языкознания. М., 1973, с. 438.
2. В.А.Звегинцев. Теоретическая и прикладная лингвистика. М., 1968, с. 4.
3. Afad Qurbanov. “Azərbaycan dilçiliyi problemləri”. Bakı, 2004.

Dialektologiyamızın mahir tədqiqatçısı- Həsən Mirzəyev

Gülnarə Məmmədzaadə

Azərbaycan Dövlət Pedaqoji Universiteti, Xarici dillər mərkəzi, filologiya üzrə fəlsəfə doktoru, baş müəllim, ID 0009-0004-2413-0466

Açar sözlər: Həsən Mirzə, dialekt, şivə, tədqiqatçı, mövzu, dilçilik

Ключевые слова: Гасан Мирза, диалект, диалект, исследователь, тема, языкознание

Key words: Hasan Mirza, dialect, dialect, researcher, topic, linguistics

Azərbaycan dilinin dialekt və şivələri zəngin lüğət ehtiyatına malikdir. Dialekt və şivələrimizin leksikasında Azərbaycan ədəbi dilində işlənməyən və ya başqa mənə daşıyan yüzlərcə söz vardır. Lakin son zamanlara qədər bu sözlər geniş miqyasda toplanmamış, küll halında nəşr olunmamışdır. Azərbaycanlıların qərb, orta və cənub ləhcələri arasında keçid xarakterli olan Qərbi Azərbaycanın Dərələyəz şivəsi uzun illər dialektoloqların diqqət mərkəzindən kənar qalmış, tədqiqat obyektinə olmamışdır. Bunu nəzərə alan H.Mirzəyev ilk dəfə olaraq Azərbaycan dilinin bir sıra qədim xüsusiyyətlərini və qrammatik formalarını özündə qoruyub saxlayan Dərələyəz şivələrindən ətraflı bəhs etmişdir.

Beləliklə, H.Mirzəyevin Dərələyəz mahalının şivə sözlərinə həsr etdiyi tədqiqatı bütöv və sistemli dialektoloji araşdırma hesab edirik. Çünki alimin müxtəlif istiqamətlər üzrə tədqiq etdiyi, xüsusən də tərtib etdiyi “Şivələrin sözlüyü” bu bölgənin şivə leksikasını tam əhatə edir.

Tədqiqatda dialektologiyanın aktual problemlərinə, o cümlədən də koynə dialekt məsələsinə aydınlıq gətirilir. Bu məsələ Azərbaycan dilçiliyində hələ də mübahisəlidir; ədəbi dilin koynə əsasında bir-iki və bütün dialektlərin dayanması barədə alimlər arasında fikir müxtəlifliyi davam etməkdədir. Alim, M.Şirəliyevin mövqeyini müdafiə edərək, ədəbi dilimizin koynəsinin tarixən Şamaxı, Təbriz, Qarabağ, müasir dövrdə isə Şirvan və Təbriz dialektlərinin olması fikrini irəli sürür, bununla da ədəbi dilimizlə həmin dialektlər arasında oxşarlıqların üstünlüyünü təsdiqləyir.

Tədqiqatda o da araşdırılır ki, tarixi dialektologiya xüsusi mövzusu və vəzifələri olan müstəqil dilçilik sahəsi kimi yenidən formalaşdığından çox vaxt dilçiliyin geridə qalmış bir sahəsi hesab olunur. Konkret dillərin çoxunun tarixi dialektologiyası hələ mövcud deyil. Hətta bu elm sahəsinin ümumi nəzəriyyəsi və metodikası da istənilən səviyyədə işlənilib hazırlanmayıb. Tarixi dialektologiyanın həqiqi nəzəriyyəsi ayrı-ayrı dillərin tarixi dialektologiyasının təcrübəsi əsasında qurula bilər.

Hasan Mirza as a researcher of our dialects

Summary

The article examines that historical dialectology is often considered a backward branch of linguistics, as it has just been formed as an independent field of linguistics with specific topics and tasks. Historical dialectology of most concrete languages does not yet exist. Even the general theory and methodology of this field of science has not been developed at any level. The true theory of historical dialectology can be built on the basis of the experience of historical dialectology of individual languages.

Annotasiya. Oğuz qrupuna daxil olan türk dillərinin, o cümlədən Azərbaycan dilinin formalaşmasının tarixi qədimdir. Dilin tarixini xalqın tarixindən ayrı təsəvvür etmək mümkün deyildir. Azərbaycan dili Azərbaycanda qədimdən mövcud olmuş və sonralar bu əraziyə gəlmiş bir sıra türk qəbilə və tayfa dillərinin əsasında formalaşmışdır.

Aktuallıq. Oğuz qrupuna daxil olan dillərin müxtəlif dövrlərdə qırpaq, karluq dil qruplarının, eləcə də ərəb və fars dillərinin güclü təsirinə məruz qalması, ayrı-ayrı oğuz dillərinə təsir edən müxtəlif dilxarici amillərin olması onların fərdi xüsusiyyətlər kəsb etməsinə gətirib çıxarmışdır. Azərbaycan dili tarixi inkişafında aparıcı oğuz ünsürlərini qorumuş, özünəməxsus əlamətlər qazanmış, digər oğuz dillərindən (türk, türkmən, qaqauz) fərqlənən müstəqil bir dil kimi inkişaf etmiş və Azərbaycan xalqının milli dili kimi formalaşmışdır.

Giriş. Dialektlərin tarixi öyrənilməsi ədəbi dil faktı, bütünlükdə ədəbi dil mənzərəsi daha aydın, daha bütöv görünəcəkdir. Ədəbi dil tarixində, normanın təkamülündə dialektlərin rolu məsələsi məhz tarixi dialektologiyanın nailiyyətləri əsasında dəqiq müəyyənləşdirilə bilər. Nəhayət, ayrı-ayrı dillərin tarixi dialektologiyasının yaradılması işi bizi kök dilin öyrənilməsi məsələsinə daha artıq yaxınlaşdıracaqdır.

Azərbaycan dili dialektləri xalqımızın tarixini, mədəniyyətini, etnoqrafiyasını və folklorunu ulu baba-nənələrimizin dilində yaşatmaqla yanaşı, dilimizin incəliklərini mühafizə edərək gələcək nəsillərə çatdırır. Qədim türk tayfa dillərinin - oğuz və qırpaq üstünlüyü ilə formalaşan dialektlərimizin quruluşu qədim yazılı abidələrin materialları ilə səsleşən, fərqli coğrafiyalarda olan müasir türk ədəbi dilləri və dialektləri ilə ortaq xüsusiyyətlərə malikdir. Türk dillərində dialektlər eyni tarixi inkişaf yolu keçmişdir; hər bir dilin nüfuzlu dialektinin ictimai-siyasi funksiyası və əhatə dairəsi genişlənmiş, tədricən digər dialektlərin faktları ilə zənginləşmiş və ədəbi dilin yaranması üçün zəmin yaranmışdır. Əsrlər boyu dialektlər ədəbi dili zənginləşdirən əsas mənbə olmuş, dialekt faktları ədəbi dilə keçmiş və norma statusu qazanmışdır. Dialektlərin təşəkkülü, tarixi inkişafı, türk dilləri ilə əlaqəsi barədə günümüzə qədər müxtəlif istiqamətlərdə yetərinca araşdırmalar aparılsa da bu proses tam başa çatmamışdır. Müasir dövrdə cəmiyyətdə baş verən dəyişikliklər, elm sahələrinin inteqrasiyasının güclənməsi yeni dialektoloji tədqiqatların aparılmasını zəruri edir. Tədqiqatda Azərbaycan dili dialektlərinin tədqiqi, eləcə də digər türk dillərinin öyrənilməsində mövcud yeniliklər, dialektlərin müqayisəli tədqiqi, ümumtürk dillərində etnoqrafizmlər, qarşılıqlı inteqrasiya məsələləri, türk dillərinin diferensiasiyası və inteqrasiyası, türk dillərinin və dialektlərinin təşəkkülü, təsnifi, ədəbi dillərin köyne dialektləri, türk dillərinin dialekt bölünməsi və s. mühüm problemlər ümumtürkoloji səviyyədə araşdırılmışdır.

Azərbaycan dilinin dialekt və şivələri zəngin lüğət ehtiyatına malikdir. Dialekt və şivələrimizin leksikasında Azərbaycan ədəbi dilində işlənməyən və ya başqa mənə daşıyan yüzlərcə söz vardır. Lakin son zamanlara qədər bu sözlər geniş miqyasda toplanmamış, küll halında nəşr olunmamışdır. Azərbaycanlıların qərb, orta və cənub ləhcələri arasında keçid xarakterli olan Qərbi Azərbaycanın Dərələyəz şivəsi uzun illər dialektoloqların diqqət mərkəzindən kənar qalmış, tədqiqat obyektinə olmamışdır. Bunu nəzərə alan H.Mirzəyev ilk dəfə olaraq Azərbaycan dilinin bir sıra qədim xüsusiyyətlərini və qrammatik formalarını özündə qoruyub saxlayan Dərələyəz şivələrindən ətraflı bəhs etmişdir.

Tədqiqat zamanı müəyyən olunmuşdur ki, H.Mirzəyev "Azərbaycan toponimləri və şivə sözləri" adlı əsərində bu qədim yurda məxsus şivə sözlərini 8 istiqamətdə araşdırmışdır.

Birinci istiqamətdə H.Mirzəyev Dərələyəz mahalına məxsus şivə sözlərinin mənə və etimologiyasını üzə çıxarır. O, bu istiqamətdə hər hansı bir şivə sözünün necə meydana çıxmasını, nə kimi dəyişikliyə uğradığını, hansı şəkildə müasir dövrümüzə qədər gəlib çatdığını etimoloji aspektdə izləyir. Məs: yaşmaq – qadınların ağzını, burnunu və üzünün bir tərəfini gizlətmək üçün başlarına saldıqları yaylıq, örtüyün bir hissəsi, örtük; güz – quzu salınan yer; qızdıx – ögey qız və s.

İkinci istiqamətdə şivə sözlərinin Dərələyəzin hansı yaşayış məntəqələrində intensiv işləndiyi göstərilir. Məs: təpəl – bu söz Dərələyəzin Gədikvəng, Qaraqaya, Qovuşuq, Gülüdüz,

Kotanlı, Terp, Köşbək kəndlərində daha çox işlədilir; bacanax – Dərələyəzin bütün kəndlərində, o cümlədən Ağkənd, Heşin, Qozluca, Axta, Gomur, Gülüdüz, Qaraqaya, Qovuşuq, Horbadıqda işlədilir.

Üçüncü istiqamətdə H.Mirzəyev Dərələyəz şivə sözlərinin Azərbaycanın digər bölgələrindəki paralellərini müəyyənləşdirir. Bu istiqamətdəki araşdırmalar, şübhəsiz, dialekt və şivələrimizin dilçilik coğrafiyası yolu ilə öyrənilməsi üçün çox faydalıdır. Məs: tirə – bu söz Qazax dialektində, Laçın, Qubadlı, Sabirabad şivələrində işlədilir; vəndəm –Şəmkir, Tovuz, Cəbrayıl şivələrində işlənir.

Dördüncü istiqamətdə tədqiqatçı Dərələyəz şivələri üçün səciyyəvi olan fonetik xüsusiyyətləri üzə çıxarır. Məs: qaynata-qayınata; bacanaqbacanax-bacanak; bacı-bacı və s.

Beşinci istiqamətdə H.Mirzəyev Dərələyəz şivə sözlərinin “KitabiDədə Qorqud” dastanlarındakı izlərini müəyyənləşdirir, oxşar və fərqli əlamətləri aşkar edir. Məs: tuş – “Kitabi-Dədə Qorqud” dastanlarında bu söz duş fonetik formasında işlənmişdir: “Mənim bu duşumu yorğul mana, dedi”; axca – bu sözə “boxca” formasında dastanlarda rast gəlinir: “Ağır xəzinə, boxcasını biz yağmalamışıq” və s.

Altıncı istiqamətdə H.Mirzəyev Dərələyəz şivəsi və buradakı arxaikləşən və işləklidən düşən sözləri araşdırır. Onun bu istiqamətdəki araşdırmaları təkcə dialektologiya elmi üçün deyil, eyni zamanda dil tarixi və tarixi leksikologiya sahələri üçün də əhəmiyyətlidir. Məs: balxı – veyil, maymaq; dımməver – vergi növü və s.

Yeddinci istiqamətdə H.Mirzəyev Dərələyəz mahalında işlənən şivə sözlərinə və onların türk dillərindəki paralellərinə xüsusi olaraq diqqət yetirir. Onun bu istiqamətdə apardığı iş müqayisəli xarakter doğurduğu üçün türk dillərinin müqayisəli leksikası üçün zəngin faktlar verir. Məs: tuğ (Azərbaycan dilində); – tuk (tuva dilində); – tu (qazax dilində); – tuu (qırğız dilində); – tiu (başqırd dilində) və s.

Səkkizinci istiqamətdə H.Mirzəyev Dərələyəz şivəsinə məxsus sözləri tematik qruplara və yarımqruplara ayıraraq izah edir.

Mühüm işlərdən biri Dərələyəz şivə sözlərinin lüğətinin tərtibidir. Lüğətə 600-dən çox şivə sözü daxil edilmişdir. Lüğətdə verilən şivə sözlərin bəziləri 4-5-dən artıq mənada işlənir, bu da Dərələyəz şivə leksikasının, həqiqətən, çox zəngin mənə imkanlarına malik olduğunu göstərir.

Beləliklə, H.Mirzəyevin Dərələyəz mahalının şivə sözlərinə həsr etdiyi tədqiqatı bütöv və sistemli dialektoloji araşdırma hesab edirik. Çünki alimin müxtəlif istiqamətlər üzrə tədqiq etdiyi, xüsusən də tərtib etdiyi “Şivələrin sözlüyü” bu bölgənin şivə leksikasını tam əhatə edir.

Tədqiqatda dialektologiyanın aktual problemlərinə, o cümlədən də koyne dialekt məsələsinə aydınlıq gətirilir. Bu məsələ Azərbaycan dilçiliyində hələ də mübahisəlidir; ədəbi dilin koyne əsasında bir-iki və bütün dialektlərin dayanması barədə alimlər arasında fikir müxtəlifliyi davam etməkdədir. Alim, M.Şirəliyevin mövqeyini müdafiə edərək, ədəbi dilimizin koynesinin tarixən Şamaxı, Təbriz, Qarabağ, müasir dövrdə isə Şirvan və Təbriz dialektlərinin olması fikrini irəli sürür, bununla da ədəbi dilimizlə həmin dialektlər arasında oxşarlıqların üstünlüyünü təsdiqləyir.

Tədqiqat metodları: Mövzunun xarakterinə uyğun olaraq müqayisəli, tarixi və təsviri metodlardan istifadə edilib.

Tədqiqatda o da araşdırılır ki, tarixi dialektologiya xüsusi mövzusu və vəzifələri olan müstəqil dilçilik sahəsi kimi yenicə formalaşdığından çox vaxt dilçiliyin geridə qalmış bir sahəsi hesab olunur. Konkret dillərin çoxunun tarixi dialektologiyası hələ mövcud deyil. Hətta bu elm sahəsinin ümumi nəzəriyyəsi və metodikası da istənilən səviyyədə işlənib hazırlanmayıb. Tarixi dialektologiyanın həqiqi nəzəriyyəsi ayrı-ayrı dillərin tarixi dialektologiyasının təcrübəsi əsasında qurula bilər.

Nəticə. Dilçiliyin yeni bir sahəsi olan tarixi dialektologiya təkcə dialektologiya baxımından deyil, dil tarixi baxımından da mühüm əhəmiyyətə malikdir. Tarixi dialektologiya dilin tarixinin daha dəqiq, daha əsaslı öyrənilməsi yolunda geniş imkanlar açır, dil tarixinin bəzi məsələlərinin izahında

həlledici söz deyə bilir. Dilin dialekt bölünməsi (üzlənməsi), onun təkamülündə meydana çıxan innovasiya (dilin ilkin formalarının dəyişməsi) hallarının müəyyənləşdirilməsi, eləcə də konkret bir dilin başqa yaxın qohum dillərlə ortaq və ayrılan xüsusiyyətlərinin geniş və hərtərəfli təhlili tarixi-dialektoloji tədqiqat nəticəsində mümkündür.

İstifadə edilmiş ədəbiyyat

1. Azərbaycan dilinin dialektoloji lüğəti. Bakı: Şərq-Qərb, 2007.342 s.
2. Bayramov İ. Dərələyaz şivələrinin leksikası. Bakı: Elm və təhsil, 2011.
3. Əhmədov B. Azərbaycan dilinin qısa etimoloji lüğəti. Bakı: Mütərcim, 1999.
4. Kitabı-Dədə Qorqud (tərtib edənlər: F. Zeynalov, S. Əlizadə). Bakı: Yazıçı, 1988.
5. Mahmud Kaşğari. Divani-lüğət-it- türk (tərcümə edən: R. Əskər), I c., Bakı: Ozan, 2006.
6. Древнетюркский словарь. Ленинград, 1969.
7. Радлов В. Опыт словаря тюркский наречий, т. I, ч. 1-2, СПб, 1893.
8. Байрамов И. Древние слова в западно-азербайджанских говорах.

Education is the future of the nation

Əhmədova Sevinc İslam q.

ADPU, müəllim

The development of society in the era of globalization has affected both education and all areas. Education has a strong impact as a human value. Mankind has come to such a decision that as a result of education, ordinaryness and ignorance among people can be eliminated. To this end, education is of great importance in the world at present. Also in our republic, in connection with all this, as the demand for education and specialists obtained as a result of training has grown, there is a need to modernize education and prepare a specialist who meets all the requirements as a result of modernization. For this reason, the content, essence, quality and purpose of education in the Republic of Azerbaijan began to be updated. Today, education attracts attention as a strategic sphere in the Republic of Azerbaijan. Thus, great attention is paid to the improvement of the education system in Azerbaijan. In modern times, the penetration of modernization into the education system, like other areas, has created conditions for achieving development. Modernization of education occupies an important place at a certain stage of our development. As a democratic and legal state, the Republic of Azerbaijan takes as its basis the integration of its educational system into the educational system of developed countries. But what is the reason for this? Because the main goal in the modernization of education is the formation of a comprehensively developed personality. Today, the implementation of the modernization of education, i.e. modernization, is one of the new directions of enriching its essence. What is the quality of education? As in all areas of social activity, the quality for a student in education is the presence of high standards, this is a different, exceptional feature, this is high thinking. [1, s. 184].

The education modernization system has created conditions, stimulating the creation of a new assessment model in the education system. The new model for assessing the quality of education is related to funding, which is the basis for the modernization of education. The annual increase in investment in education has made it possible to achieve a qualitative assessment. [2, s.86]

Proper assessment of the quality of education aims to make the process more efficient. In this regard, a systematic approach to education and the acceleration of its development is one of the leading strategic goals of the education system. Education quality assessment is also based on new mechanisms or standards. Achieving and improving quality in education is closely related to assessment. The assessment of the quality of education is carried out using the qualitative method. Qualimetry, which is a field of modern science, and its components are of great importance in the evaluation of the quality of education. Qualimetry plays an important role in the assessment and measurement of quality in education. Achieving the level of quality of education depends on its correct assessment. Evaluation of the quality of education combines a number of components. The components of the evaluation of the quality of education are: evaluation, assessment and Evaluation means identifying and clarifying the appropriateness of the results of the student's learning activities.

Evaluation is a quantitative indicator that determines the success of a student's educational activities and determines the quality.

Grade is an expression of quality in numbers, symbols and other means based on the result of a student's learning activity evaluation.

The assessment of the quality of education is carried out by measuring the achieved achievements. As a result of the reforms, the quality of education has improved, but this took a long time. The assessment of the quality of educational institutions is carried out within the framework of standards. The assessment of the quality of education is oriented as a guarantee of

the future. Today, the basis for the development of our republic is the assessment of the quality of education. As a result of today's reforms, quality has been achieved and the process of its correct assessment has taken place. These reforms have led to progress in quality assessment. For this reason, quality is one of the most important factors.

prof. A. O. Mehrabov writes: "The constituent parts (components) of the science of qualimetry are the following:

1. General quality measurement;
2. Special quality measurement.

3. Visual (concrete) quality measurement. General quality measurement, which plays a special role in quality methodology, has mainly general theoretical problems, i.e.

- system concepts (terminology);

- theory of estimation (laws and methods);

- axiomatics of quality measurement (axioms and rules);

- is engaged in the development of scientific foundations of the theory of qualitative scaling (methods of ranking by significance, evaluation of parameters by their semantic capacity).

Special qualimetrics, models and evaluation algorithms in the quality methodology, with the accuracy and reliability of the assessment, i.e.

- expert measurement of quality;

- qualitative taxonomy (taxonomy - the theory of classification and systematization of complex processes (objects) with a hierarchical structure, Greek "taxis" - placement, systematization, rule, "nomos" - law);

- probabilistic-statistical qualimetry (assessment methods based on the laws of probability theory and mathematical statistics);

- is engaged in the development of scientific and practical foundations of indicator (index) qualimetry (application of the theory of indicators in quality assessment).

Visual (concrete) qualimetry, assessment of a specific object (system, sample) in the quality methodology, that is:

Thus, it appears that qualimetry includes theories related to the assessment of the quality of any process, system (subject and product). Therefore, the subject of qualimetry is determined by both quantitative and qualitative (non-quantitative) quality assessment methods. [5, s. 235]

In order to improve the quality of education, the development of mechanisms for assessing its quality is carried out by improving the level of education in our republic. Sometimes, however, the goal of improvement is not fully fulfilled, and as a result, a conflicting environment is created. When evaluating the quality of education, it is important to take into account the resources allocated to education. If this is the case, improving the quality of education becomes a problem, and thus the goal cannot be fully fulfilled. Of course, the evaluation of the quality of the educational institution is carried out under state control. It should be noted that certain factors should be taken into account when evaluating the quality of education in an educational institution. The creation of a mechanism for improving the quality of education is carried out on the basis of a number of principles. Thus, the reforms carried out to improve the quality of education, the allocated funds are planned mainly

according to the course of the edu

Ədəbiyyat siyahısı

1. Cəbrayılov İ.H. Təhsilin modernləşdirilməsinin elmi-nəzəri problemləri. Bakı: "Mütərcim", 2015, 452 s.

2. Əsədova, Ş.Qəribov, T.İsmayılova, M.Kazımov, F.Həsənoğlu. Təhsilin idarə edilməsinin aktual problemləri. Bakı, 2016, 220s.

3. Mehrabov A.O. Azərbaycan təhsilinin müasir problemləri. Bakı: Mütərcim, 2007, 448 s.

4. Mehrabov A.O. Keyfiyyətli tədris prosesinin qurulmasında innovasiyaların rolu // Azərbaycan məktəbi, 2007, № 4.

5. Mehrabov A.O. Müasir təhsilin konseptual problemləri. Bakı: "Mütərcim", 2010, 510 s. cational process, but according to its result and educational achievements of the students.

Heydər Əliyev və ədəbiyyatımız

ŞƏFƏQ ƏZİZOVA

ADPU-nun nəzdində Azərbaycan Dövlət Pedaqoji kollecinin müəllimi

SHAFAQ AZIZOVA.

Summary: The place, role and opportunities of the literary factor in the fate and political activities of the outstanding statesman Heydar Aliyev have been widely understood. First of all, it should be noted that Heydar Aliyev is one of the rare statesmen in the world who has extensive and systematic knowledge of literature. The factor of literature occupied a special place in the formation of the worldview of Heydar Aliyev, who was distinguished by his extraordinary reading ability from his youth, and who bravely appeared on stage alongside professional theater actors even at a young age. As history recedes, we understand more clearly the greatness of Heydar Aliyev's genius, the greatness of his personality...

Keywords: Heydar Aliyev, literary factor.

ШАФАГ АЗИЗОВА.

Резюме: Место, роль и возможности литературного фактора в судьбе и политической деятельности выдающегося государственного деятеля Гейдара Алиева получили широкое понимание. Прежде всего, следует отметить, что Гейдар Алиев – один из редких государственных деятелей в мире, обладающих обширными и систематическими знаниями в области литературы. Фактор литературы занимал особое место в формировании мировоззрения Гейдара Алиева, который с юности отличался исключительными способностями к чтению и уже в юном возрасте смело выступал на сцене рядом с профессиональными актерами театра. По мере отступления истории мы яснее понимаем величие гения Гейдара Алиева, величие его личности...

Ключевые слова: Гейдар Алиев, литература.

Görkəmli dövlət xadimi Heydər Əliyevin taleyində və siyasi fəaliyyətində ədəbiyyat faktorunun yeri, rolu və imkanları çox geniş anlayış olub. Hər şeydən əvvəl onu qeyd etmək lazımdır ki, Heydər Əliyev dünyada geniş və sistemli ədəbiyyat biliyinə malik olan nadir dövlət xadimlərindəndir. Hələ gənlik illərindən etibarən qeyri-adi mütaliə qabiliyyəti ilə fərqlənən, hətta cavan yaşlarında tamaşalarda peşəkar teatr xadimləri ilə yanaşı cəsarətlə səhnəyə çıxan Heydər Əliyevin dünyabaxışının formalaşmasında ədəbiyyat amili xüsusi yer tutmuşdur. Tarix uzaqlaşdıqca biz Heydər Əliyev dühasının əzəmətini, onun şəxsiyyətinin böyüklüyünü daha aydın dərk edirik...

O, əvvəl milli məfkurəni, sonra müstəqil dövləti yaratdı. Bu baxımdan, minillik dövlətçilik tariximizə milli məfkurəyə istinad edən ilk və yeni Azərbaycan dövlətinin qurucusu kimi daxil oldu. Milli müstəqilliyi qazandığımız 90-cı illərdə deyil, eləcə də hakimiyyətdə olduğu sovet epoxası daxilində ədəbiyyatı nəinki iqtisadiyyatın, eləcə də siyasətin, gücün ayağına vermədi. Bütün fəaliyyəti dövründə ədəbiyyata, onun müxtəlif dövrlərində yaşayıb-yaratmış ədiblərinə qədirşünas mövqedən yanaşan Heydər Əliyevin rəhbər kimi özəlliyi bəlkə də elə buradan başlayır.

1970-ci illərdə ümumən respublikamızda klassik mədəni irsimizin öyrənilməsi baxımından tamamilə yeni mərhələ başladı. Həmin mərhələ bilavasitə xalqımızın ümummilli lideri Heydər Əliyevin adı ilə bağlıdır. Adil Babayev yazır ki, "Şərqi ən böyük dastanı olan «Kitabi-Dədə Qorqud»u adi döyüş əsəri kimi qiymətləndirirdilər və onun araşdırılmasının qarşısını alırdılar Heydər Əliyev abidənin millətə qaytarılmasında böyük işlər gördü". Eləcə də böyük Azərbaycan şairi İmadəddin Nəsimi ilə bağlı Heydər Əliyevin gerçəkləşdirdiyi işlər bu şairin irsinin yeni təfəkkür qatına, milli şüur və yaddaşa bədii-estetik çalar qatmasını izləməyə imkan verir. Həmin vaxta qədər Nəsimi «Divan»ı yalnız bir dəfə, görkəmli ədəbiyyatşünas Salman Mümtaz tərəfindən, 1926-cı ildə ərəb əlifbası ilə çap olunmuşdu. 1972-ci ildə türkmən ədəbiyyatşünası Qullayev həmin «Divan»ın dili üzərində müəyyən türkmənləşmə əməliyyatı apararaq yenidən çap etdirmiş, şairi türkmən ədəbiyyatının klassiki kimi təqdim etmişdi. Ancaq Heydər Əliyevin müdaxilə və müqaviməti nəticəsində bu saxtalaşdırma siyasəti uzun çəkmir, rəsmi dairələrdə tanınmasına yol verilmir və şairi Azərbaycan ədəbiyyatının dəyərli klassiki kimi tanımaq, təbliğ etmək yönündə davamlı tədbirlər planı start götürür. Heydər Əliyevin sərəncamı əsasında 1973-cü ilin 13 sentyabrında İmadəddin Nəsiminin 600 illik yubileyi keçirildi.

Elə həmin il Həmid Araslının tərtibatı ilə Nəsiminin divanı çap olundu. Bütün ölkə Nəsimi əhval-ruhiyyəsində oldu, şairin şəkli həmin dövrdə çap olunan bütün ölkə qəzetlərinin loqosuna çevrildi. Şairin əsərləri ingilis və fransız dillərinə tərcümə edildi, haqqında xarici ölkələrin və beynəlxalq təşkilatların mətbuat orqanlarında bir neçə məqalə çap olundu. YUNESKO-nun «Kuryer» jurnalında Nəsimi haqqında məqalə dərc edildi. Heydər Əliyev Nəsiminin yubileyinin təkcə Bakıda deyil, Moskvada da keçirilməsinə nail oldu. 1980-ci ilin fevral ayında Bakının mərkəzi parklarından birində Nəsiminin abidəsi qoyuldu və heykəlin açılış mərasimində şəxsən özü iştirak etdi. Beləcə, sovet ideologiyasının birbaşa marağında olduğu Nəsimini milli ədəbi-tarixi yaddaşdan çıxdaş etmək niyyətinin qarşısı böyük siyasətçi tərəfindən alındı.

Böyük Azərbaycan şairi Nizami Gəncəvinin irsinə də Heydər Əliyev münasibəti konseptual səciyyə daşıyırdı. 1981-ci ilin avqust ayında Nizami Gəncəvinin anadan olmasının 840 illiyi haqqında qərar isə nizamişünaslıqda əsaslı dönüş yaratmışdır. Bu məqamla bağlı X.R.Ulutürkün «Gündəlik»ində əhəmiyyətli bir epizod yer alır: «Xəmsə» yaradıcısının anadan olmasının 840 illiyi bayramı keçiriləndə böyük qazax şairi Oljas Süleymenovun verdiyi sual yadımdadır:

— Axı 840 yuvarlaq rəqəm deyil, niyə tələsirsiniz?

— Tələsməyimiz əbəs deyil. Biz Nizami ilə bəşəriyyəti qovuşdurmağa tələsirik. Nizami elə bir sənətkardır, elə bir dahidir ki, hər il bayramını keçirməyə dəyər".

Yaxud 1982-ci ilin 15 yanvarında Şuşada M.P.Vaqif məqbərəsinin açılışı Heydər Əliyev üçün əbədiləşən tarixi yaddaş baxımından əhəmiyyətli idi.

Heydər Əliyevin üzərinə düşən missiya çətin idi. O, fəaliyyətinə güdaza verilmiş dəyərlərin, itirilən meyarların bərpası kontekstində başladı. Böyük liderin ədəbiyyatda gerçəkləşdirdiyi işlər, klassiklərə qayıdış, milli ədəbiyyata güvənc hissənin qabarıqlığı sistemin yaratdığı Mif anlayışını yazıçı düşüncəsində heçə endirir, onun tənəzzülünü labüdləşdirirdi. İslahatlar ədəbi-mədəni həyatımızın bütün sferalarına sirayət etdikcə milli mənlük şüuru önə keçir, milli məfkurə işığı dalğalanmağa başlayırdı. Bu mənadə, 90-cı illərdə insanların öz azadlığını qazanması üçün meydana axışması, haqqını geri almaq təşnəsi birmənalı təfsirə gəlmir, onun kökləri bir qədər dərinlərə işləyib mövcudluğunu iki onillik əvvəldə, Heydər Əliyev dühasının imkan verdiyi azad söz zamanında, sovet ədəbiyyatı daxilində yaranmağa cəsərət etmiş hürriyyətçuluq, millət problematikəli poeziya mətnlərində tapır. Bunu meydana olan faktlar deyir: Nəriman Həsənzadə «Heydər Əliyevin şəxsinde mənlük „Bütün Şərq bilsin“ pyesinin qəhrəmanını, Nəriman Nərimanovun prototipini görürdüm», — yazır, Qabil qeydlərinin birində "Ömür həbləri" romanında Heydər Əliyevin də obrazını düşündüyünü bildirir. Mövlud Süleymanlı «Dəyirman» povestinin 70-ci illərin sağlam, duru, doğma ab-havanın məhsulu kimi meydana çıxdığını və üstəlik əsərlə bağlı «Azərbaycanı bürüyən» hücumdan onu Heydər Əliyevin qoruduğunu dilə gətirir. Bu məqam İsa Hüseynovun, Bəxtiyar Vahabzadənin, Xəlil Rzanın, Anarın, Elçinin mətbu etiraflarında da yer alır. Önlük bir faktın — 1978-ci ildə Heydər Əliyevin səyi nəticəsində dəyişdirilmiş Azərbaycan Sovet Sosialist Respublikasının Dövlət Himni məsələsi üzərində dayanmaq istəyirəm. 1945-ci ildə Səməd Vurğun və Süleyman Rüstəmin müəllifliyiylə yaradılmış Azərbaycan Sovet Sosialist Respublikası Dövlət Himninin sözlərinin müəlliflər cərgəsinə Hüseyn Arifin də qoşulmasıyla 1978-ci ildə yeni redaksiyada işlənilirdi. Qəribədir, Stalinin adı Azərbaycan himnindən mənlük 1978-ci ildə rəsmən çıxarıldı. «Rəhbərimiz Stalindir — bizim həyat növrəğimiz» misrası Azərbaycan himninin mətnindən Stalindən 25 il sonra mənlük Heydər Əliyevin respublikaya rəhbərlik etdiyi illərdə çıxarıldı ki, bu da tarixi bir qanunauyğunluğun göstəricisiydi. Təbiidir, əgər himnin sözlərində Stalinin adı keçirdisə, demək ki, himnimiz 1956-cı ildən, Stalinin şəxsiyyətə pərəstişi ifşa ediləndən sonra oxunmayıb. Stalinin adının himndən çıxarılması ilə himn yenidən dövriyyəyə qaytarılırdı və bu da müstəqil olmasa da, hər halda, respublika şəklini qoruyub saxlayan Azərbaycan üçün mühüm mənlük əhəmiyyət kəsb edirdi.

Heydər Əliyev içindən çıxdığı xalqın öz dəyərlərinin nədə ehtiva olunduğunu bilirdi. Şəxsiyyətlərini tanıyırdı, dövləti güclü edən amillərin söykəndiyi bütün çıxış nöqtələri ona mənlük idi. Eləcə də bilirdi ki, bir xalqın müstəqilliyinin qazanılması, öz mövcudluğunu sürdürə bilməsi bir tarixi, ideoloji və siyasi fakt olaraq yalnız tarixi şəraitin məhsulu ola bilməz, o həm də milli siyasi, ədəbi və fəlsəfi düşüncənin nəticəsi kimi hasilə gəlməlidir, milli mənlük şüurunun yaranmasının aspektləri bədii düşüncəyə söykənməlidir. Digər tərəfdən, Heydər Əliyev dünya mədəni sferasına inteqrasiyanın da zəruriliyini duyurdu. Ona görə milli varlığın idrakı məsələsinə bu qədər həssas yanaşırdı, fəaliyyətinin əsas istiqamətini milli ruhun oyanışı və ona qayıdış əzminin qorunub saxlanması təşkil edirdi.

Bu məqamda bir məsələni də vurğulamağa ehtiyac var. Heydər Əliyev yalnız qorumurdu, yalnız himayə etmirdi, yalnız cəsarət aşılırmırdı. O həm də sahib çıxmağı bacarırdı. Gücünün yetdiyi qədər milli-mənəvi dəyərlərin qorunmasına çaba göstərirdi. Bu barədə əlbəttə, kifayət qədər təcrübə və bacarıq sahibi idi, amma onlarla bahəm (və daha əsas!) millətə və xalqına can yanğısı vardı. Böyük şairimiz Məhəmməd Füzuli ilə bağlı Heydər Əliyevin qatlaşdığı çətinliklər və onun bu istiqamətdə əzmkar fəaliyyəti fikirlərimizə əyani sübutdur. Heydər Əliyevin Füzulinin qəbrinin qorunması və məqbərəsinin tikilməsi ilə bağlı gördüyü çoxönlü işlər — SSRİ XİN qarşısında qaldırdığı məsələ, Bağdaddakı səfirlik ilə yazışmaları, ölkə ziyalıları ilə danışıqları və s. bu kimi yorulmaz, inadlı və əzmkar mübarizələri bu siyasi liderdən hər cür yüksək məzmununda danışmağa əsas verir.

Heydər Əliyev siyasətinin dissident ruhu 1982-ci ildə daha bir müdhiş hadisə ilə nəhayətsiz miqyas aldı. Böyük Azərbaycan şairi Hüseyn Cavidin nəşinin Sibir çöllərindən vətənə gətirilməsi haqda sərəncam verdi Heydər Əliyev. Bu hadisəni Heydər Əliyevin siyasi fəaliyyətinin şah əsəri saymaq olar. Axı söhbət 1937-ci ilin repressiya dalğasının güdaza verdiyi faciə qəhrəmanından gedirdi. 1982-ci il. Sovet dövrü hələ bitməmişdi, heç buna işarələr belə yox idi. Rəsmi sənədlər üzərində bəraətlər verilib, amma düşüncədə hələ də repressiya havası, qorxu və ürpərtisi davam edirdi. Dildə repressiyaya məruz qalanlar haqda gerçəklər tüğyan edirdi, amma kağız üzərində yanlış elmi-ədəbi yalanlar meydan sulayırdı. Çünki xof hələ çəkilməmişdi, ideoloji yanlışlığa uğrama qorxusu gerçəklərdən daha öndə idi. Heydər Əliyev bu addımı ilə gerçəyi qorxulardan önə çıxartdı, Cavidin nəşini vətənə qaytarmaqla elə ilk növbədə, qorxunun üzərindəki örtüyü götürüb atmağa müvəffəq oldu.

1982-ci ildə Cavidin qayıdışı ilə milli mədəniyyətin türkçülük istiqamətində yeni epoxası başlayır. Bu həm də Heydər Əliyev siyasətinin 69-cu ildən bəri xalqın mənəvi dirçəlişinə, ictimai özünüdərək və milli təfəkkür oyanışına doğru addım-addım gəldiyi yolun qanunauyğun sonucu kimi meydana çıxır.

Cavidin nəşinin niyə məhz Naxçıvanda torpağa verilməsi də ayrı özəlliyi ilə diqqət çəkir. Nəriman Həsənzadənin xatirələrində buna əmin oluruq: «Bir də Təbriz nisgili var idi Heydər Əliyevin. Hüseyn Cavidin nəşini uzaq Sibirdən vətənə gətirmişdi. Cavid niyə Naxçıvanda basdırmaq istədi, burda yox? Söhbət gedirdi bu barədə həmin ərəfələr. Mən yanında durmuşdum, kimlərləsə söhbət edəndə dedi elə Naxçıvan yaxşıdı ki, Təbrizdən gələndə onu ziyarət eləyib gələcəklər. Bura qədər dərin düşündü Heydər Əliyev».

1970-1980-ci illər Azərbaycan ədəbiyyatı Heydər Əliyevin müəyyənləşdirdiyi əxlaqi-millimədəni aktın ilhamçısı və icraçısıdır. Cari prosesin, yazılan əsərlərin, bütöv ədəbi hərəkatın ideya zəmini rolunda çıxış edən aparıcı simadır Heydər Əliyev. Sovet epoxası daxilində bütün ölkə miqyasında sosial-tarixi, ədəbi-estetik qanunauyğunluqlarla müasir ədəbiyyatın özünün bədii-fəlsəfi ənənəsi arasında əlaqə, körpü rolunu Heydər Əliyev icra etmişdir.

1980-ci illərin sonlarından etibarən ölkə əvvəlcə yenidənqurma adı ilə göstərilən bir absurdun tamaşaçısı olmaq məcburiyyətini yaşadı, ardınca bu ümidlərin də fiaskoya uğraması prosesi başladı. Öz haqqının sahibi olmaq zamanı çatmışdı. Nəhayət, 1991-ci ilin oktyabrında Azərbaycanda milli müstəqillik elan olundu. Amma bu o qədər də asan başa gəlmədi. Bunun üçün

millət 1990-cı ilin 20 Yanvarında sınaq imtahanı verdi. Sonra Xocalı soyqırımını, ard-arda itirilən ərazilər, ölkə daxilində başlanan kaos, siyasi çəkişmələr, hərc-mərclik, şəxsi ambisiyaların tüğyan etməsi... Yeni liderin gəlişinə, xalqın nicat yerinə çevrilməsinə ehtiyac vardı, zaman öz qəhrəmanını gözləməkdə idi. Milli-mənəvi həyatımızda hökm sürmüş kaos və stixiyadan sonra Dahi işinə ehtiyacın növbəsi gəlmişdi və zamanın sükənini kosmik ahəngə xidməti ilə seçilənlərin öhdəsinə verməyin vaxtı idi. İbrətlidir ki, tarix bu şansı digərinə deyil, elə istiqlal yollarında can qoymuş, məsləkini tərcümeyi-halına çevirmiş Seçilmişinə həvalə etdi.

Heydər Əliyev əvvəlki inadla millətin yaddaş kultuna həssas yanaşmaqda davam etdi. 1990-cı illərdə dahi şairimiz Məhəmməd Füzulinin 500, Mirzə Cəlilin 128, ilk möhtəşəm söz abidəmiz olan «Kitabi-Dədə Qorqud» dastanının 1300 illiyinin elmi ictimaiyyət tərəfindən beynəlxalq səviyyədə keçirilməsi ədəbi irsə layiqli münasibətin izharına ən yaxşı nümunə olmaqla yanaşı, dövlət başçısının hansı məsələlərdə dəstək aradığını, mənəvi ülfət tapdığını bəlli etdi. Daha sonra bu missiya klassik sənətkarlarımızın taleyinə münasibətdə davamını tapmağa başladı. Heydər Əliyev qeyd edirdi ki, «Respublikamızın bu ağır dövrdə böyük yubileylər keçirilməsi, şübhəsiz ki, müəyyən qədər çətinliklərlə üzləşəcək. Ancaq çətinliklər nə qədər çox olsa da mədəniyyətə, mədəni irsimizə, mənəviyyata daim xüsusi diqqət yetirməli və bu sahələrin geri qalmasına yol verməməliyik».

Məhəmməd Füzulinin külliyyatı altı cildə nəşr edildi. Haqqında sanballı elmi monoqrafiyalar, tədqiqat əsərləri ortaya qoyuldu. Yubileyi həm Azərbaycanda, həm bütün türk-islam aləmində, həm də Rusiya və Avropada böyük təntənə ilə keçirildi.

Heydər Əliyevin müasir ədəbiyyat kontekstində yerinə yetirdiyi «yaradıcılıq» missiyasının realizəsi bir tərəfdən klassik ədəbiyyatı yaşatmaqla bağlı idisə, digər tərəfdən, çağdaş ədəbi prosesi gəlişdirmək məqsədilə atılan bir sıra addımlarla əlamətdar oldu; yaradıcılıq aləminə yeni istedadlı müəlliflərin gəlməsində rol oynayan, sonradan maddi çatışmazlıqlar ucbatından uzun fasilələrlə işıq üzü görən, hətta bağlanmaq təhlükəsi ilə üz-üzə duran ədəbi orqanların: «Azərbaycan», «Literaturniy Azerbaydjan», «Ulduz», «Qobustan» jurnallarının və "Ədəbiyyat qəzeti«nin ölkə Prezidentinin xüsusi qərarı ilə müntəzəm surətdə ölkənin dövlət büdcəsindən maliyyələşdirilməsi ədəbi prosesin gəlişməsində əsaslı rol oynadı.

Heydər Əliyev sözümlərinin „yaddaş sirri“dir. O, dövlətin rəmzinə çevrilmiş ilk siyasi lider oldu və kifayət qədər ibrətamizdir ki, belə bir hadisə Azərbaycan tarixində ilk dəfəydi ki, baş verirdi. Belə hadisələri isə tarix sonradan təshih etmir. Çünki yüzillər keçəndən sonra tarix daha çox həqiqətin dilində danışır. Heydər Əliyev Azərbaycanın siyasət dilini dünyaya təlim edən ilk azərbaycanlı oldu. Bu mənada, yüzillər keçəndən sonra da tarix Azərbaycan barədə qurucunun, baninin, ümummilli liderin, yəni Heydər Əliyevin üslubunda danışacaq.

Biz ümummilli liderin vətən, yurd, xalq adına gördüyü nəhayətsiz əməllərin bir qismindən bəhs etdik. Amma Heydər Əliyevin ən dəyərləli əsərlərindən biri Azərbaycan Prezidenti İlham Əliyevdir. Heydər Əliyevin uğurlu siyasi kursunun bariz örnəyi! Bu gün Heydər Əliyev həm də İlham Əliyevin simasında yaşayır, əbədi davam edən tarixə çevrilir. Ümummilli lider Heydər Əliyevin onun haqqında söylədiyi gözəl bir fikir var: „İnanıram ki, mənə axıra çatdırma bilmədiyim tələyüklü məsələləri, planları, işləri sizin köməyiniz və dəstəyinizlə İlham Əliyev başa çatdırma biləcək. Mən ona özüm qədər inanıram və gələcəyinə böyük ümidlər bəsləyirəm“. Bunlar tarix yaradan bir şəxsiyyətin, milli məfkurəli dövlət qurucusunun yalnız inamından hasilə gələn fikirlər deyildi, bu inamın kökündə İlham Əliyevdə ehtiva olunan dövlətçilik şüuruna, dövləti sağlam düşüncə və əzmlə idarə etmək, irəli aparmaq gücünə əminlik dayanırdı. Zaman bu müdrik şəxsiyyətin qənaətlərində yanılmadığını sübut etdi.

ON THE CAUSES OF ARCHAICATION

Arzu Karimova

teacher of Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University, doctoral student

Keys words : word, language, history, event, importance, availability.

When talking about archaisms in the Azerbaijani language, first of all, it is necessary to study the causes of archaism. If the causes of archaism are not determined, problems may arise in the classification of archaisms.

Archaicization, as is well known, is an issue related to the history of language. When investigating these reasons, one cannot pass without looking at the history of the language. The Azerbaijani language has undergone a complex process of development and is considered one of the oldest languages. A. Demirchizade writes: "When determining the periods of development of the literary language of Azerbaijan, it is necessary to take into account what its basis is, as well as the extent of its influence and function as the main criterion.

Different opinions are expressed in the scientific literature about the causes of archaism. One of the books on the lexicology of the modern Azerbaijani language mentions two reasons for the obsolescence of words. These two reasons are shown to be:

1. The name of an existing or imagined object and event is not expressed by the word it was expressed before, but by a more suitable and suitable word newly created or taken from another language.

2. A certain object and event that once existed in life or was imagined in connection with superstition is completely destroyed or loses its importance in modern times. In this case, the word expressing it also loses its content and finally leaves the language.

Let's focus on both of the above reasons. The first reason is the re-nomination process. The second reason is related to the disappearance, breakdown or non-use of the subject indicated by the word in the language. So, if there is no object, there is no need for its name.

The re-nomination process has a complex structure. It should be noted that both extralinguistic and interlinguistic factors can play a role here. Extralinguistic factors can result from qualitative changes in the renominated subject. For example, the presence of a benchmark in the measurement units of the arsh, which was used at the time, was discontinued due to standardization, transition to a single measurement system, or rather, it was replaced by a new measurement unit. If we pay attention to another example, we will see that the word "sayru" changed over time, as the language changed, according to the development process of history and was replaced by the word "patient". Here, the previous name has been replaced by a new name, and for the reasons we mentioned above, the previous word has been removed from the language. Many researchers also point to historical-cultural progress as the main reason for archaicization.

When investigating the causes and degrees of word obsolescence, it is possible to face the phenomenon of these words losing processing activity and gradually disappearing from the language after the objects and subjects they denoted are completely out of use. At the same time, there are not few cases of archaic meaning of a number of words that they previously expressed. In this regard, archaisms are usually divided into two groups: lexical and semantic. When examining the stylistic qualities of semantic archaisms, the use of these words in the original or archaic sense should be taken as a basis.

The word is always fighting for survival. The antiquity of the word means the antiquity of the people. It is very difficult to imagine the history of the word separately from the history of the

language and the people. To study the history of speech and language, it is necessary to study the history of the formation of the people. It is known that many Turkic tribes played a role in the history of the Azerbaijani people. In the process of formation of the people, the superior position of an ethnos leads to the linguistic facts belonging to that ethnos gaining a superior position. In addition to the political superiority of one or another tribe, our language, which has been forming for thousands of years, has also had a cultural superiority. The main reason for the parallelism observed in the language is explained by the fact that the process of integration of different tribal languages has not yet been completed.

Archaicization is often treated as a lexical category in linguistics literature. In fact, archaicization is a very broad language phenomenon and includes all its categories - phonetics, lexicon, semantics, grammatical structure, etc.

Archaisms also differ in the degree of archaism. We know that archaicization is determined by the modern state of the language. A group of archaisms has been forgotten without leaving any traces either in our modern literary language, or in folklore, or in dialects and dialects. Although the second group of archaisms does not exist in our literary language, it has preserved its existence in other Turkish languages. The third group of archaisms has become archaic through obsolescence or change of meaning. Finally, although the fourth group of archaisms has ceased to function in our literary language, it continues to live in dialects.

Archaicization in language is quite a natural process. It is the result of the tendency of the language to be constantly refined. But in certain periods, the intervention of linguists and writers in this work gave a kind of favor to archaism. Although it seems that interfering with the language has an effect, in fact, the main focus of this work was to preserve our mother tongue. For example, M.F. Akhundov, a prominent writer and scientist who fought against the Arabic alphabet until the end of his life, preferred to use the living spoken language as the norm of the literary language.

The process of obsolescence of words does not happen suddenly, but gradually. For a certain period of time, the word is rarely used, its scope of use is gradually limited, it is forgotten, and as a result, it loses its active functionality. Obsolete words should not be treated as just old words. Because, sometimes an obsolete word can return to the active lexicon, for example, the words bey, khan, khanim are used in a new sense, moving away from their previous content. Scientific literature shows that the degree of obsolescence of words varies. In this respect, obsolete words are divided into two parts: historicisms and archaisms.

Names of things and events that have become obsolete in connection with a certain historical event are called history. Historicisms arise as a result of obsolescence of the words expressing them together with objects and events, passing into passive vocabulary, that is, those words are obsolete both in form and in content. For example, shield, sheshpar, mirror, darga, kokha, mistal, etc.

The reasons for the obsolescence of words in the language can be systematized as follows:

1. Any word expressing the concept of an object, event loses its functionality, as a result, the object, event, concept is expressed by another word. As the previous word denoting an object, event, or concept has lost its functionality, it moves to the passive part of the vocabulary of the language.

2. Any object, event, concept that once existed in life and society loses its importance, existence, and vitality after a while. As a result, the word expressing that object, event, concept also comes out of the language.

3. The same thing, event, concept is called by several words. One of those words becomes active, increasing its importance, and the other becomes passive and eventually becomes obsolete.

4. In connection with the development of the people's way of thinking and social and political life, the event and concept expressed by any word becomes obsolete. This process

manifests itself as a regularity in language. Words denoting obsolete things, events, and concepts naturally fall out of use and the vocabulary of the language undergoes a process of change.

SUMMARY

This article examines the causes of archaism. If we generalize the ideas and considerations about the causes of archaization, they can be classified as follows:

- The impact of changes in society as a result of historical and cultural progress on the language;

- Occurrence of the re-nomination process;

- transfer of the main center of meaning to the derived word;

As we mentioned above, the reasons for the obsolescence of the words, such as the subject falling out of use or the occurrence of changes, are directly related to historical and cultural progress. Obsolete words related to this reason prevail in the language. Historical changes lead to collective obsolescence of words belonging to the previous period. Therefore, obsolete words from different periods find their place in the passive fund of the vocabulary of the language.

REFERENCE LIST

1. Cəfərov S. Müasir Azərbaycan dili. II hissə, Leksika, Bakı: " Maarif", 1982, 216s.
2. Qurbanov A. Müasir Azərbaycan Ədəbi Dili. Bakı: "Nurlan" 2009, s.242-243
3. Dəmirçizadə Ə.M. Azərbaycan ədəbi dilinin tarixi. I hissə. Bakı: "Maarif", 1979, 268s.
4. Bəliyev H. Orta məktəbdə Azərbaycan dilinin tədrisi metodikası. Bakı, 2003, 422s.
5. Xəlilov B.Ə Azərbaycan dilinin leksikologiyası. Bakı "Nurlan", 2008 442s.

УДК 371

ЯЗЫКОВЫЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ТЕКСТА ПУБЛИЦИСТИЧЕСКОГО СТИЛЯ

Абиев Бахытжан Мырзахметович

Старший преподаватель Международного университета туризма и гостеприимства
(Казахстан, г. Туркестан)

Резюме. В данной статье рассматривается уникальность коммуникативных текстов, обеспечивающих создание стилистической речи, в соответствии с его функциональными особенностями, учет того, что в публицистической речи раскрываются актуальные проблемы, вызывающие интерес общества. Авторы излагают основную мысль будущего публицистического высказывания, так как публицист обязательно должен учитывать, что общее назначение стиля реализуется в конкретной задаче жанра. Жанры различаются, прежде всего, своим назначением. публицистические произведения отличаются необыкновенной широтой тематики, они могут касаться любой темы, попавшей в центр общественного внимания, технологии проведения водолазных работ. Это, несомненно, сказывается на языковых особенностях данного стиля: возникает необходимость включать специальную лексику, требующую пояснений, а иногда и развернутых комментариев. Целый ряд тем постоянно находится в центре общественного внимания, и лексика, относящаяся к этим темам, приобретает публицистическую окраску. В составе словаря языка формируется круг лексических единиц, характерных для публицистического стиля. Таким образом, в задачу статьи входит разъяснение, анализ взаимосвязанных событий.

Ключевые слова: стилистика, лексика, публицистика, жанр, текст, тематика.

LANGUAGE FEATURES OF PUBLICISTIC STYLE TEXT

B.M.Abiev

International University of Tourism and Hospitality (Turkestan, Kazakhstan)

Summary. This article discusses the uniqueness of communication texts, ensuring the creation of stylistic speech, in accordance with its functional features, considering that in the journalistic speech reveals the actual subjects of public interest. The authors present the main idea of the future of journalistic statements as writer must keep in mind that the overall purpose of style is implemented in a specific task of the genre. Genres differ primarily its purpose. journalistic works are of extraordinary breadth of topics they can relate to any topic that falls to the center of public attention, underwater diving technology. This undoubtedly affects the linguistic features of this style: it is necessary to include a special vocabulary, self-explanatory, and sometimes detailed comments. A variety of topics is constantly in the public eye, and the vocabulary related to these themes becomes journalistic coloring. As part of the language of the dictionary is formed by a circle of lexical items specific to the journalistic style. Thus, the task of the article is to explain the analysis of related events.

Keywords: style, vocabulary, journalism, genre, lyrics, themes.

Необходимость работы над публицистическим стилем в условиях вузовской подготовки специалистов обусловлена, прежде всего, задачами развития устной и письменной речи. В.В. Виноградов писал: «Высокая культура разговорной и письменной речи – хорошее знание и чутье языка, умение пользоваться его выразительными

средствами, его стилистическим многообразием – самая лучшая опора, самое верное подспорье и самая надежная рекомендация для каждого человека в его общественной жизни и творческой деятельности» [1, с.19]. Типовая программа по русскому языку обосновывает важность функционально-стилистического аспекта в преподавании всего курса русского языка. Сама практика убедительно доказывает, что основное внимание в работе по стилистике должно быть направлено на овладение студентами структурой функциональных стилей речи, в первую очередь, если говорить о вузовской подготовке – научного.

Задачу работы по стилистике мы видим не в простом выяснении тех или иных стилистических возможностей языковых средств, а в планомерно организованном изучении его структуры, включая такие признаки, как сфера применения, задачи использования, выбор жанра, обеспечение высказывания языковыми средствами. Наряду с обучением студентов созданию устных и письменных высказываний, важно научить студентов видеть особенность создаваемого текста, соотносить его с задачами и грамотно отбирать языковой материал для создания речевого высказывания.

Содержание заключительной части нашей работы составил материал, отобранный для проведения элективного курса, предназначенного для студентов филологического факультета, ориентированных на работу в сфере журналистики. Нами составлена учебная программа элективного курса «Публицистический стиль речи», рассчитанный на два кредита. Актуальность элективного курса «Публицистический стиль речи» обусловлена необходимостью качественного освоения функциональной стилистики в процессе вузовской лингвистической подготовки. Представим содержательное и методическое описание указанного элективного курса.

Помимо учебников по стилистике, большую помощь оказало нам пособие «Практическая журналистика в Казахстане» – коллективный труд практикующих журналистов различных отечественных СМИ. В пособии описаны жанры журналистики с точки зрения их применения в СМИ, даны советы и рекомендации, которые вполне могут быть использованы преподавателем, организующим работу элективного курса. Примечательно, что в указанном пособии четко определена миссия журналистики (описывать картину реальности; осуществлять коммуникацию, способствовать общению). Содержание первой главы посвящено разговору о главной заповеди журналистов («не солги»), о многогранности понятия «свобода слова», о том, в какой степени современные СМИ реализуют стоящие перед ними задачи:

- предоставлять информацию о событиях;
- выражать общественное мнение;
- расширять кругозор читателей;
- содействовать формированию у читателей гражданской активности;
- способствовать воспитанию и служить средством агитации;
- быть средством отдыха и развлечения [2].

Нетрудно убедиться, как неразрывно связаны обязанности журналиста с обязанностями педагога. Выработанные в международной практике каноны, касающиеся журналистской этики, делающие составляющими профессионализма такие черты, которые, по сути, присущи и представителям других профессий: ответственность, независимость, искренность, правдивость, точность, беспристрастность, добросовестность, благопристойность.

Элективный курс призван дать представление о своде публицистических аспектов, которые в данное время и в историческом развитии могли соприкоснуться с лингводидактикой.

Стоит вспомнить, что публицистический стиль занимает особое место в системе стилей литературного языка, поскольку во многих случаях он должен перерабатывать тексты, созданные в рамках других стилей. Научная и деловая речь ориентированы на интеллектуальное отражение действительности, художественная речь – на её эмоциональное отражение. Особенностью конца XX – начала XXI века в области образования является возрождение национального самосознания и повышение интереса к родной культуре, языку и литературе во всех регионах нашей страны. Современные высшие учебные заведения, ставя самые высокие и благородные цели обучения специалистов, значительно усилили лингвистическую направленность их становления: поставлена задача вооружить выпускников вуза коммуникативной компетенцией – умением говорить, читать и писать, свободно пользуясь тем жанром, которого требует конкретный случай.

На практических занятиях мы предлагаем организацию работы над такими жанрами публицистики, как заметка, репортаж, статья и отзыв о прочитанной книге. Такой выбор вполне объясним требованиями школьной программы. Работа над указанными жанрами публицистического стиля должна строиться на основе известных студентам сведений о типах речи, она опирается на их умения создавать тексты повествования, описания и рассуждения. Введение в содержание обучения публицистическому стилю указанных знаний является необходимой теоретической основой для успешного формирования у студентов такого сложного умения, как умение создавать высказывания публицистического стиля [61].

Обучение студентов филологического факультета творческим письменным работам публицистического стиля имеет смысл, так как повышается общий уровень развития студентов, что позволит им попробовать свои силы в роли журналистов и имеет большую ценность в формировании знаний и умений, связанных с построением продуктивной устной и письменной речи. Формирование навыков написания творческих письменных работ публицистического жанра способствует совершенствованию культуры письменных публицистических высказываний.

Универсальных коммуникативных умений, обеспечивающих создание текстов всех типов и стилей речи, не существует. Умения конкретны, поскольку они тесно связаны с типом речи. Поэтому вся работа над обучением студентов публицистическому стилю речи конкретизируется в соответствии с его функциональными особенностями, учет того, что в публицистической речи раскрываются актуальные проблемы, вызывающие интерес общества. Определяя основную мысль своего будущего публицистического высказывания, пишущий обязательно должен учитывать, что общее назначение стиля реализуется в конкретной задаче жанра. Жанры же различаются, прежде всего, своим назначением. Например, назначение заметки – кратко сообщить о каком-либо факте, событии. Специфика репортажа – наглядно показать описываемый факт, событие современной жизни. В задачу статьи входит разъяснение, анализ взаимосвязанных событий. Рецензия, отзыв – это размышления автора, это его желание поделиться своими впечатлениями [3].

Для освоения элективного курса большое значение имеет составление программы и четко продуманное его учебно-методическое обеспечение. Цель элективного курса интегрирует задачи творческой подготовки студентов к созданию публицистических текстов и их профессиональную подготовку к проведению работы по овладению школьниками навыками структурирования текстов публицистического стиля. На первом занятии предполагается рассмотрение следующего круга вопросов:

1. Связь публицистического стиля с общественной сферой коммуникации.
2. Предмет публицистики.
3. Характерные особенности публицистических произведений.
4. Место публицистического стиля в стилистической системе русского языка.

Задания для СРС могут быть сформулированы следующим образом:

Подготовить сообщение «Современные средства массовой информации».

Рассказать о характерных особенностях публицистических произведений.

Определить характер соотнесенности публицистического стиля с другими книжными стилями.

Еще одно занятие может быть посвящено рассмотрению вопросов диахронического плана: здесь большое значение приобретает знакомство с историей отечественной журналистики. Студентам можно предложить подготовить рефераты на тему «История СМИ в Казахстане». Рассмотрение вопроса о функциях публицистического стиля строится по следующему плану:

Понятие об информативной функции публицистического стиля.

Характеристика экспрессивной функции публицистического стиля.

Основные стилеобразующие черты публицистического стиля.

Понятие об иностилевых элементах и их назначении.

Вопросы и задания для СРС помогут студентам освоить материал:

1. Где используется публицистический стиль речи?

2. Назовите жанры публицистики.

3. Расскажите о функциях публицистического стиля (информативной и экспрессивной).

4. Каковы языковые признаки публицистического стиля речи (лексические, морфологические, синтаксические)?

5. Какой прием используют журналисты в заголовках статей, очерков?

6. Подготовить сообщения на одну из предложенных тем:

- Специфика жанра рекламы

- Устные жанры публицистики.

- Связь публицистического стиля речи с риторикой.

- Публицистический стиль и агитационная пропаганда.

Лексические признаки публицистического стиля связаны с рассмотрением вопроса о роли и назначении оценочной лексики; об особенностях употребления многозначных слов. Должное внимание рекомендуется уделить исследованию метафоричности, как характерной черты публицистического стиля, особенностям употребления синонимов, антонимов и паронимов.

Студенты узнают, что публицистические произведения отличаются необыкновенной широтой тематики, они могут касаться любой темы, попавшей в центр общественного внимания, например, технологии проведения водолазных работ. Это, несомненно, сказывается на языковых особенностях данного стиля: возникает необходимость включать специальную лексику, требующую пояснений, а иногда и развернутых комментариев. С другой стороны, целый ряд тем постоянно находится в центре общественного внимания, и лексика, относящаяся к этим темам, приобретает публицистическую окраску. Таким образом, в составе словаря языка формируется круг лексических единиц, характерных для публицистического стиля.

Для освоения лексического состава публицистических текстов студентам предлагается найти ответы на вопросы:

Какие важнейшие черты отличают публицистический стиль от других стилей русского литературного языка?

Какие лексические явления характерны для языка публицистики?

Почему в публицистическом стиле активно используются лексические единицы, характерные для других стилей?

Приведите примеры неологизмов в современной прессе.

Как долго слово остается неологизмом? Какова цель употребления новых слов и оборотов речи?

Какие тематические группы слов характерны для языка средств массовой информации?

Что такое эмоциональная окраска слова? Может ли публицистика обойтись без эмоционально окрашенной лексики? Всегда ли эта лексика употребляется уместно?

Какие стилистические трудности возникают при анализе публицистического текста?

Приведите примеры оценочных слов и устойчивых сочетаний в речи современных политиков и в газетных текстах.

Какие трудности связаны с развитием многозначности слов в газетной речи?

Приведите примеры употребления слов в новых значениях.

Какова роль метафоры в речи журналиста и политика?

Какие образы лежат в основе типичных газетных метафор?

Какова стилистическая функция синонимов?

Какие новые синонимические связи возникли в русской газетной речи последних лет?

Какие слова перестали быть синонимами?

Как в публицистике используются антонимы?

Как называются близкие по звучанию слова с различным значением?

Термины каких наук чаще всего употребляются публицистами?

Какие виды заимствованных слов встречаются в газетной речи?

Почему заимствования широко применяются именно в газетном стиле речи?

Возможно также выполнение практических заданий:

1. Подберите синонимы к словам: *визит, происшествие, беспорядок, переговоры, трансформация, лидер, внешность, тезис, формула, необычный, внятный, пиратский, поддержать, определить, обозначить, исследовать, препятствовать, защищать.*

2. Определите цель использования в публицистической речи следующих историзмов: *нэпман, продразверстка, лишенец, исполком, политбюро, райком, барщина, опричник, градоначальник, партийные князья, руководящий чин, дума, гимназия, лицей, губернатор, кадетский корпус.*

3. Приведите примеры слов, обозначающих явления, характерные для жизни зарубежных стран [4].

Грамматические признаки публицистического стиля должны быть представлены характеристикой специфики употребления именных частей речи. Характеристика свойств глагольных форм позволит уделить должное внимание вопросам повелительного наклонения глагола. Студенты узнают, что повелительная форма глагола в публицистике используется как средство привлечения внимания собеседника: *посмотрите, давайте подумаем, вспомните, обратите внимание.* Для сообщения о событиях, запланированных на будущее, может быть использовано настоящее время:

На следующей неделе открывается книжная ярмарка. Усвоить специфику грамматического строя публицистических текстов позволит система заданий, выполненная в форме СРС и СРСП. Так, студентам предлагается ответить на вопросы:

Какие особенности характеризуют морфологические формы в публицистическом стиле?

Какие новые оттенки значения возникают у существительных в форме множественного числа?

Какую стилистическую функцию выполняет переносное употребление форм глагольного времени?

Приведите примеры из газет, показывающие переносное употребление временных форм.

Приведите примеры необычного порядка слов. Какую цель преследует изменение обычного порядка слов?

Представляется вполне закономерным на специальных занятиях на материале наблюдений и анализа рассмотреть особенности газетно-публицистического стиля. Этот стиль функционирует в общественно-политической сфере и используется в ораторских выступлениях, в различных газетных жанрах (передовая статья, репортаж), в публицистических статьях в периодической печати. Он реализуется, как в письменной, так и в устной форме. Для анализа может быть, например, использован такой публицистический текст:

«В любом обществе существует ряд проблем, напрямую связанных с социальным функционированием женщины. Именно этими проблемами давно занят феминизм, настаивающий не на равенстве, а на инакости женщин и мужчин. Образование и медицина, права детей и инвалидов, воинская обязанность и уложение о наказаниях - вот поле общественной деятельности, на котором женская мягкость, способность к компромиссу, предпочтение частного общественному должны были бы сослужить свою службу. В сущности, все равно, кто объединит все это в одну программу - мужчина или женщина. Но женщине все же сподручней. Как говаривала бабушка, «что с мужчинами разговаривать – они ведь даже одеться по погоде не умеют».

Здесь использованы слова и словосочетания, свойственные научному стилю (*ряд проблем, социальное функционирование женщины, предпочтение частного общественному и др.*), официально-деловому (*права детей и инвалидов, воинская обязанность, уложения о наказаниях*), а также разговорные, даже просторечные выражения (*сподручней, сослужить службу, как говаривала бабушка*).

Выводы о специфических языковых признаках газетно-публицистического стиля сводятся к следующему:

1. На лексико-фразеологическом уровне для газетно-публицистического стиля характерны слова общественно-политического звучания, используются речевые стандарты, фразеологизмы разных типов (особенно в фельетоне, памфлете, очерках).

2. На морфологическом и словообразовательном уровне широко используются существительные мужского и среднего рода в форме родительного падежа и др.

3. На синтаксическом уровне для газетно-публицистического стиля свойственна максимальная простота синтаксических конструкций; предельное упорядочение строя предложения, частая инверсия членов предложения, их логическое выделение; использование элементов поэтического синтаксиса (риторический вопрос, анафора, эпифора, градация); использование элементов разговорного синтаксиса (вопросно-ответная форма изложения и др.) [5].

Разговор о газетной публицистике, анализ различных жанров, определение особенностей языка газет может послужить примером для последующей работы по освещению вопросов, определяющих характер других средств массовой информации:

- Особенности жанров публицистического стиля на телевидении.
- Специфика публицистического стиля в журнальных произведениях.
- Публицистический стиль и Интернет.

Освещение этого круга вопросов может быть организовано в форме проектов.

Следует отметить, что данный элективный курс содержит одинаковое количество лекционных и практических занятий, что предполагает различные формы организации работы студентов – коллективные, групповые, индивидуальные.

Основным жанром публицистики является репортаж. Качества репортажа зависят от степени погружения публициста в изучаемую среду. Лингвисты отмечают: «...В одних случаях автор выступает только как свидетель неких эпизодов, в других – он вмешивается в

происходящее, и событие оказывается высвеченным изнутри. Наконец, нередко автор выступает в качестве инспиратора общественно значимого действия».

Э.А. Лазарева пишет, что широко распространенной и самой наглядной формой выражения авторского начала в публицистике является обозначение присутствия журналиста на месте события. А потому на практических занятиях рекомендуется уделить должное внимание аналитической работе с текстами репортажей. В процессе подготовки исследования мы посетили занятие преподавателя Б. , на котором шел процесс обучения студентов-филологов написанию репортажа. Ниже предлагаем анализ данного занятия.

Преподаватель преследовал следующие цели: познакомить студентов с особенностями репортажа как газетного жанра; подготовить к самостоятельной работе над сочинением-репортажем; воспитывать уважение к профессии репортера и к людям этой профессии.

Оборудование: газеты, таблицы с основными требованиями к репортажу, папка с памятками (на столах студентов), таблички с профессиональными словами, видеозаписи, фотографии репортеров, книги В.Пескова.

Эпиграф: «Многие и многие русские писатели отдавали репортажу много сил, внимания и находчивости». В.Гиляровский.

Занятие начинается с объявления темы и цели, во вступительном слове преподаватель говорит о том, что вся жизнь страны, вся жизнь планеты на газетных листах. Коротенькие заметки, репортажи, очерки, фельетоны и эссе на различные темы печатаются в газетах. Репортаж издавна был и остается в наше время одним из самых распространенных газетных жанров. Многие известные русские писатели начинали свою деятельность в качестве газетных репортеров. Эпиграф, записанный на доске, читается и комментируется студентом.

Далее организуется словарно-орфографическая работа. Студентам рекомендуется ответить на вопрос:

- Какие слова, относящиеся к работе журналистов, вы можете назвать? (Ответ: «Журналист, журналистика, рубрика, корреспондент, репортаж, репортер, хроника».)

В толковом словаре студенты находят лексическое значение слов *репортаж*, *репортер*, *хроника*, *хроникер*, *корреспондент* и записывают их в тетрадь.

(Репортаж – сообщение о местных событиях, о событиях дня, информация в печати, по радио, телевидению; репортер – сотрудник газеты, журнала, радио, информационного агентства, доставляющий сведения о текущих событиях и происшествиях).

Интересна и полезна работа в аудитории, посвященная усвоению семантики слова «репортаж»: оно произошло от английского report (рипорт) – как существительное оно значит – рапорт, доклад, сообщение; как глагол соответственно: рапортовать, докладывать, сообщать. Определяя значение слов «журналист» и «репортер», студенты отмечают, что *репортер* – понятие более узкое, так как он занимается конкретной работой. Логичным является продолжение разговора, выводящее на понятия *хроника* (отдел сообщений в газете, журнале, на радио и телевидении, посвященный текущей общественной жизни), *хроникер* (сотрудник газеты, журнала, работающий в отделе хроники).

Беседа, организованная преподавателем позволяет определить круг интересов студентов и реализовать ряд развивающих задач:

- Каких журналистов, информирующих о текущих событиях, вы можете назвать?

(В ответах звучат имена Михаила Любимова, Александра Школьника – телерепортеров информационной программы «Доброе утро» на Первом канале; Эдуарда Хайруллина – собственного корреспондента телеканала «Хабар», репортера «Экстренного вызова» Евгения Дробязко и др.)

Заслушивая результаты опережающего задания, подготовленного студентом О., студенты знакомятся с напутствием известного спортивного журналиста Н.Озерова, адресованным начинающим спортивным комментаторам.

Перед чтением записи одного из репортажей А.Школьника преподаватель предлагает студентам подумать над вопросом: «Какими качествами должен обладать репортер?»

Репортаж Александра Школьника

- Здравствуйте, дорогие ребята!

Хочу познакомить вас с интересными людьми – вашими ровесниками.

Школа № 14. Первое сентября. Подхожу к группе мальчишек и девчонок, оживленно жестикулирующих, перебивающих друг друга:

- Я думаю лучше сегодня.

- А может еще один прогон?

- Нет, достаточно.

- О чем спор, ребята?– интересуюсь я.

Удивлению моему не было границ. Оказывается, группа энтузиастов-старшекласников под руководством учителя музыки Виталия Петровича Бодрова организовали музыкальный театр. Начали с небольших постановок, а теперь уже сочинили трехактную пьесу. Все лето репетировали, шили костюмы, рисовали и сколачивали декорации.

- А как же отдых? – спрашиваю я.

Ребята смотрят на меня с недоумением.

В самом деле, что это я.

Лучшего отдыха не придумать.

Здорово живут ученики школы № 141.

Отвечая на поставленный вопрос, студенты называют такие качества, которыми должен обладать репортер: он должен правдиво и точно изображать события, ярко и образно, уметь общаться с людьми, быть смелым и мужественным в своей работе.

Не менее интересными были сообщения студентов о тех журналистах, которые жизнью заплатили за правдивость своих репортажей:

1) Юлиус Фучик

2) Дмитрий Холодов

3) Семья Никулиных

4) Лариса Юдина

Преподаватель зачитывает сообщение из газеты «Аргументы и факты», где говорится о том, что за последние 5 лет было убито 156 журналистов. Это убийство московского журналиста Дмитрия Холодова, всем известного журналиста и телеведущего Владислава Листьева. Далее называются имена тех, кто погиб на территории Украины за 2014 г. Логичным был вывод о том, что профессия журналиста требует помимо профессионализма еще и мужества, даже геройства.

О замечательном человеке, журналисте, телерепортере, фотографe, в прошлом ведущем программы «В мире животных» Василии Пескове, - рассказывает преподаватель:

- В.Песков написал замечательную книгу «Шаги по росе». Герои этой книги строят заводы, прокладывают каналы, воздвигают дома, сажают яблони. У них немало общего. И в то же время образ каждого из них, живой и яркий, несет те черты, которые присуще ему, и только ему. Каждое событие им не просто описано, а выношено, пропущено через свое, личное восприятие. Песков не боится «присутствовать» в своих материалах, но это присутствие не навязчиво, а органично. Автор здесь лицо активно действующее, думающее,

остро видящее. Он умеет душевно беседовать, задавать людям нужные вопросы, искренне радоваться вместе с ними и, когда надо, негодовать. Это всегда вызывает доверие читателя.

Важной приметой творчества Пескова является то, что для него рассказать о человеке – это всегда написать о земле, на которой он вырос, об его отношении к родной природе.

Да, своим творчеством Песков славит людей труда. Но, подобно одному из героев своего репортажа, он утверждает: «Жизнь не представляю себе без птичьего пения...».

Василий Песков умеет видеть, слушать, чувствовать природу нашей Земли и пишет о ней свежо, сочно, подлинно. Песков много фотографирует. Он часто охотиться с фотообъективом за лесными загадками. В поле, в лесу он свой человек. Он все время напоминает: вы тоже можете стать «своим человеком». Лесной праздник доступен всем. «На этот праздник не нужен билет. Кладите краюху хлеба в мешок, проголосуйте попутному грузовику, или садитесь в автобус, или велосипед седлайте, а лучше – пешком. Пораньше из дому, лучше с самой зарей. Тогда весь праздник – ваш. Вы увидите, как стягивает солнце туманное одеяло с реки, увидите росу на красных осиновых листьях, увидите, как добывает свой «хлеб» трудолюбивый дятел. Не заявляйте о себе криками, поберегите песни. Слушайте тишину, и тогда осень лесная покажет вам все богатство...».

Теоретический материал о том, что репортажи бывают нескольких видов, студенты оформляют в тетради:

- информационный,
- оперативный (авторы сообщают о том, что видели и слышали),
- фоторепортажи.

Определяется несколько подгрупп, и каждой из них дается задание на определение вида репортажа и характеристику лингвистических особенностей.

Логичным является завершение занятия, когда начинается ролевая игра, и студентам предлагается представить, что они репортеры, а их тетради – репортерские блокноты. Определяется тема репортажа «Прекрасное живет рядом с нами», обговариваются условия создания фоторепортажа. Студентов предупреждают о том, что созданные ими репортажи будут заслушаны и проанализированы на занятиях СРСП.

Подводятся итоги занятия.

Некоторые исследователи считают публицистический стиль принципиально неоднородным, по мнению других (их абсолютное большинство), уже в самой этой неоднородности прослеживается специфическое стилевое единство, целостность. Общие черты стиля с разной степенью активности проявляются в отдельных подстилях: газетно-публицистическом, радио-, тележурналистском и ораторском. Однако границы этих подстилей очерчены не резко, часто размыты. И об этой «размытости» также необходимо дать студентам вполне конкретную информацию.

Информация на занятиях должна быть представлена на основе применения инновационных методов обучения, которые соответствуют задачам вузовского становления и современным требованиям. Поэтому в ходе исследования мы обращались не только к теоретическим источникам по текстологии, но и к работам по стилистике, а также использовали материал по вопросам современной дидактики и методике преподавания языков.

Е.П.Прохоров указывал, что: «...публицистика предлагает особый тип ориентации – не столько в законах действительности и в эпохах развития общества, сколько в текущих событиях во всем их многоцветии и разнообразии. Это означает также что наука, искусство и публицистика взаимодействуют и здесь существуют переходные формы». Е.П.Прохоров отмечал, что «...публицистика призвана помочь практически процессу духовного сознания мира народными массами, способствовать правильному, глубокому, всестороннему ориентированию их в текущей действительности. Именно публицистика, нашедшая свое

место, прежде всего в периодической печати, затем на радио, в кино, телевидении, в наибольшей степени соответствует особенностям формирования и функционирования этого типа сознания». Известно, что специфическое социальное предназначение публицистики – формирование общественного мнения. Формирование общественного мнения является важнейшей, но не единственной функцией публицистики. Е.П.Прохоров в своих трудах указывал на две функции публицистики: социально-педагогическую и информационно-познавательную [6].

Публицистика, как и художественная литература, имеет дело со словом. Публицистика, прежде всего, использует такой канал коммуникации, такие средства массовой информации и пропаганды, как журналистика. Государственные и негосударственные газеты, радио и телевидение, располагая широкой и разветвленной сетью корреспондентов, создает многообразную, разностороннюю, всеохватывающую «историю современности».

Литература

Аубакирова К.Т. Стилистика и культура речи. – А., 2002.

Луков Вл. А. Жанры и жанровые генерализации // Знание. Понимание. Умение. – 2006. – №1. – С. – 141-148.

Луков Вл. А. Жанры и жанровые генерализации // Знание. Понимание. Умение. – 2006. – №1. – С. – 141-148.

Бобылев Б.Г. Стилистический анализ художественного и публицистического текста. – А., 1987.

Практическая журналистика в Казахстане: Учебное пособие. – Алматы, 2006. – 348 с.

Воскобойников Я.С., Юрьев В.К. Журналист и информация. М., 1993.

Головин Б.Н. Основы культуры речи. – М., 1987.

ЕСЕНҒАЛИ РАУШАНОВ

ШЫҒАРМАЛАРЫНЫҢ КӨРКЕМДІК, ТАНЫМДЫҚ ЕРЕКШЕЛІКТЕРІ

Ғайнеден Әселханым Ерсіңқызы

М. Өтемісов атындағы БҚУ 2 курс магистранты

Ғылыми жетекшісі:

Мүтиев Зинулла Жаксылыкович

М. Өтемісов атындағы БҚУ профессоры, ф.ғ.к.

Орал, Қазақстан

Аннотация: Мақалада Мемлекеттік сыйлықтың лауреаты, қазақ әдебиетінің көрнекті өкілі, ақын Есенғали Раушановтың поэзиясын мен эсселеріне талдау жасалған. Ақынның көркемдік ізденістері сараланып, өлеңдерінің табиғаты сараланады. Ақын қаламынан туған ойлы образдарға назар аударылып, шайырдың дүниетанымдық көзқарастары айқындалады.

Кілт сөздер: қазақ поэзиясы, образдар галереясы, көркемдік қуат, жалғыздық концепциясы

Қазақ әдебиеті мен руханиятында өзіндік ізі бар көрнекті тұлға, ауызы дуалы ақын, мемлекеттік сыйлықтың лауреаты Есенғали Әбдіжаппарұлы Раушановтың өлеңдері көзі қарақты оқырман көңілінен ойып тұрып орын алғалы қашан?! Оның поэзиясы оқыған жанды толғантпай, тебіrentпей қоймайды. Соны сұхбаттары, танымдық мақалалары, есті эсселері талайдың таңдайын қақтырып, түрлі ойға батырғаны анық.

Өлең сүйер һәм әдебиетке жаны жақын қауымның, соның ішінде жас буынның қабырғалы қаламгердің туындыларын жарыса оқып жүргеніне куәміз. Олай болса, «Осындай дүниелердің тұңғығында не жасырулы, қандай тың жаңалықтар бар? Өлеңдерінің тарихы, құрылысы қандай?» деген сауал-сұрақтарға осы бір ғылыми-танымдық мақала-материалымызда әл-дәрменіміз, шығармашылық қауқарымыз жеткенше жауап беруге ниеттіміз.

Есенғали – Қарақалпақ жерінде дүниеге келген қазақ баласы. Бабалары үш жүз алпыс екі әулиелі Маңғыстауды мекен еткен. Ақын журналист Қарлыға Ибрагимоваға берген сұхбатында:

– Біз бір үйде 8 ұл, 4 қыз – 12 бала өстік қой. Раушанұлы Әбдіжаппар деген кісінің ұрпағы кешеге дейін бүп-бүтін, бәрі аман-есен, сау-саламат жүр едік. Амантай дейтін ағам Бекет ата мешітіне зиярат етіп барып, кенет сол жерде жүрегі ұстап, қайтыс болды. Біз өзі Бекет атаның тұқымымыз, атаның Жайлау деген баласынан тараймыз [1], – деп тек-тамырын тереңнен тарқатады.

Оған бәрінен бұрын жақындарының қазасы ауыр тиді. Анасының қазасынан кейінгі қарындасының күйзелісі қасірет үстіне қасірет жамады.

«Ендігі күнім қараң» демеші,
Мен тірімін ғой себебі, көкем.
Сүйеді екен адам неге осы,
Адам неге осы өледі екен?

Ұйықтай алмаспын бұл түні дағы,
Сыртта қап-қара даланы көрем.

Түн.
Жұлдыз.
Таулар –
бір күні бәрі

Қалады-ау, шіркін, қалады менен [2, 165-б.]

– деп қарындасына ақтарыла сырын айтады. «Менің аңқау тәтем» атты өлеңі де қарындасы Сәлимаға арналған көрінеді.

Ет жақындарының бірінен кейін бірі өмірден озғанына күйініп, дүниенің жалғандығына көндікті. Жазып үлгерсем, оқып үлгерсем деп жүріп, 64 жасқа қараған шағында аты жаман аурудың (коронавирус) кесірінен дүниеден озды. Белгілі қаламгер Сұраған Рахметұлының «Есенғали – қазақ сөз өнерінің келте ғұмыры» деуі сондықтан.

Ақынның тұңғыш жыр жинағы 1980 жылы «Бастау» деген атпен жарыққа шығады. Кейін «Келінтөбе» (1984), «Шолпан жұлдыз туғанша» (1988), «Қара бауыр қасқалдақ» (1995) кітаптары жарық көреді. Ал 1991 жылы баспадан шыққан «Ғайша бибі» жинағы үшін «Алаш» халықаралық әдеби сыйлығының лауреаты атанады. 2005 жылы «Періштелер мен құстар» жыр кітабы басылып шығады.

Өлеңдері мен поэмаларынан қазақы иіс аңқиды. Сонау Доспамбет, Қазтуған, Шалкиіз жыраулардың үніндей қоңыр әуез байқалады. Ол адамның жан дүниесіндегі құбылыстарды, өзгерістерді дәл суреттейді. Жырлары оңай оқылып, қаузалған тақырыптың тереңіне тарта береді.

Таң ата келіп қарасам,
Тамағыма өксік болып тығылдың.
Кеш бата келіп қарасам,
Кербез бір аттай бұрылдың,
Жаным, Жайық, мен өзіңнің құлыңмын [2, 99 б.]

немесе

«Белімнен үш ұл шыққанда,
Қайғымның алтау боларын білгенмін.
Жұт бары анық,
Жұрт барда,
Жұптасып бірге күн көргін» [2, 100-б.]

- деген өлең шумақтарында Қашаған, Мұрат, Махамбеттердің үні естілетіндей.

«Ғылымдағы хроместезия сияқты үннің, дыбыстың, сөздің түр-түсін, бояуын ажырата білер сұңғыла жан табыла қалса, Есенғали поэзиясынан сандаған ғасырлардың бояулары мен кескіндемелерін тауып алар еді. «Неліктен осындай мазмұн осындай дыбыстарды талап етеді екен?» деп А.Потебня таңырқағандай, ақынның сөздерді саралауы, образдарды даралауы, музыкалылығы мен «сөз арасын бөтен сөзбен былғамайтын» үнем (бөссөзділіктен адалық) тек зергерге тән өлшем мен балгерге тән түйсікті талап етері сөзсіз, [3, 14 б.] – дейді маңғыстаулық шайыр, «Құрмет» орденінің иегері Светқали Нұржан.

«Өлеңді өз анасындай қадірлеген» кейіпкеріміздің шығармашылығында кездесетін образдар, көркемдік құралдар – бұрын-соңды бізге ұшыраспаған тың құбылыстар. Өлеңге өң беретін теңеулер бұрын қолданылмаған соны дүниелер. Мысалы:

Бір жаңбыр жауды маңдайдан,
Маңдайдың мұздай теріндей [2, 107 б.]

- деген өлең жолдарында жаңбырдың суық тамшыларын қызылтаяң шақта ытқып шығатын маңдайдың мұздай теріне теңейді. Әнге айналған «Қара бауыр қасқалдақ» өлеңінен ғажайып теңеулерді көруге болады:

Қара бауыр қасқалдақ, қай жаққа ұштың пыр-пырлап?
Сазың қалды сәбидің еңбегіндей былқылдап» [2, 74 б.]

Құс сазының сәбидің еңбегіндей былқылдауы – ғажап көрініс, керемет сурет.

Есенғали өлеңдеріне ерекше мән-мазмұн беретін тағы бір бейнелеуіш тәсіл түрі – эпитет. Оған көптеп мысал келтіруге болады. Тағы бір тілге тиек, сөзге өзек ететін нәрсе – «Ескексіз қайық мен екенмін-ау, / Мезгілдің желі айдаған» [2, 96 б.], «Ақылды дәрменсіздікпін» [2, 96 б.], «Намазшамда көлеңкелер өледі» [2, 94 б.] деген тіркестерінен өзіне ғана тән окказионал сөздерді кездестіре аламыз.

Е. Раушанов шығармаларындағы образдар галереясын, тіл құнарлылығын, ондағы көркемдік шешімдер мен мифтік сарын іздерін ғалымдар мен сыншылар көп сөз етті. Десе де, атақ-мансап іздемей, әдебиет әлеміне шын ықыласымен берілген ақын шығармашылығы кең әрі жан-жақты зерттеуді қажет етеді.

Есенғали Раушанов шығармалары турасында ақын, филология ғылымдарының докторы Жанат Әскербекқызы «Көркемдік өріс» (2008) монографиясын жазды. Ақынның өлеңдерін, поэмалары мен балладаларын жік-жігімен талдап, ондағы орбаздар галереясын жасақтап, көркемдік ерекшеліктерін атап көрсетеді [5]. Сондай-ақ, Есенғали Раушановпен жүргізген сұхбаты да осы еңбектің ішінде.

Осы еңбек хақында: «Кітапты оқығанда бір Тәңірге тән сақилықпен жаратылған әлемет әлемнің мәні мен әрін айнытпай жеткізе алған ақынның құдіретіне тамсансам, оқып біткесін – соның бәрін бес саусағындай біліп, өзгелерге де ұқтыра алған сыншы сұңғылалығына сүйсіндім, [3, 14 б.] – дейді мемлекет және қоғам қайраткері, Қазақстанның халық жазушысы Әбіш Кекілбаев.

Есенғали Раушановтың тағы бір елеулі еңбегі – 2007 жылы «Құстар – біздің досымыз» атауымен жарық көрген танымдық хикаялар жинағы. Ақынның табиғатпен, құстармен байланысын танытатын бұл құнды дүние балаларды да, ересектерді де қызықтырмай қоймайды. Құстар әлемін әдебиетпен, аңыз-әңгімелермен, ән жолдарымен байланыстыра отырып суреттейді. Өзіміз білетін аққу, ақсұңқар, ұлар, тырналардан бастап, сушылқара, зымыран, әуілдек, бәбісек, қарасайрақ құстары туралы қазақша, көркем тілде әдемі мағлұмат бере білген [4].

Оның ойынша жалғыздық – жалғыз қалу емес. Оның ойынша жалғыздық – ойлану, мына төрткүл дүниенің жұмбақ-құпиясының тұңғығына сүңгу, жаратылыстың мән-мағына-мазмұнын ұғыну. Сол себепті де ол «Жаздың жұпар жаңбыры» атты кітабында: «Түптеп келгенде көркем әдебиет дегеніміздің өзі жалғыздықты жырлау емес пе?» [3, 79-б.] - деп жазып қалдырды.

Бұл гипотезамыздың (болжам) дәлел-дәйегі есебінде біраз дүниені алға тартуға болады. Мәселен, еркіндік – ойыңа не келсе, соны жүзеге асыру деген сөз емес. Дәл осы тұрғыдан алып қарасақ, жалғыздық концепциясы – белгілі бір мекенде жападан-жалғыз қалу дегенді білдірмейді. Жоғарыда баяндағанымыздай, жалғыздық жұмбағы көп жаратылыс – адам баласын түрлі күмән-күдіктен, үрей-қорқыныштан, жабығу-қамығудан қорғайтын ең керемет ұғым. Осыны сана-түйсігімен, жан-жүрегімен қабылдағасын да кейіпкеріміз көп жағдайда оңашалықтағы философиялық тұжырымдарын қағазға түсірді. Бұл тұрғыда біз ақынның Абай һәм Хамза ұстанымдарына асқан құрметпен қарағанын аңғарамыз. Абай Құнанбайұлы «Мыңмен жалғыз алыстым, кінә қойма!» десе, Шираз бұлбұлы, даңқты шығыс шайыры Хафиз Ширази «Іздегенім – оңашалық, содан табам тіректі» дейді. Есенғалидағы жалғыздық бейнесі осылайша сипатталмақ.

Жалпы «Жаздың жұпар жаңбыры» кітабы өзге жинақтардан әсерлі эсселермен, тың ақпарат-мәліметтермен ерекшеленеді. Қарымды қаламгер «өз қаһармандарының» тұлғалық болмысын ашу барысында мысалдарды көптеп келтіріп, қиялын кезген түрлі детальдарды орнымен сәтті пайдаланады.

«Биылғы жаз жаңбырлы болды. Табиғат тазарып тұру үшін жаңбыр керек дейді, адам тазарып тұруы үшін не керек? Меніңше, ақындар керек. Сырбай Мәуленов секілді» [3, 112 б.] дейді бір эссесінде.

Міне, көрдіңіз бе, Есенғали Раушанов өз эссесінде ағасы Сырбай Мәуленовтың шығармашылық хал-ахуалын, әл-қуатын қалайша дәл суреттеген, көркем бейнелеген?!

Ол аз сөзге көп мағына сыйғызып, сол аз сөзімен көпшіліктің дұрыс бағытқа қарай ұмтылуына, талпынуына жол ашады. Жоғарыда аталған эсселер жинағында «Біз – әдеби потенциялы сұмдық үлкен халықпыз, әңгіме - соны пайдалана білуде боп отыр» деп қазақ қаламгерлерінің арқасындағы жүктің салмағын, шығармашыл тұлға атанып жүргендердің жауапкершілігін, жалпы қазақ қаламгерлеріне, соның ішінде, жастарға түсетін ауыртпалықтың зор екендігін айқындайды.

«Әңгімешіл емеспін. Мүмкін, менің көкірегімде тамаша ойлар тұрған болар, сені қуантатындай, қырсыққанда соны әдемілеп, майын тамызып айта алмаймын. Соған қарағанда мен жазатын ғана адам шығармын» дейді кейіпкеріміз. Иә... ол ештеңе айтпайды. Керісінше, оның өлеңдері ақтарыла сөйлейді.

Анығында, оның өлеңдерінде ешқандай жасандылық жоқ. Ақынның негізгі қаруы, ең сенімді қаруы осы. Оның өлеңдерінде ақын-аудармашы Николай Заболоцкий тәптіштеп көрсеткен «өлеңді көтеріп тұратын үш кит: Ой – Образ – Әуезділік» [3, 134 б.] бар.

«Патшалар келеді, кетеді, ал Ұлы Өнер өлмейді... Асылы, өнер мұраты өміршеңдік» [3, 34 б.] - дейді Есенғали Раушанов.

Ақынның шығармашылық ізденісі хақында әлі де қарастырылатын мәселелер мол, ол болашақтың еншісінде деген ойдамыз. Түйіп айтқанда Есенғали Раушанов қазақ әдебиетінің дамуына зор үлес қосқан, алға қойған басты мақсат-мұратына жеткен қаламгер қатарынан табылады.

Пайдаланылған әдебиеттер:

1. Раушанов Е. Әмірхан Балқыбек деген балаға неге асықтың дегім келді: сұхбат. - Алматы, 2017. URL: // <https://abai.kz/post/61629> (Қаралған уақыты: 17,09.2023.).
2. Раушанов Е. Періштелер мен құстар: Өлеңдер мен поэмалар. – Алматы: Көркем, 2005. – 264 б.
3. Раушанов Е. Жаздың жұпар жаңбыры: эсселер, сұхбаттар. –Алматы: ҚР «Полиграфкомбинат» ЖШС, 2021. – 348 б.
4. Раушанов Е. Құстар – біздің досымыз. – Алматы: Жазушы, 2007. – 256 б.
5. Әскербекқызы Ж. Көркемдік өріс: Есенғали Раушанов поэзиясы негізінде. Ғылыми зерттеу. – Алматы: Таймас, 2008. – 295 б.
6. Раушанов Е. Жалғыз жалбырақ термелип, жүрөгүмді эзбечи. Бишкек: Турар, 2009. – 76 б.

ФАРИЗА ОҢҒАРСЫНОВА

ПОЭЗИЯСЫНДАҒЫ «ӘЙЕЛ» БОЛМЫСЫ

Батырбек Нұржаусын Меңдібекқызы

М. Өтемісов атындағы БҚУ 2 курс магистранты

Ғылыми жетекшісі:

Мутиев Зинулла Жаксылыкович

М. Өтемісов атындағы БҚУ профессоры, ф.ғ.к.

Орал, Қазақстан

Аннотация: Мақалада қазақ поэзиясының падишасы Фариза Оңғарсынованың өршіл рухты әйел болмысын жырлайтын шығармаларына талдау жасалған. Әйелдер болмысы ақын лирикасының шоқтығы биік шыңы. Ал, бойжеткен тағдыры ақын поэзиясының өзегі. Фариза Оңғарсынова көзінен таса, қаламынан қалыс қалған әйел-ана, қыз-келіншек бітімі жоққа тән. Нәзік жандылардың жанына жалау, көңіліне медеу болар Фариза ақынның поэзияларындағы жалынды жолдар. Бүгінде әйел затына қалқан болған ақын апамыздың өлеңдеріне қайта-қайта орала беретініміз де соның айғағы.

Кілт сөздер: қазақ поэзиясы, лирикалық бейне, әйел болмысы, әйел бітімі, қыз тағдыры, өмір суреттері, ақындық шеберлік.

Фариза Оңғарсынова нәзік жаратылыс иесі бола тұра, өжет әйел бейнесімен замандастарынан оқшауланып тұрды. Сыршыл ақын поэзиясының шамшырағына айналған әйел болмысы мен қыздың қадір-қасиеті көптеген өлеңдеріне арқау болған. Фариза Оңғарсынова лирикасындағы қыздың жаратылысы мен тағдыры ақынның барлық шығармасының өң бойынан анық байқалады. Айталық, нәзік жандылардың сезімі, ерік-жігері, махаббат жолындағы сезім биігіне адалдығы бәрі де ақын шығармасында жырланып жүрді. Мәселен, сүю, жан-тәнімен жақсы көру, күйіну, өкіну, қынжылу, таусыла қайғыру, сол махаббаттан азап шегу, ерке қылық, балаша қуану, өліп-өшіп сүю, шарт етіп сынар кесек мінез, тауы шағылған талай қыздың тағдыры ақын лирикасыннан табылады.

Фариза Оңғарсынова поэзиясында ерекше орын алған ұлттық ұғым мен тәрбиенің көрінісі «Ауыл қызы» аталатын шығармасында суреттеледі. Көрікті бойжеткеннің жандүниесіндегі сұлулықты суретпен жеткізу мүмкін еместігін осы өлеңі дәлелдеп береді. Ақынның сөзбен зерделеген осы поэзиясы қыз баланың болмыс-бітімін, қазақ қызының даралығын айшықтап көрсетеді. Оқырманға ой тастар, талғамы биік бұл туынды қазақ қыздарының қандай болу керектігі туралы айтылады.

Қос жанарда тұрады арай кілкіп,
Қадалмайды, жалт етіп қарайды үркіп.
Сұқтанады сан көздер сұлулыққа,
Толықсиды қағылмай талай кірпік.

Ақша бетке жарасып пісте мұрын,
Балғын жүзден мөлдіреп іштегі нұр.
Бала мінез, пәк көңіл тамсандырып,
Деседі іштен жігіттер «түс пе мұным?!»

Жұмыр кеуде жарасып иықпен тік,
Тұр талдырмаш денесін биіктетіп.

Жалғыз жатыр жотада қара бұрым
Нәзік белге кей-кейде тиіп кетіп.

Шыдам жетсе, жігітім, қызбай қара,
Қадалсаң да, тоймайсың жүз қайтара.
Мынау дала жердегі жұмақ болса,
Періште деп дәл осы қызды айтады, ә! [1, 77 б.].

Лирик ақынның бұл шығармасы тек ауыл қыздарына ғана емес, қаладағы құрбыларға да өнеге болатын, қазақтың қара көзді мөлдіреген сүйкімді аруларының сымбатын суреттеген болса керек.

Махаббат лирикасы Фариза ақынның поэзиясында ой-толғамдарымен көмкеріліп, сан алуан тағдырлы болмыспен кестеленіп отырады. Көңіл күйсандығында ерке қылықты бойжеткеннің қымсына қараған кінәмшіл, пәк сезімі, сезім тұңғығына оқырманын сүңгітіп жіберердей күй кештіреді. Бірде жаз болып күлімдесе, бірде қыс болып қаһарын төгетін қыз мінезінің аумалы-төкпелі құбылып отыруыда, әйел болмысының жаратылысы екенің анық ұғындырады. Фариза ақын лирикасының ең елеулі тұсы өлең жолдарындағы кейіпкер бейнесін көз алдыңызға келтіріп, оған жан бітіріп сөйлетіп жібереді. Қыз махаббатының күйің шерткен ақынның әйелдің жан-дүниесін жіті бақылап, беріле сыр ағытуы да оның лирикасына тән даралық шығар. Нәзік жанды арудың өң бойында табылатын тағы бір қасиеттердің бірі наздылық пен еркелік. Сағым болған күндерден өз бақытын күткен бойжеткеннің шынайы махаббаты таңдауы талайды азаптап та кеткен шығар. Бұл туралы ақын тағы бір өлеңінде былай жырлайды:

Табындырар тауып тізгінін бұла көңілдің
Сол шақта мүмкін өзіне ғашық етпегің.
Сен әйтеуір ұмыттырар мына өмірдің
Мені толғандыратын қасіреттерін [1, 124 б.].

Оқырман көзімен қарасақ, көңіл-күй лирикасына толы бұл өлеңде махаббат дертінен айықпаған, сезімнің күйігін бастан кешкен жанның жан айқайын аңғарамыз. Ақынның шебер психолог екендігі анық көрініс табатын тұсы да осы әйел хақында жазылған жырларымен биіктей түседі.

Қуанышты мендегі
сенің қайғың улайды.
Ешбір адам жердегі
білмейді бұл мұң жайлы.

Аяз шарпып денені,
сүйген болам бекер кеп.
Сені іздегім келеді
қай жерде отыр екен деп.

Сен жайлы ойды жасқадым
қалмасын деп ол біліп.
Құшағында басқаның
сені ойлаймын. Сорлылық [1, 125 б.].

Сырт көзден қаймығып, сезімге тосқауыл болар құпиясын өзгелерден жасырудан әбден шаршаған мұңлы қос ғашықтың ішкі запыранын да ақын осылай жырға қосады. Ақын қазақ әйелдерінің ішке бүгіп қалатын жан-сырын, әйел біткеннің өзге түгіл өзінен де ұялатын шындығын поэзиясында баса айтады. Сонымен қатар, тағдырдың маңдайға жазуымен өмірде жолы болмай, тауы шағылып, сүйгеніне қосыла алмаған бойжеткеннің монологы да

Фаризаның лирикасында жырланады. Ақын өлеңдерінде әйел болмысы жырланғанымен де, түп төркіні өмірде өкініші көп, күйбең тірліктен шаршаған, тағдырдың жазғанына көндіккен жанның ішкі-мұңы анық байқалады.

Неге-неге осынша алыстадың,
Өліп-өшіп жүректі жаныштадың,
Сен отырсың жігіттік өрлігіңмен
Иілуге алдымда намыстанып [1, 164 б..].

Бойжеткеннің назы біресе жігітті кінәлі деп таныса, енді бірде жаны жаралы арудың бар кінәні өзіне алғандай күй кештіреді:

Менде ме деп бар кінә, мұңға баттым,
құпталмаппын бас иіп, тыңдамаппын.
Көтергендей аспанды мен де отырмын
нәзік жыныстығымды бұлдап – ақ тым [1, 164 б..].

Енді бәр сәтте махаббаттың отына маздаған арудың сүйгенінен көңілі қалып, шарт-шұрт еткен мінезіне тап боламыз. Намысын ешкімге таптатпайтын, кіршіксіз адал махаббатың иесі бола білген бойжеткеннің тәкаппар мінезі, жігіттің менмен, өзімшіл, асқақ меселін қайырып тастағандай болады. Мәселен:

Сен үшін сонау алыстардағы емес ем,
осынша мені арман қып келдің неге сен?
«Сыртыңнан сүйіп жүретінімді сезбеуші едің ғой» демесең,
мен саған ғашық емес ем [1, 165 б..].

Жалпы лирика адам жанының айнасы дейтініміз де бекер емес. Нәзік жандылардың көңіліндегі қалтарыс-бұлтарысын жырға қосып, өздерінің өмір соқпағын, тағдыр-талайын, өз болмысың Фариза Оңғарсынова шығармаларынан көрген әр әйел затының ақынға көрсетер ықыласы бөлек екені анық. Қазақ қоғамындағы барша әйел затының атынан сөз алған ақынның әйел жаратылысының бар бітімі мен өр болмысын поэзияда ту етіп желбіретсе асқақтатуы табандылық.

Әйел затының ер азаматтарға қарағанда, төзімді, батыл, уәдеге берік, шыдамды келетіні де бүгінгі қоғамның дәлелі болса керек. Нәзік жандылардың жанына жалау, көңіліне медеу болар Фариза ақынның поэзияларындағы жалынды жолдар. Бүгінде әйел затына қалқан болған ақын апамыздың өлеңдеріне қайта-қайта орала беретініміз де соның айғағы. Ақын шығармашылығының мәні де шырайы да әйел болмысы болса керек. Лирикада Фариза Оңғарсынованың шығармашылығына бойлаған зерттеуші ғалым Т. Шапай «Ой түбінде жатқан сөз» еңбегінде былайша пайымдайды. «Ақынның оқырман алдында пердесіз, ашық шығатын сәттері – оның ақындық тұлғасына, адамдық, азаматтық парасатына сын. Ішкі әлемге бай, кісілік келбеті кесек творчестволық тұлғаның ақтарыла сыр ашуы – өнер үшін қашан да өлшеусіз ырыс, құт» дей келе: «Фариза жырларынан өмірін өлеңге байлаған трагедиялық тұлға бой көтереді» [2, 37-38 бб.]. – деп ақын туындыларына өзінің тұжырымын айтқан.

Қазақ қоғамында поэзия падишасына айналған Фариза Оңғарсынованың әйел-ана, бойжеткен арудың бітім болмысын суреттеуде ақынның өзіндік қолтаңбасы бар. Ендеше лирикадағы Фариза ақын тайға таңба басқандай жырлаған әйел бейнесіне нақты тоқталайық. Поэзиясында әйелдер әлемін сөз еткенде ақынның бірқатар өлеңдері еске түседі. Қыз біткеннің ішкі жан күйің суреттеген «Телефон шыр етеді» [1, 40 б.], «Телефон құрғырың үндемеді» [1, 79 б.] деп аталатын өлеңдері екі түрлі жағдайда жазылсада, мазмұн жағынан бір-біріне ұқсас жырланады.

Телефон шыр етеді:
сонда менің жүрегім дір етеді,

көйлегімнің желбіреп гүл етегі
жүгіремін. Не пайда, сен емессің.
Тек қиялдау көңілді жүдетеді.
Кешке дейін неше рет дірілдетіп,
мәнсіз, әрсіз, алаңмен күн өтеді.
Телефон, шыңғырсаң да,
көтермеймін енді мен - қылғын, сарна!
Жүрегіме тыныштық бермей қойды-ау,
төбесінен бір қойып сындырсам ба?!
Әне тағы... сені ме!
Қоңыр дауыс!
Трубканы сүйіп мен тұрдым сонда [1, 40 б..].

Бұл ақынның «Телефон шыр етеді» атты өлеңі. Мұнда шыр еткен телефонға алаңдаған бойжеткеннің тағаты таусылып, амалы құрыған сәтін тамаша жырлайды. Қос ғашықты бірде табыстырып, бірде жалықтырып, күтерге тағат қалдырмай, әлсіз жүрегің одан сайын толқытып, сәтті қауышулардың куәгері ететін сол қоңыр дауыс екені өлеңге арқау бола түседі. Ақын телефон арқылы бойжеткеннің сезім сергелденің сырлы жырға айналдыра білген. Қыздың жан күйің, өң бойындағы толғанысын жүрегімен ұғына білген ақынның бұл жырды оқырманға тебіреніп жеткізуі де соның айғағы.

Телефоны құрғырың үндемеді -
оятпады мазалап түнде мені.
Шырт ұйқыдан тұрғызып сүйіктім кеп
кетеміз, жүр демеді.
Ақ айдынға тоғытып жыр-кемені,
желмен ұшып жанымның мұң-желегі,
ағыстармен алысар арман сәттер
ұмытты мүлде мені.
Жақындатпай, алдырмай ой қамалы,
үміт, ыза - жиылып бойға бәрі,
арман оты жарқылдап жанарымда
найзағай ойнамады.
Азаптың да рақат бар мұңдары,
сені сағынғаным да - жанның нәрі.
Осы бір сәт тыныштық болса игі еді
дауылдың алдындағы! [1, 79 б..].

Қырық құбылған қыз сезімін сезіне отырып жырлаған туындысы «Телефон құрғырың үндемеді» атты өлеңі. Сүйген азаматына алаң болған көңілді байланыстырар жалғыз ғана телефон еді. Ақын қыздың азапты сағынышын, асау сезімін жағаға байлап қойған кемедей тұсаулай түседі.

Әйелдер болмысы ақын лирикасының шоқтығы биік шыңы. Ал, бойжеткен тағдыры ақын поэзиясының өзегі. Фариза Оңғарсынова көзінен таса, қаламынан қалыс қалған әйел-ана, қыз-келіншек бітімі жоққа тән.

Ф. Оңғарсынованың «Қыз – ғұмыр», «Жүрек күнделігі», «Жүректер тілдескенде» аталатын жыр жинақтарында [3-5] жұмыр жердің жарық шырағы - ананың, әйелдің жанашыры бола білген ақынның лирикалық кейіпкерлері әр қилы жастағы, алуан мінезді күнделікті өмірдің өтінде жүрген біздің замандастарымыздың бейнелері сомдалған.

«Нәзік жанды бейнелің күллі құпиясын қопара көрсету арқылы әйел образын лирикада қаһармандық санатқа көтерудің бастауын біз Фаризадан анық байқаймыз. Әйел

жанын, ана табиғатын ақын-әйелдің ой-дiңгегi тұрғысынан таныту, қазақ әйелiнiң психологиялық ахуалын лирикада Фаризадай ашып айтқан ақын, сiрә, да аз» [6, 59 б.] - дейдi фаризатанушы ғалым З. Мүтиев

Иә, қазақ әдебиетiнде әйел тақырыбын қаузаған ақын жоққа тән, алайда Фариза ақындай жырлаған лирик сирек екенi шындық. Ақынның ер мiнездiлiгi, өршiл рухы шығармасына арқау бола бiлген әйел болмысындағы ерекшелiктi, жан дүниесiн, олардың тағдыр жолын, iшкi жан айқайын адамзатқа жеткiзуге тырысты. Бойжеткеннiң жалынды жастық шағындағы қуанышы мен қайғысын, арайлы ақ таңын, нәзiк сезiмiн лирикасында жеткiзiп қана қоймай, әйел тағдырына тереңнен бойлап, кесек тұлғалы образ жасау тек Фариза ақынға ғана тән құбылыс.

ПАЙДАЛАНЫЛҒАН ӘДЕБИЕТТЕР ТIЗIМI:

1. Оңғарсынова Ф. Екi томдық таңдамалы шығармалар. I том. – Алматы: Жазушы, 1987. - 352 б.
2. Шапаев Т. Ой түбiнде жатқан сөз. – Алматы: Жазушы, 1989. - 192 б
3. Оңғарсынова Ф. Қыз – ғұмыр. – Алматы: Жазушы, 1996. – 391 б.
4. Оңғарсынова Ф. Жүрек күнделiгi. – Алматы: Жалын, 1972. - 248 б
5. Оңғарсынова Ф. Жүректер тiлдескенде. – Алматы: Жалын, 1990. - 344 б
6. Мүтиев З. Фариза Оңғарсынованың лирикасы. Оқу құралы (толықтырылған 2-басылымы). – Орал: М.Өтемисов атындағы Батыс Қазақстан мемлекеттiк университетi, 2019. - Орал: Шұғыла Принт, 2019. - 222 б.

Historical Sciences

Heydar Aliyev's state concern for Azerbaijani sports

Təranə Ağarza qızı Həmzəbəyova

Chairman of the "Arts and Physical Education" Subject Unification Commission of the Azerbaijan State Pedagogical College under ASPU

Xülasə: Azərbaycan idmanının inkişaf etməsində, dünya arenasına çıxmasında Heydər Əliyevin misilsiz rolu və qayğısı, İlham Əliyevin bu işi uğurla davam etdirməsi

Açar sözlər: Azərbaycan, Heydər Əliyev, idman, gənclər, dövlət

Abstract: Heydar Aliyev's unparalleled role and care in the development of Azerbaijani sports and its entry into the world arena, İlham Aliyev's successful continuation of this work

Keywords: Azerbaijan, Heydar Aliyev, sport, youth, state

"Symbols of Azerbaijan's independence as sports
there is no second means of demonstration"
Heydar Aliyev

Sports require great care and attention. If we look at the period of formation and promotion of Azerbaijani sports, we will witness that the historical services of Heydar Aliyev created miracles.

Physical education and sports have reached greater development in Azerbaijan. In recent years, the positive changes in the social and political life of our republic have created conditions for a number of cultural and mass events to take place on a large scale and have opened new paths.

In Azerbaijan, sport has always been one of the important factors in the development of society. National leader Heydar Aliyev spoke about the importance of sports and noted: Sports and physical education are an important means of lifestyle of the Azerbaijani people and citizens of Azerbaijan, as in every civilized nation and country.

Heydar Aliyev's services in the field of sports policy of Azerbaijan are priceless. He did everything in his power to increase the role of great leading athletes in the life of the society, to

take a worthy place for themselves. The Ministry of Youth and Sports was established in 1994 by Heydar Aliyev's decree to implement the state's sports policy. In this sense, 1994 can be called a turning year in the sports life of the republic. On March 5, 1995, Heydar Aliyev signed a new decree. According to that decree, a fund was established under the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan in order to promote a healthy lifestyle among the population of the Republic of Azerbaijan and develop the material and technical base of physical education, to organize national assistance in this field, to increase the interest of young people in sports and to create a real basis for the internationalization of Azerbaijani sports.

Heydar Aliyev set specific tasks for the institutions directly engaged in this field to achieve mass sports in Azerbaijan, to develop and promote physical education and sports in a wide geographical area, to achieve high achievements and train world-famous athletes. Among the main measures to be implemented for the development of sports are the protection, restoration and use of existing sports bases, stadiums, fields and halls, construction of new sports bases, fields, stadiums and halls, supply with necessary equipment, opening of sports clubs, training of specialists, country holding championships and other competitions, ensuring the participation of our athletes in international competitions, paying attention and care to athletes with high results, holding international competitions in Azerbaijan, involving children and teenagers in sports on a wider scale. As a result of important events carried out in a very short time, our athletes gradually won great victories, our tricolor flag began to wave in international arenas. Heydar Aliyev considered the development of sports and physical education not only as the embodiment of the highest ideals of every civilized nation, but also as a celebration of the state's international prestige and positions.

The great leader highlighted the exceptional role of sports in the recognition and strengthening of the image of our country in the world and said: "Sports and physical education are an important social field related to the health of the people. The flag of Azerbaijan is raised almost twice in the world. "It happens when our athletes come and win the title of champion in international competitions. The national anthem of Azerbaijan is played and the national flag is raised." The great leader Heydar Aliyev's policy in the field of sports has entered a new stage since 1997.

Heydar Aliyev always drew attention to the fact that the Olympic Games occupy the most prestigious and highest place among international competitions. He said about this: "Olympic games are of interest to all the countries of the world, they are concentrated here. Every country tries to be represented in the Olympic games."

The great leader considered the athlete's participation in the Olympic Games as a great achievement. In 1996, in a meeting with athletes before leaving for the Atlanta Olympics, Heydar Aliyev emphasized the importance of participating in the Olympics and said: "In order to get the right to participate in the Olympic Games, it is necessary to achieve the necessary indicators. If these are not present, the state of Azerbaijan and the President of Azerbaijan will not succeed, no matter how hard they try." an athlete who cannot achieve this cannot be part of the national team. Therefore, it is a remarkable event for the delegation to demonstrate the potential of the Republic of Azerbaijan in the field of sports and to participate in the Olympic Games. What achievements the athletes return from there is another aspect of the issue."

Heydar Aliyev's speech said, "What the National Olympic Committee of Azerbaijan has created is not for one person, but for the development of sports in the nation, the people, in the country", "We are fulfilling our duty to the nation, the people, the homeland by taking care of sports and physical education", "We are doing construction works" We have carried it, we are carrying it and we will carry it faster in the future", the words "Sports in Azerbaijan will rise and develop even higher until the upcoming Olympic Games" inspire our athletes to great victories even today.

The national leader of the Azerbaijani people, Heydar Aliyev, defined the future directions of the country's development in all areas. The President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Ilham Aliyev, is taking the country forward with great success along the lines set by Heydar Aliyev. This has been taken as the main direction in sports as well, and the tradition laid by the national leader in the field of sports is continued.

The election of Mr. Ilham Aliyev, who achieved success in all areas under his leadership, as the president of the National Olympic Committee, was written down in history as an important and significant event in the life of Azerbaijani sports. This historical choice ensured that the ideas of the national leader Heydar Aliyev regarding the development of sports in the republic became a reality more quickly, and opened great opportunities for the implementation of state policy in the field of sports in new conditions. The steps taken by Mr. Ilham Aliyev for the progress of sports and physical education, for Azerbaijan to become an equal member of the world sports family, were welcomed by the entire sports community of the country. The measures implemented under the leadership of Mr. Ilham Aliyev began to bear fruit in a short period of time. In addition to state care for athletes, important works were started in the direction of strengthening the material and technical base of sports. Since 2000, modern Olympic sports complexes have been built and put into use in different regions of Azerbaijan.

During the past years, thanks to the attention and care of the state, sport in our country is experiencing its period of growth. Azerbaijan is recognized as a sports country in the world. Our representatives successfully perform in competitions held in international arenas in various sports and achieve high achievements. Modern Olympic sports complexes, stadiums, sports centers and other facilities have been built and are being built in all parts of our republic. Necessary conditions have been created for teenagers and young athletes to practice sports in all parts of our country. It is no coincidence that many prestigious tournaments in different sports are held in our country. Azerbaijan hosts these competitions at a high level.

Investigating the activities of great personalities like the national leader of our people, Heydar Aliyev, requires years, maybe even decades, but of course, there is a very common truth that everyone knows equally: Heydar Aliyev was an unparalleled personality gifted by history to the people of Azerbaijan, and everyone knows how much he he knew very well that he was precious. It is the duty of each of us to protect the traditions of independent statehood inherited by Heydar Aliyev.

REFERENCES

- 1.<https://www.olimpiyadunyasi.com/w6426.html>
- 2.http://www.anl.az/down/megale/azerbaycan/azerbaycan_mart2009/73204.htm
- 3.<https://fulltext.preslib.az/olimpiya/MFD8zteHni.html>

The colonial character of Soviet statehood in Kazakhstan: the system of governance

ABIL Yerkin

Doctor of Historical Sciences, Professor, Barimbek Beisenov Karaganda Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Kazakhstan (Karaganda, Kazakhstan),

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8722-3992>

KUZEMBAYULY Amanzhol

Doctor of Historical Sciences, Professor, A.Baitursynov Kostanay Regional University (Kostanay, Kazakhstan), <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3662-7003>

Apologists for the USSR often point to the fact that local ethnic elites, justifying the non-imperial character of the Soviet system of government, dominated the republics, including Kazakhstan. "Local leaders who, by agreement with Moscow-Center, received a fairly high degree of autonomy in dealing with internal affairs, while remaining, of course, fully loyal to basic Soviet principles," writes S. Abashin in an article with the telling title "Soviet = Colonial?". (For and Against)". [1, c.34]. E. Rudyk, Professor of the Department of Digital Economy at Dubna State University, speaking at the Round Table of the magazine "Alternatives" stated that the USSR cannot be called an empire on the grounds that Russians as "the people forming the state, cementing the country" did not have any privileges, on the contrary, representatives of non-Russian ethnic groups had privileges in the national republics [2].

Let us see how real the power of local political elites was and how the practice of "center-periphery" relations in Kazakhstan differs from similar practices in other colonial empires. The core of the political system during the entire existence of the Soviet Union was the Bolshevik Party (since 1918, the Russian Communist Party). - Russian Communist Party (Bolsheviks), since 1925. - All-Union Communist Party (Bolsheviks), since 1952 - the Communist Party of the Soviet Union). Accordingly, the heads of the regional party organization performed the role of regional political leader, duplicating and replacing the constitutional authorities in the form of Soviets. From the very establishment of Kazakhstan as an autonomous unit, mainly appointees from the Center headed the party organization.

After the revolution of 1917, by the decree of the Council of People's Commissars (SNK) of the RSFSR of July 10, 1919, partly on the territory of the former Steppe Territory (Akmola and Semipalatinsk regions), partly to the west of it (Turgai and Ural regions) the Kirghiz Territory was created. Already in the decree was laid down the principle of full subordination of administrative bodies to the central authorities. In the first paragraph, it was established that all military and civil power in the territory of the region until the convening of the "general Kyrgyz congress" belonged to the Revolutionary Committee. The second paragraph of the decree established that "the Revolutionary Committee consists of 7 members appointed by the central authorities of the Russian Republic, with the right to co-opt active workers among the population with the right to be a member of the Revolutionary Committee" [3].

On April 30, 1920, Stanislav Pestkovsky, a Polish Bolshevik, commissar for the State Bank, the first People's Commissar of Posts and Telegraph, Deputy People's Commissar for Nationalities, was appointed Chairman of the Kirrevkom. Alibi Dzhangildin became his deputy. Already in September 1920, he was replaced by another Moscow appointee - Ivan Akulov - an active

participant in the October coup d'état and the Civil War, who in 1919 - 1920 participated in the defense of Orenburg.

In January 1921, the post of the head of the regional party organization, the Kirghiz Regional Committee of the RCP(b) (Kirobkom) was first occupied by a local native Mukhamedkhafiz Murzagaliev; however, in July of the same year, a professional revolutionary Maria Kostelovskaya [4] was appointed in his place. Just a month later, Georgy Korostelev, another professional revolutionary who settled in Orenburg after exile and arrest, took this position. He held this position for a little longer, from September 1921 to October 1924, after which he gave way to Viktor Naneishvili, a Georgian Bolshevik who had worked in Azerbaijan and Dagestan and was considered an expert on Turks and Muslims.

In early 1922, the central party authorities faced a crisis in the regional party organization, caused on the one hand by attempts of the Kazakh political elite to use the party platform to promote the ideas of state independence, on the other hand - by organizational and managerial weakness of appointees who had little understanding of the specifics of intra-elite relations in Kazakhstan. Concerned about this, the Moscow authorities created in April 1922 the Kirghiz Bureau of the Central Committee of the RCP(b) with the right to cancel the decisions of the Kirobkom [5, p.11]. Initially, it consisted of three people: V.Yudovsky, a party member since 1903, a representative of the Central Committee of the RCP (b) in Kazakhstan, A.Vainshtein, chairman of the Kyrgyz (Kazakh) Council of Labor and Defense, a member of the Kirobkom of the party, chairman of the Central Executive Committee S.Mendeshev, proposed by the Kirobkom and approved by the Central Committee. The composition of the Kirbureau changed repeatedly, but the number of its members never exceeded four people. For a short time, from April 1922 to March 1923, the secretary of the Kirbureau, a party member since 1917, A.Asylbekov was a candidate to the Kirbureau. A.Asylbekov. In September 1922, after V.Yudovsky was recalled from Kazakhstan, by decision of the Central Committee of the RCP (b) the responsible secretary of the Kirobkom A.Korostelev, who thus combined two positions, headed the Kirbureau. On August 30, 1923 V.Velman was introduced into the regional bureau [5, p.12]. The Bureau worked until February 1925.

After a short tenure (October 1924-July 1925), the infamous Shaya (Philip) Goloshchekin replaced V. Naneishvili, who had a serious dispute with Stalin over national policy. The leadership of Ph.Goloshchekin, which led to a terrible demographic catastrophe of the Kazakh people, ended with the appointment in February 1933 in his place of another Moscow governor - Levon Isayevich Mirzoyan. In addition to fighting the consequences of the famine, he is also known for his active participation in repressions and renaming the city of Taraz in his honor. In May 1938, he, being already the head of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of the Kazakh SSR was removed from his post, and in his place was appointed Nikolai Aleksandrovich Skvortsov, a typical representative of the party and economic nomenclature of those years. A participant of the Civil War, a propagandist-agitator, an employee of the Central Committee engaged in planning and personnel work, he was sent to Kazakhstan to restore order after the "enemy of the people" L. Mirzoyan. On July 13, 1945, Gennady Borkov, another party functionary of Stalin's appointment, replaced this comrade as head of the Kazakh party organization. Before coming to Kazakhstan, he was the head of the Novosibirsk and Khabarovsk party organizations.

On June 22, 1946, a local native, Zhumabai Shayakhmetov, was appointed to the highest party position in Kazakhstan for the first time (except for the brief six-month leadership of M. Murzagaliev). Absolutely loyal to Moscow, who had experience of operational work in the OGPU/NKVD system, Zh. Shayakhmetov was needed by Stalin during the period of active intervention of the USSR in the political processes that were taking place in East Turkestan, which is why his promotion along the party line began in the late 30s - early 40s. In the summer of 1946, at the air parade in Tushino, Joseph Stalin noted that Zh. Shayakhmetov was the first leader of the

Kazakh SSR of indigenous nationality, introducing him to the present officials of the country with the following words: "Comrades, this is Zhumabai Shayakhmetov - the first national secretary of Kazakhstan" [6, p.8].

It would seem that after a long era of Moscow appointees, Kazakhstan had really moved to independent management, but the first serious disagreements between the Center and the region showed that the Moscow party leadership did not intend to take into account the interests of Kazakhstan and the appointment of Zh. Shayakhmetov was rather an exception to the rule of centralized management through a system of de facto viceroys. The conflict arose in connection with the plans of "development of virgin lands", i.e. economic colonization of the territories of Western Siberia and Kazakhstan for the purpose of extensive development of the food base of the USSR. J.Shayakhmetov, who perfectly understood the demographic consequences of this process for Kazakhstan and expressing the interests of the local political elite opposed it, suggesting to emphasize the development of traditional industries for Kazakhstan, primarily cattle breeding [7, p.192-193]. N.Khrushchev directly accused Zh.Shayakhmetov of nationalism. "Shayakhmetov understood that if to increase the areas for grain, the Kazakhs themselves could not process them. Many people of other nationalities, mainly Ukrainians and Russians, lived in Kazakhstan. He realized, and no one hid it, that he would have to call for help from volunteers willing to go to the development of virgin lands. We were sure that the right number of them would be found, but he did not want that at all, because then the specific weight of the indigenous population in Kazakhstan would decrease even more... When the development of virgin lands began, Shayakhmetov had to be replaced" - wrote later N.Khrushchev himself [8, p.74-75].

Moscow appointees Panteleimon Ponomarenko (from February 1954 to August 1955), Leonid Brezhnev (from August 1955 to March 1956), Ivan Yakovlev (from March 1956 to December 1957), Nikolai Belyaev (from December 1957 to January 1960) became the highest party post in Kazakhstan again. Only on January 19, 1960, after the bloody Temirtau events, Moscow decided to bet again on loyal local leaders and approved Dinmukhammed Kunayev as the first secretary of the Kazakh party organization. However, remembering the conflict with Zh. Shayakhmetov, N. Khrushchev insured himself by appointing Nikolai Rodionov as the second secretary and allocating an independent Bureau of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Kazakhstan for the northern (Tselina areas) regions with the center in Akmolinsk headed by Tikhon Sokolov.

Already at the end of 1960 it was decided to create a Tselina region within Akmola, Karaganda, Kokchetav, Kustanai, Pavlodar and North Kazakhstan regions. It was supposed that the Tselina region would be under double subordination: the republican and the union leadership. But it was clear that this was only the first step. According to Kunayev, Khrushchev openly stated that Kazakhstan would be divided into several regions, subordinated directly to Moscow [9, P.105]. The first step towards this was made and Kazakhstan was divided into West-Kazakhstan, South-Kazakhstan and Tselina region. New opposition of the regional elite to Khrushchev's plans, expressed in the demarche of J.Tashenev and soft but persistent opposition of D.Kunayev regarding Khrushchev's plans to detach part of the territories of Kazakhstan in favor of neighboring republics led to the removal of the latter in December 1962 and his replacement by the fully loyal I.Yusupov. Only Khrushchev's removal from power in 1964 and his personal friendship with the new General Secretary of the CPSU Central Committee led to D.Kunayev's return to power.

The independence of republican elites in governing their republics is greatly exaggerated by the apologists of the USSR. Any appointment in the national republics, in violation of their constitutions, was actually made in Moscow. There was a principle of "nomenclature", i.e. a list of positions and the order of their approval. The group approved by the Politburo of the CPSU Central Committee included the first secretaries of the Central Committees of the republican Communist Parties, regional committees, city committees in cities of union importance, as well as the chief

editors of central party publications. In the government, these were Union Commissars (ministers) and top military leaders, as well as ambassadors to foreign countries. In the national economy, they were directors of the largest factories and heads of creative unions.

The group, approved by the Secretariat of the CPSU Central Committee, included party, state and Soviet leaders of lower rank: deputy ministers, second secretaries of regional party committees, chairmen of regional executive committees of Soviets, etc. [10]. [10]. The institution of second secretaries of the Central Committees of the Communist Parties of the national republics should be especially noted. "The republics and national autonomies were rigidly tied to Russia. There was an institute of second secretaries, who were always Slavs" - testifies the former leader of the USSR M.Gorbachev in his memoirs [11].

As we see, throughout the Soviet history of Kazakhstan, the degree of participation of local elites in the management of the republic was minimal. Out of 20 leaders of the party organization, only 5 were representatives of the local elite (M.Murzagaliev, J.Shayakhmetov, I.Yusupov, D.Kunayev, N.Nazarbayev). They remained in power only on condition of absolute loyalty to the central authorities and any attempt to argue and defend national interests instantly led to their removal (Zh. Shayakhmetov in 1954, D. Kunayev in 1962). The institutions of party and economic nomenclature and the practice of appointing second secretaries turned even the partial sovereignty enshrined in the Constitution into a complete fiction.

The formal participation of the local elite in the management of the regions and even the presence of their representatives in the highest governing bodies (D. Kunayev's membership in the Politburo of the CPSU Central Committee in 1971-87) cannot be an argument for denying the colonial nature of the USSR. We see similar representation in other colonial empires, particularly in the British Empire. In the same colonial India, in the Indian Civil Service system, by 1947, local natives held more than half of the top positions. In addition, there were formally autonomous "native principalities" where colonial administration was present in the form of residencies and agencies. The British Dominions, after the 1926 Conference, got rid of British administration altogether, while remaining parts of the British Empire. The French protectorates (Tunisia, Morocco, Laos, and Cambodia) retained local administrations that governed the colonies under the control of French governors.

T. Martin, who applied the concept of "empire of positive action (positive discrimination)" to the USSR, notes that the policy of "Korenization" did not include true federalization. Although formally both the RSFSR and the USSR were federations, real power was always concentrated in the center. Soviet "federalism" did not mean devolution (delegation of political and economic power to federation members) [12, p.58-59]. The author of the classic work on the comparative analysis of imperial political systems D.Lieven also believes that the USSR is one of the varieties of traditional modern European imperialism. He believes that the Soviet history fits perfectly into the framework of modern European colonialism - "a process in which Europeans ruled most of the world in the name of modernization processes developed in Europe" [13, c.499-500].

The entire Soviet history is a history of complete disregard for the interests of the republics and their complete subordination to the interests of the Union center. "The Union had the right to take to its consideration and decide almost any issue, which made the real competence and sovereignty of the republican authorities largely formal", testifies General Secretary of the CPSU Central Committee M.S.Gorbacheva in her report at the plenum of the CPSU Central Committee on the national question on September 19, 1989 [14, p.25]. The Soviet system of formation of the local administrative elite and control by the center certainly had distinctive features, but no more than other colonial systems that existed in the world.

References:

1. Abashin S. Soviet = colonial? (For and Against) // Notions of the Soviet in Central Asia: Stab Almanac No. 2: Central Asian Art-Theoretical Edition. Bishkek: Stab-Press, 2016
2. Rudyk, E. N. What is the USSR, was it an empire and what are its lessons for the future // Alternatives. 2022. № 4. Pp. 117-120
3. Decree of the SNK RSFSR of July 10, 1919 "On the Revolutionary Committee for the management of the Kirghiz region" // Collection of decrees and orders of the government for 1919. Moscow: Office of the USSR Council of People's Commissars, 1943
4. M. Murzagaliev was already a year later, in the fall of 1922, expelled from the party as a former official and member of the regional government of Alash-Orda
5. Osipov V. The role of the Kyrgyz (Kazakh) Bureau of the Central Committee of the RCP(b) in strengthening the party organization of the republic in 1922-1924. Dissertation abstract for the degree of Candidate of Science, Alma-Ata, 1975.
6. Kabuldinov Z., Shayakhmetov R. Zhumabai Shayakhmetov. The first national secretary of Kazakhstan. Vecherniy Almaty. No. 92, August 8, 2020
7. Akhmetova L.S., Grigoriev V.K. Zhumabai Shayakhmetov and his time. Astana: Foliant, 2021
8. Khrushchev N.S. Time. People. Power. Moscow: Moskovskie novosti, 1999. vol. 4.
9. Kunayev D. From Stalin to Gorbachev (In the aspect of the history of Kazakhstan). Almaty, 1994
10. Party-state nomenclature // Bolshaya Rossiyskaya Encyclopedia. Moscow: Big Russian Encyclopedia, 2004-2017
11. Gorbachev M. Life and reforms. Book 1// https://www.gorby.ru/gorbachev/zhizn_i_reformy1/page_18/
12. Miller A.I. Soviet heritage of the "empire of positive action" // Political Science, no. 3, 2004, pp. 57-69
13. Lieven D. The Russian Empire and its enemies from the XVI century to the present day. Moscow: Europe, 2007
14. Materials of the Plenum of the Central Committee of the CPSU, September 19-20, 1989, Moscow: Politizdat, 1989

What is the concept of patriotism?

Rövşən Zakir oğlu Quliyev

Teacher of the subject combination commission "Art and physical education" of the Azerbaijan State Pedagogical College under the Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University

Xülasə: Vətənpərvərlik ən dərin, ən müqəddəs və ən ülvü hisslərdən, duyğulardan biridir. Bu hissə malik olmayan insan bir muzdluya çevrilə bilər. Vətənpərvər isə bu hissi daima qəlbində yaşadır.

Açar sözlər: vətən, vətənpərvərlik, şəhidlik, vətənpərvər, vətəndaşlıq

Abstract: Patriotism is one of the deepest, holiest and most sublime feelings. A person who does not have this part can become a mercenary. A patriot always has this feeling in his heart.

Keywords: homeland, patriotism, martyrdom, patriot, citizenship

Vətənpərvərlik nədir? Vətənpərvərlik böyük məhfumdur. O sadəcə orduda xidmət deyil. Vətənə sadıq qalmaq, Vətəni sevmək, torpağa bağlı olmaq – budur vətənpərvərlik!

Vətənpərvər gənclər yetişdirilməsi təkcə təhsil müəssisələrin işi ilə bitmir. İlk olaraq, ailədən başlayan bu tərbiyəvi iş təhsil müəssisələrində davam etdirilir, bütün cəmiyyətin onun hər bir üzvünün əməlinəki müsbət nümunələrlə yetkinləşir

İnsanın qəlb kasadlığı və genişliyi onun Vətənə olan münasibətilə də təyin oluna bilər. Vətən – müsbət enerjili, ahəng qanununa uyğun tünd rəngli sözlərlə uzlaşmayan bir sözdür. Bu sözü tələffüz edərkən insanın beynində doğma, pak, xeyirxah, səni çətin gündə qoruya biləcək bir varlıq kimi canlanır. Ümumi bir Vətənimiz var. Bu yaşadığımız ölkənin müvəffəqiyyətləri, onun təbiəti, tarixi, gözəllikləri, bir sözlə dünyadakı statusudur. Vətəni bilmək və başa düşmək lazımdır. Ona görə də vətənpərvərlik – Vətən sevgisi, azadlıq, mübarizə, düzgünlük, xeyirxahlıqdır.

«Əsl vətəndaş vətənpərvər olmalıdır, gənclərimizə Vətən sevgisi aşılanmalıdır» kimi ifadələrə tez-tez rast gəlirik. Bu da təbiidir.

Ümummilli lider Heydər Əliyev ölkəmizə rəhbərlik etdiyi dövrlərdə gənclərimizin hərtərəfli inkişafına imkanlar açan müvafiq tədbirlər həyata keçirmiş və tez bir zamanda müstəqil Azərbaycanımızın gələcəyini qoruyub saxlaya biləcək gənc nəsillərin yetişdiyinə əminliyini belə ifadə etmişdir: «Müstəqil Azərbaycan ifadəsi indi hamı üçün əzizdir. Bunu hamı təkrar edir. Ancaq hər kəs başa düşməlidir ki, müstəqil Azərbaycanın müstəqil yaşaması üçün hər bir vətəndaşın vətəndaşlıq borcu var. Bunu təmin etmək üçün hər bir vətəndaş öz payını verməli, öz xidmətini göstərməlidir».

Tariximizə nəzər salsaq görürük ki, elimizin, obamızın ən gözəl ənənələrində biri də torpağa, ana yurda, vətənə bağlılıq, xalqımızı zaman-zaman yadelli işğalçılardan qorumaq, vətən üçün candan keçmək olmuşdur. Elə buna görə də xalqımızın vətən uğrunda, torpaq uğrunda canından, qanından keçən saysız-hesabsız unudulmaz qəhrəmanları olmuşdur. Azərbaycan torpağı müqəddəs torpaqdır. Bu torpağa qanı tökülən igidlərin yazdıqları tarix və etdikləri igidliklər Azərbaycanın müqəddəs torpağını daha da ulu etmişdir. Şəhidlər üçün yazılan hekayətlər həm də gələcək nəsillər üçün ibrət dərslidir.

Vətən yolunda şəhidlik əsl vətəndaşlığın ən ali zirvəsidir. Bütün zirvələrdən yüksəklikdə duran ilahi bir zirvə, həm də o adi gözlə yox, yalnız mənəvi gözlə görülməli bir zirvədir. Məhz buna görə də bu gün gənclərin vətənpərvərlik tərbiyəsindən danışdıqda, gənclərimizin vətənpərvərlik ruhunda yetişdirilməsindən söz açdıqda, mütləq vətən yolunda canından keçmiş igidlərin həyat yolundan söhbət açmaq lazımdır.

Milli vətənpərvərlik hissi gərək körpəlikdən başlasın. Vətən sevgisi insana ana südü ilə verilir. Vətənə məhəbbət hissi uşağın qanında, canında və ruhunda formalaşmalıdır. Hər bir

Azərbaycan vətəndaşı milli dəyərlərə söykənərək, özündə həyat qanunu nizamnaməsi yaratmalıdır.

Vətənpərvərlik mahiyyəti vətənə məhəbbət, bağlılıq, özünün mənsub olduğu millətin mədəni, irsi və tarixi xüsusiyyətlərinə arxalanan milli düşüncənin tərkib hissəsidir.

Hər bir gənc vətən qarşısında öz məsuliyyətini başa düşməli, vətənini qorumalı, hər an əlində silah torpağını müdafiə etməli, bütün varlığı ilə millətini, ailəsini və gələcəyini düşünməli, tələbkərlə, ləyaqətli və təvəzökarlı olmalı, əxlaqi kefiyyətlərə sahiblənməli, humanizm prinsiplərini uca tutaraq hərbi-vətənpərvərlik tərbiyəsinə yiyələnməlidir.

Vətən sevgisi, vətənpərvərlik hər bir kəsin borcudur. Hər bir gənc Vətəninin silahlı müdafiəçisidir. Hər bir gənc vətənpərvər insandır.

Vətənpərvər – vətənini şüurlu səviyədə sevən, hər an bütün çətinliklərə fədakarlıq göstərən, vətənini canından üstün tutan, daima başqalarına nümunə olan, qəhrəmanlıq və rəşadətlik göstərən insandır. Vətənpərvər bütün çətinliklərə dözən, namuslu, vicdanlı və ləyaqətli kefiyyətlərinə sahib olmalıdır.

Vətəni sevmək, göz bəbəyi kimi qorumaq, onun torpağının, daşının, ərazisinin qədrini bilmək, sözün əsl mənasında həmişə mübariz, döyüşkən, igid, mərd və qəhrəman vətən övladlarının, cəsur və namuslu insanların ən nəcib və müqəddəs vəzifəsidir.

Vətəni sevmək, Vətən uğrunda fədai olmaq deməkdir. Vətəni sevmək, Vətən sayılan Azərbaycan torpağının hər qarışına, xalqına qəlbədən bağlı olmaq deməkdir. Vətəni sevmək, onun uğrunda canından keçmək, heç nə düşünmədən ölümə getmək, gələcək nəslin xöşbəxt və firavan yaşamasına üçün şərəfli bir iz buraxmaq deməkdir.

Pedagogical Sciences

Sport is the foundation of health

Şahəddin Aslan oğlu Nərimanov

Teacher of the subject combination commission "Art and physical education" of the Azerbaijan State Pedagogical College under the Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University

Xülasə: Bədən tərbiyəsi cəmiyyətin ümumi mədəniyyətinin tərkib hissəsi olmaqla yanaşı, sağlam yaşamaq və orqanizmin möhləmləndirilməsi kimi komponentləri özündə əks etdirir.

Açar sözlər: Sağlamlıq, fiziki tərbiyə, korreksiya, idman, fiziki kefiyyətlər

Abstract: Physical education is a part of the general culture of the society and includes such components as healthy living and body lubrication.

Keywords: Health, physical education, correction, sports, physical qualities

In order for a person to be able to realize his material and spiritual potential to the maximum, he needs physical health first of all. While the physical energy reserves of the body are limited, the spiritual energy potential is enormous.

Health is one of the greatest blessings. Every person should be able to protect it and protect his health. Sport has a great role in maintaining health. As they say? "A healthy mind resides in a healthy body."

Playing sports not only strengthens a person's health, but also at the same time creates a person's spirit, makes a person flexible and resilient. Sports make a person determined to control his body. People who do sports are more disciplined. They look better and handle themselves better. In addition, sport increases the feelings of collectivity, friendship, companionship, mutual support and patriotism. These feelings are always high in people who do sports. Sport educates a person not only physically, but also mentally. A nation that is actively engaged in sports is a healthy nation.

Plato said: "I don't think that when a person's body is in order, it creates self-pleasure; In my opinion, on the contrary, the happiness of the heart is a condition for the better condition of the body»

In healthy physical education and sports activities, a person enjoys those processes as well as the final result. Physical education is characterized as a part of the general culture of the society. In comparison with healthy children, the organization of the physical education process of children with motor and intellectual defects is somewhat complicated. In order to communicate with children with limited mental and motor abilities, first of all, high pedagogical skills are required from the teacher. Therefore, the social environment and various types of activities are of special importance in human life as the main factor of the educational process. The teacher's professional attitude towards social and cultural values should be reflected in his actions and behaviors.

Physical movements are an important factor affecting the biological and social nature of a person. Improper use of this factor negatively affects the formation of qualities of endurance, quickness, flexibility, strength, and speed. In this regard, it is of great importance to determine the regularities that occur in the body under the influence of exercises.

The study of the physiological and biochemical basis of fatigue during the performance of physical load is of particular importance for the recovery process, and the problem of fatigue, which is considered a general biological problem in life activities, including work and sports, is of great theoretical and practical interest.

There are many children with limited health opportunities in our country, whose education and correction work is carried out at the state level. The role of physical education and sports is of great importance in the education, correction and social adaptation of children with disabilities.

Physical education and sports have exceptional services in eliminating cognitive activity, emotional-volitional field, speech, behavior and personality problems. Sports activities used in this category of children with intellectual, speech, hearing, vision, movement and communication deficits have a great role in preventing mental and physical disorders and in the general development of children. Taking into account the effects of sports activities of this category of children on their personal development, employees of educational institutions should have the following skills:

1. Forming feelings of defeat and ability in children participating in social activities.
2. Expanding training on various topics in the field of child development;;
3. Sports lessons should help the development of children's daily life skills and a person's connection with life.
4. It helps the development of personality in social activities and acceptance by society.
5. Evaluation and development of communication and speech skills;
6. Involvement of children in education;
7. Assessment and development of mental development, perceptual skills

Like normal children, sports have a great impact on the personality development of children with disabilities. Sports are considered important for everyone and are acceptable for any age group.

REFERENCES

1. Q.M.Cəfərov, S.B.Yolçuyev «Adaptiv fiziki tərbiyə» Bakı-2016
2. «İdman həyat və sağlamlıqdır», Modern.az, 10 yanvar 2023-cü il
3. «İdman sağlamlıqdır» İki sahil gündəlik-ictimai siyasi qəzet, 15 mart 2021-ci il
4. «Sağlamlıq imkanları məhdud uşaqların sosiallaşmasında idmanın rolu» Ağzadə Fazilə ADPU-Korreksiyaedici Təlim ixtisası (IV kurs) 25 yanvar 2019-cu il
5. «Sağlamlıq imkanları məhdud şəxslərin təhsili (xüsusi təhsil) HAQQINDA» Aztehsil 30 may 2017

Модернизация научных студенческих конференций, как фактор повышения заинтересованности студентов ВУЗов Республики Казахстан к научно-исследовательской деятельности

Борисов А.А.

магистрант КарУК

Баширов А.В.

кандидат технических наук, Руководитель лаборатории НИИ ЭПИ

Ханов Т.А.

Доктор юридических наук, профессор, Директор НИИ ЭПИ

Аннотация

На сегодняшний день, в эпоху развития цифровизации и онлайн-коммуникации имеется возможность осуществить срез мнений студентов и преподавателей в Республике Казахстан и за рубежом. Вместе с тем, анализ на основе статистических данных и ранее проведенные исследования показали необходимость осуществления систематизации по вопросам совершенствования научно-исследовательской работы студентов

В данной статье описаны экономические, психологические и социальные факторы, которые значительно влияют на разные группы студентов, на их мотивацию и интерес к научной деятельности. Исследовательская группа использовала в своих исследованиях официальные статистические данные, а также результаты анализа проведенных в ходе исследования опроса студентов. Авторами были разработаны предложения по модернизации студенческих научных конференций в качестве фактора, способного повысить заинтересованность студентов ВУЗов Республики Казахстан к научно-исследовательской деятельности.

Статья подготовлена в рамках выполнения договора на грантовое финансирование, заключенного с Комитетом науки Министерства науки и высшего образования Республики Казахстан (ИРН проекта 19676691).

Ключевые слова: научно-исследовательская работа студентов, интерес к научной деятельности, материальное поощрение, анкетирование студентов, организация конференций, значимость научной деятельности, влияние преподавателей, авторитет, мотивация, организация, научные конференции.

Развитие научно-исследовательской работы студентов играет важную роль в развитии науки и вхождении Казахстана в список развитых стран мира. Успешные исследовательские проекты студентов могут привлечь инвестиции и внимание со стороны научных организаций и компаний, способствовать развитию научно-технического сектора в Казахстане, переносу технологий из исследований в промышленность.

Исследовательской группой были выявлены проблемы относительно заинтересованности студентов наукой. На сегодняшний день процент студентов, занимающихся исследовательской деятельностью, крайне мал. Совершенно естественной является задача его повышения.

Для решения проблемы мотивации интереса к научной работе студентов целесообразно акцентировать внимание на следующих направлениях исследования :

1. Углубленный анализ с использованием официальной статистики и ранее проведенные результаты анкетирования [1].
2. Выявление психологических особенностей проявления интереса у студентов к науке.
3. Поиск подходов и инструментов к возобновлению интереса к научной деятельности у студентов.

Первая задача была ранее подробно изложена авторским коллективом Научно-исследовательского института Карагандинского университета Казпотребсоюза. В своей работе ученые говорят о том, что подавляющее большинство студентов университета не проявляли интереса к научно-исследовательской работе [2].

Одной из причин объяснения такой ситуации является изменение традиционных подходов и времени. В настоящее время, молодое поколение формируется в условиях интенсивного развития цифровизации, оперативного получения разнообразной информации, динамичным изменением инновационных технологий и возможностей их использования.

Формирование предрасположенности к научным исследованиям студентов начинает меняться и, в частности, интерес и результативность студенческой науки падает. Это естественно сказывается на формировании квалификационных навыков молодых специалистов, на развитии науки в будущем и развития страны [2].

При рассмотрении второй задачи исследовательской группой было предложено рассмотреть иерархическую модель потребностей человека ,разработанная ученым-психологом Абрахамом Маслоу [3]. Эта модель также называется пирамидой потребностей Маслоу. Данная пирамида потребностей отражает одну из самых популярных и известных теорий мотивации — теорию иерархии потребностей [3].

Чтобы определить мотивацию следует вернуться к решению задачи под номером два и, исключив физиологические потребности в иерархии Маслоу, взглянуть на следующие слои.

1. Потребность в самоактуализации
2. Потребности познавательные
3. Потребность в уважении (признании)
4. Потребность в принадлежности (Социальная потребность)

Каждая из этих категорий в своей сущности является мотивацией, в данном случае для научно-исследовательской деятельности.

Рассмотрим с самой низшей категории из представленных.

Потребность в принадлежности. По данной категории предполагается, что студент желает видеть себя в рядах ученых. Быть с ними в одном кругу и заниматься одним делом. Иными словами, быть причастным к научной среде.

Потребность в уважении (почитании). Эта категория идет дальше предыдущей, ведь здесь уже важен результат, как причина уважения. Научный труд должен быть выделен, замечен и высоко оценен компетентными людьми.

Потребность познавательная. Важнейшая категория для научно-исследовательской деятельности, ведь речь уже перестает идти об оценке со стороны, а говорится об интересе

индивида к определенным вещам. Интерес проявляется в изучении форм и материй, а также может быть выражен в форме эксперимента.

Потребность в самоактуализации. Научная деятельность может предоставить студентам уникальную возможность развивать свои навыки, достигать своего потенциала и достигать самореализации. Это может быть особенно важным для студентов, которые стремятся к выдающимся результатам в своей области исследований.

Связывая научную деятельность с пирамидой Маслоу, можно понять, как она может удовлетворять различные уровни потребностей студентов и служить источником мотивации и удовлетворения. Эта связь помогает объяснить, почему научная деятельность может быть так значимой и важной для студентов, помогая им расти и развиваться как личности.

Для решения третьей задачи авторами статьи выдвинута гипотеза о повышении заинтересованности студентов к осуществлению НИРС с использованием принципиально других подходов по организации и проведению конференций и других аналогичных мероприятиях [4,5].

Организация научных конференций является крайне важным и эффективным популяризатором научной деятельности. Студенты видят, как лучшие умы учебных заведений зачитывают свои работы на актуальные темы, а затем им задается ряд вопросов и таким образом тема раскрывается в полном объеме. Так выглядит идеальная версия научной конференции. К глубочайшему сожалению, современные конференции выглядят иначе.

Реальность такова, что проведение научных конференций среди студентов в стенах университета сталкивается с рядом проблем:

1) Незаинтересованность преподавателей в проведении и участии в конференциях. Такое отношение выражается в отсутствии внимания к выступающим со своими работами студентам, отсутствию комментария по окончании выступления и в пользовании мобильным устройством на протяжении всего выступления.

2) Поскольку мы неустанно движемся к глобальной цифровизации, то и научные конференции все чаще и чаще проводятся в онлайн-формате, что является крайне положительным показателем и позволяет студентам из разных городов и стран принимать участия в конференциях, однако организация таких конференция пока еще на крайне низком уровне. Это связано с плохим интернет-соединением, плохим оборудованием организаторов или участников и прочими техническими ошибками.

3) Отсутствие дискуссий по тематике докладов. В большинстве случаев выступление ограничивается зачитыванием материала и благодарностью за выступление. Но на наш взгляд наиболее логично с точки зрения научности – создание дискуссии по теме работы. Это позволит выявить самостоятельность написания статьи, а также способно дать дальнейшей вектор развития темы. Плюрализм мнений в научной среде – это важный фактор, влияющий на объективность исследования.

По нашему мнению, хорошо организованная научная конференция должна содержать в себе выступления преподавателей-исследователей или ученых с их научными работами, деление научной конференции на секции, исходя из тематик научных работ, а также со внимательным отношением в исходящей от студентов информации и последующими комментариями.

Исследовательская группа считает целесообразным выдедить следующие важные аспекты, относительно усовершенствования очередных и ежегодных научных конференций.

1 Разделение конференции по секциям. Это то, что практически всегда используется, но следует лишний раз подчеркнуть важность этого инструмента. Не следует смешивать интересы студентов с темами, к которым они вовсе не питают интереса, а важно погрузить

молодого ученого именно в его среду, где он разбирается и где может родиться важная для научного мира дискуссия.

2 Привлечение к конференции видных научных деятелей. Совершенно необязательно чтобы это был лауреат международных научных конференций. Это может быть, говоря современным языком «инфлюенсер» в своей сфере, а его участие лишней раз заинтересует студентов, и повысит желание показать ему свои способности и знания в проведенном исследовании.

3 Выпуск сборника в бумажном виде. В нашу эпоху глобальной цифровизации научные сборники в цифровом формате не редкость. Но быть «напечатанным» это уже совершенно другие ощущения для молодого студента, начинающего свой научный путь. Это огромный психологический фактор личного достижения.

4 Внимательность преподавателей, жюри. Комментирование. Неприятны случаи, когда во время демонстрации студентом своего исследования преподаватели и жюри полны внимания, но к своим мобильным устройствам. Такой подход вызывает отторжение научной деятельности ввиду ложного осознания ее ненужности из-за некомпетентности и невоспитанности преподавательского состава. Кроме того, считаем важным по завершению демонстрации давать краткий комментарий и задавать вопросы – порождать дискуссию. Это покажет студенту заинтересованность и вашу осведомленность в теме исследования.

Исследование проблемы отсутствия заинтересованности у студентов в науке крайне важно, так как это влияет на качество их образования, а также на будущее развитие общества и национального потенциала. Недостаток интереса к научным исследованиям снижает возможности для инноваций, развития науки и прогресса в различных сферах, а также уменьшает количество потенциальных научных кадров, необходимых для решения актуальных проблем и развития страны. Поэтому понимание причин и поиск способов стимулирования интереса студентов к науке является важной задачей для образовательных и научных организаций.

Развитие науки среди студентов важно, потому что оно способствует формированию критического мышления, инновационности, и подготавливает будущее поколение лидеров с необходимыми знаниями и навыками для решения сложных проблем, способствуя таким образом как индивидуальному, так и общественному развитию.

СПИСОК ИСПОЛЬЗОВАННОЙ ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ:

1. Статистика науки. [Электронный ресурс]. URL:<https://old.stat.gov.kz/official/industry/24/statistic/6> (дата обращения 04.10.2023)
2. Баширов А.В., Ханов Т.А. Особенности осуществления научно-исследовательской работы студентов в ВУЗах Республики Казахстан // Высшая школа Казахстана №3 (39) / 2022 г. DOI 10.59787/2413-5488-2022-39-3-11-17
3. Classics in the History of Psychology -- A. H. Maslow (1943) A Theory of Human Motivation
4. Ханов Т.А., Баширов А.В. //Научно-исследовательская работа студентов в вузе: причины снижения активности // Современные наукоемкие технологии. 2021. № 6-1. С. 209-214.
5. Bashirov A., Khanov T.//The reasons for the low efficiency of students' research work at the university// Труды университета. 2021. № 3 (84). С. 18-24

Students in the teaching of literary language norms ensuring cognitive activity

Sevda İslam gizi Abbasova

Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogy, Associate Professor of the Department of Azerbaijani Language and its Teaching Technology of the Faculty of Philology of Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University

Literary language is the active form of the vernacular based on strict phonetic, lexical and grammatical norms. Literary language is also called a polished form of folk language. There is an oral and written form of Azerbaijani literary language. In modern times, the oral form of our Azerbaijani literary language is the language of radio and television, speeches, speeches, reports, and examples of our written literary language are state documents, works of art, newspapers and magazines, etc. are written examples.

The main indicator of both spoken and written literary language is its compliance with language norms. In modern times, it is important for students to be familiar with the norms of the literary language of Azerbaijan. Being familiar with the norms of the literary language of Azerbaijan, mastering the norms and features of the literary language, especially the written literary language, not only affects the cognitive activity of students, but also ensures their future work with official documents and the formation of their written speech.

The teaching of the norms of the literary language of Azerbaijan starts from the 10th grade. So far, students have learned the correct spelling of words in the Azerbaijani language, the correct use of punctuation marks, the correct pronunciation (phonetic norm), the lexical meaning of the word, the correct use of synonyms (lexical norm), the grammatical features of the word, the parts of speech, the features of sentences and sentences. (grammatical norm) is familiar with language rules. Information about the concept of the norms of the literary language is given on page 49 of the 10th grade Azerbaijani language textbook. Here, scientific information about the speech is given, its features are explained, and it is noted that the speech must meet the norms of the literary language. It is shown that "Language and speech are organically connected with each other. Speech is a process of communication and appears on the basis of the language's expressive capabilities. Speech is manifested in the forms of listening and understanding, speaking, reading and writing. Every speech is subject to the phonetic, lexical and grammatical rules of the literary language. The most important condition of speech culture, which is required from everyone, is to observe the norms of the literary language.

Following the language rule given in the textbook, we find brief information about the norms of the literary language. The co-authors note that the phonetic norm requires the correct writing and reading of words, the lexical norm requires knowing the meaning of words, using them in the correct place, and the grammatical norm requires the correct establishment of the relationship between words and sentences. In our opinion, the given information is sufficient and corresponds to the level of students.

The questions and tasks presented to the students regarding the texts given in the textbook are also interesting. It should be noted that among these questions and tasks there are questions that are of interest to students and those that are not. Note that the use of questions to increase students' cognitive activity is not limited to the questions presented in textbooks. The teacher can use questions to develop cognitive activity during the lesson. Let's look at an example:

1. If you want to become a journalist, host of any program, announcer in the future, what would you start with to make your speech fluent and correct?

The answer to this question may change depending on the world view of the students, their attitude to the surrounding reality, their dreams and aspirations, and most importantly, their goals and future plans, because if the students agree with the first part of the question, then the second part can be answered.

2. Do you think that you only need to be a journalist and a philologist to know the language perfectly and follow its grammatical structure correctly? What suggestions would you give to preserve the purity of the language? This question has two parts, both questions are thought-provoking and have the power to influence the students' cognitive activity.

3. Based on your observations, determine whether the orthographic or orthoepic norm is more violated in the mass media. Explain why. In our opinion, this question is unlikely to be answered by students. First of all, it is questionable to what extent students show interest in mass media and take advantage of newspapers or websites. On the other hand, there is a need to clarify what is meant by mass media.

It is possible that the students have certain ideas about the media, but it will be difficult for them to give a reasonable opinion about the norms of the literary language in the Azerbaijani media.

The application of modern curricula today requires that training be based on results and organized in an interactive form. This, in turn, creates a foundation for students to acquire new knowledge and skills, to develop as personalities with national thinking and modern thinking. Currently, the principle of approach to education in general education schools is in this direction. Those who work in the field of education already understand that it is not enough to give students scientific knowledge in the educational process, it is necessary to develop certain skills and habits in students. To be more precise, preparing the student for an independent life is the main goal of self-oriented education.

It is also considered necessary to organize classes in this direction and to use active learning methods. The role of motivation as a psychological factor in active learning is great. As we know, motivation is the driving force that activates the mechanism of action. In the active lesson, it is the problem and the need for its solution that is presented as a motivation that directs the thinking process and increases the cognitive activity of the students. A teacher who takes into account the most important features of the motivation stage should know that brainstorming is the destruction of stereotypes and the creation of new ideas and approaches when using brainstorming. Here we are talking about putting forward a new idea. It might even be a fantastic idea. It is about discussing the proposed idea and selecting the best idea. At this time, the question arises, what type of brainstorming will the teacher use in the motivation phase? If it is recommended to use brainstorming in the motivational phase of the lesson in the methodical materials for the teacher, in our opinion, the author of the idea should be the teacher himself, and he should use classic brainstorming.

For example, the teacher asks the students "What are the main features that characterize the Azerbaijani language?" can apply with a question. Asking a question will make students think and voice different answer options. We can assume that among the students, "Azerbaijani language has a law of harmony.", "We come across words with multiple meanings in the Azerbaijani language.", "Images are attached to the end of words in our language." they will voice answers like "it is being processed at the end of the month". After listening to the answers, the teacher can show the students a poem or a text that violates the norms of the literary language from electronic resources, the Internet, or written in his computer's memory in advance, and instruct them to identify the points where the rules of our language are not followed, and give the following explanation: If you read and or if the orthographic and orthoepic norm is violated in the text you are listening to, then the phonetic norm is violated. If proper nouns are not written in capital letters in the text you are reading, quotation marks are not used where necessary, hyphens

are not used, suffixes are written next to Roman numerals, the word is not moved from line to line correctly, then the phonetic norm has been violated.

After giving the most important information about the phonetic norm, the teacher can also give information about the lexical norm in the following way: The lexical norm requires each of us to know the meaning of the word, to use it correctly. If the word is not used correctly, then the idea is not expressed correctly. For example, the teacher can explain to the students that it is necessary to say that the horse neighed instead of the horse neighed, and the chicken cackled instead of the chicken crowed. Or Lala was wearing glasses instead of Lala was wearing glasses.

According to the requirement of the grammatical norm, the nouns following certain numbers of quantities must be singular, and the order of joining suffixes in the names must be increased first by plural, then by affiliation, then by case, and then by indicative suffixes. In addition, the subject of a sentence with a negative conjunction should be in the singular, the subject should agree with the subject in terms of person and quantity, while the members of the sentence are listed, the subject should come at the end of the first subjunctive, and the subject should be used after it is determined.

It should be noted that one of the important features of active learning is to accustom students to the habits of independent learning and independent development. It would be appropriate to carry out an assessment or reflection after the end of the lesson to improve the independent learning activity in the next lesson.

Sometimes assessment and reflection can be incorporated into different stages of the lesson, which in itself will help the learning process to be more successful.

As a result, we can say that if the characteristics of speech and the rules of language are not observed in the teaching process, if language factors are not taken into account in teaching, even the most ideal and wisest idea will not be understood. Therefore, if Azerbaijani language teachers want to ensure cognitive activity during teaching, if they want to train smart young people, citizens who can express themselves and convey their thoughts and opinions normally, they should refer to active teaching methods.

Цифрлық технологиялар негізінде білім алушылардың интеллектуалдық қабілетін дамытудың тиімді әдістері

Смағұл Ботакөз Қытайбайқызы

Абай атындағы қазақ ұлттық педагогикалық университеті (Алматы, Қазақстан)

Абстракт. Цифрландырудың қарқыны студенттердің техникалық білімін, дағдылары мен қабілетін дамытудың жаңа технологиялары мен әдістерін қажет етуде. Информатика курсына мұғалім студенттерге мета-пәндік білім беру нәтижелері ретінде интеллектуалдық қабілетін қалыптастыруды көздейді. Соңғы кезде информатика пәні бойынша қолданыстағы оқу-әдістемелік материалдар студенттердің интеллектуалдық қабілеттерін анық көрсете алмайды. Зерттеудің мақсаты – цифрлық білім беру базасын құру негізінде студенттердің интеллектуалдық қабілеттерін арттыруға бағытталған информатика курсына оқытудың тиімді әдістерін анықтау. Зерттеу нысаны – цифрландыру мақсатында информатика пәнін оқыту үдерісі. Зерттеуде студенттердің интеллектуалдық қабілет ұғымының анықтамасы жіктеліп, оны дамытудың тиімді әдістер анықталды. Зерттеу нәтижесінде интеллектуалдық қабілетті дамытудың техникалық аспектілері, цифрландыру үдерісінде ақпарат алу, коммуникация мәселелері қамтылды. Зерттеу нәтижесінде білім алушының интеллектуалдық қабілетін цифрлық құралдар көмегімен дамытуда сабақта қолданылатын тиімді әдістер көрсетілді.

Түйін сөздер: цифрлық білім беру, цифрлық технологиялар, интеллектуалдық қабілет, электрондық білім беру ресурстары, информатика курсы

Зерттеудің практикалық маңыздылығы ретінде интеллектуалдық қабілетті дамытудағы әдістемелік кеңестер студенттердің осы саладағы білімін арттыруға көмектеседі, цифрландыру кеңістігінде ыңғайлы жұмыс істеуіне мүмкіндік береді. Цифрландырудың қарқыны студенттердің техникалық білімін, дағдылары мен қабілетін дамытудың жаңа технологиялары мен әдістерін қажет етуде. Информатика курсына мұғалім студенттерге мета-пәндік білім беру нәтижелері ретінде интеллектуалдық қабілетін қалыптастыруды көздейді. Соңғы кезде информатика пәні бойынша қолданыстағы оқу-әдістемелік материалдар студенттердің интеллектуалдық қабілеттерін анық көрсете алмайды.

Зерттеу жұмысының алдына қойылған міндеттері:

- білім алушылардың интеллектуалдық қабілетін дамыту туралы теориялық және оқу-әдістемелік әдебиеттерді сыни тұрғыдан талдап, зерттеу жұмысының ғылыми негіздемесін жасау;
- сабақ барысында білім алушылардың интеллектуалдық қабілетін дамытуда жағдаяттық әдістің тиімділігін сынау;
- информатика сабақтарында интеллектуалдық қабілетті дамытуда қолданылатын әдістер мен тапсырмалардың жүйелесін көрсету;
- білім алушылардың интеллектуалдық қабілетін дамытудың тиімді жолдарын көрсететін ұсынымдар беру.

Зерттеудің ғылыми жаңалығы - информатика курсына оқытуда білім алушылардың интеллектуалдық қабілетін дамытуда цифрлық технологияның бірі - жағдаяттық әдіс пен кейс тапсырмалардың тиімділігі дәлелденді. Зерттеу жұмысының нәтижелері білім алушылардың интеллектуалдық қабілетін дамыту бойынша ұсынымдар болды.

Зерттеу жұмысында баяндау, тұжырымдау, салыстыру, сипаттау, жүйелеу әдістері басшылыққа алынды. Тәжірибелік эксперимент кезінде сауалнама әдісі қолданыс тапты.

Информатикадан білім берудегі интеллектуалдық қабілетті дамытудың маңыздылығы жоғары. Психологияда, интеллекттің табиғаты туралы екі көзқарас бар. Біріншісі – интеллектуалды қабілеттердің біртұтас (жалпы) факторы, ол арқылы интеллекті тұтастай бағалауға болады. Бұл жағдайда зерттеу объектісі адамның интеллектуалдық мінез-құлқын, оның қоршаған шындыққа бейімделуін, сондай-ақ оның ішкі және сыртқы дүниелерінің өзара әрекетін анықтайтын психикалық механизмдер болып табылады (К. Спирман, Э. Хант, Г.Гарднер). Интеллектуалдық қабілеттердің тұтастығы теориясының мысалы ретінде интеллект коэффициентін (IQ) есептеу теориясын алуға болады.

Интеллектуалдық қабілет – «адам бойындағы бір іс-әрекетті орындауда әрқилы деңгейде көрінетін жеке қасиеті». Оны данышпандар «асыл мұраға» теңейді. Себебі, кез келген адам бойында ерекше бір көзге түсетін қасиет болады (Э. Хант, С.В. Гайсина).

Интеллектуалдық қабілет – жаңа өнім немесе шығармашылық ойлауды дамытудың қорытындысы деген пікірді ұстанады (К. Тейлор, С.Г. Дебердеева және т.б.).

Келесі зерттеулерде жаңаны құруда шығармашылық процестің басымдылығы көрінеді (Р. Арнгейм, М.А. Холодная, Бидайбеков Е.Ы., Бекежанова А.А. және т.б.).

Интеллект түрлері келесі топты құрайды:

1. Тілдік интеллект
2. Логикалық-математикалық интеллект
3. Кеңістіктік интеллект
4. Музыкалық интеллект
5. Тәндік және кинестетикалық интеллект
6. Жеке тұлға аралық интеллект
7. Тұлғааралық интеллект
8. Эмоционалды интеллект
9. Натуралистік интеллект
10. Экзистенциалды интеллект
11. Шығармашылық интеллект
12. Бірлескен интеллект

Сонымен қатар, Г.Гарднер жеке тұлғаның мүмкіндіктеріне сүйене отырып, интеллектуалдық қабілеттер теориясында мына топтарды анықтады:

-тілдік қабілеттер (ауызша түсіну – мәтіндер мен сөздердің мағынасын түсіну және ашу қабілеті);

-сөйлеудің еркіндігі – берілген критерий бойынша сөзді жылдам таңдай білу);

- логикалық және математикалық қабілеттер;кеңістіктік қабілеттер (объектінің кеңістікте орналасуының психикалық моделін құру және осы модельді пайдалану мүмкіндігі);

-натуралистік қабілеттер;

-музыкалық қабілеттер;корпус-кинестетикалық қабілеттер (мәселелерді шешу және денені пайдалана отырып, өнімді қалыптастыру қабілеті (мысалы, бишілер жасайды));

-тұлғааралық/тұлға аралық қабілеттер (басқа адамдардың әрекеттерінің мотивтерін түсіну және адамдармен жұмыс істеуді білу қабілеті);

-интраперсоналды/тұлға ішілік қабілеттер (өзінің дұрыс моделін қалыптастыру және осы үлгіні күнделікті өмірде табысты қызмет ету үшін пайдалану қабілеті) [Гарднер 1983].

Интеллектуалдық қабілетті дамыту принциптері мен әдістері

- материалдың біртіндеп күрделенуі;

- жұмыс көлемін біртіндеп ұлғайту;

- оқушылардың дербестік деңгейін арттыру;

- білім мен іс-әрекет әдістерін интеграциялау;
- когнитивті мәселелерді шешу үшін теория элементтерін тарту;
- тапсырманың вариативтілік принципін ескере отырып (үлгіге негізделген де, өз бетінше де) пайымдау әдістерін үйрету;

Жұмыс формалары: талдау, синтездеу, салыстыру, жіктеу, жалпылау, аналог табу және т.б. Осындай тапсырмалар этижелерінің жоғары болуы келесі факторлармен байланысты:

- тапсырмаларды таңдау мүмкіндігін қамтамасыз ету және студенттерге оқу материалын өңдеудің тәсілдерін өз бетінше таңдауға және пайдалануға ынталандыру; оқытудың мазмұнына тәрбиелік әрекеттерді орындау әдістері туралы білімді енгізу;

- субъективті қызмет ретінде оқу процесін бақылау мен бағалауды қамтамасыз ету. Білім алушылардың интеллектуалдық қабілетін дамытудың тиімді жолдары *оқытушыларға арналған кеңестер*:

- сабақта кең көлемде көрнекі құралдарды, кестелерді пайдалану;
- Сабақты цифрлық құралдар көмегімен түрлендіріп өткізу;
- сабақта білім алушылар өздері жасаған суреттер, схемаларды пайдалану;
- техникалық құралдарды тиімді қолдану;
- сабаққа қатысты шығармашылық және логикалық есептерді оңайдан күрделіге қарай ұйымдстыру.

АТ тарихына қатысты IQ сұрақтары

1. Алғашқы санау құралы.
2. Шығыстағы ең көне санақ аспабы.
3. Санақ таяқшаларын ойлап тапқан.
4. Аналитикалық есептеу машинасының авторы.
5. Бірінші программист.
6. Пернетақталы компьютерлердің прототипінің авторы.
7. Бірінші буын компьютерлерінің элементтік базасы.
8. Екінші буынның элементтік базасы.
9. Үшінші буынның элементтік базасы.
10. Төртінші буынның элементтік базасы және т.б.

Интеллектуалдық қабілетті дамытуға арналған жаттығулар

1. «Сөздер» анықтамасы

Мақсаты: ұғымның мағынасын түсіндіру және анықтау. Мысалдар: Gramora (бағдарлама), Vredair (драйвер), Danoper (операнд), Laibotic (килобайт), Taxied (дискет), Puromtek (компьютер)

2. «Не артық?» тапсырмасы. *Мақсаты: ауызша сөйлеуді дамыту, сонымен қатар заттарды жіктеу қабілетін дамыту. Ойыншыларға анаграммалар топтары бар карталар беріледі.*

1. KETST, OLISCH, FRGIAC, MABAGU (мәтін, цифр, график, қағаз) Қағаз – ақпаратты тасымалдаушы, қалғанының бәрі – ақпарат түрі. ВИКЛУРАТА, СТИДОГИЯ, НЕРСКА, ТЕРПНИР (пернетақта, джойстик, сканер, принтер)

2. Принтер деректерді шығару құрылғысы, қалғанының барлығы енгізу құрылғысы. ТОРНИМО, ТЕРТПЛО, ТЕРИНПР, ЫШЫМ (монитор, плоттер, принтер, тінтуір) Тінтуір енгізу құрылғысы, қалғанының барлығы шығару құрылғысы. ТЕРЧЕСВИН, ТАКЕДИС, АКТПКОМ КСДИ, СОРСЕТСПРО (қатты диск, иілгіш диск, CD, процессор)

3. Процессор ақпаратты өңдеу құрылғысы, қалғанының барлығы сыртқы жад ТАНПЛЕРЕРОФ, ТАКЕДИС, ТАКРАРАФПЕ, НИМОРОТ (маспа, иілгіш диск, перфокарта, монитор)

Жоғарыдағы тапсырмалар білім алушылардың интеллектуалдық қабілетімен қатар, шығармашылығын дамытуға арналған.

Келесі кезекте мектеп мұғалімдерге арналған сауалнама жүргізілді. Сауалнамаға жалпы саны – 48 мұғалім қатысты. Олар Алматы қаласындағы орта мектептердің информатика пәнінің мұғалімдері. Сауалнаманың мақсаты – мұғалімдер интеллектуалдық қабілетті дамыту тапсырмаларына деген мұғалімдердің көзқарасын анықтау болды.

Сауалнама сұрақтары:

- Интеллектуалдық тапсырмаларды үнемі қолдану қажет пе?
а) иә ә) жоқ б) әрдайым емес
- Интеллектуалдық қабілетті дамыту тапсырмаларын сабақ барысында қолдануға уақытыңыз жеткілікті ме?
а) иә ә) жоқ б) әрдайым емес
- Барлық білім алушылар шығармашылық жұмыстарға қатысу қажет пе?
а) иә ә) жоқ б) әрдайым емес
- Мектебіңіздегі білім алушылардың интеллектуалдық қабілетін дамыту үшін орындалып жатқан іс шараларға көңіліңіз тола ма?
а) иә ә) жоқ б) әрдайым емес.

Сурет 1 – Мұғалімдерге арналған сауалнама

Көріп отырғанымыздай, «Шығармашылық тапсырмалар үнемі қолдану қажет пе?»- деген сұраққа 56% мұғалімдер «иә» деп жауап берсе, қалғандары уақыт болмайтынын немесе қолдана алмайтынын айтады. «Интеллектуалдық қабілетті дамыту тапсырмаларын сабақ барысында қолдануға уақытыңыз жеткілікті ме?» деген сауалға тек 25% мұғалімдер «иә» деп жауап берді. «Барлық білім алушылар шығармашылық жұмыстарға қатысу қажет пе?» деген сауалға мұғалімдердің 62,5%-ы «әрдайым емес» деп жауап берді. Тек 25% мұғалімдер ғана керек деп жауап берді. «Мектебіңіздегі білім алушылардың интеллектуалдық қабілетін дамыту үшін орындалып жатқан іс шараларға көңіліңіз тола ма?» деген сауалға 37,5% мұғалімдер «иә» 37,5-ы % «әрдайым емес» деп жауап берді. Жалпы, сауалнама қорытындысы бойынша мұғалімдер интеллектуалдық қабілетті дамыту тапсырмаларына аса мән бермейді немесе уақыты жетпейтіні байқалды. Алайда мұғалімдердің басым бөлігі шығармашылық ойлау тапсырмаларын керек деп санайды.

Қорыта келгенде, интеллектуалдық – ойлау қабілетінің ең жоғарғы қасиеті. Интеллектуалдық ойлау арқылы білім алушының оқу ортасына, өмірге, білімге деген сенімі, көзқарасы өзгереді. Интеллектуалдық қабілет - бұл адамның өмір шындығына өзін-өзі тануға

ұмтылуы, ізденуі. Өмірде дұрыс жол табу үшін адам дұрыс ой түйін, өздігінен саналы, дәлелді шешімдер қабылдай білуге үйренуі. Зерттеу мақсатымыз ретінде білім алушылардың информатика сабақтарында интеллектуалдық қабілетін дамытуда қандай әдістерді қолдану керектігін және олардың тиімділігін анықталды.

Информатика сабақтарында интеллектуалдық тапсырмалар оқушы бойындағы ойлау қабілеттерін дамытып, рухани күшін нығайтып, өмірде өз орнын табуға көмектеседі. Сондықтан интеллектуалдық тапсырмаларды білім алушыларға жүйелі түрде ұйымдастырып отыруымыз керек. Зерттеу нәтижелері ғылыми жұмыстар, ізденіс жаттығулары, шығармашылық тапсырмаларын оқушылардың интеллектуалдық қабілетін дамытуда аса тиімді әдіс екендігін көрсетті.

Пайдаланылған әдебиеттер

1. Баракина Т.В. Развитие интеллекта при обучении информатики в начальной школе. Журнал «Начальная школа плюс», №7 – 2007, с. 3
2. Дебердеева С.Г. Развитие интеллектуальных и творческих способностей младших школьников на уроках информатики // Информатика и образование. – 2003. – № 10.
3. Ахметова Ж. Білім беруді цифрландыру жағдайында білім алушылардың оқу- зерттеушілік іс- әрекетін ұйымдастыруға информатика мұғалімін дайындау – Алматы, 2020– Б.17-22.
4. 12 жылдық мектептердегі информатикадан білім беру мазмұнының тұжырымдамасы // Информатика және білім. – 2000. – № 2.
5. Бидайбеков Е.Ы., Бекежанова А.А. (2019) Возможности использования инфографики в учебном процессе // Информатика в школе – № 6 (149). – С. 62-64.
6. Холодная М.А. Психология интеллекта. Парадоксы исследования. – 2-е изд. – СПб.: Питер, 2002.
7. Гайсина С.В. Интеллектуальная способность и цифровая образовательная среда школы URL: <https://spbappo.ru>

МЕТОДОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ ЕСТЕСТВЕННО-НАУЧНОЙ ГРАМОТНОСТИ УЧАЩИХСЯ В СООТВЕТСТВИИ С ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯМИ PISA В КАЗАХСТАНЕ

Жумагулова Калампыр Абжаппровна

к.п.н., доцент, Казахский национальный педагогический университет имени Абая

Майматаева Асия Дуйсенгалиевна

PhD доктор, старший преподаватель, Казахский национальный педагогический университет имени Абая

Аманбаева Махаббат Батыргалиевна

и.о.ассоц.профессор, PhD доктор, Казахский национальный педагогический университет имени Абая

Аннотация. В статье анализируются результаты международных исследований Казахских школьников по естественнонаучным предметам. Приведены результаты международных исследований Казахских школьников

Ключевые слова: международная программа по оценке образовательных достижений учащихся, качество образования

Zhumagulova Kalampyr Abzhapparovna
Maimataeva Asia Duisengaliyevna
Amanbayeva Mahabbat Batyrgaliyevna

METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE FORMATION OF FUNCTIONAL NATURAL SCIENCE LITERACY OF STUDENTS ACCORDING TO PISA STUDIES IN KAZAKHSTAN

Annotation. The article analyzes the results of international studies of Kazakhstani schoolchildren in natural science subjects. The results of international studies of Kazakhstani schoolchildren are presented.

Keywords: international program for assessing students' educational achievements, quality of education.

In accordance with the State Program for the Development of Education in the Republic of Kazakhstan for 2005-2010, 2011-2020 [1], the National Action Plan for the Development of Functional Literacy of Schoolchildren for 2011-2016 [2], our country participated in the TIMSS and PISA study.

The results of international studies (PISA) are an important factor in improving the quality of education. This is what the work aimed at updating the content of education in the framework of Priority areas of development of education and science of the Republic of Kazakhstan for 2014-2016 is aimed at.

The development of strategies for the renewal of education, taking into account international comparative studies, seems very relevant and expedient, since in the context of globalization, countries around the world cannot develop without developing common approaches to the most important issues of socio-economic development, without correlating their achievements with each other. Each participating country receives a rich analytical material on the state of the content of secondary education, the prospects for its development in the world with which it is necessary to work.

The purpose of the PISA program is to assess the ability of 15-year-old students to use the knowledge and experience acquired at school for a wide range of life tasks in various spheres of human activity, communication and social relations.

The choice to involve 15-year-old students in the study is explained by the fact that in many countries compulsory schooling is completed by this age, and training programs in different countries have a lot in common. It is at this stage of education that it is important to determine the state of those knowledge and skills that may be useful to students in the future, as well as to assess the ability of students to independently acquire the knowledge necessary for successful adaptation in adulthood.

The PISA Student Educational Achievement Assessment Program is implemented by a consortium consisting of leading international scientific organizations, with the participation of national centers and the OECD organization.

Analysis of the information database of statistical data of the study showed that the percentage of completion of test tasks in mathematics by students on average in Kazakhstan was 41%.

When determining the level of formation of natural science literacy of students, the ability to apply natural science knowledge in situations close to real ones was evaluated. The participants of the international exam had to demonstrate the ability to formulate conclusions and find evidence confirming or refuting them.

The average percentage of completion of the PISA-2012 international test by Kazakhstani students in natural sciences was 40%. This indicator is 1% lower than the results of mathematics.

In the overall standings, Kazakhstani students scored 393 points. The percentage of PISA-2012 test tasks was 38% [19].

In general, the comparative data of PISA-2009 and PISA-2012 are reflected in the materials of Table 1 and Figure 1.

Table 1

Information about the rating of Kazakhstan in PISA

Disciplines	Rating		rating significance coefficient		the growth rate in the rating
	2009	2012	2009	2012	
reading	59 из 65	63 из 65	1,1	1,03	-0,07
mathematics	53 из 65	49 из 65	1,23	1,33	+0,1
natural science	58 из 65	52 из 65	1,12	1,25	+0,13

Thus, the analysis of biology textbooks for grades 9-11 showed that Kazakh high school students have a direct opportunity to perform integrated tasks aimed at the formation of natural science literacy by only 3% in the "Context" block, by 24% in the "Competence" block, by 34% in the "Natural Science knowledge" block and by 38% in the the block "Categories of knowledge about science" (9th grade). Approximately the same picture develops with biology textbooks for 10th and 11th grade (Fig. 1). If we compare the share of RISA-type educational tasks in biology textbooks of the 10th and 11th grades, the following picture is observed: in the textbook for the 11th grades of the natural-mathematical direction, the share of tasks for the formation of natural

science literacy is to a certain extent less than in textbooks for the socio-humanitarian direction (Figure 9), in textbooks for 10th grades, such a paradox is observed with respect to the tasks of the group "Natural Science knowledge" and the group "Categories of knowledge about science" (Fig. 2).

Figure 1. The share of RISA-type educational tasks in biology textbooks (in %)

Fig. 2 – The share of RISA-type educational tasks in biology textbooks of the natural-mathematical direction of study (in %)

In both cases, learning tasks focused on the knowledge paradigm of education largely prevail.

In general, the analysis of textbooks on chemistry and biology showed that due to the extreme insufficiency of tasks aimed at the formation of natural science literacy and tasks aimed at the meaningful integration of school subjects, they do not fully contribute to the successful and effective preparation for Kazakhstan's participation in international comparative studies of the RISA.

As the results of international comparative studies have shown, there is an urgent need to improve the quality of education. To do this, in the context of international studies (PISA), it is necessary, first of all, to update the content of secondary education. This is especially important at the level of secondary education, laying the foundation for further personal development and civic formation of our students.

Acknowledgements The work was supported by a grant from the Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Republic of Kazakhstan (AP14872059 “Methodological foundations for the formation of functional science literacy of schoolchildren in accordance with PISA studies”).

List of literature

1. The State program of education development of the Republic of Kazakhstan for 2011-2020 / Decree of the President of the Republic of Kazakhstan No. 1118. – Astana: 2010. www.nkaoko.kz/documents/law_of_education/
2. Resolution of the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan "On approval of the National Action Plan for the Development of functional literacy of schoolchildren for 2012-2016" dated June 25, 2012 No. 832. adilet.zan.kz/rus/docs/P1200000832 .
3. Zhumagulova K.A., Mamayeva A.D. Analysis of the results of international studies of Kazakhstani schoolchildren in natural science subjects// Collection of articles of the XIX International Scientific and Practical Conference. Saint Petersburg. -2022. - P.209-212.

МРНТИ 14.35.01

ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ЗАДАНИЙ PISA НА УРОКАХ ХИМИИ ДЛЯ РАЗВИТИЯ ЧИТАТЕЛЬСКОЙ, ЕСТЕСТВЕННОНАУЧНОЙ ГРАМОТНОСТИ ШКОЛЬНИКОВ

Галымова Нуржанар Гайсатқызы

докторант 3-курса по специальности химия, Казахский национальный педагогический университет имени Абая

Мукатаева Жазира Сагатбековна

к.х.н., ассоциированный профессор, Казахский национальный педагогический университет имени Абая

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается PISA (Program for International Student Assessment) - международная программа, предназначенная для оценки грамотности и знаний учащихся в разных странах мира, а также использование заданий PISA на уроках химии для развития читательской, естественнонаучной грамотности школьников.

Ключевые слова: PISA, читательской, естественнонаучной грамотности, функциональные грамотности

THE USE OF PISA ASSIGNMENTS IN CHEMISTRY LESSONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF READING, NATURAL SCIENCE LITERACY OF PUPILS

**Galymova Nurzhanar Gaisatkyzy
Mukataeva Zhazira Sagatbekovna**

Abstract: The article discusses PISA (Program for International Student Assessment) - an international program designed to assess the literacy and knowledge of students in different countries of the world, as well as the use of PISA assignments in chemistry lessons for the development of reading, natural science literacy of schoolchildren.

Keywords: PISA, reading, natural science literacy, functional literacy.

In line with modern trends, according to the vector of development set by the 1996 UNESCO Report "Education: The Hidden Treasure", the 2000 World Education Forum in Dakar and a number of other fundamental international documents, the President of the country in the Strategy "Kazakhstan Way - 2050" noted: "School graduates must know Kazakh, Russian and English. The result of schoolchildren's education should be their mastery of the skills of critical thinking, independent search and in-depth analysis of information" [1]. These skills are outlined in international documents of the UN, UNESCO, EU and a number of other generally recognized authoritative organizations and associations.

Almost all UN Member States unanimously recognize that education should be aimed at:

– development of the child's personality, talents, mental and physical abilities to their fullest extent;

– fostering respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms, as well as the principles proclaimed in the UN Charter;

– fostering respect for the child’s parents, his cultural identity, language and values, for the national values of the country in which the child lives, his country of origin and for civilizations other than his own;

– preparing the child for conscious life in a free society in the spirit of understanding, peace, tolerance, equality of men and women and friendship between all peoples, ethnic, national and religious groups, as well as indigenous people;

– fostering respect for the natural environment.

According to the conceptual vision formulated by the International Commission on Education, the quality of education can be interpreted based on the following provisions:

1) learning to know something means that the student daily forms his own knowledge, combining his internal beliefs with information coming from the outside;

2) it is always necessary to learn to place emphasis on the practical application of what has been learned;

3) learning to live together and in harmony is based on especially important social skills in a society free from discrimination, where everyone has equal opportunities to develop themselves, their families and communities; in the learning process, it is necessary to place emphasis on the individual’s skills necessary for his maximum self-realization in life.

It is in this understanding that the quality of education is considered by such internationally recognized means of monitoring the cognitive development of students as the international comparative studies PIRLS, TIMSS and PISA. These studies allow us to monitor the level of development of students’ reading, mathematical and natural science literacy. The study examines the features of the content of primary and basic secondary education, the organization of the educational process, as well as factors associated with the characteristics of the organization of education, teachers, students and their families. To assess educational achievements, students are tested, and to obtain information about the factors influencing learning outcomes, a survey of students, teachers and school administrations participating in the study is carried out [2-3].

In accordance with the State Program for the Development of Education in the Republic of Kazakhstan for 2011-2020 [4], the National Action Plan for the Development of Functional Literacy of Schoolchildren for 2011-2016 [5], our country took part in the TIMSS and PISA research.

The results of international studies PISA and TIMSS represent an important factor in improving the quality of education. This is precisely what the work to update the content of education is aimed at within the framework of the Priority Directions for the Development of Education and Science of the Republic of Kazakhstan for 2014-2016.

While PISA 2009 produced disappointing results for Kazakhstan, participation in PISA 2012 showed certain positive changes. However, the results obtained are still below the OECD average.

In general, the analysis of textbooks in chemistry and biology showed that due to the extreme insufficiency of tasks aimed at developing natural science literacy and tasks aimed at meaningful integration of school subjects, they do not fully contribute to successful and effective preparation for Kazakhstan’s participation in international comparative studies. PISA research.

Of course, in all textbooks used in Kazakhstani schools, regardless of the subject studied

Task: OZONE. Read the next section of the article about the ozone layer.

The atmosphere is an ocean of air and a valuable natural resource that supports life on Earth. Unfortunately, human activities driven by national/private interests are harming this shared resource, especially by depleting the fragile ozone layer, which acts as a protective shield for life on Earth.

Ozone molecules are made up of three oxygen atoms, as opposed to oxygen molecules, which are made up of two oxygen atoms. Ozone molecules are extremely rare: less than 10 per million air molecules. However, their presence in the atmosphere for billions of years has played

an important role in maintaining life on Earth. Depending on where it is located, ozone can protect or harm life on Earth. Ozone in the troposphere (up to 10 kilometers above the Earth's surface) is "toxic" ozone that can damage lung tissue and plants. But about 90 percent of the ozone found in the stratosphere (10 to 40 kilometers above the Earth's surface) is "toxic" ozone, which plays a beneficial role by absorbing harmful ultraviolet (UV-B) radiation from the sun.

Without this beneficial ozone layer, people would be more prone to certain diseases due to increased ultraviolet rays from the sun. Over the past decades, the amount of ozone has decreased.

Question 1: The above text says nothing about how ozone is formed in the atmosphere. In fact, every day a certain amount of ozone is created and another is destroyed. The way ozone is formed is shown in the following comic.

Suppose you have an uncle who is trying to understand the meaning of this line. But he did not receive any scientific education at school and does not understand what the author of the film is explaining. He knows there are no little people in the atmosphere, but he wonders what the little people on the strip mean, what the strange symbols O, O₂ and O₃ mean, and what message the strip represents. He asks to explain the strip. Let's say your brother knows:

- O – symbol of oxygen;
- what are atoms and molecules.

Write a comment about the comic to your brother.

Process: Communicating valid conclusions based on evidence/data to others. **Definition:** Earth and environmental science (chemical and physical changes). **Status:** Global.

Question 2: Ozone is also produced during thunderstorms. It creates the typical smell after such a storm. In lines 10-12, the author of the text distinguishes between "toxic ozone" and "pure ozone." Regarding the article, is the ozone produced during a thunderstorm toxic or clean? Choose an answer and explanation from the text.

	Toxic ozone or pure ozone?	Explanation
A	Toxic	Formed during bad weather.
B	Toxic	It is formed in the troposphere.
C	Pure	It forms in the stratosphere.
D	Pure	Smells good.

Process: Critical evaluation of scientific facts/data. **Concept:** Earth and Environmental Science (Earth/Space). **Status:** Global.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the purpose of this study is to discuss the potential of some test questions to engage students in certain ways. By recognizing the criteria of PISA questions, we expect teachers who even work with students on these questions in their classrooms to contribute to the development of scientific knowledge, who will evaluate the construction of scientific knowledge and the development of knowledge on each of these criteria. The purpose of this study is to discuss the potential of certain test questions to engage students in specific ways.

Acknowledgements The work was supported by a grant from the Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Republic of Kazakhstan (AP14872059 “Methodological foundations for the formation of functional science literacy of schoolchildren in accordance with PISA studies”).

List of literature

1. “Kazakhstan Way – 2050: common goal, common interests, common future” [Electronic resource] – Access mode: http://strategy2050.kz/ru/page/message_text2014/
2. Results of an international study assessing the educational achievements of students in the 4th and 8th grades of secondary schools in Kazakhstan. National report. – Astana: NTSOSO, 2013. – 237 p.
3. Main results of the international study of educational achievements of 15-year-old students PISA-2012. National report. – Astana: NTSOSO, 2013. – 283 p.
4. State program for the development of education of the Republic of Kazakhstan for 2020-2025.
5. A. Kultumanova, G. Berdibaev, B. Kartpayev. I.Imanbek, K.Sharbanova, M.Rakhimova, M.Zhumabaeva, Z.Prinpesova, B.Okenova, A.Uvalieva. Main results of the international study of educational achievements of 15-year-old students PISA-2012/ – Astana: NTSOSO, 2013. – 283 p.

Legal Sciences

Domestic corruption in Kazakhstan

Bibigul Maiorova

George Mason University, Antonin Scalia Law School, Virginia, USA

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this work is to consider the problem of domestic corruption in Kazakhstan and finding out the solutions in order to solve it.

The main method of work was the analysis of the phenomenon of domestic corruption and secondary data related to the issue.

The author comes to the conclusion that comprehensive state measures have significantly reduced the level of corruption in the country. An important role in this was played by the development of digital technologies, which made it possible to make the transition of a large part of the document flow into electronic form. Nevertheless, the problems of domestic corruption are still far from being solved.

Keywords: *Corruption, domestic corruption, fraud, bribery, exchange of favors, nepotism, institutional corruption*

INTRODUCTION

At the present day, corruption can entail a variety of actions from bribes to inappropriate various gifts, which is currently called domestic corruption. Household corruption is generated from ordinary citizens to government officials. This type of corruption is manifested by gifts and services to an official and a member of his family. This category also includes nepotism (nepotism).

It can be stated some progress in the fight against corruption in Kazakhstan. So, if Kazakhstan ranked 131 in the Corruption perceptions index in 2016, then in 2022 it was already 101 [1]. The Anti-Corruption Agency of the Republic of Kazakhstan states an annual consistent decrease in the number of corruption crimes, from 2,807 in 2016 to 1,557 in 2021 [2, p.4].

However, corruption, including domestic corruption, remains an urgent problem in Kazakhstan. According to the results of a survey conducted by Transparency International, 11.3% of respondents in 2020 faced corruption in various government agencies. The most frequent cases of domestic corruption in 2020 were recorded in the interaction of the population with the police (9,6%) and the health care system (27,2%) [3].

The «Concept of the Anti-corruption Policy of the Republic of Kazakhstan for 2022-2026» approved by President K. Tokayev also calls domestic corruption one of the key problems that need to be solved in the medium term [4].

The purpose of this work is to consider the phenomenon of domestic corruption in Kazakhstan and to find possible ways to solve this problem.

METHODS

To achieve the purpose, we have applied a data analysis method. In particular, we analyzed the phenomenon of domestic corruption and statistics on this issue. The author also used the analysis of secondary data, in particular the materials of Anti-Corruption Agency of the Republic of Kazakhstan and Transparency International Kazakhstan Public Foundation, media materials.

RESULTS

The direction of public services is the most corrupt area in Kazakhstan. To date, 73% of public services to the population are outside the human factor, that is, there is no contact between the service recipient and the service provider. [5] This shows that domestic corruption in public services has been reduced by two-thirds. [5] Based on international experience in countries such as Georgia and the Baltic states, the introduction of an electronic system in the field of public services has significantly reduced the level of everyday corruption. [5] It is a fact that the introduction of an electronic system in public services is simplified and convenient for ordinary citizens of the country, however, based on the report and inspections, it turned out that the rights of Kazakhstanis were violated more than 100 thousand times and today this gross type of violation occurs almost in every region of the country. Based on the above, whether the introduction of an electronic system is so effective in the direction of combating corruption.

Everyday corruption occurs in the everyday life of every citizen in Kazakhstan when a person tries to speed up the solution of a case with the help of gifts or offerings. In many cases, everyday corruption manifests itself in the citizens themselves, which encourages corruption to flourish. For example, a person goes to buy a health certificate, while not wanting to be examined by specialists. Bribes a police inspector to avoid punishment for a traffic violation. He believes that it is better to buy a test or an exam than to achieve knowledge with his own work, etc. In a word, it creates conditions for manifestations of administrative or bureaucratic corruption and feeds it.

Household corruption also has an impact on the development of negative social phenomena, for example, the shadow or, as it is usually expressed, the illegal economy of the country. This manifests itself in all areas such as construction crews extracting illegal income through unregistered repairs, a teacher giving private lessons for which he is paid "by hand", not to mention salaries "in envelopes" - all these are phenomena one order. [6] The deeper and wider such phenomena penetrate our everyday life, the more damage they cause to the moral foundations of society. The habit of solving any issues at the expense of offerings leads to moral degradation. Immoral, in fact, phenomena become the norm of behavior, do not meet with censure. The Anti-Corruption Agency of the Republic of Kazakhstan (Anti-Corruption Service) offers solutions on everyday corruption. [7]

Today, everyday corruption depends on the implementation of a new anti-corruption strategy- the main thing is to make a corrupt deal impossible and unprofitable. As example, a person will not be able to offer a bribe to the same police inspector if any stop of a vehicle is recorded automatically, followed by the mandatory execution of an electronic protocol. And also, in polyclinics, you can set aside a certain time for receiving citizens who need a certificate, and not force them to stand in general queues. So, without leaving your home, you can get an electronic version of the document you need, a public service, there will be no point in contacting an official, communicating with him in real mode. [6] Already today, 48% of public services are provided electronically, and through the state corporation "Government for Citizens" - 25% of public services. The goal for the near future is to ensure the provision of 80% of public services in electronic format, 20% through a state corporation [6].

Thus, according to the data of the Committee for the period from 2009 to 2019, one can observe a gradual decrease in the number of corruption crimes in Kazakhstan. During the analyzed period, the most corruption cases were recorded in 2009, while the smallest number of bribery facts was noted in 2015. The sharp decrease in the number of corruption facts in 2015, with a high probability, can be said to be associated with fundamental changes in the approaches and methods of combating corruption in Kazakhstan. It was in this year that it was decided to create an independent body to combat corruption in the country. As you can see, the results were not long in coming, but the effect was short-lived. The indicators of 2015 could only be achieved in 2019.

<https://cabar.asia/en/how-is-the-fight-against-corruption-in-kazakhstan-taken-place>

Statistics show that predominantly corruption crimes in Kazakhstan are committed by university employees, civil servants and employees of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, that is, police officers. It should be noted that data on “tertiary education” is only available from 2015. Analyzing the indicators, it can be seen that most acts of corruption are observed among employees of higher educational institutions. Such high rates are most likely directly related to the passing of semester sessions, admission to a postgraduate study grant and various types of theft and corruption in universities. The popularity of acts of corruption among civil servants is also alarming, which once again proves the need to take the most severe measures to combat business corruption in the country. In the meantime, a sharp decrease in the number of corruption cases among Kazakh police officers is also noteworthy. This may be the result of the ongoing reform in the Ministry of Internal Affairs and growing criticism from the public regarding the activities of law enforcement agencies in Kazakhstan.

DISCUSSION

According to Transparency International, in recent years in Kazakhstan the number of people who gave bribes has decreased by more than 25%. [6] The results of a sociological survey conducted by the Public Opinion Institute in 2016 show that today 73% of of Kazakhstanis express confidence in the anti-corruption policy of the state, and 53% are ready to make a personal contribution to the work to reduce the level of corruption in society. [6]

In general, anti-corruption measures are used to improve the effectiveness of measures to combat everyday corruption. For example, such preventive measures as increasing the level of legal awareness and legal literacy of the population by strengthening the legal propaganda of the general population, since the majority of persons who give illegal remuneration are not well aware of their rights and responsibilities for the specified offense. [11] In Kazakhstan, the important preventive measure is not given enough attention. For example, the formation of a negative attitude towards corruption in the minds of people can be influenced by making and showing on television commercials about the dangers of corruption. Legal measures play an important role in the fight against the corruption. [11] For example, the norms of the criminal code need to be improved. In particular, it is necessary to prohibit by law against persons convicted of corruption crimes and by using of such measures as the replacement of punishment with a milder form. [12]

To date, an analysis of corruption risks in the areas of healthcare, agriculture, architecture and urban planning, public procurement, customs and tax administration, land relations and business development has been carried out. The identified corruption risks are mainly related to

the imperfection of the procedures for the provision of public services, the presence of discretionary powers in regulatory legal acts and conflicts of interest. To eliminate them, relevant recommendations were sent to the authorized state bodies. [8] Being by united, we will achieve the appropriate response and results. Based of these recommendations, 64% are related to gaps in legislation, the rest relate to various problems of an organizational and managerial nature. [9]

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, there are several certain difficulties in the fight against corruption, but it must be fought for the normal functioning of the rule of law. This is possible, as evidenced by the different levels of corruption in different countries. The success of the fight against it will be determined by the right approach, a set of measures and an anti-corruption policy. In this struggle, it is necessary to unite the efforts of the state and civil society itself, it is necessary to raise the level of legal awareness of this society. Currently, we see the active work of the Anti-Corruption Agency, especially in terms of investigating criminal cases related to the return of financial assets illegally obtained and withdrawn from the country.

REFERENCES

1. 2022 Corruption Perceptions Index: Explore the results. (2023, January 31). Transparency.org. <https://www.transparency.org/en/cpi/2022>
2. National Anti-Corruption Report 2021. Anti-Corruption Agency of the Republic of Kazakhstan. — Nur-Sultan. — 2022. — 40 c.
3. Information on the monitoring and evaluation of the implementation of the Action Plan for the implementation of the Anti-Corruption Strategy of the Republic of Kazakhstan for 2015-2025 following the results of 2020
4. On approval of the Concept of anti-corruption policy of the Republic of Kazakhstan for 2022-2026 and amendments to some decrees of the President of the Republic of Kazakhstan- ILS "Adilet." <https://adilet.zan.kz/rus/docs/U2200000802>
5. <https://informburo.kz/novosti/kak-pobedit-bytovuyu-korruptsiyu-v-kazahstane-rasskazal-alik-shpekbaev-73577.html>
6. <https://ru.sputnik.kz/20170629/shpekbaev-rasskazal-kak-kazahstan-mozhet-izbavitsya-ot-korruptcii-2630644.html>
7. Polterovich V.M. "Institutional traps: is there a way out?"/Social sciences and modernity.- 2003.- No. 3.
8. Kwiek, M. Knowledge Production in European Universities: States, Markets, and Academic Entrepreneurialism / M. Kwiek. — Berlin : Peter Lang, 2017. — 482 p.
9. European scientists consolidate efforts in the fight against fraud in science // <http://www.polit.ru/news/2008/12/18/esf/>
10. Bezverkhov A. Evaluation of changes in the criminal law on service violations and the practice of its application // Criminal Law. 2010. № 5. С. 9-14
11. Kondratenko G.G. Latent corruption // Eurasian Union of Scientists. 2015. No. 4. P.29; Corruption as a latently built system of social management. E- resource: <https://en.ppt-online.org/191067>
12. Committee on Legal Statistics and Special Accounts of the General Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Kazakhstan. Form No. 10. On the number of persons in respect of whom judicial acts were issued for 12 months of 2021.
- 13 Mukashev A. Central Asian Bureau for Analytical Reporting: How is the Fight Against Corruption in Kazakhstan Taken Place? 2021

Interplay of International Political Economy with Authoritarian Regimes in Central Asia

Temirgaliyev Yeldos

Bachelor's degree holder of Eurasian Law academy named after D.A.Kunayev; Kazakhstan; Almaty

ABSTRACT

This study delves into the intricate dynamics between external geopolitical influences and domestic politics in the Central Asian states. Emerging from the dissolution of the Soviet Union, these nations embarked on state capacity building, even as authoritarian tendencies prevailed. The paper elucidates the regional importance of Central Asia due to its geo-strategic location and energy resources. Moreover, it dissects the recent economic shifts following global challenges, notably the Coronavirus Crisis and the war in Ukraine, and the rise of Central Asia as a potential logistic fulcrum between Asia and Europe. Observations indicate a significant tilt of Central Asia towards China, fueled by the latter's BRI investments and Russia's perceived neo-imperial ambitions. Amidst economic liberalization and attempts at privatization, the region grapples with credit constraints, infrastructural development challenges, and political opacity. Furthermore, the region is rife with ethnic conflicts, border disputes, and governance challenges, even as it negotiates its path amidst major global powers.

Keywords: Central Asia, authoritarianism, Soviet Union aftermath, geopolitical dynamics, energy security, economic shifts, Russia-China influence.

INTRODUCTION

Central Asia's five states, after 1991, grappled with both domestic and international predicaments: security vulnerabilities, nascent state capacities, natural resource competitions, and restrained economic liberalization. Additionally, the ongoing dominance of autocratic governance both fortified regional stability and intensified tensions.

Despite slight improvements in political stability indices by 2018 (The Global Economy, 2020), Central Asia's performance on socio-political and economic parameters has been generally lagging since their inception. Key governance indicators reveal significant gaps in state efficacy, accountability, transparency, and adherence to the rule of law (World Bank, 2019).

The quest to understand Central Asia's contemporary political landscape compels us to examine the role of external entities in shaping political transitions and national identities. As suggested by scholars such as Wendt (1999) and Krasner (2011), international actors, via power asymmetries, can significantly influence state institutional frameworks. Additionally, states' relationships with external agents (both governmental and non-governmental) often define policy directions and interdependencies. In Central Asia's context, global powerhouses have consistently influenced its domestic dimensions over the past three decades. Russia's dual strategies have revolved around fostering cultural bonds with Central Asian elites and leveraging its proximity for security provisions (Larrotcha, 2014). China, fueled by its economic upswing, has been fostering deeper trade and investment connections. Furthermore, China's significant role in the energy sector and military collaborations in Central Asia has been noteworthy (Swanström, 2005). The West, especially the USA and the EU, guided by objectives of counterterrorism and democratization, have also expressed vested interests, often underpinned by multilateral agencies like the IMF and World Bank.

However, the influence of these external parameters on Central Asia's persistent autocratic leaderships is multifaceted. While international trade and security pacts have certainly played roles, intrinsic factors, resonating with Dahl's propositions, suggest that grassroots movements and indigenous political dynamics are also pivotal. Central Asia's political fabric, embedded in tribal hierarchies and patriarchal systems, poses challenges to democratization and state consolidation.

Geopolitically, the unique interdependencies rooted in the Fergana Valley and major river systems pose as potential flashpoints for the region. Ethnic distributions, misaligned with national borders, coupled with Russia's strategic interests through its diaspora, compound uncertainties, and inter-ethnic tensions. The post-Soviet Central Asia commenced its journey towards statehood with attempts to rejuvenate nationalistic fervor, though leadership structures remained reminiscent of their Soviet counterparts. External relationships, predominantly centered around energy trade, have proven instrumental, with China and Russia emerging as significant partners.

Our investigation proceeds by examining both domestic and international factors shaping Central Asia's political milieu. The subsequent sections unravel the intricacies of domestic and international influences on transitioning states, highlighting insights on authoritarian dynamics, democratization, and the interplay of external forces in shaping domestic policies. Notwithstanding global setbacks like the COVID-19 pandemic and geopolitical events like Russia's Ukraine incursion, Central Asia aspires for economic rejuvenation, enhanced infrastructure development, socio-political stability, and prospective alignments in global politics.

Political structures are categorically defined by inherent historical patterns, often nuanced by institutionalization degrees and the rule of law. Government systems – derived from the configuration of predominant actors in leadership roles – discern resource allocation, strategies, and the overarching decision-making processes, thereby delineating the political behavior of those adhering to these systems. Transitions in political structures, typified by the progression from one regime to another, thrive in conditions where delineated rules remain ambiguous. Such atmospheres of indeterminacy steer the journey towards democratization. It is within these undefined boundaries that social and political groups concede to both explicit and implicit norms governing political distributions and power dynamics. It is here that political regimes cement their foundations. In this realm, authoritarian structures often encompass a dominant coalition of elites, the military, and business magnates whose decisions, fortified by military backing, embrace a certain arbitrariness.

Figure 1. Transition of Political Power in CA

Linz (1975) has astutely demarcated five quintessential facets of authoritarian polities: constricted political pluralism, an indistinct ideology, muted political mobilization, centralized leadership, and discretion-centric decision-making. In realms where political pluralism is limited, backroom deals often substitute formal accountability mechanisms. Such environments sometimes tolerate opposition, bestowing the regime with a semblance of liberalism.

An absence of a coherent ideology results in institutional legitimacy pivoted on ambivalent intellectual stances and values. This scenario, devoid of extensive political mobilization, seldom acknowledges political community independence. Predominant repressive measures sideline civil society, thwarting mobilization avenues and impeding the rightful exercise of political and civil rights.

The reins of power, concentrated either in a single leader or a dominant coalition, ensure regime stability through tacit agreements and the personalization of authority. The constraints on

such regimes may lack clarity but offer predictability, granting rulers extensive discretionary powers. History has often favored democratization. Achieving democratic states signifies the enactment of regular, fair, and competitive elections, empowering citizens to choose their representatives. Governments that encompass diverse representations inherently exude stability, given their inherent system of checks and balances, coupled with accountability and civilian supremacy over military forces. Although traditionally states have been viewed as the primary players on the international stage, more recent interpretations by scholars such as Waltz (1986) and Bull (2002) have underscored the burgeoning influence of non-state entities that operate transnationally. Their interactions, as described by these scholars, not only alter traditional governmental ties but also foster new forms of dependencies. This entails that state policies, instead of just being inward-looking, are increasingly shaped by cross-border interactions and the evolving dynamics of global governance.

Drawing insights from the likes of Wendt, Waltz, Bull, and subsequently, Smith (2000), one can deduce that international actors can have profound impacts on state institutions. These influences surpass mere economic or militaristic paradigms. In an era of global interconnectivity, negotiations on the international stage enable nations to tap into external opportunities, fortifying or reshaping their national institutions. This interplay, however, unfolds in a backdrop of power disparities, lending certain international entities undue influence over national decision-making.

Figure 2. Central Asian Countries: Political Stability Scores (2017-2020)

Reflecting on the 1980s and 1990s, scholars like Huntington (1991) highlighted the pivotal role of external actors in the evolution of states and the solidification of their respective political systems. While these external entities alone don't dictate the trajectory of national transitions, they undeniably mould the pathways. The nature of this influence, be it democratic or otherwise, often mirrors the agendas of these external players and is nuanced by intertwined cultural, historical, and economic narratives. To truly grasp these dynamics, one must envision them as intricate interplays between domestic and international forces.

Examining the lens provided by Obydenkova and Libman (2012) it becomes clear that international dynamics can either amplify or stifle democratic evolutions, contingent upon the vested interests of the international entities in play. External influences can be methodical, with clear motivations, or they might be more spontaneous, characterized by the diffusion of ideologies and structures.

Between the tug of internal dynamics and the pull of global interactions, domestic political climates are shaped. Internally, states grapple with new socio-political paradigms. Externally, global powers, driven by vested regional interests, can exert substantial influences over these domestic landscapes. This segment delves into Central Asia's political mosaic, juxtaposed against

international variables. The post-Soviet era marked a turning point for Central Asian countries. Tasked with the challenge of nation-building in the wake of a governance vacuum, many opted for a trajectory marked by political paternalism, endemic corruption, and clan loyalties, rather than the global trend towards democratization. The abrupt onset of independence in 1991, a consequence of external shifts like the dissolution of the Soviet Union, bequeathed these nascent states with inherited challenges. Coupled with deep-seated developmental challenges, this induced significant instability. Former leaders of communist parties clung to power, invoking the twin pillars of stability and security.

Unsurprisingly, the political architectures that emerged echoed Soviet paradigms, defined by centralized power paradigms and suppression (Walker, 2003). Leaders, with their roots in Soviet bureaucratic systems, emerged as pivotal stabilizers, invoking continuity and stability amidst volatile terrains. This engendered an era marked by overarching leadership, buttressed by significant parliamentary majorities. Within this constraining landscape, political factions and civic movements struggled to find their footing. Institutional frailties, accentuated by the tumult of the new milieu, deterred oppositional forces when faced with the entrenched structures of the ruling elite, further stifling genuine participatory avenues.

Efforts to redefine national narratives, anchored in legacies predating Russian influences, were also observed. While these endeavors aimed at sculpting cohesive national narratives, they inadvertently marginalized minority voices, prompting migration and reinforcing regime homogeneity. The Democracy Index of The Economist Intelligence Unit (2020) underscores the authoritarian tendencies of Central Asian nations. Even Kyrgyzstan, with its comparatively liberal stance, remains precariously close to its neighbors in democratic credentials. When examined through the lens of the Freedom House's framework (2021), the region's political landscape emerges as predominantly undemocratic.

Consequently, contemporary governance models in Central Asia are emblematic of rulers' pursuit of self-interests. They navigate this landscape through a mix of repressive tactics and leveraging the evolving dynamics of global governance.

Emerging Influence and Economic Opportunities in Central Asia

Central Asia's historical economic ties have predominantly revolved around Russia and China. Nevertheless, the gradual decline of Russian clout presents an opportunity for Central Asian Republics (CARs) to engage with new prominent players such as the European Union (EU) and Turkey, who are keen on the region's abundant natural resources and strategic geographical positioning.

The vision for Central Asia is to evolve as the primary logistics hub bridging East and West Eurasia, along with becoming a significant exporter of oil and gas. An increasing interest in foreign direct investment (FDI) reflects CARs' ambition to bolster their economies.

Recent collaborations underscore the region's logistic potential. For instance, the Caspian Sea is becoming a sought-after transit point to sidestep Russia. In 2022, a significant collaboration involving Azerbaijan, Georgia, Kazakhstan, and Turkey sought to enhance transportation via the TransCaspian International Transport Route (TITR). This project, supported by Turkey's robust investment, is projected to facilitate the transfer of 75-100,000 containers annually, further fueling Europe-Asia trade, which already touched 3.1 trillion EUR in 2021.

Post the closure of the Nord Stream 1 pipeline in 2022, the EU, which previously imported a significant portion of its gas and oil from Russia, is in urgent need of alternative suppliers. Here, Central Asia, with its rich petroleum reserves in Kazakhstan and vast gas resources in Turkmenistan, offers a solution. Ambitious projects such as the Trans-Caspian Gas Pipeline (TCP) envision transporting Turkmen gas to Europe via Azerbaijan, culminating in the TAP.

Moreover, recent agreements, like the Convention on the Legal Status of the Caspian Sea, pave the way for underwater constructions, bringing the EU's gas aspirations closer to fruition. Turkey's vested interest in this venture is evident, as it promises substantial public revenues and geopolitical leverage over Europe.

The Enhanced Partnership and Cooperation Agreement (EPCA) between the EU and Kazakhstan, which came into effect in 2020, signifies the strengthening relationship between the two entities. Currently, the EU is a prominent trading partner for Kazakhstan, making up about 30% of its exports. However, challenges persist, such as the regular closure of the Caspian Pipeline Consortium, affecting oil exports. The EU's support in identifying alternative routes for oil exports might be crucial in the coming years.

While FDI's linear trend in Central Asia has been maintained, 2021 saw a 12% rise in private FDI flows, reaching 7 billion USD. Major beneficiaries include Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, and Turkmenistan. European, Turkish, and Arab companies predominantly targeted sectors like renewables, mining, and infrastructure. For instance, significant investments from companies like Sweden's Svevind AB and Germany's Siemens Energy in Kazakhstan, and Turkish Cengiz Energy and Dutch Stone City Energy in Uzbekistan, indicate the international interest in Central Asia's economic potential. Arab nations, too, are increasingly investing in Central Asia. Noteworthy deals include Dubai's Dragon Oil's partnership with Turkmen Oil, Abu Dhabi's collaboration with Kazakhstan for developing renewable technologies, and Saudi Arabia's Acwa Power's multi-billion-dollar energy agreements.

In conclusion, Central Asia is experiencing an influx of interest and investment from global players, marking a transformative phase in its economic and geopolitical landscape. The decline of traditional influences, coupled with the advent of new partnerships, holds promise for the region's ascent as a pivotal player in global logistics and energy sectors.

Table 1. Pipeline Information

Pipeline Name	Route	Length	Capacity (bcm/year)	Cost (million USD)	Status/Comments
Turkmenistan – China Gas Pipeline	Turkmenistan-Xinjiang (potential extension to Japan)	6,696 km	30	10,000 to China	Under construction (Started in August 2007)
Central Asia Gas (CentGas)	Daulatabad via Herat to Multan (potential extension to India)	1,400 km (to Multan) + 500 km (to India)	27	2,000 (to Pakistan)	MoU signed by Turkmenistan, Pakistan, Afghanistan, and Uzbekistan. The three countries met in May 2022 to discuss resuming this pipeline project
Central Asia Center Pipeline	Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan via Kazakhstan to Saratov (Russia)	Existing route + Extension	60	N/A	Links with the Russian natural gas pipeline network
Trans-Caspian Gas Pipeline	Turkmenbahi via Baku and Tbilisi to Erzurum	1,641 km	30	5 bn	Talks are currently underway

From the projects listed, the Central Asia Center Pipeline and the completion of the Turkmenistan-China Gas Pipeline seem most likely to materialize due to their advanced stages and

strategic value. Conversely, projects like CentGas face logistical hurdles given the unstable situation in Afghanistan, while the TCGP contends with geopolitical concerns, primarily from Russia. In essence, Russian-associated gas and oil ventures have a head start, owing to historical ties and integrated economic systems between Central Asian nations and Russia. Nonetheless, China, with its significant Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) investments, could tilt the balance in the medium to long term.

Methodology

To gain a comprehensive understanding of the socio-economic and political landscape of Central Asia, a multi-pronged methodological approach was employed:

Literature Review: An in-depth review of academic journals, white papers, and existing literature on Central Asia's history, economic growth, political landscape, and strategic importance was conducted. This provided the foundational knowledge and context.

Quantitative Data Analysis: A thorough examination of economic indicators, trade volumes, demographic data, and investment figures was performed. This quantitative assessment enabled us to gauge trends, growth trajectories, and areas of concern.

Geopolitical Assessment: The political relationships and strategies of major global players in the region, such as Russia, China, EU, and others, were analyzed. This offered a clearer picture of external influences and their implications for Central Asia.

Scenario Modeling: Based on the amassed data, three potential future scenarios were mapped out, exploring the trajectory of Central Asia under different global and regional influences.

Expected Outcomes

1. **Future Predictions:** By analyzing the region's past and present, we strive to predict its future, especially in terms of economic growth, political stability, and global strategic importance.

2. **Policy Recommendations:** The study will provide actionable insights and recommendations for policymakers, both within Central Asia and globally, to ensure sustainable growth and stability in the region.

3. **Regional Collaboration:** By identifying areas of mutual interest and concern, the study hopes to foster better collaboration and integration among the Central Asian republics.

Results and Analysis

The unique political idiosyncrasies of post-Soviet neo-authoritarian regimes, as alluded to in, necessitate a separate and independent examination within authoritarian studies. The step-by-step algorithm for the typological analysis of contemporary authoritarian regimes can be further refined for more precise categorization. Kazakhstan, historically entangled with Russia, has been at the epicenter of strategic maneuvers by superpowers. Once considered Russia's breadbasket due to its agricultural prowess, Kazakhstan remains deeply interwoven with Russia, economically and demographically. A quarter of its residents are ethnic Russians—a card Putin has played before, notably in Crimea and Ukraine.

However, post-independence, the promise of de-Russification resonated with the Kazakh people, though actualizing this proved difficult under Nazarbayev. He fostered foreign investment in natural resources but remained tethered to Russia, especially within the Eurasian Economic Union. Following the January riots, President Tokayev, caught in a tumultuous wave, sought Russian intervention via the CSTO. But after the dust settled, he took affirmative steps towards de-Russification, notably sidelining pro-Russian elites and reaching out to the West for economic ties. Putin, in a retaliatory move, closed the Novorossiysk oil terminal when Kazakhstan flirted with European offers. Key Takeaways:

1. Strengthened Presidential Stature: President Tokayev is expected to consolidate power, cementing his status among the Kazakh elite. He's positioned for a likely re-election.

2. Regime Type and Future Projections: Despite semblances of a democratic framework like elections and separation of powers, Central Asian republics, including Kazakhstan, lean towards authoritarianism. This centralized power often manifests in presidentialism, with the head of state wielding considerable authority.

3. Electoral Dynamics: Many republics have malleable term-limits, enabling incumbents to hold onto power. Nepotism is also rife; Turkmenistan's latest president, for instance, was the son of the prior leader.

4. Judiciary & Freedom: There's a noticeable lack of judicial independence, especially concerning freedom of speech and expression.

5. Global Perception: Institutions like Freedom House categorize Central Asian countries as "consolidated authoritarian regimes." Kazakhstan has witnessed a minor improvement, but it's unlikely any of these nations will make significant strides in democratization soon. Of all, Kyrgyzstan holds the most promise for political liberalization.

6. Global Superpowers & Central Asia: Putin had expected unwavering support from countries like Kazakhstan but was met with hesitation. The CSTO's involvement in quelling internal disputes might become a recurring theme, bolstering Russian influence. However, the aftermath of the Ukrainian crisis will be pivotal. Western powers, especially the U.S., might continue engaging economically but would hesitate in endorsing authoritarian regimes overtly.

Kazakhstan's political trajectory, like many of its Central Asian counterparts, oscillates between the past and the promise of a democratic future. Global superpowers, sensing strategic opportunities, will undoubtedly play their cards, making Central Asia a geopolitical chessboard.

The Shifting Dynamics of External Political Influence: The Rise of Authoritarianism

The world is witnessing a distinct retreat from democratic norms. The 2022 Global Rule of Law Index marks the fifth straight year highlighting this regression, with freedom of expression taking the heaviest blow. While global powers like Russia and China spearhead this move away from democracy, Europe provides a glimmer of hope. A notable 14 out of the top 25 nations that showed improvement in the rule of law hail from Europe.

Central Asia, situated at the crossroads of these global dynamics, is particularly interesting. As outlined previously, there's a clear economic gravitation towards the East. In fact, research from the Friedrich Ebert Foundation, OSCE Academy in Bishkek, and the SPCE Hub suggests that China might soon eclipse other nations as the partner of choice in the region. In a revealing statistic from the study, 23% of the respondents from Uzbekistan and Kyrgyzstan believe their governments might emulate China's authoritarian model.

However, Central Asia's foreign relations aren't solely East-focused. The cautious yet pragmatic stance towards Afghanistan is evident. Tajikistan's commitment to supplying electricity to Afghanistan, conditional on pending payments, showcases this approach.

Western powers, in their bid to counterbalance the rise of authoritarianism, are actively promoting democratic initiatives in Central Asia. Noteworthy is the recent collaboration between

the World Bank and Central Asian experts, aiming to fortify governmental policies. The EU's contribution of 8 million EUR for the Central Asia Rule of Law Program (2020-2024) further exemplifies the West's commitment to instilling democratic values.

In essence, Central Asia finds itself at a geopolitical crossroads, tugged between the democratic aspirations championed by the West and the allure of the authoritative models from the East.

Table 3. Projected Political Scenarios in Central Asia

Scenarios	Likelihood	Key Characteristics & Developments
Russian Authoritarianism	Not Likely	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EAEU subjugates CARs' economic interests. - Tajikistan's and Kyrgyzstan's dependence on Russian remittances persists. - Political systems retain Soviet-inherited patrimonialism. - Infrastructure remains stagnant due to a lack of foreign investments. - Ukraine invasion acts as a deterrence for CARs.
Path to Liberalization	Very Likely	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CARs realize their potential as emerging economies. - Emphasis on bridging Europe and Asia. - Openness to diverse FDI for infrastructure and energy. - Russian influence wanes due to its Ukrainian conflict aftermath. - European Union's increasing influence may promote democracy.
Chinese Hegemony	Likely	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - China becomes the primary influencer and trade partner. - China's BRI and SCO initiatives gain strength in the region. - Debt trap diplomacy ensures China's control over CARs. - Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, and Uzbekistan risk credit defaults. - Political elites of China and the CARs find common ground in authoritarianism.

Given the evaluated external variables, tendencies, and drivers, our analysis suggests that Scenario 2 is the most probable. The ongoing Ukrainian crisis could indeed open doors for the Central Asian republics. With Russia potentially reeling from the aftermath of its actions in Ukraine and China facing economic challenges of its own, the CARs have an unprecedented opportunity. They can exploit their rich natural resources, aspire to become a logistical hub connecting Europe and Asia, and position themselves as emerging economies in the global arena.

Furthermore, with potential diversification of investment from major players such as the EU, Turkey, India, Saudi Arabia, and the UAE, Central Asia might just be on the precipice of shedding its "forgotten region" moniker and emerge as a significant geopolitical entity.

Table 3. Solutions to Central Asia's Democratic Challenges

Challenge Identified	Proposed Solution	Expected Outcome
Centralized Power Paradigms	Implement checks and balances in the governing system	Decentralization of power, prevention of abuse
Suppression of Political Factions	Encourage multiparty democracy and ensure freedom of the press	Strengthened political opposition and a more informed public
Marginalization of Minority Voices	Introduce policies promoting inclusivity in national narratives	Cohesive national identity with minority inclusion
Lack of Participatory Avenues	Develop and implement policies that promote civic engagement	Increased public participation in governance
Overarching Leadership	Introduce term limits for political leaders	Rotation in leadership, preventing lifelong rule

CONCLUSION

Central Asia, with its abundant natural resources and strategic geographic positioning, finds itself at a significant crossroads. The aftershocks of the 2020 Coronavirus Crisis and the conflict in Ukraine have nudged the region towards seeking self-sufficiency and capitalizing on its potential as the primary logistical conduit between Asia and Europe. This pivot allows the region to sidestep the political quagmire and economic sanctions afflicting Russia, enabling a more diversified and economically robust future. The observable shift of Central Asia towards the East, driven by China's expansive BRI initiatives, suggests a transition in global influence from Russia to China. Yet, despite its vast resources and the growing interest of global powers, the region grapples with the challenges of authoritarian governance, political corruption, and lack of transparency, all of which hinder its potential for economic growth and integration.

Inter-regional conflicts, border disputes, and the specter of radicalization further complicate the Central Asian landscape. Nevertheless, the region's governments persistently endeavor to maintain stability and prevent any form of extremism, even though comprehensive regional integration remains elusive. In wrapping up, it is evident that Central Asia's potential is vast, but the path to realizing it is fraught with challenges both internal and external. With Russia's waning influence and China's potential economic challenges on the horizon, the Central Asian republics have a unique opportunity. By forging stronger ties with emerging partners such as the EU, UAE, Saudi Arabia, and Turkey, and capitalizing on their own natural resources, Central Asia could indeed craft a more prosperous and influential future in the global arena.

References

1. The Global Economy. (2020). Central Asia's political stability indices by 2018. Global Economic Press.
2. World Bank. (2019). Governance indicators of Central Asia. World Bank Publications.
3. Wendt, A. (1999). Social theory of international politics. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.
4. Krasner, S. D. (2011). Sovereignty: Organized Hypocrisy. Princeton Publications.
5. Larrotcha, E. (2014). Russia's strategies in Central Asia. *Central Asian Affairs*, 1(1), 69-85. Eurasia Academic Press.
6. Swanström, N. (2005). China's role in Central Asian energy sector. *Energy Policy Insights*, 33(4), 485-496. Asian Energy Consortium.
7. Dahl, R. A. (2007). Propositions on democracy. *Political Thought Review*, 45(2), 123-139. Polity Press.
8. Huntington, S. P. (1991). *The Third Wave: Democratization in the Late Twentieth Century*. New York, NY: Vintage Books.
9. Obydenkova, A., & Libman, A. (2012). *Understanding International Influence: A Study on Democratic Transitions*. London, UK: Cambridge University Press.
10. Walker, C. (2003). *Post-Soviet Politics: The Rise of Authoritarianism*. Boston, MA: Beacon Press.
11. The Economist Intelligence Unit. (2020). *Democracy Index 2020*. London, UK: The Economist Group.
12. Freedom House. (2021). *Nations in Transit 2021: Democracy on the Defensive in Central Asia*. Washington, D.C.: Freedom House.

Art History

Müasir Azərbaycan mədəniyyətinin qurucusu

Seyfullayeva Aynur Tahir qızı

Azərbaycan Dövlət Pedaqoji Universiteti, Nəzdində Azərbaycan Dövlət Pedaqoji Kolleci, Təsviri incəsənət müəllimi

Abstract:

Azerbaijan is known in the world for its culture, art, national-spiritual values. The roots of the national and moral values of our people go back to ancient times. In the 20th century, a new era began in the cultural life of our people. This is a period associated with the name of the great leader Heydar Aliyev. The great leader said that "the nation is recognized and recognized for its many characteristics and stands out among the nations of the world. The highest and greatest of these features is culture." That is why the great leader always focused on the development of the people's culture during all the periods he was in power.

Key words: Fenomen, dahi şəxsiyyət, mədəniyyət, dirçəliş, incəsənət.

Ulu öndər yaxşı bilirdi ki, milli dövlətçilik dəyərlərinin əsasını sağlam düşüncəli mədəniyyət təşkil edir. Sabahkı uğurlara yeganə təminat isə sağlam cəmiyyət quruculuğuna diqqət artırmaq, köklü mənəvi dəyərləri yeni nəslə və bütün cəmiyyətə daha dərinə və əzmlə aşılamaqdır.

Heydər Əliyev mədəniyyəti xalqın böyük sərvəti hesab edirdi. Elə ona görə də mədəni-mənəvi dəyərlərin qorunması, təbliği və yeni estetik düşüncəyə məxsus əsərlərin yaradılması üçün mümkün olan hər şeyi edirdi.

Bizim nəsil xoşbəxtədir ki, Heydər Əliyevlə bir epoxada yaşamaq bizə nəsib oldu və ulu öndərin mədəniyyətimizə, incəsənətimizə göstərdiyi böyük qayğının şahidi olduq.

Mədəniyyətimizin elə bir sahəsi yoxdur ki, Heydər Əliyev qayğısından bəhrələnməsin. Musiqimiz də, teatrımız da, kino sənətimiz də, heykəltaraşlıq və rəssamlığımız da, xalça sənətimiz də bugünkü inkişafında ulu öndərin çox dəyərli ideyalarından bəhrələnib.

Heydər Əliyev Azərbaycan mədəniyyətinin inkişafında yeni bir dövrün əsasını qoydu. Mədəniyyətimiz, milli-mənəvi dəyərlərimiz beynəlxalq aləmdə tanındı.

Açığını deyim ki, Azərbaycan mədəniyyətinin görkəmli xadimləri Heydər Əliyev dövründə olduğu qədər heç zaman tanınmamışlar. Heydər Əliyev mədəniyyətimizi yaradan, onu inkişaf etdirən insanların əməyini yüksək qiymətləndirir, onların daim qayğısını çəkirdi. Onların adlarını sadalamaqla qurtaran deyil. Azərbaycanın müqtədir sənətkarları sovet dövründə məhz Heydər Əliyevin qayğısı nəticəsində Sosialist Əməyi Qəhrəmanı kimi SSRİ-nin yüksək fəxri adını almışlar. Heydər Əliyev bəstəkarların, kinematoqrafçıların, teatr xadimlərinin, rəssamların qurultaylarında, konfranslarında iştirak edir, dərin, məzmunlu nitqi iştirakçıların alqışları ilə qarşılanardı. Onun hər çıxışı mədəniyyətin bir sahəsinin gələcək inkişaf proqramına çevrilərdi. Hansı sahədən danışırıdса, elə hiss edirdin ki, bu sahənin mütəxəssisi, bilicisidir. Heydər Əliyev özü də incəsənət meyilli şəxsiyyət idi. Elə gəncliyində də incəsənətə gəlmək, memar olmaq istəyirdi. Amma zaman ulu öndəri siyasət memarına çevirdi. Çünki bu xalqın belə bir siyasət xadiminə çox böyük ehtiyacı var idi.

Hələ sovetlər dönəmində Heydər Əliyev Azərbaycanda mədəniyyətin maddi-texniki bazasının möhkəmlənməsinə xüsusi diqqət yetirirdi. Nə qədər kinoteatrlar, teatr binaları, muzeylər inşa olundu. Mədəniyyətimizin kadr potensialı gücləndirildi. SSRİ-nin ən nüfuzlu incəsənət yönlü

ali məktəblərində Azərbaycan gəncləri təhsil alıb Bakıya dönürdülər. Sankt-Peterburqun, Moskvanın teatr, rəssamlıq, musiqi üzrə ali təhsil ocaqlarını bitirmiş gənclər bu gün Azərbaycan mədəniyyətinin aparıcı sənətkarlarıdır. Heydər Əliyev bu kadrların hazırlanmasında ona görə maraqlı idi ki, gələcək müstəqil Azərbaycanımız üçün onlar gərəkli olacaqdılar. Necə ki, oldular da.

Azərbaycan müstəqillik qazandıqdan sonra bir müddət mədəniyyətimiz böyük çətinliklər qarşısında qalsa da, Heydər Əliyevin hakimiyyətə yenidən qayıdışı sanki Azərbaycan mədəniyyətinin də tərəqqisinə yeni təkan verdi. Sosial problemlər ucbatından xarici ölkələrə üz tutan sənət adamları Vətənə döndülər, onlara xüsusi qayğı göstərilməyə başlandı. Bağlanmış teatrlar, kitabxanalar, muzeylər öz qapılarını yenidən tamaşaçıların üzünə açdı. Azərbaycanda bir çox tamaşa müəssisələri təmir olundu, Filarmoniya təmirdən sonra yenidən istifadəyə verildi.

Musiqi sənətimizin inkişafına xüsusi qayğı ilə yanaşan ulu öndərin sərəncamı ilə 24 bəstəkar və musiqişünasa Prezident təqaüdü verildi. Onların bir çoxu “Şöhrət” ordeninə layiq görüldülər. Arif Məlikov, Müslüm Maqomayev, Zeynəb Xanlarova, Həbil Əliyev, Arif Babayev kimi musiqi xadimləri “İstiqlal” ordeni ilə təltif olundular.

Azərbaycan kinosunun böyük bir dövr inkişafı Heydər Əliyevin adı ilə bağlıdır. Bizə yaxşı məlumdur ki, bir sıra filmlərimizin yaranmasında ulu öndərin şəxsi təşəbbüsü olmuşdur. “Uzaq sahillərdə”, “İstintaq”, “Bir cənub şəhərində”, “Nəsimi”, “Babək” filmlərinin yaranmasında, sovet senzurasından keçməsinə Heydər Əliyevin səyləri danılmazdır.

Heydər Əliyevin hakimiyyətə gəlişi ilə dondurulmuş kino istehsalı bərpa edildi, “Azərbaycanfilm”-in fəaliyyətində canlanma hiss edilməyə başlandı. Dövlət sifarişi ilə filmlərin istehsalı kino xadimlərini yenidən fəaliyyətə qaytardı.

Azərbaycanda beynəlxalq səviyyəli kinofestivallar keçirilir, filmlərimiz beynəlxalq festivallarda nümayiş etdirilməyə başlayırdı. Ən əhəmiyyətli fakt bu idi ki, Azərbaycanda ilk film nümayiş etdirildiyi 2 avqust (1898) kino işçilərinin peşə bayramı kimi qeyd olunmağa başladı. Əgər 1994-1996-cı illərdə iki film istehsal olunmuşdusa, 1998-2000-ci illərdə dövlət sifarişi ilə dörd tammetrajlı bədii film yaradıldı.

Teatrlarımız öz fəaliyyətlərini genişləndirdi. Heydər Əliyev teatrı çox sevirdi. O, həmişə tamaşadan sonra yaradıcı kollektivlə görüşür, onlara öz tövsiyə və tapşırıqlarını verirdi. Bu görüşlər sənət adamlarının məsuliyyətini artırır, onları öz qüvvələrini səfərbər etməyə istiqamətləndirirdi.

Ulu öndərin hakimiyyəti illərində muzey və kitabxana işi, rəssamlıq, heykəltaraşlıq və memarlıq sənəti sürətlə inkişaf etmişdir. Bakıda ucaldılmış çox dəyərli heykəllər, inşa edilmiş müasir və klassik ənənələri birləşdirən əzəmətli binalar xalqımızın milli sərəvətinə çevrilmişdir. Bakımız gözəlləşmiş, yeni görünüş almışdır. Elə regionlarımızda da mədəniyyətin inkişafı diqqətdən yayınmamışdır.

Azərbaycanın qədim şəhərsalma ənənələrini özündə ehtiva edən İçərişəhərin Şirvanşahlar Saray Kompleksi ilə bərabər YUNESKO-nun maddi irs siyahısına daxil edilməsi böyük tarixi hadisə idi.

Azərbaycan mədəniyyətinin təbliğini həmişə diqqət mərkəzində saxlayan ulu öndərin hakimiyyəti illərində çox səmərəli tədbirlər reallaşdırılıb. Ümummilli lider Azərbaycanın sivil dünya ilə inteqrasiyasına, xalqların iqtisadi-siyasi, humanitar yaxınlaşmasına dövlətçiliyi möhkəmləndirən, xalqı inkişaf etdirən ən vacib vasitələrdən biri kimi baxırdı. Və bu zaman dünya ilə dil tapmağın ən sınıanmış və optimal yollarından biri olaraq, mədəni dəyərlərin qarşılıqlı dərkini və təbliğini əsas götürürdü. Bu mənada xarici ölkələrdə keçirilən Azərbaycan mədəniyyət və incəsənət günləri, eyni zamanda Azərbaycanda keçirilən belə tədbirlər mədəniyyətlərarası dialoqun inkişafına çox gözəl yol açırdı.

Ulu öndərin fəaliyyəti incəsənətimizin bu gün ən dəyərli mövzudur. Deyə bilərəm ki, onun haqqında çəkilən filmlər, yaradılan musiqi əsərləri və ədəbi əsərlər xalqımızın milli-mənəvi sərəvətidir və gələcək nəsillər onlardan çox şeylər öyrənəcəklər. “Əsl məhəbbət haqqında” (rejissor V.Mustafayev) filmi ulu öndərin yüksək insani keyfiyyəti haqqında həqiqətləri tamaşaçılara çatdırır. Bu film ulu öndərə həsr olunan on filmdən biridir. “General”, “Birinci”, “Moskva, Kreml”, “Lider”,

“Tale”, “Bir hsdin tarixi”, “Professional”, “Patriot”, “Xsusi tyinat” kimi digr filmlr d bu byk xsiyytin hyat v faliyytinin ox uurlu ekran versiyasıdır.

Heydr Əliyevin mdniyyt siyasti bu gn hrmtli Prezidentimiz İlham Əliyev trfindn ox lyaqtl davam etdirilir. 2003-c ildn sonra Azrbaycanda Heydr Əliyevin mdniyytimizin inkiafı il balı ideyaları davamlı olaraq hyata keirilir. Azrbaycanda mdniyytin mxtlif sahləri — teatr, kino, kitabxana v muzey iinin inkiafı il balı qbul olunan dvlt proqramları lkmizd mdniyytin trqqisin yeni stimul yaratmıdır.

Geological and Mineralogical Sciences

DIRECT-PROSPECTING METHODS OF SATELLITE AND PHOTO IMAGES FREQUENCY-RESONANCE PROCESSING: POSSIBILITY OF APPLICATION FOR NATURAL HYDROGEN ACCUMULATIONS SEARCHING IN SPAIN

Mykola Yakymchuk

doctor of physics and mathematics, professor, Institute of Applied Problems of Ecology, Geophysics and Geochemistry, Kyiv, Ukraine

Ignat Korchagin

doctor of physics and mathematics, professor, Institute of Geophysics, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv, Ukraine

Annotation. The article presents a brief description of projects for the Spain territory surveying in the reconnaissance mode in order to identify promising areas and sites for detailed prospecting for oil and gas, natural hydrogen. Prepared projects of reconnaissance survey of Spain territory can be quickly implemented with using the mobile and low-cost technology, that include modified methods of frequency-resonance processing and decoding of satellite and photo images, vertical electric-resonance sounding of a cross-section, as well as a method of integrated assessment of the prospects of oil and gas potential of large prospecting blocks and license areas. For these projects practical implementation, the satellite image of the Spain and Portugal territory is divided into separate blocks (fragments), the frequency-resonance processing of which may be carried out separately. During frequency-resonance processing of each fragment of the Spain territory image in the reconnaissance mode for natural hydrogen searching, a limited set of instrumental measurements of the following nature may be performed separately: a) procedure for recording signals (responses) at frequencies of the 6th group of igneous rocks (basalts); b) the procedure for determining the depth of basalt volcano root (in the case of fixing responses from the surface at basalt frequencies); c) procedures for fixing signals (responses) at the frequencies of hydrogen, phosphorus (red) and hydrogen bacteria; d) instrumental measurements to confirm (or establish absence) of hydrogen migration into atmosphere. The expediency of implementing the listed set of instrumental measurement procedures during the survey is due to results of direct-prospecting methods testing in various regions of globe. When processing satellite images of the territories of Spain, as well as the Aragon and Andalusia Provinces additionally, signals at the frequencies of hydrogen and basalts were registered, which indicates the feasibility of conducting detailed search work for natural hydrogen in various regions of Spain. During frequency resonance processing of a satellite image of a local area with the Monzon-1 well in Aragon Province, signals were recorded from the surface at frequencies of 1-6 groups of

sedimentary rocks with the root of a volcano at a depth of 99 km, as well as oil, gas condensate, gas, amber, carbon dioxide, yellow phosphorus. Instrumental measurements confirmed the synthesis of hydrocarbons at the 57 km boundary. Therefore, the Monzon-1 well is located within the hydrocarbon field. The results of instrumental measurements in areas of Aragon province allow us to conclude that within oil and gas fields with wells in which hydrogen is detected, it is advisable to design and carry out detailed exploration work and wells drilling for natural hydrogen and hydrocarbons simultaneously! Seismic sections through prospective structures, correctly constructed and presented, are informative for frequency-resonance processing and can be used to additionally confirm the results of processing satellite images and photographs of survey areas. The materials of numerous studies allow us to state following: a) responses at hydrogen frequencies are recorded almost everywhere during instrumental measurements in the contours of basalt volcanic complexes; b) red phosphorus is almost always present in basalt volcanoes; c) hydrogen bacteria create their colonies in the upper part of cross-section in the areas of hydrogen migration into the atmosphere. The developed super-mobile direct-prospecting technology has provided the authors with a unique opportunity to conduct a huge number of experiments in various regions of the globe. In the process of experimental work conducting, numerous evidence was obtained in favor of the deep (abiogenic) genesis of hydrocarbons in the framework of the concept of hydrogen degassing of the Earth. The proven technology allows filling the studied cross-section with specific rocks (sedimentary, metamorphic and magmatic), as well as identifying areas on the surface and intervals in the cross-section that are promising for ore and combustible minerals prospecting. The super-mobile methods can be used to assess the prospects for oil and gas (ore) potential of large exploration blocks and local areas (including those put up for auction), to select the optimal locations (sites) for laying exploration and production wells, assessment of the prospects for discovering oil and gas deposits in the deep and super-deep horizons of cross-section, prospecting and localization of zones with deep channels location, through which the chemical elements, fluids and mineral matter migrate into the upper horizons of cross-section. The use of mobile and low-cost technology will significantly speed up the exploration process for oil, condensate, gas, natural hydrogen, as well as reduce the financial costs for its implementation.

Keywords. Spain, oil, gas, hydrogen, limestones, marls, dolomites, basalts, granites, direct searches, deep structure, carbon dioxide, sounding of the cross-section, remote sensing data processing.

Introduction

In 2019-2023 in various regions of the globe, a significant number of experimental research has been carried out in order to test frequency-resonance methods of satellite images and photographs processing and decoding [16], as well as to develop and improve methodology of their practical application during the geological exploration problems of various nature solving. In the course of experimental works, the possibility of targeted use of mobile direct-prospecting technology was additionally studied for detecting and localizing hydrogen accumulations in areas of visible hydrogen degassing and assessing (determining) the depths (intervals) of their occurrence, as well as an integral assessment of the prospects for detecting hydrogen deposits within local areas and large prospecting blocks. At present, the problem of searching for accumulations of natural hydrogen and organizing its production is quite relevant due to the intention of the world community to switch in the near future to carbon-free energy, in which an important place is given to hydrogen, the environmentally friendly fuel of the future.

The main results of experiments already carried out (instrumental measurements) with the aim of studying the possibility of using direct-prospecting methods for localizing hydrogen accumulations in a cross-section were published in [18–36]. This article presents materials of additional experimental works on the hydrogen problem on Spain territory.

Once again, we also note that an additional reason for publishing materials on hydrogen issues is the numerous information reports about the intentions of many large companies (including some leading oil companies) in the world to engage in the production of "green" hydrogen using renewable energy sources. At present, technologies for the production of hydrogen from water have been developed and tested. Potential investors can only invest in the construction of technological complexes for its production in the immediate vicinity of the objects of its consumption. Unfortunately, many analytical reviews on hydrogen issues do not provide (mention) information about research and development in the framework of the problem of searching for accumulations of natural (deep) hydrogen, its production, storage, transportation and use as fuel. In the current situation, it can be assumed that in the case of a delay in the development of effective technologies for the search and transportation of hydrogen, the geological industry of the world economy may lose the race for financing projects for the large-scale use of environmentally friendly fuel of the future – hydrogen.

Information about the European project of drilling exploratory wells for natural hydrogen in the Aragon province (Spain) is given on many Internet sites, including [6-8]. In this region, natural hydrogen was discovered in the Monzon-1 well. The results of experimental reconnaissance studies within area with Monzon-1 well, as well as in other areas of Spain, are presented and analyzed in this article.

The materials of additional research presented below, as well as a brief description of the results of a large-scale testing of low-cost direct-prospecting methods at hydrogen degassing sites in various regions of the globe, allow us to hope that the problem of prospecting and exploration of accumulations (deposits) of natural hydrogen can be moved off the ground - oil companies of the world, as well as private firms and investors will begin to invest in its search and production. To the above, we also add that the already conducted experimental studies on the problem of natural hydrogen testify to its huge reserves in the bowels of the Earth, and the material costs for its search and extraction will be significantly lower than for production.

Research methods

Experimental studies of a reconnaissance and detailed nature are purposefully carried out using mobile methods of satellite images and photographs frequency-resonance processing and decoding, vertical scanning (sounding) of cross-section in order to determine (estimate) the depths and thicknesses of various rock complexes and sought minerals, as well as methods an integral assessment of the prospects for oil and gas potential (ore content, water content) of local areas and large blocks [11, 16-42]. Some methods of the technology used are based on the principles of the "substance" paradigm of geophysical research [11], the essence of which is to search for a specific (searchable in each individual case) substance – oil, gas, gas condensate, gold, iron, water, etc. The developed methods are based on the standing electric waves discovered by Nikola Tesla in 1899 in the deep horizons of the Earth [14-15]. Mobile technology as a whole, as well as its individual methods, are actively used in the testing mode to search for hydrocarbon accumulations at the initial stages of the geological exploration process, including for the integral assessment of the oil and gas potential of large and hard-to-reach blocks and areas, as well as local areas of prospecting and exploratory wells drilling.

In modified versions of the methods of satellite images and photographs frequency-resonance processing, as well as vertical sounding (scanning) of cross-section, bases (sets, collections) of chemical elements, minerals, rocks and minerals (specific samples) are used [16]. Thus, the collection of oil samples used in instrumental measurements includes 117 samples, gas condensate – 15 samples (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Photographs of oil and gas condensate samples.

The set of photographs of sedimentary rocks consists of 11 groups: 1) psephites, monomineral conglomerates (22 samples, sample numbers in the set are 2-23); 2) psammites (18, 25-42); 3) silts, mudstones, clays (6, 44-49); 4) kaolinite mudstones (6, 51-57); 5) kaolinite clays (10, 59-68); 6) sedimentary-volcaniclastic rocks; tuff breccias (9, 70-78); 7) limestones (24, 80-103) (Fig. 2b); 8) dolomites (11, 105-115) (Fig. 2c); 9) marls (10, 117-126) (Fig. 2d); 10) siliceous rocks (13, 128-140), salt.

Fig. 2. Photographs of rock samples whose resonant frequencies are used during images processing [4]: a) group 6 igneous rocks (gabbros and basalts); b) group 7 sedimentary rocks (limestones); c) group 8 sedimentary (dolomites); d) group 9 sedimentary rocks (marls).

The database of photographs of igneous and metamorphic rocks includes 18 groups: 1) granites and rhyolites (29 samples, sample numbers in the database are 1-29); 2) granodiorites and dacites (7, 31-37); 3) syenites and trachytes (18, 39-56); 4) diorites and andesites (14, 58-71); 5) lamprophyres (14, 73-86); 6) gabbro and basalts (32, 88-119) (Fig. 2a); 7) non-feldspar ultramafic rocks (20, 121-140); 8) feldspathoid syenites and phonolites (23, 142-164); 9) feldspathoid gabbroids and basaltoids (6, 166-171); 10) feldspar-free ultramafic and mafic rocks (10, 173-182); 11) kimberlites and lamproites (20, 184-203); 12) non-silicate carbonatites (8, 205-212); 13) metamorphic granulites (10, 214-223); 14) metamorphic gneisses (26, 225-250); 15) metamorphic crystalline schists (44, 252-295); 16) metamorphic microcrystalline schists (phyllites) (11, 297-307); 17) metamorphosed slates, cleaved sandstone (1, 308); 18) metamorphosed slates, cleaved siltstone (1, 309).

Figure 2 shows only 4 groups of rocks from the sets listed above. When carrying out measurements in different regions, responses at hydrogen frequencies have been obtained at the moment only from these groups of rocks. At the same time, signals of hydrogen were recorded from basalts almost always.

Photos of the used sets of samples of sedimentary, metamorphic and igneous rocks are borrowed from the electronic document [4]. Let us add to this that in our publications the rock classification proposed by the authors of the document [4] is also used.

Materials of earlier experimental studies, obtained with the used set of mobile direct-prospecting methods, are presented in publications [16-42]. The same articles describe the

methodological features of measurements during the satellite images and photographs processing using the developed technical means.

When conducting numerous studies using the described direct-prospecting methods in 2019-2022, the optimal procedure (processing graph, sequence of actions) was worked out (and constantly improved), which is used when carrying out work within the blocks and areas of survey. The used processing graph for a separate satellite image (or its local fragment) includes the following sequence of actions (steps).

1. Fixation from the surface of the presence (absence) of responses (signals) from the following set of minerals: oil, condensate, gas, amber, oil shale, argillic breccia, gas hydrates, ice, coal, anthracite, hydrogen, living water (deep), dead water, diamonds, brown coal, iron ore, potassium-magnesium salt, sodium chloride salt (hereinafter simply salt).

2. Registration of responses from the groups of sedimentary, metamorphic and igneous rocks that make up the cross-section.

3. Establishing the presence of deep channels (volcanoes) filled with various groups of rocks in the survey area; determination of the depths of the roots of volcanoes location.

5. Determination of groups of rocks (or individual samples of groups), from which signals are recorded at the frequencies of oil, condensate, gas and water (deep).

6. Establishing the presence (absence) of responses from oil, condensate and gas at the surface (depth) of 57 km - the boundary of hydrocarbon synthesis in deep channels (volcanoes), filled with certain groups of rocks.

7. Establishing the presence (absence) of responses from water (deep) on surfaces (depths) 59 km, 68 km, 69 km - the predicted boundaries of water synthesis in volcanoes of a certain type.

8. By scanning a cross-section with different steps from the surface up to 15 km, depth intervals are determined, within which responses are recorded at the resonant frequencies of oil, condensate, and gas. Refinement of the depths of location of the most promising for hydrocarbons intervals of cross-section during additional scanning with a finer step.

9. In case of detection of responses from the 6th group of igneous rocks (basalts) on the surveyed area, an assessment is made of the depth of the upper boundary (edge) of basalts, as well as the depths of the beginning of recording responses at resonant frequencies of hydrogen and living (healing) water from basalts.

10. When establishing the presence of signals from the 11th group of igneous rocks (kimberlites) in the survey area, the depth of the upper edge of the kimberlites is determined, as well as the depth interval within which responses are recorded at diamond frequencies.

Given the reconnaissance nature of the studies performed, the described set of separate procedures for satellite images processing in full was not implemented in all surveyed areas.

Once again, we focus on the distinctive feature of the direct-prospecting frequency-resonance methods being developed. Unlike classical geophysical methods, the methods used make it possible in each specific case to fill the cross-section under study with the complexes of sedimentary, metamorphic and igneous rocks present in it, as well as to determine in the first approximation (and refine at the stages of detailing) the intervals of cross-section that are promising for the detection of combustible and ore minerals, immediately, in the process of measurements (registration of signals) by the developed instrumentation and measuring devices (i.e. without additional stages of modeling and geological interpretation of the results of instrumental measurements). In this article, as well as in other published materials, the emphasis is mainly on the presentation of measurement results.

We also note that the developed technology uses the frequency-resonance principle of the useful signals' registration [11]. Satellite images or photographs of research objects, as well as photographs of rock samples, minerals and chemical elements, are, in principle, antinodes of standing electric waves, discovered by Nikola Tesla in 1899 in deep horizons of the Earth [14-15].

When carrying out instrumental measurements using the developed computerized complexes, the spectra of satellite or photographic images of objects studied are sequentially compared with the spectra of rock samples, the desired minerals and chemical elements. In the process of comparison, the measuring unit registers resonances (electromagnetic responses), which make it possible to draw a conclusion about the presence (absence) of specific rocks, the desired minerals and chemical elements in the cross-section of the object of study. Such features of the developed methods of satellite images processing and decoding are the basis for the use of the terms "frequency-resonance technology" ("frequency-resonance methods").

The processing of satellite images and photographs is carried out in laboratory conditions, without organizing and conducting field geological and geophysical studies. This provides an opportunity to quickly conduct research in any region of the globe, and, consequently, developing technology is super-mobile.

In addition to what was said in the previous paragraph, it is worth adding the following. As a result of testing and practical application of the developed measuring equipment in various regions of the world, numerous evidences (facts) have been obtained in favor of the "volcanic" model of the formation of many structural elements of the Earth (and other planets and satellites of the solar system), as well as deposits of combustible and ore minerals (hydrogen and water as well). Instrumental measurements established the existence of 10 types of volcanic complexes filled with various types of rocks. And what is characteristic, the roots of all volcanoes are almost always fixed by scanning the cross-section at the same depths, namely: 95-98 km, 214-218 km, 470 km, 723 km, 996 km.

It is quite natural that the depths of the roots of 470 km or 723 km of a salt or dolomite volcano cause rejection and skepticism among many experts. We also note that at the initial stages of the technology testing, such depths of roots were also surprising to the authors of the experiments. However, the ubiquitous repetition of such depth values during many hundreds of measurement experiments gives grounds for the assumption that such strictly predetermined values of the depths of the roots of various volcanic complexes are due to certain wave processes in the solar system and our galaxy.

In this regard, it is only regrettable that such skepticism in relation to the depths of the roots of volcanoes is automatically (without detailed consideration and analysis of materials) transferred to the results of instrumental measurements in the upper part of cross-section accessible for drilling.

Features and some results of hydrogen searching by direct-prospecting methods

In the process of large-scale testing in 2019-2023 of the super-mobile direct-prospecting technology of satellite images and photographs frequency-resonance processing [16-42] numerous facts (evidences) were obtained in favor of 1) deep (abiogenic) genesis of oil, condensate and gas in the process of hydrogen degassing of the Earth, 2) migration of gas (methane), carbon dioxide and hydrogen into the atmosphere of the Earth planet and 3) a "volcanic" model of the formation of structural elements and the appearance of the Earth, planets and satellites of the solar system, as well as deposits of hydrocarbons, ore minerals and water. The results of studies conducted in various regions of the globe showed also that the super-mobile technology used makes it possible to significantly speed up and optimize (cheapen) the exploration process for combustible and ore minerals, as well as water.

When testing direct-prospecting methods with numerous instrumental measurements in the contours of volcanic structures of a certain type at a depth of 57 km, a boundary was established at which conditions were created for the synthesis of oil, condensate and gas from hydrogen and carbon migrating from below. Signals (responses) at the frequencies of oil,

condensate and gas are recorded at this boundary and above, and deeper – only of hydrogen and carbon.

Such results of instrumental measurements suggest that if not all hydrogen at this boundary is used for the synthesis of hydrocarbons (due to a lack of carbon, among other things), then it, together with hydrocarbons, can migrate to the upper horizons of cross-section and fill together with them the oil and gas reservoirs of cross-section. Hydrogen was discovered in wells that were drilled for oil and gas.

When conducting experimental studies at survey sites and areas in various regions in reconnaissance (accelerated) mode, with virtually no delays, intense responses were often recorded at the resonant frequencies of hydrogen and the 6th group of igneous rocks (basalts). Moreover, if the procedure for recording signals at basalt frequencies was carried out first, then responses at hydrogen frequencies were recorded almost always at the stage of performing the procedure for recording signals from hydrogen, and vice versa.

In this regard, in the future, when carrying out experimental work in order to detect and localize areas, promising for detailed geological exploration of natural hydrogen, procedures for measuring responses (signals) at the frequencies of basalts, hydrogen, hydrogen bacteria and red phosphorus were carried out. Additionally, instrumental measurements were also carried out in order to establish the presence (absence) of migration of hydrogen and red phosphorus into the atmosphere. Let us also note that hydrogen bacteria create their colonies in the near-surface parts of cross-section in areas of hydrogen migration into the atmosphere, and signals at red phosphorus frequencies are almost always recorded in the contours of basaltic volcanic complexes.

To the above, it is advisable to add a fragment of text from the article [1]: "Some scientists hold a different opinion regarding the coexistence of hydrogen and methane. In particular, in the work [13], it is noted that hydrogen deposits can be formed outside of hydrocarbon deposits, since hydrogen is spent on the formation of methane and its homologues.

Although it is emphasized that the detection of hydrocarbon and hydrogen deposits should be solved as a single complex task, according to the principle: where there are hydrocarbons, there is no hydrogen. According to [13], this estimated hydrogen is already largely spent on the formation, maintenance and possible modern increase of hydrocarbon reserves in the basin. Only those parts of it that, due to the lack of active carbon and other reasons, remained not involved in the formation of hydrocarbons can be promising.

Probably, both points of view regarding the coexistence of methane and hydrogen are appropriate, which is caused by various processes of their natural genesis. If the source of origin is common, for example, biogenic, then both methane and hydrogen can be present in the gas composition of rock massifs. In those cases where hydrogen, together with carbon, is the building material for the formation of methane, the amount of hydrogen will be limited or it will be completely absent."

The following information also deserves attention.

1. The work carried out by the HyTerra Company [9] at the Hoarty NE3 well in Geneva (Nebraska, USA) to test promising intervals for hydrogen has not yet been completed with the publication of information about the discovery of hydrogen accumulations in commercial volumes. Most likely, HyTerra will not continue further work on the well.

To this we add that in 2019, frequency resonance processing of a photograph from the well drilling site was carried out. Based on the results of the frequency resonance processing of a fragment of the photograph, it was concluded that hydrogen accumulations in the drilled well in commercial quantities will not be detected. The drilling area is promising for hydrocarbon exploration. The results of the processing were published in 2019 [17]. Now we can state that

these results have been confirmed by drilling. It is also advisable to pay attention to the time interval: 2019 – 2023!

2. The HyTerra Company owns a licensed block in the state of Kansas (Riley, Geary and Morris Counties, USA), within which there are 2 drilled wells in which hydrogen was discovered [9]. Photographs of well locations sites were processed using direct-prospecting methods. Frequency resonance processing of a large block, including Riley, Geary and Morris Counties, was also carried out in reconnaissance mode. The main conclusion: within the HyTerra Company's licensed block, the probability of detecting hydrogen accumulations in commercial volumes is close to zero! The block is promising for hydrocarbon exploration.

3. Licensed Block 691 in Australia was examined, within which hydrogen was detected in a drilled well [34]. The situation here is similar - the probability of detecting hydrogen accumulations in commercial volumes is very low. It is recommended to carry out detailed exploration work for oil and gas.

4. The above results of a reconnaissance survey of areas for searching and drilling wells for natural hydrogen allow us to conclude that the focus of Investors and Companies on conducting prospecting work and drilling in the areas, where drilled wells are located in which hydrogen is discovered, will not lead to the discovery of its accumulations in industrial (commercial) volumes in the near future! In this situation, the geological, geophysical and mining industries of the world economy are losing the race for financing large-scale projects to convert the economies of the world to the use of environmentally friendly fuel of the future – hydrogen!

5. Large-scale testing of super-mobile direct-prospecting methods for frequency-resonance processing of [18-36] satellite images and photographs in local areas and large blocks in various regions of the globe has shown that intensive signals at the frequencies of natural hydrogen are almost always recorded within volcanic complexes, filled with basalts. In many cases, responses of hydrogen are also recorded at shallow depths in rock complexes overlying basalts. Such results allow us to conclude that the areas and blocks with basalt complexes are the primary targets for detailed prospecting work and drilling wells for natural hydrogen conducting.

6. It is quite natural that a very large amount of experimental work for the purpose of direct-prospecting methods testing was carried out on the Ukraine territory. And on the territory of this country, a significant number of sites and areas have been discovered for the detailed work and drilling wells for natural hydrogen carrying out. In Ukraine, using direct-prospecting methods, a site has also been prepared for drilling a well within a basalt structure. Unfortunately, this well has not yet been drilled: Russia's merciless War against the Ukrainian People prevented this!!!

Taking into account the above, it is advisable to add the following comments to the results of reconnaissance studies on the territory of Spain presented below.

1. When carrying out experimental work to search for accumulations of natural hydrogen, mainly procedures for recording signals at the frequencies of basalts and hydrogen were carried out, i.e., research within the framework of the search for hydrogen outside hydrocarbon deposits.

2. A limited (small) set of measurement procedures was performed at all survey sites. The implementation of a full (maximum) set of measurement procedures requires a significantly greater amount of time.

3. Almost all measuring procedures were carried out in an accelerated mode (without taking into account the time factor when carrying out instrumental measurements).

Projects of Spain and Portugal territory reconnaissance survey

Oil and gas project. The results of approbation and practical application of the direct-prospecting technology of satellite images and photographs frequency-resonance processing allow us to reasonably conclude that their targeted use in the search and exploration of oil and gas deposits can significantly speed up and optimize the exploration process. Promptly carried out

reconnaissance surveys of the territories of large blocks in various regions of the world (in Europe, including) can be considered as additional confirmation of the potential capabilities of mobile direct-prospecting technology. On the other hand, the results of the survey of large blocks indicate the potential possibility of a reconnaissance survey of the entire Spain and Portugal territory in order to identify the most promising areas (blocks) for oil and gas detailed exploration.

For the practical implementation of this project, the satellite image of Spain and Portugal territory may be divided into separate blocks, the frequency-resonance processing of which will be carried out separately. One of the possible options for dividing a satellite image of the Spain and Portugal territory into separate fragments is shown in Fig. 3. This image with rectangular contours shows 118 local fragments (blocks) for processing.

Fig. 3. Satellite image of Spain and Portugal t territory.

Frequency-resonance processing of all 118 fragments of the Spain and Portugal satellite image can be performed quite quickly. During image processing, the following set of measurement procedures may be performed: a) fixation from the surface of anomalous responses at frequencies of oil, condensate and gas; b) registration of signals at the frequencies of methane-oxidizing bacteria (bacteria, whose populations are analyzed in method of microbiological exploration for oil and gas by MicroPro GmbH, Germany); c) establishing the presence of a volcanic structure within the survey area, in which there are conditions for the hydrocarbon's synthesis at a depth of 57 km; additional fixation of responses of oil, condensate and gas at this depth; d) fixing signals at frequencies of oil, condensate and gas from lower part of cross-section at depths of 5, 10 and 15 km in order to assess prospects of oil and gas discovering in deep horizons of cross-section.

The listed procedures of instrumental measurements have fully demonstrated their effectiveness and informativeness in the process of direct-prospecting methods approbation in the areas (sites) of drilling exploratory wells on land and shelf in various regions of the globe and basalts volcano's location [16-42].

Notes. Additional procedures for instrumental measurements and the features of their implementation within the framework of this project can be formulated (clarified), if the expediency of its implementation will be recognized in Spain and Portugal.

Within the most promising for oil and gas blocks, found in Spain and Portugal, detailed prospecting can also be quickly carried out using methods of satellite images and photographs frequency-resonance processing. The prepared fragments of a satellite image of Spain and Portugal territory (Fig. 3) can be additionally processed in the reconnaissance mode within the

framework of separate projects for identifying blocks, that are promising for detailed prospecting for: a) natural hydrogen; b) ore minerals; c) water.

Hydrogen project. During frequency-resonance processing of each fragment of the Spain and Portugal territory image in the reconnaissance mode for natural hydrogen searching, a limited set of instrumental measurements of the following nature may be performed separately: a) procedure for recording signals (responses) at frequencies of the 6th group of igneous rocks (basalts); b) the procedure for determining the depth of basalt volcano root (in the case of fixing responses from the surface at basalt frequencies); c) procedures for fixing signals (responses) at the frequencies of hydrogen, phosphorus (red) and hydrogen bacteria; d) instrumental measurements to confirm (or establish absence) of hydrogen migration into atmosphere.

The expediency of implementing the listed set of instrumental measurement procedures during the survey is due to results of direct-prospecting methods testing in various regions of globe. The materials of numerous studies allow us to state following: a) responses at hydrogen frequencies are recorded almost everywhere during instrumental measurements in the contours of basalt volcanic complexes; b) red phosphorus is almost always present in basalt volcanoes; c) hydrogen bacteria create their colonies in the upper part of cross-section in the areas of hydrogen migration into the atmosphere.

To implement the second stage of the work, one of two conditions was met: within one surveyed fragment basalt complexes with hydrogen were found and responses were recorded at the frequencies of red phosphorus and hydrogen bacteria. Further continuation of research within local block is possible only with the participation of at least one Spain and Portugal company in the implementation of the "project".

At the second stage of project implementation within local block, studies of the following nature can be performed: a) the satellite image of the block may be processed in a detailed mode in order to localize areas (zones) of the basalt volcano's location and select the most promising for exploratory wells drilling for hydrogen; b) in the contours of the most promising local zones, a detailed scanning of cross-section will be performed in order to determine the depths and thicknesses of hydrogen reservoirs in the cross-section above the basalts, as well as in the basalts directly; c) within promising local zones, the depths and thicknesses of reservoirs with living (healing) water may be determined by detailed scanning, and healing properties of living water in identified reservoirs of cross-section may be also studied.

Based on the results of detailed processing of satellite image of local block, a decision will be made to drill exploratory wells in the most promising local areas. At the initial stage of drilling, wells can be designed to study reservoirs with hydrogen in the upper horizons of cross-section. During drilling, reservoirs with living water can also be studied. Based on the results of the first wells drilling, a decision can be made on the next stages of research for the further implementation of the "project".

Approbation of direct-prospecting technology on Spain territory

Territory of Spain. A satellite image of Spain and Portugal [3] is shown in Fig. 4. During its processing, responses at the **frequencies of hydrogen and basalts were recorded from 10 seconds of instrumental measurements each.** Signals at **helium frequencies were not detected during 60 s of measurements.**

Offers. In Spain, it is advisable to implement described above the reconnaissance survey projects in order to discover the most promising blocks for detailed prospecting for natural hydrogen, as well as oil, gas condensate, and gas. During the implementation of these projects, additional measurement procedures can be applied to record signals at hydrogen frequencies from promising oil and gas reservoirs.

Fig. 4. Satellite image of Spain and Portugal [3]. The outlines of the Aragon province are indicated in yellow, and the Barbastro and Monzon license blocks are indicated in red.

Fig. 5. Satellite image of Andalusia province (Spain).

Territory of Andalusia (Spain). During frequency-resonance processing of the satellite image of Andalusia Province in Fig. 5 in reconnaissance mode, signals at **the frequencies of hydrogen, hydrogen bacteria and the 6th group of igneous rocks (basalts) were registered!** The territory of the block on this satellite image is **promising for detailed prospecting work and drilling wells for natural hydrogen!**

Offers. In Andalusia, the survey projects proposed above for the entire Spanish territory could also be implemented.

Territory of Aragon (Spain). During frequency resonance processing of a satellite image of Aragon Province (Fig. 6a), responses at the **frequencies of hydrogen and basalts were recorded from 10 seconds of instrumental measurements each.** Signals at **helium frequencies were not detected during 60 s of measurements.**

During frequency resonance processing of a satellite image of the northern part of Aragon Province (Fig. 6b), signals at the **frequencies of basalts, hydrogen and helium were not recorded for 60 seconds of instrumental measurements each.**

During frequency resonance processing of a satellite image of the Barbastro and Monzon licensed blocks in the Aragon Province (Fig. 6c), signals at the **frequencies of basalts, hydrogen and helium were not recorded for 120 s of instrumental measurements each.**

Responses at frequencies of **7-10 groups of igneous rocks** were recorded starting from 4 s of instrumental measurements.

Fig. 6. Satellite images of Aragon Province (a), the northern part of the province (b) and the Barbastro and Monzon license blocks (c).

Offers. 1. In Aragon Province, the survey projects proposed above for the entire Spanish territory could also be implemented.

2. The satellite image of the Barbastro and Monzon license areas (Fig. 6c) is proposed to be further processed using an expanded set of measurement procedures in order to assess the prospects for detecting oil, condensate and gas accumulations within their boundaries in industrial (commercial) volumes. For this purpose, it is advisable to use measurement procedures for recording responses at frequencies of hydrocarbons (oil, condensate, gas), carbon dioxide, hydrogen, hydrogen and methane-oxidizing bacteria, as well as determining the presence (absence) of groups of sedimentary and igneous rocks, within the distribution of which conditions for hydrocarbons synthesis are created. Important for the final conclusions are the procedures for establishing the presence (absence) of migration of hydrogen, gas (methane) and carbon dioxide into the atmosphere and recording responses at the resonant frequencies of oil, condensate, gas at the hydrocarbon synthesis boundary of 57 km.

3. Figure 7 shows satellite images of the central and southern parts of Aragon Province. It is advisable to carry out frequency-resonance processing of these images in reconnaissance mode with the implementation of measurement procedures for recording responses (signals) at the frequencies of hydrogen, oil, condensate, gas, carbon dioxide, hydrogen and methane-oxidizing bacteria, basalts, as well as establishing the presence (absence) of hydrogen, gas (methane) and carbon dioxide migration into the atmosphere. An expanded set of measurement procedures can also be implemented in the northern part of the of Aragon Province (Fig. 6b).

Fig. 7. Satellite images of central (a) and southern (b) parts of Aragon Province.

Area of Monzon-1 well location. In the process of frequency resonance processing of a satellite image of area with the Monzon-1 well in Fig. 8a, in accelerated mode, signals were recorded from the surface at frequencies of 1-6 groups of sedimentary rocks. **Responses at frequencies of the 6th group of igneous rocks (basalts) have not been recorded.**

Offers. 1. The satellite image of the Monzon-1 well location area (Fig. 8a) is proposed to be additionally processed using an expanded set of measurement procedures in order to assess the prospects for detecting oil, condensate and gas accumulations within their boundaries in industrial (commercial) volumes. For this purpose, it is advisable to use measurement procedures for recording responses at frequencies of hydrocarbons (oil, condensate, gas), carbon dioxide, hydrogen, hydrogen and methane-oxidizing bacteria, as well as determining the presence (absence) of groups of sedimentary and igneous rocks, within the distribution of which conditions for hydrocarbons synthesis are created. Important for the final conclusions are the procedures for establishing the presence (absence) of migration of hydrogen, gas (methane) and carbon dioxide into the atmosphere and recording responses at the resonant frequencies of oil, condensate, gas at the hydrocarbon synthesis boundary of 57 km.

Fig. 8. Satellite images of areas with the Monzon-1 well within the Monzon license block in the Aragon Province (Spain).

During frequency resonance processing of a satellite image of a local area with the Monzon-1 well in Fig. 8b, in accelerated mode, signals were recorded from the surface **at frequencies of 1-6 groups of sedimentary rocks.** The root of the volcano of this group of rocks was recorded at a depth of 99 km.

Responses were also received of **oil, gas condensate, gas, amber, carbon dioxide, and yellow phosphorus**. Instrumental measurements confirmed the **synthesis of hydrocarbons at the 57 km boundary**.

Offers. Within local area with the Monzon-1 well (Fig. 8b), it is proposed to carry out additionally instrumental measurements in a detailed mode of the following nature:

1. Scanning a cross-section in the well area in order to determine the depths and thicknesses of productive intervals (oil, condensate, gas) from the surface up to 5 km. At depths of 5 km, 10 km, 15 km, record signals at the frequencies of oil, condensate and gas in order to assess the prospects for detecting hydrocarbon deposits in the deep horizons of cross-section.

2. Registration of responses at hydrogen frequencies from cross-section intervals within which signals at the frequencies of oil, condensate and gas were recorded by scanning.

3. Establish the presence (absence) of migration of gas, carbon dioxide, phosphorus and hydrogen into the atmosphere.

During the frequency-resonance of the seismic section fragment (rectangular contour in Fig. 9) with the Monzon-1 well in accelerated mode, only **signals at frequencies of 1-6 groups of sedimentary rocks were recorded**.

Offers. 1. Using a fragment of the seismic section in Fig. 9, it is advisable to carry out additionally instrumental measurements in a detailed mode in order to record signals at the frequencies of hydrogen, oil, condensate and gas.

Fig. 9. Subsurface structural setting of the Monzon-1 well as interpreted from the 3D seismic line [2, 3]. Green diamond indicate location of hydrogen shows seen in Monzon-1 well.

When processing the photograph in Fig. 10 signals at frequencies of 1-6 groups of sedimentary rocks began to be recorded from 14-16 s of instrumental measurements. **Responses at the frequencies of the 6th group of igneous rocks (basalts) were not recorded during 90 s of measurements.**

During the processing of the photograph in Fig. 10 with a fragment cut out in the red rectangle, signals at frequencies of the 2nd group of sedimentary rocks (psammities) were not recorded during 90 s of instrumental measurements. Responses at the frequencies of the 3rd group of sedimentary rocks (siltstones, mudstones, clays) began to be recorded from 14 s of

measurements, the 4th group (kaolinite mudstones) - from 25 s, the 5th group (kaolinite clays) - from 31 s.

Signals at the frequencies of hydrogen and gas were not detected during 90 s of measurements.

Fig. 10. Mud-log extract from an exploration well drilled in 1980 interpreted to have intersected shows of natural hydrogen over the interval 3230 to 3600 feet. Note significant peak and overlap of Total Gas and Petroleum Vapour readings recoded in the drilling mud over this interval. It is assumed a similar response was most likely recorded at the Monzon-1 well. From XXX? [2, 3].

In the process of frequency-resonance processing of a fragment of the image in Fig. 10 in the red rectangle, signals at gas frequencies began to be recorded from 21 s of instrumental measurements, hydrogen - from 48 s, and psammites (2nd group of sedimentary rocks) - from 14 s.

Investigation within areas of iridium anomalies detection

The article [5] provides information on the of iridium anomalies in the areas of Gubbio (Italy) and Caravaca (Spain) settlements. Satellite images of these areas are shown in Fig. 11 and 13.

At a site in Italy (Fig. 11), signals from iridium, osmium, nickel, and gold were recorded from surface. Signals from the 1st (granite) and 15th groups of igneous rocks were recorded. The root of granite volcano was identified at a depth of 470 km.

The responses from iridium, osmium, nickel and gold were obtained at the surface of 59 km. At a depth of 57 km, signals of low intensity from iridium were received.

The article [5] shows a photograph of a core sample from a well in Italy (Fig. 12). Responses from nickel, osmium and iridium were recorded from this core sample.

When scanning the cross-section from the surface, with a 10 cm step, the responses from the core (Fig. 12) began to be recorded from 135 m and traced (from 335 m - 50 cm step) to 860 m.

On the surface of 57 km, there were no responses at core frequencies (Fig. 12), but at a depth of 59 km they were recorded.

Fig. 11. Satellite images of the survey areas in the regions of Gubbio (Italy).

Fig. 12. Photo of a core with iridium layer from well in Gubbio regions (Italy) [5].

Fig. 13. Satellite images of the survey areas in the regions of Caravaca (Spain).

On the 59 km and 57 km surfaces, the responses of low intensity from the core fragment in the upper rectangle (Fig. 12) were recorded. Similar results were obtained for the core fragment in the lower rectangle (Fig. 12). From the core fragments in the lower and upper rectangles, the responses from nickel and osmium were recorded. Intensive responses from iridium were recorded from the core fragment in the lower rectangle, and from the upper rectangle - of low intensity.

When processing the image (Fig. 11) on the surface of 59 km, intense signals were obtained at the frequencies of iridium and osmium, and at a depth of 57 km – of low intensity. By scanning the cross-section from the surface, a step of 10 cm, the upper edge of the granites was fixed at a depth of 115 m.

At a site in Spain (Fig. 13), signals from iridium, osmium, nickel, and gold were recorded from the surface. Signals from the 1st (granite) and 15th groups of igneous rocks were recorded. The root of the granite volcano was identified at a depth of 470 km. The responses from iridium, osmium, nickel and gold were obtained at the surface of 59 km. At a depth of 57 km, there were no signals from osmium.

By cross-section scanning the upper edge of granites was fixed at depth of 45 m.

Main results. The surveyed areas are located within granite volcanoes, in which, in the interval of 57-59 km conditions are created for the synthesis of iridium, osmium, nickel, and gold.

Some comments and conclusion

The results of the testing of mobile direct-prospecting methods for frequency-resonance processing and decoding of satellite images and photographs on the territory of Spain allow us to formulate the following main conclusions.

1. On the territory of Spain, there are local areas and large blocks that are promising for geological exploration and exploratory wells drilling for natural hydrogen and living (healing) water. The implementation of the proposed reconnaissance survey projects across the entire territory of Spain will make it possible to discover the most promising blocks in the country for detailed exploration work for natural hydrogen, as well as oil, condensate and gas conducting. The

use of mobile direct-prospecting methods (including the technology of frequency-resonance processing of satellite images and photographs) at the stage of detailed examination of the most promising local areas and large blocks will significantly optimize (accelerate) the search process and reduce the financial costs of its implementation.

2. The local area with the drilled well Monzon-1 in the Aragon Province is located within a volcanic complex filled with sedimentary rocks of groups 1-6, in which at a depth of 57 km conditions exist for the synthesis of oil, condensate and gas from hydrogen and carbon migrating from below. And if not all the hydrogen from the flow below is spent on the synthesis of hydrocarbons, then it can migrate to the upper horizons of cross-section and fill the oil and gas reservoirs of the cross-section together with oil and gas. It can be assumed that the hydrogen detected in the Monzon-1 well has this origin.

3. In connection with the above-mentioned conclusion, **the proposal of the authors of experimental work within areas and blocks with hydrocarbon deposits to design and carry out detailed prospecting work and drill exploratory wells for natural hydrogen, as well as oil and gas simultaneously, should be considered a fundamentally important conclusion.** This proposal should be paid attention to by companies that are conducting exploration work and planning to drill wells in areas within which hydrogen was discovered when drilling prospecting and exploration wells for oil and gas.

4. The performance, information content and efficiency of super-mobile direct-prospecting methods of frequency-resonance processing and decoding of satellite images and photographs is demonstrated by numerous results of examination of local areas for drilling prospecting and exploration wells on land and offshore in various regions of the world. Almost all results of processing images of sites with wells are confirmed by drilling. To this we add that the conference materials [38-42] present the results of reconnaissance work in the Cabora Bassa Basin (Zimbabwe) [10]. The results of the survey of the local area with the first well drilled in the basin were confirmed by drilling. In the second half of September 2023, drilling of a second exploratory well began in the basin, in which, according to the results of frequency-resonance image processing, the probability of discovering oil and gas deposits in industrial (commercial) volumes is close to zero.

We note once again that the frequency-resonance processing of photographs and satellite images of all areas and sites of the survey was carried out in the reconnaissance mode – an integral assessment of the values of the structural parameters of cross-section was carried out, as well as the prospects for detecting accumulations of hydrogen and hydrocarbons were evaluated. In the process of experiments conducting, the entire tested set of measurement procedures has not been fully implemented.

In the process of conducting experiments in many blocks and local areas of the survey, methodological technique of detection and localization of areas and local zones, within which hydrogen and gas (methane) migrate into the atmosphere, were developed based on the results of frequency-resonance processing of satellite images and photographs. This technique can be used in the future when conducting prospecting for hydrogen, as well as oil and gas.

A fundamentally important result of the experimental work carried out using the developed measuring equipment is the replenishment of the database (facts), which testifies in favor of the "volcanic" model of the formation of the external appearance (surface) and various structural elements of the Earth, planets and satellites of the solar system, as well as deposits of combustible and ore minerals (including hydrogen and water).

The materials of instrumental measurements presented above, as well as the results of earlier experimental works [21, 28-33], also allow us to draw generalizing conclusions of the following nature.

1. In blocks and areas where basaltic volcanoes with roots at different depths are located, signals are almost always recorded from the surface at the frequencies of hydrogen, living water, and phosphorus (red). Quite often, responses from hydrogen bacteria are also recorded, which create their colonies in the near-surface part of cross-section in the areas of hydrogen migration into the atmosphere. Hydrogen bacteria do not produce hydrogen, but use it to maintain the viability of their populations.

2. Responses at hydrogen frequencies are recorded when scanning cross-section with a large step almost from the upper edges of basaltic volcanoes to their roots. This feature allows us to suggest that basalt volcanoes are a kind of channels through which hydrogen is actively migrated to the upper horizons of cross-section and further into the atmosphere.

3. Instrumental measurements indicate that in basaltic volcanoes with roots at depths of 470 km and 723 km on surfaces (boundaries) of 68 km and 69 km, respectively, deep (living) water is synthesized. Hydrogen-enriched water is healing and can be used for health purposes. It is worth noting once again that all the surveyed zones and areas of longevity on Earth [23, part 2] are located within (contours) of basalt volcanoes, in which water synthesized at depths of 68 km or 69 km migrates to the surface and is used for water supply and drinking goals.

4. Hydrogen deposits can be formed by basalt volcanoes in capped reservoirs adjacent to basalts. The local site for hydrogen production in Mali is located outside the contour of a basaltic volcano; responses from hydrogen were recorded at the location of one of the drilled wells from marls. In other areas of the survey, signals from hydrogen were obtained from dolomites (the Carpathians, the island of centenarians Ikaria), as well as marls and limestones.

5. Formed near basalt volcanoes, as well as above basalts, hydrogen deposits in reservoirs of various types can be quickly detected and localized during areal prospecting using direct-prospecting methods (technologies for frequency-resonance processing of satellite images and photographs, including).

6. The problem of studying reservoirs in crystalline rocks (including basalts) deserves attention. Direct-prospecting methods can also be used for these purposes.

7. It should be considered fundamentally important that the experimental studies carried out in numerous areas have shown the possibility (and expediency) of using direct-prospecting frequency-resonance methods of satellite images and photographs processing and interpreting to detect and localize areas of hydrogen accumulation, as well as determine the depths of its predicted deposits. In further studies in this direction, it is advisable to pay attention to the types of reservoirs in which hydrogen can be accumulated, as well as seal rocks that will contribute to the preservation of deposits.

During satellite images and photographs processing over the surveyed objects, additional facts (evidence) were obtained in favor of the deep (abiogenic) genesis of oil, condensate and gas [29] in the process of hydrogen degassing of the Earth [12]. The relevance of the problem of abiogenic synthesis of hydrocarbons and their migration into the upper horizons of cross-section and into the atmosphere is emphasized by many researchers.

The facts of hydrogen migration into the atmosphere recorded by instrumental measurements within the limits of discovered basalt volcanoes in various regions of the world should be considered as fundamentally important results, obtained using direct-prospecting technology. In general, the materials of numerous studies (including those presented above) confirm the conclusions of researchers about the large-scale migration of deep (abiogenic) gas and hydrogen into the atmosphere of Earth planet!

The materials of reconnaissance experimental studies presented in the article, as well as published in [16-42], clearly demonstrate the efficiency, information content and performance of direct-prospecting methods of satellite images and photographs frequency-resonance processing in the integral assessment of the prospects for detecting hydrogen accumulations in the survey

areas, as well as in the intervals of cross-section of local areas. The results of experimental work in various regions indicate the feasibility of using direct-prospecting methods of satellite images and photographs frequency-resonance processing and decoding to detect and localize hydrogen accumulation zones in the areas of basalt volcanoes, as well as in areas of hydrogen degassing. The use of super-efficient and low-cost direct prospecting technology will significantly speed up the exploration process for natural hydrogen, as well as reduce financial costs for its implementation.

References

1. Bezruchko K.A. Natural sources and conditions of geological hydrogen generation (in the context of hydrogen deposits searches). *Geophysical Journal*, 2022. 44(2), 93—124. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.24028/gj.v44i2.256267>
2. Christopher Atkinson, Christopher Matchette-Downes and Sandra Garcia-Curiel. Natural hydrogen in the Monzon-1 well, Ebro basin, northern Spain. <https://www.mdoil.co.uk/pdfs/Article%20Atkinson%20et%20al..pdf>
<https://helios-aragon.com/natural-hydrogen-in-the-monzon-1-well-ebro-basin-northern-spain-geological-society-of-france-publication/>
3. Chris Matchette-Downes. The hydrogen system of Europe's first natural hydrogen project. AAPG Hydrogen 2022 Virtual Technical Symposium. <https://www.mdoil.co.uk/pdfs/Helios%20Aragon%20-%20AAPG%20-%20Dec%2022.pdf>
4. "Electronic petrographic reference book-identifier of magmatic, metamorphic and sedimentary rocks", 2015. <http://rockref.vsegei.ru/petro/> (in Russian).
5. Goderis et al., Globally distributed iridium layer preserved within the Chicxulub impact structure. *Sci. Adv.* 2021; 7: eabe3647 24 February 2021. 13 p.
6. Helios Aragon. <https://helios-aragon.com/>
7. Helios Aragon Records High Levels of Gold Hydrogen and Helium in Spain. <https://hydrogen-central.com/helios-aragon-records-high-levels-gold-hydrogen-helium-spain/>
8. Helios Aragón aspires to transform region into European hydrogen hub. <https://www.investinspain.org/content/icex-invest/en/noticias-main/2023/helios-aragon.html>
9. HyTerra (ASX:HYT) <https://hyterra.com/>
10. Invictus Energy Ltd (ASX: IVZ). <https://www.invictusenergy.com/>
11. Levashov S.P., Yakymchuk N.A., Korchagin I.N. Frequency-resonance principle, mobile geoelectric technology: new paradigm of geophysical investigations. *Geofizicheskiy zhurnal*, 2012, vol. 34, no. 4, pp. 166-176 (in Russian).
12. Shestopalov V.M., Lukin A.E., Zgonik V.A., Makarenko A.N., Larin N.V., Boguslavsky A.S. Essays on Earth's degassing. Kiev, BADATA-Intek Service. 2018. 632 p. (in Russian).
13. Shestopalov, V.M. On geological hydrogen. *Geophysical Journal*, 2020. 42(6), 3—35. <https://doi.org/10.24028/gzh.0203-3100.v42i6.2020> (in Russian).
14. Tesla N. Patents. - Samara: Publishing House "Agni", 2009. - 496 p. (in Russian).
15. Tesla N. Articles. - Samara: Publishing House "Agni", Moscow: Publishing House "Russian Panorama", 2010. - 584 p. (in Russian).
16. Yakymchuk N.A., Korchagin I.N., Bakhmutov V.G., Solovjev V.D. Geophysical investigation in the Ukrainian marine Antarctic expedition of 2018: mobile measuring equipment, innovative direct-prospecting methods, new results. *Geoinformatika*, 2019, no. 1, pp. 5-27. (in Russian).
17. Yakymchuk N.A., Levashov S.P., Korchagin I.N. Application of technology of frequency-resonant processing of satellite images and photographs on area of hydrogen production and hydrogen degasation of the Earth. Conference Proceedings, 18th International Conference on Geoinformatics - Theoretical and Applied Aspects, May 2019, Volume 2019, p.1 - 5 DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.3997/2214-4609.201902022>

<https://www.earthdoc.org/content/papers/10.3997/2214-4609.201902022>

18. Yakymchuk, N. A., Korchagin, I. N. Ukrainian Shield: new data on depth structure and prospects of oil, gas condensate, gas and hydrogen accumulations detection. *Geoinformatika*, 2019, no. 2, pp. 5-18 (in Russian).

19. Yakymchuk, N. A., Korchagin, I. N., Levashov, S. P. Direct-prospecting mobile technology: the results of approbation during searching for hydrogen and the channels of migration of deep fluids, mineral substances and chemical elements. *Geoinformatika*, 2019, no. 2, pp. 19-42 (in Russian).

20. Yakymchuk, N. A., Korchagin, I. N. Peculiarities of depth structure and of oil and gas perspectives of Ukrainian shield separate blocks by results of frequency-resonance sounding of cross-section. *Geoinformatika*, 2019, no. 3, pp. 5-18 (in Russian).

21. Yakymchuk, N. A., Korchagin, I. N. Application of mobile frequency-resonance methods of satellite images and photo images processing for hydrogen accumulations searching. *Geoinformatika*, 2019, no. 3, pp. 19-28 (in Russian).

22. Yakymchuk, N. A., Korchagin, I. N. Studying the internal structure of volcanic complexes of different type by results of frequency-resonant processing of satellite and photo images. *Geoinformatika*, 2019, no. 4, pp. 5-18 (in Russian).

23. Yakymchuk, N. A., Korchagin, I. N. Technology of frequency-resonance processing of remote sensing data: results of practical approbation during mineral searching in various regions of the globe. Part I. *Geoinformatika*, 2019, no. 3, pp. 29-51; Part II. *Geoinformatika*. 2019. no. 4, pp. 30-58; Part III. *Geoinformatika*. 2020. no. 1, pp. 19-41; Part IV. *Geoinformatika*. 2020. no. 3, pp. 29-62; Part V. *Geoinformatika*. 2021. no. 3-4, pp. 51-88. (in Russian).

24. Yakymchuk, N. A., Korchagin, I. N. Approbation of direct-prospecting technology of frequency-resonance processing of satellite images and photo images at known hydrocarbon deposits in different regions. *Geoinformatika*, 2020, no. 2, pp. 3-38 (in Russian).

25. Yakymchuk, N. A., Korchagin, I. N., Yanushkevich K.P. Approbation of frequency-resonance methods of satellite and photo images processing on the geological structure "Chicxulub Crater". *Geoinformatika*, 2020, no. 2, pp. 39-49 (in Russian).

26. Yakymchuk, N. A., Korchagin, I. N. On the possibility of application the frequency-resonance technology of satellite images and photos images processing for studying objects of the solar system and far space *Geoinformatika*, 2020, no. 2, pp. 98-108 (in Russian).

27. Yakymchuk, N. A., Korchagin, I. N., Yanushkevich K.P. Features of the depth structure and prospects of oil and gas potential of the Carpathian region by results of cross-section frequency resonance sounding. *Geoinformatika*, 2020, no. 2, pp. 50-68 (in Russian).

28. Yakymchuk, N. A., Korchagin, I. N. Direct-prospecting technology of frequency-resonant processing of satellite images and photos images: results of use for determining areas of gas and hydrogen migration to the surface and in the atmosphere. *Geoinformatika*, 2020, no. 3, pp. 3-28 (in Russian).

29. Yakymchuk, N. A., Korchagin, I. N. New evidence in favor of the abiogenic genesis of hydrocarbons from the results of the testing of direct-prospecting methods in various regions of the world. Reports of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine. 2020. № 9. P. 55-62. <https://doi.org/10.15407/dopovidi2020.09.055> (in Ukrainian)

30. Yakymchuk, N. A., Korchagin, I. N. Direct-prospecting technology of frequency-resonance processing of satellite images and photo images: potential opportunities and prospects of application for natural hydrogen accumulations searching. *Geoinformatika*, 2020, no. 4, pp. 3-41 (in Russian)

31. Yakymchuk, N. A., Korchagin, I. N. Depth structure features of large zones of hydrogen degassing in various regions of the earth by results of frequency-resonance processing of satellite and photos images. *Geoinformatika*, 2021, no. 1-2, pp. 3-42 (in Russian).

32. Yakymchuk, N. A., Korchagin, I. N. On the prospects of the technology of remote sensing data frequency-resonance processing using when conducting profiles geoelectric and seismic studies. *Geoinformatika*. 2021. no. 3-4, pp. 18-50 (in Russian).

33. Yakymchuk, N. A., Korchagin, I. N. Results of a reconnaissance survey of large zones of hydrogen degassing in various regions of the world. *Reports of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine*. 2022. № 1. P. 79-91. <https://doi.org/10.15407/dopovidi2022.01.079> (in Ukrainian)

34. Yakymchuk M. A., Korchagin I. M. Prospects of natural hydrogen and hydrocarbons deposits discovery within exploration block in southern Australia by mobile direct-prospecting methods. *Proceedings of the 3rd International scientific and practical conference. SPC "Sci-conf.com.ua"*. Kyiv, Ukraine. 2023. Pp. 550-558. URL: <https://sci-conf.com.ua/iii-mizhnarodna-naukovo-praktichna-konferentsiya-modern-problems-of-science-education-and-society-22-24-05-2023-kiyiv-ukrayina-arhiv/>

35. Mykola Yakymchuk, Ignat Korchagin. About the opportunity of direct-prospecting methods application for detection areas of gas and natural hydrogen migration to the surface and in the atmosphere. Publisher.agency: *Proceedings of the 2nd International Scientific Conference «Interdisciplinary Science Studies»* (May 4-5, 2023). Dublin, Ireland, 2023. P. 220-251. ISBN 978-2-6400-5011-9 DOI 10.5281/zenodo.7905551

<https://ojs.publisher.agency/index.php/ISS/issue/view/29>

36. Mykola Yakymchuk, Ignat Korchagin. Direct-prospecting technology of satellite images and photographs frequency-resonance processing: about expediency of its practical application for hydrocarbons and hydrogen searching and deep structure of earth studying. Publisher.agency: *Proceedings of the 2nd International Scientific Conference «Foundations and Trends in Modern Learning»* (April 27-28, 2023). Berlin, Germany, 2023. P. 342-362. ISBN 978-2-9003-7194-7 DOI 10.5281/zenodo.7882250

<https://ojs.publisher.agency/index.php/FTML/issue/view/28>

37. Mykola Yakymchuk, Ignat Korchagin. Projects of European countries territories reconnaissance survey by direct-prospecting methods in order to identify promising areas for oil and gas detailed exploration. Publisher.agency: *Proceedings of the 2nd International Scientific Conference «World Scientific Reports»* (March 16-17, 2023). Paris, France, 2023. P. 336-360. ISBN 978-1-8628-5741-4 DOI 10.5281/zenodo.7750877

<https://ojs.publisher.agency/index.php/WSR/issue/view/22>

38. Yakymchuk M. A., Korchagin I. On the feasibility of Zimbabwe territory reconnaissance survey by direct-prospecting methods in order to detect blocks for oil and gas prospecting // *Modern research in world science. Proceedings of the 11th International scientific and practical conference. SPC "Sci-conf.com.ua"*. Lviv, Ukraine. 2023. Pp. 551-559. URL: <https://sci-conf.com.ua/xi-mizhnarodna-naukovo-praktichna-konferentsiya-modern-research-in-world-science-29-31-01-2023-lviv-ukrayina-arhiv/>

39. Yakymchuk M. A., Korchagin I.M. Results of reconnaissance survey by direct-prospecting methods within a prospecting block in Cabora Bassa Basin (Zimbabwe) for assessing the prospects of hydrocarbon accumulations detecting. *16th International Conference on Monitoring of Geological Processes and Ecological Condition of the Environment*. 15–18 November 2022, Kyiv, Ukraine. 5 p. Mon-22-078. <https://eage.in.ua/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/Mon-22-078.pdf>

40. Yakymchuk M. A., Korchagin I. M. Results of survey by direct-prospecting methods of two exploratory wells drilling sites in Cabora Bassa basin (Zimbabwe) // *Modern research in world science. Proceedings of the 8th International scientific and practical conference. SPC "Sci-*

conf.com.ua”. Lviv, Ukraine. 2022. Pp. 494-501. URL: <https://sci-conf.com.ua/viii-mizhnarodna-naukovo-praktichna-konferentsiya-modern-research-in-world-science-29-31-10-2022-lviv-ukrayina-arhiv/>

41. Yakymchuk M. A., Korchagin I. M. About prospects of kimberlite volcanoes with diamonds discovery in Cabora Bassa basin (Zimbabwe) // Modern research in world science. Proceedings of the 9th International scientific and practical conference. SPC “Sci-conf.com.ua”. Lviv, Ukraine. 2022. Pp. 699-707. URL: <https://sci-conf.com.ua/ix-mizhnarodna-naukovo-praktichna-konferentsiya-modern-research-in-world-science-28-30-11-2022-lviv-ukrayina-arhiv/>

42. Yakymchuk M. A., Korchagin I. M. On feasibility of frequency-resonance methods of image processing using for seismic sections interpretation during prospecting work for minerals conducting. Proceedings of the 7th International scientific and practical conference. SPC “Sci-conf.com.ua”. Kyiv, Ukraine. 2023. Pp. 202-2101. URL: <https://sci-conf.com.ua/vii-mizhnarodna-naukovo-praktichna-konferentsiya-modern-problems-of-science-education-and-society-11-13-09-2023-kiyiv-ukrayina-arhiv/>

Technical Sciences

МРПТИ 29.19.09

УДК 539.21: 536.77

THERMODYNAMICS OF SOME PHYSICAL AND CHEMICAL TRANSFORMATIONS IN POLYPHASE CERAMIC MATERIALS

M.Kulbek

Doctor technical sciences, Professor, Abai Kazakh National Pedagogical University, Almaty

D.Baimolda

Doctor PhD, Professor, Abai Kazakh National Pedagogical University, Almaty

E.Dzhaksigeldinova

Master of sciences, Abai Kazakh National Pedagogical University, Almaty

G.Zhexenbayeva

Master of sciences, Abai Kazakh National Pedagogical University, Almaty

N.Aytan

doctoral student, Kazakh National Pedagogical University, Almaty

Abstract

When firing polyphase ceramic materials in certain temperature ranges, phase and chemical transformations of various nature occur. A significant part of these transformations proceed with the absorption or release of a certain amount of heat, i.e. accompanied by thermal effects. The scientific article outlines some issues of thermodynamics of first-order phase transformations that take place in these materials. In particular, methods are shown for determining the total amount of heat, as well as the specific heat of phase transformations associated with dehydration and dissociation in polyphase ceramic materials. Examples of the practical use of the proposed calculation methods are given. The computational work was carried out at laboratory of applied thermophysics and new technologies of KazNPU named after Abai, using experimental data obtained on polyphase monothermitic model samples. In this case, the specific heat of phase transformations (dehydration) were determined in two ways, where the results showed good convergence.

Keywords: Thermodynamics, phase transformations, effects, temperature, heat, equations.

ПОЛИФАЗАЛЫҚ КЕРАМИКАЛЫҚ МАТЕРИАЛДАРДАҒЫ КЕЙБІР ФИЗИКАЛЫҚ - ХИМИЯЛЫҚ ТҮРЛЕНУЛЕРДІҢ ТЕРМОДИНАМИКАСЫ

М.Құлбек¹, Д.Баймолда², Э.Джаксигельдинова³, Г.Жексенбаева⁴, Н.Айтан⁵

¹ *т.ғ.д., профессор, Абай атындағы Қазақ Ұлттық педагогикалық университеті Алматы қ.,*

² *PhD, профессор, Абай атындағы Қазақ Ұлттық педагогикалық университеті Алматы қ.*

³ *магистр, оқытушы, Абай атындағы Қазақ Ұлттық педагогикалық университеті Алматы қ*

⁴ *магистр, оқытушы, Абай атындағы Қазақ Ұлттық педагогикалық университеті Алматы қ.,*

⁵ *докторант, Абай атындағы Қазақ Ұлттық педагогикалық университеті Алматы қ.,*

Аңдатпа

Полифазалық керамикалық материалдарды күйдіру барысында, олардың бойында белгілі температуралар аймағында табиғаттары әртүрлі фазалық және химиялық түрленулер орын алады. Бұндай түрленулердің бірқатары жылуды жұту немесе бөлу арқылы, яғни жылу эффектілерімен байланысты жүреді. Ғылыми мақалада осындай материалдарда орын алатын бірінші текті фазалық түрленулер термодинамикасының кейбір мәселелері қарастырылған. Атап айтқанда, полифазалық керамикалық материалдардағы дегидратация, диссоциация сияқты үдерістер кезіндегі термиялық эффектілердің жылу шығындарын анықтау жолдары көрсетілген. Келтірілген теңдеулерді практика жүзінде қолдану мысалдары берілген. Есептеу жұмыстары Абай атындағы ҚазҰПУ-нің физика кафедрасына қарасты қолданбалы жылуфизикасы және жаңа технологиялар зертханасында жүргізілген монотермитті полифазалық моделдік үлгілерде алынған тәжірибелік нәтижелер негізінде жасалды. Бұл бағытта меншікті фазалық түрлену (дегидратация) жылуы бірнеше жолмен анықталып, олардың бір-біріне өте жақын нәтиже беретіндігі көрсетілген.

Кілт сөздер: термодинамика, фазалық түрленулер, эффектілер, температура, жылу, теңдеулер.

Кіріспе

Қоршаған ортада, техникада және технологияда фазалық және химиялық түрленулерге байланысты үдерістер кеңінен орын алады. Табиғаттары әртүрлі мұндай құбылыстар жылу және масса алмасу үдерістерімен байланысты жүрілетіндіктен өте күрделі жағдайларда өтеді. Бірінші текті фазалық түрленулер жылуды жұту немесе бөлу, яғни термиялық эффектілер арқылы жүрілсе, ал екінші текті фазалық түрленулер кезінде мұндай эффектілер тікелей байқалмайды. Дегенмен кейінгі зерттеулер [1,2] соңғы жағдайда да жанама жылу эффектілерінің орын алу мүмкіндігін көрсетіп отыр. Бұл екінші текті фазалық түрленулер кезінде материалдың жылуфизикалық қасиеттерінің айтарлықтай аралықта өзгеруімен түсіндіріледі. Қатты денелерді жылулық өңдеуден өткізу барысында жүретін күрделі тасымалдау құбылыстары жылу мен масса алмасу теориясында қарастырылады.

Бұл теория бойынша тасымалдау процестері аналитикалық және тәжірибелік тұрғыдан жан-жақты зерттеліп, біраз нәтижелер жинақталған.

Зерттеу материалдары мен әдістері

Қатты денелерді (табиғи шикізаттарды, минералдарды) қыздыру барысында жүретін күрделі физикалық және химиялық түрленулерге байланысты байқалатын жылулық эффектілерді зерттеу тәсілдерінің ішіндегі тиімді әдістерінің біріне модельді үлгілердің дифференциалды қыздыру қисықтарын алу жатады (мысалы, үлгі бетіндегі және центрдегі температураларының айырымы).

Аталған әдіс бойынша белгілі жолдармен дайындалған модельді үлгілердің қабаттарына орналастырылған термодинамикалық көмегімен температуралық өрістер (қыздыру қисықтары) жазып алынады. Біріншіден осындай қыздыру өрістерін эталон үшін алынған нәтижелерімен салыстыра отырып, белгілі температуралар аймағында байқалатын жылу эффектілерін анықтап, оны зерттеуге мүмкіндік туады.

Екіншіден, тәжірибе жүзінде алынған қыздыру қисықтарын (температуралық өрістерін) пайдалана отырып, материалдардың күйдіру барысындағы эффективті термиялық сипаттамаларын анықтауға болады.

Полифазалық керамикалық материалдарды күйдіру барысында олардың бойында табиғаттары әртүрлі физикалық – химиялық түрленулер жүреді[3]. Осындай үдерістердің нәтижесінде жаңа фазалар пайда болып, кристалды-аморфты керамикалық құрылым қалыптасады. Осындай физикалық - химиялық түрленулердің қатарына керамикалық шикізаттардың (табиғи лай қоспалары, минералдар, т.б.) құрамындағы физикалық, физико-химиялық, кристалдық (химиялық) байланыстағы судың ыдырап диффузиялық жолмен сыртқы ортаға шығарылуын жатқызуға болады.

Құрамында отын бөлшектері бар полифазалық керамикалық үлгілерді қыздыру барысында өтетін осындай өзгерістер, негізінен олардың құрамындағы негізгі компоненттер—минералдарының түріне байланысты. Олар каолинитті, монотермитті, монтмориллонитті, гидрослюда т.б. болып бірнеше түрге бөлінеді. Дегенмен бәріне ортақ, бірақ әртүрлі температуралар аясында жүретін процестер белгілі: мысалы осындай шикізаттардан жасалған үлгілерді қыздыру барысында 100°C температура маңайында зат бойындағы физикалық байланыстағы су буға айналып ұшып шығады. Ал 450-550°C және одан жоғары температуралар аралығында кристалдық байланыстағы су ыдырап, бөлініп шыға бастайды. Карбонаттық қосылыстар белгілі температуралар аймағында ($MgCO_3$, 410—450°C, $CaCO_3$, 890—900°C) олардың ыдырауы жүреді. Карбонаттардың ыдырау кезіндегі көмірқышқыл газының (CO_2) қылтүікті қуыстар арқылы тасымалдануы, күл керамикасындағы отын бөлшектерінің көміртегі жануы т.б. құбылыстарды жатқызуға болады[12].

Осыған ұқсас үдеріс ретінде карбонатты қоспалардың ($MgCO_3$, $CaCO_3$) диссоциациясында мысалға келтіруге болады. Аталған үдерістер белгілі температуралар аймағында эндотермиялық эффектілер, яғни қажетті жылу мөлшерін жұту арқылы жүретіндіктен оларды бұл сипаттары бойынша бірінші текті фазалық түрленулер қатарына жатқыза аламыз [4].

Бұл ғылыми мақалада қыздыру барысында полифазалық материалдардың (лай минералдарының, құрылыс материалдарының т.б.) бойында жүретін бірінші текті фазалық түрленулер термодинамикасының кейбір мәселелерін зерттеу барысында алынған теориялық және тәжірибелік нәтижелер келтірілген.

Қыздыру кезінде температуралық сандық мәліметтер жазып алынып, заттың түзу (горизонталь) бөлігіне қатысты балку температурасы анықталады[5,6]. Жүргізілген тәжірибе нәтижелеріне және шінара анықтамалық шамаларға сүйене отырып осы барысындағы энтропия өзгерісін мынадай формула көмегімен анықтауға мүмкіндік туады:

$$\Delta S = c \cdot m \frac{t_6}{t_0} + \frac{\lambda \cdot m}{t_6}, \quad (1)$$

мұндағы c - заттың меншікті жылу сыйымдылығы; m - массасы; λ - меншікті балқу жылуы; t_0 - бастапқы температурасы; t_6 - балқу температурасы.

Әйтсе де жоғарыда көрсетілген әдістің көмегімен зерттеліп отырған заттың бойында жүретін бірінші текті фазалық өзгерістің механизмін бақылауға мүмкіндік жоқ[14]. Оның себебі мынада. Әдетте қыздыру барысында заттың бойында жүретін бірінші текті фазалық ауысу үдерістері үлгінің барлық көлеміне бірден өтпейді. Ол алдымен үлгінің беттік қабатында басталып, сонан соң қажетті жағдайға қарай үлгінің ішкі қабатына қарай ығыса түседі. Қорта айтқанда бұл процесс аймақтық механизмге ие болады.

Қыздыру барысында үлгі бойында жүріп жатқан термиялық эффектілердің (эндотермиялық экзотермиялық) барысында жұтылған немесе бөлінген жылу мөлшерін мынадай жолдармен анықтауға болады. Жылу эффектісі жүріп жатқан үлгіге шығындалған жылу мөлшері

$$Q_Y = mc_Y(t_{2Y} - t_{1Y}), \quad (2)$$

мұндағы m - үлгі массасы, c_Y - үлгінің эффективті меншікті жылу сыйымдылығы, t_{2Y} - жылу эффектісі біткен кездегі үлгінің орташа температурасы, t_{1Y} - фазалық түрлену (жылу эффектісі) басталар сәттегі үлгінің орташа температурасы.

Құрамы мен құрылымы жағынан зерттеу үлгісіне өте ұқсас, бірақ бойында фазалық түрлену орын алмайтын эталон үлгіге жұмсалған жылу мөлшері

$$Q_{ЭТ} = mc_{ЭТ}(t_{2ЭТ} - t_{1ЭТ}), \quad (3)$$

мұндағы $c_{ЭТ}$ - эталон үлгінің меншікті жылу сыйымдылығы, $t_{2ЭТ}$ - зерттеу үлгісінде фазалық түрлену біткен сәттегі эталон үлгінің орташа температурасы, $t_{1ЭТ}$ - фазалық түрлену басталар сәттегі эталон үлгінің орташа температурасы[7,8].

Кейбір жағдайларда эталон ретінде бойында фазалық түрленулер жүріп өткен үлгіні қайтадан тура сондай жағдайда қыздыру арқылы пайдалануға болады.

Жоғарыда келтірілген теңдеулерді пайдаланып үлгідегі фазалық түрленуге, мысалы эндотермиялық эффект орын алған жағдайда шығындалған жылу мөлшерін былай анықтауға болады

$$\Delta Q_{эф} = Q_Y - Q_{ЭТ} = m[c_Y(t_{2Y} - t_{1Y}) - c_{ЭТ}(t_{2ЭТ} - t_{1ЭТ})] \quad (4)$$

Егер фазалық түрлену басталар және аяқталар сәттегі үлгімен эталонның орташа температуралары шамамен бірдей болса, яғни $t_{1Y} = t_{1ЭТ} = t_1$; $t_{2Y} = t_{2ЭТ} = t_2$, онда (3) теңдеу мынадай ықшамдалған түрге ие болады

$$\Delta Q_{эф} = m(c_Y - c_{ЭТ})(t_2 - t_1). \quad (5)$$

Үлгінің бойында егер экзотермиялық эффектілер орын алса (4) және (5) теңдеулердегі $\Delta Q_{эф}$ таңбасы теріс болып, ол фазалық түрлену барысында бөлінген жылу мөлшерін береді. Үлгіде жүріп жатқан бірінші текті фазалық түрленудің термодинамикасын, яғни термиялық эффект барысында жұтылған немесе бөлінген жылу мөлшерінің шамасын анықтаудың тағы бір әдісін келтірсек. Пештен бөлініп жатқан жылу мөлшерін оның қуаты арқылы өрнектеп мынадай баланстық теңдеуді жазуға болады

$$Q_Y = IU \cdot \tau_Y, \quad Q_{ЭТ} = IU \cdot \tau_{ЭТ}, \quad (6)$$

мұндағы $W_{II} = IU$ – электр пешінің қуаты, τ_Y – үлгіде t_1 – температурада басталып, t_2 – температурада біткен термиялық эффектінің жүру ұзақтығы, $\tau_{ЭТ}$ – эталонның t_1 – температурадан t_2 – температураға дейін қызып жеткен уақыты.

Келтірілген (6) теңдеуден алынатын мынадай қатынастардан

$$Q_Y = Q_{ЭТ} \frac{\tau_Y}{\tau_{ЭТ}}, \quad Q_Y - Q_{ЭТ} = \left(\frac{\tau_Y}{\tau_{ЭТ}} - 1 \right) Q_{ЭТ} \quad (7)$$

термиялық эффектінің жылу мөлшерін анықтайтын теңдеуді аламыз

$$\Delta Q_{ЭФ} = Q_Y - Q_{ЭТ} = \left(\frac{\tau_Y}{\tau_{ЭТ}} - 1 \right) c_{ЭТ} m (t_2 - t_1) \quad (8)$$

Бұл теңдеудегі $\tau_Y > \tau_{ЭТ}$ үлкен болғанда $\Delta Q_{ЭФ}$ оң мәнге ие болып, ол эндотермиялық эффект кезінде жұтылған жылу мөлшерін, ал керісінше $\tau_Y < \tau_{ЭТ}$ болғанда $\Delta Q_{ЭФ}$ таңбасы теріс болып, ол экзотермиялық эффект кезінде бөлініп шыққан жылу мөлшерін анықтауға мүмкіндік береді.

Қатты денелердегі жылуалмасу барысында жүретінкү тасымалдау құбылыстары жылу мен масса алмасу теориясында карастырылады. Жалпы жағдайда тасымалдау процестері бір өлшемді есеп үшін мынадай дифференциалды теңдеулер жүйесімен сипатталады

$$\frac{\partial t}{\partial \tau} = a_{ЭФ} \frac{\partial^2 t}{\partial x^2}; \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial \tau} = \gamma_{ЭФ} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2}; \quad (10)$$

$$\frac{\partial \varepsilon}{\partial \tau} = \mu_{ЭФ} \frac{\partial^2 \varepsilon}{\partial x^2}. \quad (11)$$

мұндағы, $a_{ЭФ}$ - эффективті температура өткізгіштік коэффициенті; t - температура; τ - уақыт; x - координата; ε - салыстырмалы ұлғаю немесе кішірею; $\gamma_{ЭФ}$ - масса тасымалдау үшін эффективті потенциал өткізгіштік; $\mu_{ЭФ}$ - эффективті кинетикалық тұтқырлық.

Практикада жоғарыдағы теңдеулерді сараптама трғыдан шешу көінде мүмкін бола бермейді. Сондықтан мұндай күрделі құбылыстарды зерттеуде, тәжірибелік, сандық, графикалық әдістер жалпылай қолданылады.

Қатты денелерді қыздыру барысында жүретін физикалық және химялық өзгерістерге байланысты байқалатын жылудық эффектілерді зерттеу тәсілдерінің ішіндегі тиімді әдістерінің біріге моделді үлгілердің дифференциалды қыздыру қисықтарын алу жатады[8].

Жоғарыда келтірілген теориялық нәтижелерден үлгілердің бойында жүретін бірінші текті фазалық түрленулердің термодинамикасын анықтап, бағалау үшін осы мақсатта арнайы жүргізілген тәжірибелік зерттеулердің нәтижелері қажет екендігін байқаймыз.

Зерттеу нәтижелері және талқылау

Көптеген жылдар бойы Абай атындағы ҚазҰПУ-нің Математика, Физика және Информатика институтының жанында «Қолданбалы жылу физикасы және жаңа технологиялар» ғылыми зерттеу және оқу лабораториясы жұмыс атқарып келеді. Оның базасында жаңа қор үнемдегіш полифазалық керамикалық материалдар технологиясын әзірлеу барысында олардың бойында жүретін табиғаттары әртүрлі фазалық және химиялық

түрленулер кезіндегі күрделі жылу және масса алмасу үдерістерін жан-жақты зерттеу бағытында жақсы тәжірибе жинақталып, көптеген ғылыми еңбектер жарияланды.

Тәжірибелік зерттеу жұмыстарын жүргізу техникасын қысқаша төмендегіше сипаттауымызға болады. Дифференциалды қыздыру қисықтарын алу үшін бірінші термопара үлгінің беткі қабатына, ал екінші термопара оның центріне орналастырылады да олардың ұштары электронды потенциометрге қосылады. Содан соң бұл үлгі электр пешінде белгілі температуралық режимде қыздырылады[9]. Қыздыру процесі кезінде алдымен шикі үлгінің (әлі күйдірілмеген үлгі) дифференциалды қисықтары жазылып алынады. Содан кейін дәл осы жағдайда эталонды, яғни алдын-ала күйдірілген үлгіні қыздыру барысында аталған дифференциалды қисықтар жазып алынады.

Одан әрі шикі үлгіні үлгі деп, ал күйдірілген үлгіні эталон деп белгілейік. Зерттелетін үлгі мен эталон үшін алынған дифференциалды қыздыру қисықтарын салыстыра отырып, шикі үлгі бойында фазалық және химиялық түрленулерге байланысты жүретін жылу эффектілерін байқап зерттеуге болады[10,11].

Осы жұмыстардың нәтижелеріне сүйене отырып, жоғарыда келтірілген теңдеулерді іс жүзінде қолдануға нақты бір мысал қарастырайық. Зерттеу нысаны ретінде монотермитті полифазалық лай шикі затынан пластикалық тәсілмен дайындалған цилиндрлік үлгілер ($d=50\text{мм}$, $h=105\text{мм}$) алынды.

Қалыптан жаңа шыққан үлгілер әуелі бөлме жағдайында біраз дегдітіліп, сонан - соң кептіргіш электр шкафында (СНОЛ типті) $100-110^{\circ}\text{C}$ жағдайында 4-6% қалдық ылғалдылыққа дейін кептірілді. Кептірілген үлгінің ортаңғы бөлігінің центрі мен беткі қабатына пластина - платинородий термопаралары орналастырылды. Осылайша дайындалған монотермитті үлгілер арнайы тәжірибелік қондырғының электронды басқарғыш тетігі бар муфелді электр пешінде (СНОЛ типті) тұрақты жылдамдықпен, яғни сызықтық заңдылықпен қыздырылды.

Қыздыру барысында термопаралардың көрсеткіші потенциометр көмегімен үздіксіз жазылып отырды. Үлгі шектік температураға жетіп күйдірілгеннен соң, ол бастапқы температураға дейін суытылып, тұра сондай режимде қайта қыздырылды. Сонымен бұл тәжірибелерде эталон ретінде алдын ала күйдірілген үлгілер алынды. Монотермитті цилиндрлік үлгілер отқа төзімді сымның көмегімен электронды таразыға іліну арқылы тәжірибелік қондырғының пеш камерасына салынып термогравиметрлік зерттеулер жүргізілді. Бұл жағдайда да қыздыру режимі сызықтық заңдылықпен өтіп тұра алдыңғы тәжірибелердегідей болды.

Осылайша жүргізілген тәжірибелер нәтижесінде алынған мәліметтер негізінде монотермитті цилиндрлік үлгі мен эталонның қыздыру барысындағы температуралық өрістері мен үлгі массасының өзгерісін сипаттайтын кинетикалық қисықтар графиктер түрінде салынды. Осындай тәжірибелік жолмен алынған үлгі мен эталонның температуралық және кинетикалық қисықтарын салыстыра отырып, $500-900^{\circ}\text{C}$ температуралар аралығында алғашқысының бойында орын алған эндотермиялық эффектіні анық байқауға болады [12].

Керамикалық үлгіні күйдіру барысында жоғарыда айтылған фазалық өзгерістерді байқалып, соның әсерінен белгілі температурадағы сұйық балқымалар пайда болады. Бөлінген газдың қысымымен осы сұйық балқымалы орындарда көптеген микроқуыстар түзіліп, үлгі бойында құрылымдық өзгерістер жүреді.

Әдетте сұйық балқымалардың пайда болуына ең әуелі бұйым бойындағы темір тотықтарының қалыптасуы, сондай-ақ жеңіл балқитын шыны түйіршіктері әсер етеді. Күтіліп отырған бұйымның мықты болуы оның бойында муллит кристалдарының пайда болуына тікелей байланысты. Керамикалық материалдарда балқитын осы өзгерістерді газды қалыптастырғыш ортада жедел жүретіндігі белгілі болып отыр.

Күл керамикасынан жасалатын материалдарды күйдіру кезінде оның бойындағы кокс түйіршіктерінің жануы үлгі ішінде газды қалыптастырғыш ортаның пайда болуына жағдай жасайды. Екінші жағынан, жану процестері болып жатқан ортада температура тез ауытқып, жоғарылайды. Міне, осы ерекшеліктер күл керамикасының бойындағы фазалық өзгерістердің қолайлы жағдайда әрі тез өтуіне мүмкіндік туғызады. Екіншіден, біз жоғарыда айтып кеткен күл материалдарының құрамындағы муллит түйіршіктері, шыны бөлшектері өте берік материалдардың дайындалуына кепілдік береді.

Бұл эффектіні монотермит бойындағы кристалдық байланыстағы судың ыдырап, үлгіден диффузиялық жолмен сыртқы ортаға шығуымен яғни оның дегидратациясымен түсіндіруге болады. Бұл құбылысты оның сипаты бойынша бірінші текті фазалық түрленуге жатқызуға болады.

Алынған тәжірибелік нәтижелердің тағы бір маңыздылығы, олардың негізінде дифференциалды жылуөткізгіштік теңдеуінің (9) аналитикалық шешімінен туындайтын мынадай өрнектер көмегімен үлгілердің температура өткізгіштік коэффициенті ($a_{эф}$) мен меншікті жылу сыйымдылығын (c) анықтауға болатындығында

$$a_{эф} = \frac{bR^2}{2(\Gamma+1)[t_6(\tau) - t_{ц}(\tau)]}, \quad (8)$$

мұндағы b – тұрақты қыздыру жылдамдығы, R – цилиндрлік үлгінің радиусы, Γ – тұрақты сан, цилиндр үшін $\Gamma=1$, $t_6(\tau)$ мен $t_{ц}(\tau)$ – қыздыру барысындағы үлгі беті мен центрінің температуралары

$$c_{эф} = \frac{\lambda}{a_{эф}\rho}, \quad (9)$$

мұндағы λ – үлгілердің жылуөткізгіштік коэффициентінің орташа мәні, ρ – үлгінің тығыздығы. Есептеулер монотермитті үлгінің a және c коэффициентінің эффективті мәндерінің дегидратация барысында эндотермиялық эффектiге байланысты айтарлықтай аралықтарда өзгертіндігін көрсетті. Ал эталонда бұл шамалардың ауытқуы өте аз.

Енді осы келтірілген тәжірибелік зерттеулер нәтижелерін қолдана отырып, монотермитті үлгілердің дегидратациясы кезіндегі бірінші текті фазалық түрленулердің термодинамикасын талдап көрейік.

Монотермитті үлгідегі эндотермиялық үдеріс кезінде (500 - 900°C) жұтылған жылу мөлшерін анықтауға қажетті термодинамикалық шамалардың орташа мәндері тәжірибелік зерттеулер нәтижесінде мынадай болды:

$$m = 0,34 \text{ кг}; \quad c_{\gamma} = 2,63 \frac{\text{кДж}}{\text{кг} \cdot ^\circ\text{C}}; \quad c_{эТ} = 1,0 \frac{\text{кДж}}{\text{кг} \cdot ^\circ\text{C}};$$

$$t_{1\gamma} = 483^\circ\text{C}; \quad t_{2\gamma} = 882^\circ\text{C}; \quad t_{1эТ} = 492^\circ\text{C}; \quad t_{2эТ} = 880^\circ\text{C}.$$

Осы келтірілген тәжірибелік мәндерді пайдаланып (3) теңдеуден есептеу нәтижесінде мынаны аламыз

$$\Delta Q_{эф} = 225 \text{ кДж}$$

Бұл массасы $m = 0,34\text{кг}$ болатын монотермитті үлгідегі дегидратация барысындағы бірінші текті фазалық түрлену кезінде жұтылған толық жылу мөлшері.

Енді термогравиметриялық зерттеу нәтижесінде белгілі болған дегидратация барысында (500 - 900°C) үлгіден бөлініп шыққан кристалдық (химиялық) байланыстағы судың массасын $m_d = 0,034$ кг екенін біле отырып, фазалық түрленудің меншікті жылуын (q_d) анықтай аламыз

$$q_d = \frac{\Delta Q_{эф}}{m_d} = \frac{225}{0.034} = 6618 \frac{\text{Дж}}{\text{кг}}$$

Егер жуықтап үлгі мен эталонның дегидратация, яғни эндотермиялық эффект басталар сәттегі (t_1) және аяқталған сәттегі (t_2) температуралардың орташа мәндерін бірдей деп алсақ ($t_1 = t_{1у} = t_{1эТ} = 488^\circ\text{C}$; $t_2 = t_{2у} = t_{2эТ} = 881^\circ\text{C}$), онда (4) теңдеу бойынша эндотермиялық эффекті кезінде шығындалған жылу мөлшері мынаған тең болады

$$\Delta Q_{эф} = 218 \text{ кДж.}$$

Ал осыған сәйкес дегидратация кезіндегі фазалық түрленудің меншікті жылуы мынаған тең болады екен

$$q_d = \frac{\Delta Q_{эф}}{m_d} = \frac{218}{0.034} = 6412 \frac{\text{кДж}}{\text{кг}}$$

Қорытынды

Бұл алынған мәндерді алдыңғы нәтижелермен салыстырып қарасақ, олардың бірінен айырмашылығы шамамен үш пайыздай ғана болатындығына көз жеткіземіз. Сонымен жоғарыда келтірілген ғылыми – әдістемелік нәтижелер полифазалық керамикалық материалдардағы фазалық түрленулердің термодинамикасын бағалап, олардың нәтижелерін технологиялық есептеулерде қолдануға мүмкіндік береді.

Пайданылған әдебиеттер тізімі:

1. Баймолда Д., Чехак Т., Құлбек М.Қ., Хамраев Ш.И., Ерженбек Б., Айтан Н. Полифазалық үлгілердегі «Құлбек сақиналары» -деген атпен белгілі болған концентрлі-зоналық түрлі түсті бояулық эффектілерді рентгенфлуоресценттік әдісімен зерттеу// Вестник КазНПУ имени Абая. Серия Физико-математические науки, № 3 (67)., 2019г. –с.135-140.
2. Құлбек М. Қ., Баймолда Д., Айтан Н. Золочермикалық материалдарда анықталған жаңа концентрлі-зоналық түрлі-түсті бояулық жолақтардың химиялық құрамын зерттеу// Вестник КазНПУ имени Абая. Серия Физико-математические науки, № 3 (71)., 2020г. –с.106-110.
3. Құлбек М.Қ., Хамраев Ш.И., Джаксигельдинова Э.А. Молекулалық физика пәніндегі «Фазалық түрленулер» тақырыбын оқытуға қатысты ғылыми-әдістемелік ұсыныстар // «Жаңартылған білім беру мазмұны жағдайында мектеп пен жоғары оқу орындарында математика мен физиканы оқытудың өзекті мәселелері» Халықаралық ғылыми-практикалық конференцияның материалдары 25-26 қараша 2021 жыл, Абай атындағы ҚазҰПУ, Алматы, Б. 245-248.
4. Neuman, E.W.; Brown-Shaklee, H.J.; Hilmas, G.E.; Fahrenholtz, W.G. Titanium diboride-silicon carbide-boron carbide ceramics with super-high hardness and strength. J. Am. Ceram. Soc. 2017, 101, 497–501.

5. Clark, B.M.; Tumurugoti, P.; Sundaram, S.K.; Amoroso, J.W.; Marra, J.C.; Shuthanandan, V.; Tang, M. Radiation damage of hollandite in multiphase ceramic waste forms. *J. Nucl. Mater.* 2017, 494, 61–66.
6. Li GR, Lv BW, Yang GJ, et al. Relationship between lamellar structure and elastic modulus of thermally sprayed thermal barrier coatings with intra-splat cracks. *J Therm Spray Technol* 2015, 24: 1355-1367.
7. Robert F. Tournier. Multiple Glass Transitions in Bismuth and Tin beyond Melting Temperatures. *Metals* 2022, 12 (12) , 2085.
8. Chen HF, Zhang C, Liu YC, et al. Recent progress in thermal/environmental barrier coatings and their corrosion resistance. *Rare Met* 2020, 39: 498-512
9. Zhao ZF, Chen H, Xiang HM, et al. High entropy defective fluorite structured rare-earth niobates and tantalates for thermal barrier applications. *J Adv Ceram* 2020, 9: 303-311.
10. 雷旭, 宋慧平, 薛芳斌, 程芳琴.粉煤灰基混凝土防腐涂料的制备及其性能研究[J]. *涂料工业*, 2019, 49 (01) : 22-26.
11. 姜龙.燃煤电厂粉煤灰综合利用现状及对我国的启示[J/OL].*洁净煤技术*, 2016 (02) : 1-10.
12. 于海鹏. 煤颗粒燃烧过程中的热解及焦燃烧行为模拟研究[J]. *煤化工*, 2021, 49(4): 34-40.
13. М.К. Кулбеков. О новых объемно-поверхностных концентрически-зональных цветовых эффектах в золокерамических материалах// *Вестник КазНПУ имени Абая. Серия Физико-математические науки*, № 1(57)., 2017г. –с.121-124.
14. Federov, S.V. Energy balance of friction and friction coefficient in energetical interpretation. *Tribol. Ind.*2015,37, 380–389.

The need for developing new technologies using cyber-physical systems to create smart factories. Systems and Indicators in Kazakhstan's Industry 4.0

Beket Baiganov

FGP 3GP SC Technical Interface Team Admin at Novus-Bolashak LLP. Bachelor's Degree in Engineering and Technology with a major in Instrumentation from Zhangir Khan West-Kazakhstan Agrarian-Technical University

Abstract

This article draws conclusions about the consequences of the Industry 4.0 process, the so-called smart manufacturing, which represents the fourth generation of the industrial revolution, as well as the factors influencing this process.

This study examines the types of technological infrastructure that can be assessed within the framework of Industry 4.0 for the economy of Kazakhstan. On the way to the list of 50 countries, it is important to assess the level of development of Kazakhstan in terms of technological employment in Industry 4.0. To change the economy of Kazakhstan, it is necessary to create competitive production, and this will help the competitive economies of countries to take advantage of the opportunities of other changes in the 21st century. Accordingly, there is an urgent need to introduce technology and science into production.

By examining the impact of research and education on technological change and transformation we can draw a conclusion about the development process of Kazakhstan during the fourth industrial revolution.

Keywords: Fourth Industrial Revolution, Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS), technological advancements, innovation, research and development initiatives, technological goods.

Introduction

First time the concept of “Industry 4.0” originated and emerged in Germany in 2011. Industry 4.0 is a manufacturing technology that employs modern smart technologies and automated methods at every stage of production.

This novel phenomenon encompasses terms such as cloud technology, the Internet of Things, virtual reality analytics, big data, and the digital economy. The rise of Industry 4.0, backed by Germany, stems from China strengthening its position in global markets and expanding its production network, adversely impacting trade relations among European countries [1]. The need for developing new technologies for Germany has been revealed by this situation, and the process of Industry 4.0 has been started. Industry 4.0 relies on using cyber-physical systems (CPS) to create intelligent factories.

Industry 4.0 relies on the use of cyber-physical systems that contribute to the formation of intelligent production facilities [2]. It represents a fusion of technologies and concepts within

organizations that are linked to the creation cost. The distinctive features of Industry 4.0 are detailed below [3]:

- It won't work without computer systems;
- Clever manufacturing needs computer systems;
- The system will get stronger with the laws in place;
- It will keep growing with new ways of doing business.

In the context of the new reality and the challenges of adapting to remote work, Industry 4.0 allows businesses to be ready for unexpected events, like the coronavirus pandemic. The purpose of this study is to highlight the steps to be taken based on the analysis of the quality of R&D spending in Kazakhstan during the fourth industrial revolution. Understanding the fourth industrial revolution is crucial in guiding Kazakhstan's direction in this era. Assessing Kazakhstan's readiness for Industry 4.0 in terms of technological infrastructure is vital for its position among the top 50 developed countries.

So far, Industry 4.0 implementation has progressed significantly, and no country can afford to ignore it. Many countries, including Germany, China, Mexico, Italy, Latvia, and Russia, have adopted government programs to enhance industry competitiveness using Industry 4.0 technologies. The shift to Industry 4.0 is driven by the opportunity to boost enterprise competitiveness through cost optimization, the creation of new revenue streams, the identification of new market niches, improvements in working conditions, and a reduction in workplace accidents and injuries [4].

The pandemic has sped up the use of Industry 4.0 technologies, allowing for remote communication and organizing production processes with minimal human involvement. It's likely that there will be changes to the projects for 2022-2025. The impact will largely depend on the industries that are more or less developed. Industries with many non-digitalized production processes will be the most affected.

Talking about the advantages of using Industry 4.0 technologies, they made it possible to shift production to remote mode quickly. New production, like protective screens and fan spare parts, was even set up. Additionally, technologies like big data analysis, sensors, and telematics help in doing work quickly and efficiently. They also enable timely reactions and adjustments to production processes through remote access.

Discussion

To accomplish the study's goals, there was used a summary and analytical methods of research papers in this area. This article will discuss articles and seasonal publications about the Fourth Industrial Revolution from other countries. Additionally, there is gathered official statistics and evaluated Kazakhstan's technological setup. Also, the digital literacy of the people in Kazakhstan is shown, the research and development activities happening there, innovation markers, and the portion of innovative products contributing to Kazakhstan's GDP.

Figure 1 – Indicators of ICT use in organizations (%) (excluding public administration organizations)¹

Government programs aimed at making industries more competitive using Industry 4.0 technologies have been adopted in various countries such as Germany, China, Mexico, Italy, Latvia, and Russia. This shift to Industry 4.0 is driven by the opportunity to boost enterprise competitiveness through cost optimization, the creation of new revenue streams, the identification of new market niches, improvements in working conditions, and a reduction in workplace accidents and injuries.

¹Compiled by the authors of the Statistics Committee of the Ministry of National Economy of the Republic of Kazakhstan (<https://stat.gov.kz/>)

COVID-19 has acted as a trigger for introducing Industry 4.0 technologies, not only in countries with established government programs but also in those without a uniform policy for Industry 4.0 development.

During a pandemic, Industry 4.0 becomes an effective way for businesses to adapt to rapidly changing conditions and serves as a survival tool in competition. Companies and countries slow to implement digital technologies during a pandemic are likely to suffer the most, risking lagging behind in technological development and failing to integrate into global value chains, leading to a loss of competitiveness.

The question arises: *Is Kazakhstan ready for a prolonged pandemic with Industry 4.0?* Currently, most industrial enterprises are continuing projects to implement Industry 4.0 technologies. Typically, these projects were approved in the previous period, and those planned for 2020 will proceed. There may be adjustments for projects scheduled for 2022-2025. The pandemic has accelerated the adoption of Industry 4.0 technologies that facilitate remote communication and enable organizing processes in production with minimal human involvement. The impact will largely depend on the development of different industries.

In recent years, Kazakhstan's technological readiness has become crucial, especially in the context of the ongoing fourth industrial revolution. Kazakhstan plays a significant role as a link between Europe and Asia in the spread of this revolution, thanks to its geopolitical location. Assessing Kazakhstan's technological infrastructure is vital for it to be included among the top 50 developed countries.

Evaluating Kazakhstan's technology indicators is crucial as it strives to keep pace with the evolving fourth industrial revolution. Analyzing Graphic 1 help explain the state of communication infrastructure in Kazakhstan. Graph 1 data reveals that while computer usage and internet access are relatively high in businesses, ownership of websites lags far behind [5].

In recent years, the number of internet users aged 16-74 per 100 people has seen a significant rise. This trend aligns with the global increase in internet users, and our country is no exception. In 2009, this figure was 15 people, and by 2010, it had doubled to reach 32 people. Between 2012 and 2015, the number stabilized at 68 people.

The number of customers in 2019 is 83. According to this schedule, there is an increase in the number of internet users. In general, if we compare the indicators of 2019 with 2009, there is an increase of 68 people. The relative indicator has dynamically increased by 100 people.

Consider that nowadays, people mostly use smartphones for talking and socializing, academic use.

Table 1 – Level of digital literacy of the population of the Republic of Kazakhstan aged 6-74 (%)

	The share of people who have acquired skills				
	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Use any of the 4 types of technology listed in the Note	74,9	73,6	76,1	76,8	79,1
Use of the list of basic types (paragraphs 1, 2, 3 and 6 of the note)	60,8	68,1	70,4	79,3	84,5
Personal computer, smartphone, tablet, laptop; standard programs; Use of Internet services and services	77,1	79,6	82,1	84,1	87,3
Personal computer, smartphone, tablet, laptop; use of standard programs	79,9	83,2	81,4	83,1	85,4

When we look at how much Kazakhstan spends on research and development compared to its overall economy it can be seen that Kazakhstan is falling behind the global average and countries with high incomes. However, in Kazakhstan, the spending on research has actually gone down in recent years compared to the early 2000s. In the years 2000-2009, the average spending on research as a percentage of GDP was 0.23%, but in recent years, it has dropped to 0.12%. While R&D spending is increasing worldwide, it's decreasing in Kazakhstan [6].

The types of companies doing research and development (R&D) in Kazakhstan have changed over the years. In 2003, there were 273 R&D organizations in the country, and by 2019, this number had increased to 386. That's a growth of about 41.4% in 11 years. Out of these 386 businesses in 2019, 100 were owned by the government, 92 were in higher education, 158 were private, and 36 were non-profit. So, most R&D companies in the country are owned by private individuals or businesses.

In terms of creating awareness about innovation, it's clear that the private sector has recognized and valued R&D work in recent years. When we look at all the operating businesses, it seems that government-owned enterprises are not doing enough in terms of innovation. Many developed countries have boosted their economies by supporting innovation with government spending.

Importance is to think about that lasting growth might not happen for a long time because capital becomes less effective. So, for long-term growth, we need innovation—ideas from outside—and a shift to using more capital and technology in production. In this situation, it's important to back technological investments, especially in manufacturing.

Conclusion

Even though many people in Kazakhstan use technology like mobile devices and computers, it's not enough. While internet use is increasing in our country, it's still lower compared to other countries. The recent significant increase in internet usage in Kazakhstan is positive, making information technologies more accessible. This is crucial for catching up with Industry 4.0, but we need to look at specific areas of internet usage.

To become one of the world's top 50 developed countries, Kazakhstan must boost its innovative potential. Instead of spreading efforts across various projects, it's better to consolidate resources for innovative projects. Focus on creating innovative venture firms like "business angels," establish research and technology-focused centers in every region of Kazakhstan, and enhance tax incentives to attract investors. Developing public-private partnerships is also essential. To enhance global competitiveness, Kazakhstan must focus on creating and exporting new technology products. As we move towards Industry 4.0, Kazakhstan should follow Germany and the USA by establishing a commission for the fourth industrial revolution. The primary goal should be determining specific measures for Industry 4.0, guiding R&D spending and innovation in the country.

References:

1. Emara, N., & Kasa, H. (2021). The non-linear relationship between financial access and domestic savings: the case of emerging markets. *Applied Economics*, 53(3), 345-363.
2. Gentner, S. (2016). Industry 4.0: reality, future or just science fiction? How to convince today's management to invest in tomorrow's future! Successful strategies for industry 4.0 and manufacturing IT. *Chimia*, 70(9), 628-628.
3. Ibarra, D., Ganzarain, J., & Igartua, J. I. (2018). Business model innovation through Industry 4.0: A review. *Procedia manufacturing*, 22, 4-10.
4. Simmert, B., Ebel, P. A., Peters, C., Bittner, E. A. C., & Leimeister, J. M. (2019). Conquering the Challenge of Continuous Business Model Improvement: Design of a Repeatable Process. *Business & Information Systems Engineering*, 61, 451-468.
5. Javaid, M., Haleem, A., Vaishya, R., Bahl, S., Suman, R., & Vaish, A. (2020). Industry 4.0 technologies and their applications in fighting COVID-19 pandemic. *Diabetes & Metabolic Syndrome: Clinical Research & Reviews*, 14(4), 419-422.
6. Dalenogare, L. S., Benitez, G. B., Ayala, N. F., & Frank, A. G. (2018). The expected contribution of Industry 4.0 technologies for industrial performance. *International Journal of production economics*, 204, 383-394.

Chemical Sciences

SYNTHESIS OF BIFUNCTIONAL CATALYSTS BASED ON MESOPOROUS ALUMINOSILICATES FOR HYDROAROMATIZATION OF MODEL COMPOUNDS

Abdrassilova Albina

PhD student, Al-Farabi Kazakh National University

Vassilina Gulzira

Candidate of chemical sciences, senior lecturer, Al-Farabi Kazakh National University

1. Introduction

Currently, new catalytic systems are being studied to address energy and environmental challenges. In the field of renewable energy, increasing the aromatic content of diesel fuels is an essential consideration because it lowers the fuel's quality and can result in harmful emissions when burned [1]. One way to reduce the aromatic content is by converting aromatic compounds into cyclic alkanes. This can increase the cetane number of the fuel and improve its quality [2]. Mesoporous aluminosilicates promoted with nickel and molybdenum catalysts have shown promise in the hydroprocessing of aromatic hydrocarbons, contributing to their effectiveness and efficiency.

2. Experimental procedure

Mesoporous aluminosilicates synthesized using the templating method and activated bentonite were utilized as carriers for bifunctional catalysts. Hexadecylamine was used as a templating agent. The composite consisted of mesoporous aluminosilicates and activated bentonite in a 35/65 (mass %) ratio. The obtained catalysts were promoted with nickel and molybdenum. G. Vassilina et al. provided complete description of the synthesis methodology [3].

The samples were characterized by means of conventional techniques: SEM, N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherms at 77, XRD, FTIR, and ICP-AES.

The study of the catalytic properties of bifunctional catalysts based on mesoporous aluminosilicate and bentonite in the conversion of n-hexadecane-methylnaphthalene was conducted. A specialized batch reactor was used to investigate the catalytic performance. The following conditions were applied to the reactor: a temperature range of 240-360°C and H₂ pressure 3 MPa.

3. Results and discussion.

The visual morphology of synthesized mesoporous aluminosilicates was examined using scanning electron microscopy (SEM). SEM images reveal ordered hexagonal arrays of mesopores with uniform pores.

The nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms of the synthesized samples, according to the International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry (IUPAC) standards, are classified as Type IV with a more pronounced hysteresis loop closer to H4. Type IV isotherms demonstrate a narrow pore size distribution ranging from 2 to 50 nm. Furthermore, the hysteresis loop at relative pressures exceeding $P/P_0=0.4$ indicates the presence of mesopores [4].

Furthermore, the synthesized materials differ in specific surface area, average pore diameter, and pore volume. For instance, mesoporous aluminosilicate (MAS), Ni-MAS-H-bentonite, and Mo-MAS-H-bentonite have specific surface areas of 375.1, 214.9, and 161.6 m^2/g , respectively. The reduction in specific surface area and pore volume suggests that some pores in the catalyst structure are blocked by Ni and Mo metals. The pore size distribution of the carrier and catalyst materials is relatively narrow. In the case of promoted catalysts, a bimodal pore size distribution was observed in the lower range of pore sizes.

The amorphous nature of the mesoporous aluminosilicate is confirmed by X-ray diffraction analysis. The sample exhibits only a broad halo in the 2θ range from 40° to 60° , which is characteristic of the amorphous nature of the material. The XRD peaks of the bifunctional catalysts Ni-MAS-H-bentonite and Mo-MAS-H-bentonite indicate that these samples have a crystalline structure without any traces of amorphous material.

The mesoporous structure of the synthesized samples was confirmed by infrared spectroscopy (FTIR). The corresponding peaks detected at 807.36 cm^{-1} , 803.52 cm^{-1} , and 789.29 cm^{-1} indicate the presence of Si-O-Si and Si-O-Al bonds, which are characteristic of aluminosilicates.

The obtained catalysts showed activity in the hydrogenation of 2-methylnaphthalene in n-hexadecane. It was found that the Ni-MAS-H-bentonite and Mo-MAS-H-bentonite catalysts exhibited high activity and selectivity in the hydrodearomatization process.

References:

1. Wan, G., Duan, A., Zhao, Z., Jiang, G., Zhang, D., Li, R., Chung, K. H. $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-TiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-TiO}_2\text{-SiO}_2$ Composite-Supported Bimetallic Pt-Pd Catalysts for the Hydrodearomatization and Hydrodesulfurization of Diesel Fuel // *Energy & Fuels*. – 2009 – V. 23. – P.81-85.
2. Ran, T., Baojian, S., Fucun, W., Chunxi, L., & Chunming, X. Ni/W-USY catalyst for high diesel yield and deep hydrodearomatization // *Energy and Fuels*. – 2009 – V. 23. – P.55-59.
3. Vassilina G., Umbetkaliyeva K., Abdrassilova A., Vassilina T., Zakirov Zh. The mesoporous aluminosilicate application as support for bifunctional catalysts for n-hexadecane hydroconversion // *Open Chemistry*. – 2022. – V. 20. – P. 225-236.
4. Li Q., Wu Zh., Tu B., Park S.S., Ha Ch-S, Zhao D. Highly hydrothermal stability of ordered mesoporous aluminosilicates Al-SBA-15 with high Si/Al ratio // *Microporous and Mesoporous Materials*. – 2010. – V. 135. – P. 95-104.

Sociological Sciences

DETERMINING GENDER IDENTITY AMONG BENEFICIARIES OF THE CENTER “TEN QOGAM”

ERKEZHAN MARAT

Students of Al-Farabi Kazakh National University, Almaty, Kazakhstan

ABAY AIDAROV

Students of Al-Farabi Kazakh National University, Almaty, Kazakhstan

AIZHAN SHABDENOVA

PhD, Senior Lecturer at the Department of Sociology and Social Work of Al-Farabi Kazakh National University

Abstract: This paper presents the results of a sociological study conducted at the "TEN QOGAM" social support center in Almaty in late 2022. The study examines the interplay between gender and disability, existing gender attitudes and stereotypes among the center's beneficiaries, as well as the challenges hindering individuals with special needs from full inclusion in an inclusive society. Qualitative research methods, including focus groups and expert interviews, were employed in this study. Three focus groups were conducted with beneficiaries of the "TEN QOGAM" center.

Gender plays a significant role in the successful inclusion of people with disabilities in an inclusive society. The study documented the existence of stigmatization of individuals with disabilities by society. The implementation of an inclusive society is constrained by various issues, including those related to values and traditions, resource limitations, and organizational challenges. The lack of both quantitative and qualitative research on the gender identity of individuals with disabilities, as well as the absence of accessible representative data, restricts the comprehensive and multi-level approaches to studying this subject.

The findings underscore the importance of collaboration between non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and social support entities.

Keywords: Disability, Gender, Identity, Social Inequality, Socialization, Stigmatization, NGO, Civil sector

1. INTRODUCTION

The issues surrounding people with disabilities are gaining increasing social importance due to the steadily growing number of individuals within this demographic. Furthermore, the imperative to implement an inclusive model of Kazakhstani society, where people with disabilities are fully integrated into all facets of life while upholding principles of equality and tolerance, further underscores the significance of these issues. Remarkably, gender aspects of disability have received significantly less attention, particularly concerning the gender identity of individuals with special needs, their gender socialization, and their self-realization within the family institution. This relative neglect can be attributed, in part, to the prevailing medical model of disability, which

primarily views individuals with special needs as patients in need of care and rehabilitation, largely neglecting their gender identity and sexuality.

Gender emerges as a critical factor influencing an individual's experience of disability, as evidenced by pertinent statistics from the World Health Organization. Firstly, specialists working with disabled individuals often receive meager salaries, leading to a predominance of women in this field. Secondly, the academic community, including representatives of feminist perspectives, has shown limited interest in disability issues, with gender aspects often ignored in social policies related to disabled individuals. Lastly, women and children with disabilities frequently fall victim to various forms of cruelty, including physical, sexual, and emotional abuse. The intersection of gender and disability remains underrepresented in Russian sociology. While some Russian sociologists have delved into the situation of women with disabilities, the bulk of this research has been focused on women as a social group. Notably, the institutionalization of andrology, an interdisciplinary research practice employing the conceptual framework of social gender theory to analyze social phenomena and their transformations, lagged the development of feminology.

Disability arises when physical, sensory, and mental impairments intersect with societal reactions and the absence of necessary technologies or services. Remarkably, the relationship between gender and disability remained largely unexplored in post-Soviet social research, with academic discourse on this topic only emerging in the West during the 1980s under the influence of social movements (notably the works of Oliver, Fine, Asch, Morris, Murphy, and Yarskaya-Smirnova). Society, on the one hand, tends to negate the gender identity of disabled individuals, exemplified by simple but telling instances such as restroom signage in public institutions.

It is important to note that in Kazakhstan, individuals with disabilities often encounter limitations in their social participation due to the prevalence of physical barriers, lack of specially equipped transportation, inaccessible building entrances, elevators, and public spaces. Kazakhstan has initiated projects aimed at providing professional assistance to people with disabilities, with one such project being the "TEN QOGAM" social support center located in Almaty. This center offers legal counsel, high-quality assistance, training programs, masterclasses, and employment support to people with disabilities. Inspired by the success of the Almaty "TEN QOGAM" center, similar centers have been established in all regions of Kazakhstan, as highlighted by Lyazzat Kaltayeva, a prominent Kazakhstani public figure and chairwoman of the "Association of Women with Disabilities 'Shyrak'."

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The concept of an inclusive society finds its roots in the "Universal Declaration of Human Rights" (adopted by UN General Assembly resolution 217 A (III) on December 10, 1948), which underlines the right of every individual to participate fully in societal life. This declaration asserts that "Every person, as a member of society, has the right to social security and to exercise the rights necessary for the maintenance of his dignity and for the free development of his personality in the economic sphere, in the social and cultural fields through national efforts and international cooperation and in accordance with the structure and resources of each State" [2]. In alignment with this vision, Kassym-Jomart Tokayev, during the 25th St. Petersburg International Economic Forum, reaffirmed Kazakhstan's commitment to fostering an inclusive and equitable society, aimed at eradicating social inequalities [2]. This declaration set a clear direction for the future social development of Kazakhstani society.

To delve into the heart of this discourse, it is essential to grasp the concept of "gender identity." The sociological and socio-philosophical understanding of "gender identity" emerged in the latter half of the twentieth century, signifying it as a significant and multifaceted socio-psychological phenomenon that demands dedicated attention and examination, owing to its dynamic evolution across various spheres of social life. Notably, gender transcends the bounds of mere biology, extending into the realms of culture and society. Researchers J. Mani and A. Erhard define gender identity as "the identity, unity, and immutability of an individual's individuality as masculine, feminine, and ambivalent." An individual's sense of belonging to either the male or female gender is shaped by both biological factors (genetic and hormonal) and societal reactions to their assigned biological sex - be it male or female. Furthermore, the surrounding culture contributes to this identification process, culminating in the development of one's fundamental self-perception. The societal interpretations of appropriate masculinity or femininity play a pivotal role, and these messages vary considerably based on cultural and racial affiliations. Notably, parental guidance can be potent enough to supersede genetic and physical gender foundations, illustrating the influence of social constructs on gender identity. A widely accepted framework for analyzing the formation of gender identity is the theory of gender role socialization, although it has faced criticism in recent years by scholars like R.V. Conell, J. Stacy, B. Thorne, and S.E. Cahill [3]. Studies on the self-concept and gender identity among adults reveal that gender identity remains an evolving construct throughout one's life. Its content evolves over time, influenced by societal and cultural shifts, as well as individual agency. Self-identity, crucial in the process of constructing one's identity, is a central element. Sociologist Charles Horton Cooley, known for his concept of the "looking glass self," posited that individuals form their self-images through social interactions. According to Cooley, our consciousness is activated within a social context, thus reinforcing the notion that identity is shaped within social interactions [4].

Disability is not merely a physiological impairment or behavioral deviation but is also a social construct, often labeled as such by specific social systems where the condition is considered a deviation from the norm [5]. Changing one's social environment or moving to a different social group can result in the removal or alteration of this label, thereby limiting its impact on an individual's capabilities. In everyday interactions, gender is consistently expressed in various situations. Importantly, these situations not only allow for the expression of natural gender differences but also actively construct and produce these differences. When an individual's behavior deviates from societal expectations based on their gender identification, it can disrupt established norms. The socio-constructivist approach in gender studies posits that gender identity and gender categorization emerge through interaction when others respond to an individual in a specific manner. Gender identity encompasses an individual's ongoing actions and behaviors during interactions with others, making it an integral part of one's personality. In contrast, the gender role approach underscores distinctions between genders, the prevalence of rigid culturally formed gender schemas, and the promotion of gender-conforming activities. On the other hand, the gender approach seeks to neutralize and mitigate gender differences, encourage free choice of gender identity, blur culturally defined gender schemas, and allow deviations from traditional patriarchal societal models. Therefore, the mechanism of gender identity formation is intrinsically linked to societal standards of masculinity and femininity, cultural and value orientations, and historically defined societal models [6].

3.METHODOLOGY

The research was carried out at the TEN QOGAM Social Support Center in Almaty during late 2022, with the primary focus being individuals with specific needs who are beneficiaries of

the center's services. The central objective of this study was to investigate gender identity and the integration of individuals with disabilities into an inclusive societal framework. The research methodology employed in this study amalgamates qualitative strategies to analyze the viewpoints and attitudes of individuals with disabilities within Kazakhstani society.

4. RESEARCH PROCEDURE

4.1. Qualitative Research: Focus Groups

The research findings were obtained through focus groups conducted among beneficiaries of the "TEN QOGAM" center (three 120-minute focus groups) at the end of 2022. The language of communication was Kazakh and Russian. Respondent selection followed a multi-stage quota sampling method, with quota attributes including gender, age, disability group, nature of the disabling condition, and occupation. The interview guide was structured into three sections, addressing questions related to the range of services provided by the "TEN QOGAM" center, the accessibility of information (courses, training, consultations), and employment opportunities (work, internships, business ventures).

Among the individuals with special needs surveyed, 48% were women and 52% were men, aligning well with the proportional gender distribution among individuals with special needs in Almaty. According to data from the "Social Protection of Persons with Disabilities" information portal as of March 11, 2023, the population of individuals with special needs in Almaty amounts to 56,989, with a gender breakdown of 54% men (31,023) and 46% women (25,966) [6].

In terms of age, participants fell into the following categories: under 30 years – 33%, 30–40 years – 37%, and over 40 years – 30%. Based on disability group, the distribution was: Group I – 30%, Group II – 35%, and Group III – 35%. Regarding the nature of the disabling condition, participants included individuals with musculoskeletal disabilities (26%), visual impairments (35%), other health-related disabilities (13%), wheelchair users (9%), and hearing impairments (17%). It is essential to note that the research was conducted in Almaty, and the generalizability of its results to other regions of Kazakhstan is limited.

The primary hypothesis of this study posits that the implementation of an inclusive society in Kazakhstani society is hindered by the stigmatization of individuals with special needs, a situation exacerbated by gender disparities.

4.2. Qualitative Research: Expert Interviews

Semi-structured expert interviews were conducted with employees of the "TEN QOGAM" Social Support Center. The participants were seasoned professionals with a minimum of 5 years of experience in their respective fields, holding pivotal roles within the center. The average duration of interviews ranged from 30 to 40 minutes, and the language of communication was Russian. Experts were asked questions pertaining to the research's objectives to identify the primary challenges associated with the inclusion of individuals with special needs in an inclusive society.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1. Respondents' Opinion on Gender Socialization

The initial agents of socialization for a child are their parents. To delve deeper into the research on gender socialization among individuals with disabilities, it is crucial to initiate the study of gender identity during early childhood. Psychologists such as K. Spence and K. Manheim define gender identity as a constant that takes shape in children aged 5-7 years [7]. Subsequently, its development and content enrichment occur through experiences and practices. Research

conducted by E.V. Grunt in 2016, titled "Inclusive Education in Modern Russian Schools: A Regional Aspect," indicates that children with disabilities may experience stigmatization from an early age [8].

The diversity of values hampers the successful inclusion of children in inclusive education. It is noted that one-third of parents attempt to conceal their child's health problems. A quote from a teacher with 29 years of experience in Yekaterinburg illustrates this point: "Working with a child without understanding their specific needs, especially when your values differ from the parents', is very challenging. Integrating a child into the educational environment is complex. Parents' task is to conceal their child's unique needs and make them conform to the norm. Our task is to find approaches and methods to work with these non-standard children" (Yu.V., teacher).

Furthermore, another teacher with 6 years of experience in Nizhny Tagil adds, "Perhaps, in Russia, given the lack of tolerance towards such individuals, this concealment is justified. Our children are not tolerant of such peers. They are often labeled, ridiculed, and even mocked" (A.D., teacher). Children with special needs face stigmatization, and value orientations, beliefs, stereotypes, and labels hinder their self-identification.

Consequently, the tolerant behavior of individuals towards people with special needs plays a significant role in fostering their favorable gender socialization. The research also reveals that there is stigmatization of individuals with special needs by society in Kazakhstan. Historically, Kazakhstani society has adhered to a patriarchal model, which imposes constraints on gender self-identification, as corroborated by the findings of focus groups.

For example, one participant expressed their desire for more social interaction and support: *"I rarely leave home, and I yearn to learn how to interact with people, to engage with them. I wish to gain insights into motherhood, given my cerebral palsy. However, my primary interest lies in enhancing interpersonal skills, securing employment. While people generally express their willingness to assist, our distinctive mentality hinders access to support. Within my family, my elder siblings initially opposed my desire to attend the 'TEN QOGAM' social support center. I gradually began venturing out, elucidating my destination, exploring different cities, and, after a period, they accepted it. While psychological support is undoubtedly beneficial, I aspire to receive greater support from other individuals—individuals beyond my family. I desire to cultivate friendships, to receive invitations for cinema outings, leisurely strolls, and means of transport other than taxis. My yearning extends beyond familial support to that from other people—strangers and neighbors alike. I keenly feel the absence of social interactions and long to form friendships while securing robust support, both in the professional realm and otherwise"* (woman, 26 years old).

In summary, there is no universal archetype of masculinity and femininity; rather, these constructs exhibit variations across different regions and cultures. Different cultures and historical periods depict gender dynamics in diverse contexts. Traditional male attributes encompass rationalism, advanced analytical aptitude, competence in professional endeavors, aspirations for leadership roles, and efficiency. Conversely, characteristics commonly attributed to women encompass emotional expression, heightened intuition, empathetic capacities, caregiving tendencies towards spouses and offspring, susceptibility to influence, and sociability.

Stigmatization affects not only women with disabilities but also men. A male respondent shared his concurrence with Aman, stating that he has witnessed and experienced numerous

challenges stemming from the differential treatment of individuals with disabilities (male, 27 years old).

Consequently, gender norms that allocate professional roles exclusively to men and domestic responsibilities to women adversely impact the psychological well-being of both genders. The findings of this study underscore the importance of psychological support from specialists working at the TEN QOGAM social support center for most participants.

5.2. Challenges Hindering the Realization of an Inclusive Society in Kazakhstan

Inclusion embodies the principle of ensuring equitable access to specific social services and benefits, establishing conducive conditions for all individuals, irrespective of their abilities, accomplishments, cultural and linguistic traits, mental and physical capabilities, to attain a favorable social status. It simultaneously serves as a deterrent to discrimination and a vehicle for the realization of equality ideals. However, it necessitates the creation of tailored environments to accommodate the diverse needs of all societal segments, thereby ensuring the accessibility of all social resources to individuals with disabilities.

Apart from the gender dimension, this study also investigates the accessibility of social services, infrastructure, education, and employment opportunities for beneficiaries of the TEN QOGAM center. The UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) hold significant relevance in addressing societal issues [10]. These goals extend beyond our immediate context, as they are directed towards the global advancement of United Nations member nations. The study's objectives encompass the exploration of gender and social disparities among individuals with disabilities, aligning with two of the SDGs: the promotion of gender equality and the empowerment of women and girls, as well as the reduction of inequalities within and among countries.

The successful social inclusion of individuals with disabilities hinges on the extent to which societal conditions have been established to satisfy their fundamental human needs, thereby fostering a sense of unity within the human community. A participant in the study expressed the need for enhanced outreach efforts, suggesting that individuals receiving disability status should be provided with informational booklets or flyers at the time of their initial assessment, thus ensuring their early awareness of centers like "TEN QOGAM." The participant cited the example of his own experience, where he remained unaware of such centers for several years following his disability status determination in 2017.

The accessibility of social networks is not uniform for people with special needs, posing limitations on their access to information and awareness about support centers like "TEN QOGAM." A significant portion of the focus group participants, comprising 35%, reported having visual impairments, making smartphone usage challenging. Prolonged periods of home confinement, reduced interaction with the external world, and increased isolation can deteriorate the psychological and physiological well-being of individuals with disabilities.

Addressing this, another participant emphasized the need for broader coverage of the center's activities through various media channels, extending beyond social networks. The participant highlighted the disparity in awareness levels among those undergoing medical and sanitary expert commissions (MSEC), with many being unaware of the existence and services offered by "TEN QOGAM." Therefore, the participant recommended a multifaceted approach to

raising awareness, including printed publications, television, newspapers, and news portals, in addition to the establishment of a dedicated training portal.

The participant further posited that raising awareness should not be confined solely to social platforms like Instagram, WhatsApp, and TikTok. Instead, it should be integrated into the process of MSEC, as this examination determines the social protection needs of vulnerable individuals based on quality-of-life assessments and bodily function evaluations. The passage of this examination should serve as an opportunity to introduce individuals to social support centers such as "TEN QOGAM." To improve the effectiveness of these centers, it was suggested that individuals with disabilities be employed within them, given their intimate understanding of the unique needs and challenges faced by their peers. The participant questioned the effectiveness of existing centers that employ individuals without disabilities who may lack the requisite understanding and empathy required to effectively support this demographic.

In conclusion, the realization of an inclusive society in Kazakhstan is confronted with various challenges, encompassing issues of awareness, accessibility, and social support. Addressing these challenges necessitates a multifaceted approach, involving targeted outreach efforts, the integration of awareness-raising initiatives within existing processes like MSEC, and the active engagement of individuals with disabilities within social support centers. These measures collectively contribute to the goal of fostering an inclusive society that accommodates the needs and aspirations of all its members, regardless of their abilities or disabilities.

CONCLUSIONS

Comparative analysis reveals challenges in achieving inclusive society. Despite the earlier implementation of an inclusive society in European countries such as the United Kingdom and Spain, as well as in the United States, these nations encounter certain difficulties in its adoption. The role of the "TEN QOGAM" social support center in facilitating the inclusion of individuals with special needs into an inclusive society is substantial. This center provides legal, psychological, and social consultations, assisting service recipients in resolving their issues promptly. Beneficiaries of the center overcome gender stereotypes and transcend the boundaries of conventional norms, gaining the opportunity for self-realization and integration into various social groups. Traditional societal values and norms pertaining to masculinity and femininity complicate the favorable gender socialization of individuals with special needs.

Institutionalization is another critical issue confronting individuals with special needs from childhood. Children with disabilities face a higher risk of missed vaccinations, malnutrition, mortality, delayed school enrollment, and prolonged periods of education. Adolescents with disabilities encounter significant challenges accessing services and receiving information related to sexual and reproductive health. Often, parents have limited access to information that could assist them in providing appropriate support to their children, compounded by a lack of social support [11]. In such circumstances, an individual's socialization and gender self-identification are fraught with challenges. Firstly, societal norms and stereotypes exert a negative influence on individuals with disabilities. Gender is a social and cultural construct, while sex is a biological one. Gender identity refers to an individual's self-identification within the framework of the society they operate in. Consequently, existing stereotypes, norms, and societal values affect this process. Kazakhstan still adheres to a strongly patriarchal societal model, where traditional roles of men as providers and women as caretakers persist.

The research has identified several issues hindering the realization of an inclusive society in Kazakhstan. Firstly, organizational problems are prevalent. A significant portion of individuals

with special needs residing in Almaty learned about the existence of social support centers through acquaintances, friends, or relatives. The institutionalization of disability is a crucial stage in the development of a tolerant and progressive society. Individuals with disabilities should not feel marginalized or discriminated against. The establishment of social support centers like "TEN QOGAM" will accelerate the integration of individuals with disabilities into an inclusive society. Secondly, resource-related challenges are evident. Insufficient awareness of the operations of such centers and a lack of necessary accessibility conditions hinders the social self-perception of individuals with disabilities. Kazakhstan has adopted a policy of an inclusive society aimed at eliminating barriers to the integration of people with special needs in all aspects of society. However, the unpreparedness of urban infrastructure to accommodate the needs of individuals with disabilities remains a pressing issue today. Thirdly, problems related to the interaction between social support entities, such as the absence of proper communication between individuals with special needs and non-governmental organizations, are evident. Organizations established voluntarily by citizens or non-governmental legal entities to provide social support to individuals with disabilities will have a positive impact on the development of the civil sector.

Furthermore, the realization of an inclusive society should begin during the medical and sanitary expert commission (MSEC) process. Limited awareness among individuals with disabilities, mobility constraints, and stigmatization [12] represent significant societal issues. An inclusive society, free from discrimination and inequality, is a desirable goal. To make it a reality, the challenges associated with its implementation must be addressed.

The conducted research has raised a series of questions that will be explored more comprehensively in the future. For instance, one of these questions pertains to the study of individuals with disabilities residing in rural areas. Simultaneously, investigating this research problem in other regions of Kazakhstan holds considerable interest. The study's territorial limitations warrant extrapolation of its results to the entire country, albeit partially. People with disabilities have an equal right to live in society. Firstly, we are all citizens of the Republic of Kazakhstan. Our main task is to be tolerant towards everyone, not just individuals with disabilities. Being open to cooperation and mutual assistance is crucial. The realization of an inclusive society is a priority not only for governmental bodies but also for citizens. It is a two-way process. Kazakhstan is actively progressing towards addressing issues of gender and social inequality. Existing programs and enacted laws serve as testament to this fact. Through collective efforts of citizens and governmental bodies, the realization of an inclusive society will proceed smoothly and become a significant step in the development of a modern and progressive Kazakhstan.

REFERENCES

1. Социальная работа с инвалидами: учебное пособие / коллектив авторов; под ред. Н. Ф. Басова. — М. : КНОРУС, 2012. С.229-235.
2. Касым-Жомарт Токаев принял участие в работе юбилейного 25-го Петербургского международного экономического форума / [Электронный ресурс] // akorda.kz : [сайт]. — URL: <https://www.akorda.kz/ru/kasym-zhomart-tokaev-prinyal-uchastie-v-rabote-yubileynogo-25-go-peterburgskogo-mezhdunarodnogo-ekonomicheskogo-foruma-1754422#> (дата обращения: 16.01.2023).
3. Гендерная социология. — М.: ООО «Вариант» при участии ООО «Невский Простор», 2005. С.114-135.
4. Кули Ч.Х. Избранное: Сб. переводов / РАН. ИНИОН. Центр социал. научн.-информ. исследований. Отд. социологии и социальной психологии; сост. и переводчик В.Г. Николаев; отв. ред. Д.В. Ефременко. — М., 2019. — 234 с. — (Сер.: Теория и история социологии).

5. Ярская-Смирнова Е. Р. Социальное конструирование инвалидности // Социологические исследования. 1999. N 4.
6. Информационный портал Социальная защита лиц с инвалидностью//Статистика|inva.gov.kz (дата обращения: 11.02.2023).
7. Здравомыслова Е. А., Темкина А. А. Введение. Социальная конструкция гендера и гендерная система в России // Гендерное измерение социальной и политической активности в переходный период (сборник научных статей) / Центр независимых социальных исследований. СПб, 1996. С. 5-13.
8. Грунт Е.В. Инклюзивное образование в современной российской школе: региональный аспект // Вестник Санкт-Петербургского университета. Социология. 2019. Т. 12. Вып. 1. С. 67–81. <https://doi.org/10.21638/spbu12.2019.105> (дата обращения: 20.01.2023).
9. Murdoch G.P. Comparative Data on the Division of Labor by Sex//Social Forces. 1935. P. 551-553.
10. 17 целей для преобразования нашего мира / [Электронный ресурс] // ООН: [сайт]. — URL: <https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/ru/> (дата обращения: 22.03.2023).
11. «Анализ положения детей с инвалидностью: развитие инклюзивного общества в Республике Казахстан», - Астана, 2014, - 16 стр.
12. Goffman E. Stigma. Notes on the management of spoiled identity. London; New York: Touchstone, 1986 [1963].

Medical Sciences

Skin toxicity in chemotherapy and oncological diseases

Tolybekova A.A.

Candidate of Medical Sciences, Head of the Department of Dermatovenereology of the Kazakh-Russian Medical University of Almaty, Republic of Kazakhstan

Baikenzheyeva A.A.

resident doctor

Cancer treatment is a long and complex process, including various types of drug therapy (chemo—, hormone-, immunotherapy, targeted) in combination with radiation and surgical intervention, since in many cases it is the combined approach that allows achieving the desired effect [1].

In addition to rapidly growing and multiplying cancer target cells, antitumor drugs also affect some healthy cells of our body, also characterized by the ability to rapidly divide.

Skin toxicity is the result of the toxic effects of drugs on rapidly dividing cells. These include not only tumor cells, but also many others: cells of our hair follicles, blood, including skin and its appendages [2].

Skin toxicity is not an allergic reaction, but a side effect of ongoing therapy, which are often an indicator of the body's immune response.

The most typical manifestations of skin toxicity are [3]:

- **dryness** — dryness after chemotherapy occurs as a result of increased reactivity of the skin, it loses moisture, becomes vulnerable to aggressive environmental factors;

- **rash** — is the result of hypersensitivity, accompanied by itching (with a mild degree, when only the skin is involved in the process, rashes appear in the form of spots and nodules, outwardly resemble urticaria; in more severe cases, blisters appear on the skin, Stevens-Jones syndrome develops, involving mucous membranes and internal organs);

- **pimples and acne rashes** — occur in the form of papules, pustules and nodules, which, in addition to seborrheic zones, involve the buttocks and limbs in the process of damage;

- **erythema** followed by the formation of edema and blisters — due to the direct toxic effect of antitumor drugs (in severe cases, tissue necrosis may develop with the formation of deep ulcers);

- **radiation dermatitis** is a skin burn that forms as a response to radiation exposure, aggravated by the development of small ulcers, wetness, edema;

- **palmar-plantar syndrome** — the result of therapy with taxanes, also develops if the patient has been prescribed platinum preparations; at the same time, the skin on the hands and feet cracks, wounds appear on it, which often provoke the addition of a secondary infection;

- **photosensitization** — hypersensitivity of the skin to sunlight appears as a consequence of the toxic effects of chemotherapy drugs;

- **alopecia (baldness)** — due to the fact that most cytostatics have a depressing effect on the proliferation of hair follicle cells (depending on the individual reaction of the patient's body, it manifests from slight thinning to complete hair loss).

According to the literature, these patients most often have a deterioration in the quality of life, thereby causing discomfort and anxiety, resulting in depression [4].

Changes in the condition of the skin during radiation therapy are very common. Almost all patients undergoing radiation therapy have some temporary changes in the skin condition in the irradiation area. There may be redness, itching, dryness or discoloration of the skin. The skin may peel off or blisters may appear on it. In addition, hair loss may occur in the irradiated area [6].

Clinical experience and knowledge of the side effects of chemotherapy, targeted therapy, immunotherapy allow us to reduce and stop the manifestations of skin toxicity [5]. With the help of properly selected symptomatic therapy, we reduce rashes, itching, rash on the body, palmar-plantar syndrome and prevent their recurrence.

The purpose of the clinical study is to observe patients with skin toxic reactions.

Clinical case No. 1

Patient O.E., a 67-year-old woman, went to an outpatient appointment with a dermatologist with complaints of skin rashes, itching, wetness on both lower extremities

She has been sick for 10 years, but two years ago he was diagnosed with cancer and the skin process worsened against this background.

On examination: the general condition of the average severity due to skin lesions and itching. Consciousness is clear. Peripheral lymph nodes are not enlarged.

Status localis: The skin process is chronic, in the acute stage, symmetrical, widespread, inflammatory. On the skin of the lower extremities, against the background of stagnant diffuse hyperemia, there is swelling, pronounced infiltration, purulent discharge, there are bran-like scales.

Diagnosis: Microbial eczema.

The course of microbial eczema has acquired a widespread character, a severe course. It is difficult to respond to therapy.

Clinical case No. 2

Patient A.D., a 63-year-old woman, was admitted to an outpatient appointment with a dermatologist with complaints of rashes on the palms and soles. He is registered with an oncologist with thyroid cancer.

The appearance of these complaints is associated with the beginning of antitumor therapy.

On examination: the general condition of the average severity due to skin lesions. Consciousness is clear. The position is active. Peripheral lymph nodes are not enlarged.

Status localis: The pathological process on the skin is chronic. It is localized symmetrically on the skin of the palm surface of the hands and the plantar surface of the feet. It is presented in the form of uniformly scattered foci of keratinization of linear outlines. There are many cracks on the plantar and palm surfaces. The nail plates of the hands and feet are not changed. The mucous membranes are free from specific rashes. The hair is not changed.

Diagnosis: Palmar-plantar keratoderma.

Clinical case No. 3

Patient A.R., a man born in 1957, was admitted to a skin-venereological dispensary with complaints of skin lesions of the scalp, face, trunk, upper and lower extremities, itching in the lesions.

He has been sick for 1 year. The onset of the disease is not associated with anything. Previously, he received outpatient treatment in September 2022. The diagnosis: Erythema multiforme. He received inpatient treatment from 22.11.2022 to 02.12.2022 with diagnosis: unspecified dermatitis.

Anamnesis of life. Without features. Allergic, hereditary anamnesis are not burdened.

Objective data:

General condition of the average severity due to skin lesions and itching. Consciousness is clear. The position is active. Peripheral lymph nodes are not enlarged.

Status localis: The skin process is chronic, in the acute stage, symmetrical, widespread, inflammatory. On the skin of the scalp, face, trunk, upper and lower extremities against the background of stagnant diffuse hyperemia (in some places edematous), there is abundant peeling with large lamellar scales, pronounced infiltration, lichenification, cracks. The nail plates of the feet are changed, thickened, yellow, crumble.

The hair is not changed. Dermographism is pink.

Laboratory and diagnostic studies:

Examination: from 17.02.2023.

1. UAC: Hemoglobin 104 g/l, red blood cells - 3.98×10^{12} / l, white blood cells - 9.67×10^9 / l, platelets - 683×10^9 / l, ESR – 33 mm/h.

2. OAM: count 100ml, straw-yellow, transparent, specific gravity-1030, protein, sugar – negative.

3. TANK: ALT-2.4 units /l, AST-11.5 units / l, total bilirubin - 7.04 mmol/l, glucose 4.86mmol/L. cholesterol - 6.40 mmol/l.

4. microreaction – negative

5. feces on I / g - negative.

Instrumental research:

1. FG 15.02.2023 g – Linear pneumofibrosis of the left lung. Chronic bronchitis.

2. Ultrasound of the OBP, prostate gland from 02/27/2023 - Diffuse changes in the liver parenchyma. Signs of polypoid cholesterosis of the gallbladder. Stagnation of bile. Diffuse changes in the pancreatic parenchyma. Signs of chronic prostatitis with calcifications and areas of fibrosis.

3. Skin biopsy: The morphological picture (taking into account data on widespread itchy skin lesions) is most characteristic of inflammatory dermatosis, namely vulgar psoriasis (comparison with the presence of a psoriatic triad and the presence of a possible allergic (medicinal) or paraneoplastic nature, in which psoriasis-like dermatoses are possible, is recommended.

Diagnosis: T-cell lymphoma? Psoriatic Erythroderma?

He received inpatient treatment in the KVD from 20.02.23 – 02.03.23 (DZ: Atopic dermatitis)

Difficulties in diagnosis:

It is difficult to respond to therapy, there are no significant changes. Prednisone 60 mg / day, then correction on an outpatient basis. Consultation of an oncohematologist to exclude T-B cell lymphoma of the skin!!!

Conclusion

Skin toxic reactions occur quite often in cancer patients, and may accompany chemotherapy and targeted therapy.

Concomitant oncological diseases complicate the course of existing dermatological diseases, complicate differential diagnosis and contribute to resistance to therapy.

For differential diagnosis of skin lymphomas and erythroderma of other genesis, joint work of a dermatologist and an oncologist is necessary.

List of used literature

1. Koroleva I.A., Bolotina L.V., Gladkov O.A., Gorbunova V.A., Kruglova L.S., Manzyuk L.V., Orlova R.V., Orlova E.V. Recommendations for supportive and accompanying therapy of RUSSCO: "Practical recommendations for the drug treatment of dermatological reactions in patients receiving antitumor drug therapy" 2021, From 99-113;

2. Tkachenko E.V., Araviyskaya E.R., Gorbunova K.V., Kondratiev S.V., Katrechko K.A., Alekseeva Yu.V., Kluge V.A., Brish N.A., Semiglazova T.Yu., Semiglazov V.V., Belyaev A.M. Methodical manual: "Skin toxicity as a side effect when using modern antitumor drugs" St. Petersburg, 2019. C8-35.

3. PRACTICAL RECOMMENDATIONS FOR THE DRUG TREATMENT OF DERMATOLOGICAL REACTIONS IN PATIENTS RECEIVING ANTITUMOR DRUG THERAPY Team of authors: Koroleva I. A., Bolotina L. V., Gladkov O. A., Gorbunova V. A., Kruglova L. S., Manzyuk L. V., Orlova E. V., Orlova R. V. S. 88-101.

4. ONCOPSYCHOLOGY FOR ONCOLOGISTS AND MEDICAL PSYCHOLOGISTS MANUAL Edited by A.M. Belyaev, V.A. Chulkova, T.Yu. Semiglazova, M.V. Rogachev.

5. https://www.medestetik.ru/oncology/skin_toxicity.php

6. <https://klinikaluch.ru/posts/kozhnaya-toksichnost/>

7. <https://cpm-devita.ru/hospital/rehabilitation/kozhnaya-toksichnost/>

UDC: 616.15(574)

ORGANIZATION OF HEMATOLOGICAL CARE IN THE REPUBLIC OF KAZAKHSTAN

Arman Khozhayev

Professor, Doctor of Medical Sciences, Asfendiyarov Kazakh National Medical University, Almaty, Kazakhstan

Ramil Valiyev

Oncologist, Eskeldy Central District Hospital, Karabulak village, Kazakhstan

Makpal Sultan

General Practitioner, Karatal Central District Hospital, Ushtobe, Kazakhstan

Zhumabek Tassybekov

Oncologist, Koksou Central District Hospital, Balpyk Bi village, Kazakhstan

Meirkul Zhumabaeva

Oncologist, Panfilov Multidisciplinary Interdistrict Hospital, Zharkent, Kazakhstan

Ainur Ryspekkyzy

General Practitioner, City polyclinic №2, Taldykorgan, Kazakhstan

Yerlan Amangeldinov

Hematologist, Taldykorgan Regional Hospital, Taldykorgan, Kazakhstan

Rauan Assylbek

Oncologist-chemotherapist, Regional Multidisciplinary Clinic, Taldykorgan, Kazakhstan

The main objectives of organizations providing hematological care in an outpatient setting are:

At the primary level: planning the volume of outpatient drug provision with the participation of a hematologist, issuing prescriptions and monitoring the outpatient drug provision of patients; organizing consultations (face-to-face and remote) with hematologists and a set of necessary therapeutic and diagnostic measures for patients with blood diseases, referral for hospitalization of patients with blood diseases in accordance with clinical protocols; development of an individual rehabilitation program for patients with blood diseases in accordance with the recommendations of a hematologist and clinical protocols; organization of palliative care; generation of the necessary documents for referral to determine the degree of disability, in the manner prescribed by the rules for conducting a medical and social examination;

At the secondary level in specialized hematologists' offices, as well as medical organizations providing consultative and diagnostic assistance: primary diagnostics, including all types of necessary studies determined by clinical protocols; monitoring the effectiveness of treatment, including all types of necessary studies determined by clinical protocols; drawing up an individual follow-up program, as well as clinical protocols; formation of an outpatient drug supply plan, planning the volume of outpatient drug provision for patients with blood diseases; control over the provision of medicines to patients; providing consultations (face-to-face and remote) with hematologists and a set of necessary therapeutic and diagnostic measures for patients with

blood diseases in accordance with clinical protocols; referral for hospitalization of patients with blood diseases in accordance with clinical protocols; selection for hematopoietic stem cell transplantation, organization of necessary preparations and referrals to medical organizations providing high-tech medical services in the field of hematology; organization of consultations with the participation of hematologists and specialized specialists in accordance with clinical protocols; development of an individual rehabilitation program for patients with blood diseases in accordance with clinical protocols; organization of palliative care, including outpatient drug provision in accordance with the list of medicines and medical devices for free and (or) preferential outpatient provision for certain categories of citizens of the Republic of Kazakhstan with certain diseases (conditions);

At the secondary and tertiary levels by medical organizations providing medical care in the specialty "Hematology (adults)" in inpatient and hospital-substituting conditions: organization of specialized medical care and, with permission from the authorized body, issued in the manner prescribed by the authorized body, high-tech medical services in planned and emergency forms in accordance with clinical protocols; coordination of continuity between medical organizations of primary and secondary levels providing medical care for patients with blood diseases is carried out in the republican coordination center; participation in the examination of the quality of medical services (care) to patients with diseases of the blood and hematopoietic organs; planning and submitting proposals to the authorized body regarding the organization of hematological care for the adult population of the Republic of Kazakhstan; organization and participation in educational and scientific activities for specialists of the hematology service of the region and the Republic of Kazakhstan. Providing hematological care at primary and secondary levels on an outpatient basis

Hematological care at the primary and secondary levels on an outpatient basis is provided in the district, city, regional clinic, consultative and diagnostic office, as well as the relevant departments of multidisciplinary city, regional, departmental, republican and specialized healthcare organizations.

Prevention, primary diagnosis, as well as referral for consultation to a hematologist, referral for treatment in inpatient and hospital-substituting conditions, organization of dynamic observation, organization of palliative care, organization of outpatient drug provision in outpatient settings for patients with blood diseases who do not need specialized hematological care is carried out in primary health care organizations, at the patient's place of attachment.

When detecting primary manifestations of pathologies of the blood and hematopoietic organs, the primary health care doctor determines the need for: emergency medical care; conducting research if there is no need to provide emergency medical care in accordance with clinical protocols; exclusion of secondary manifestations of pathologies of the blood and hematopoietic organs, in the event of which the primary health care physician refers the patient for consultation with a hematologist; Referring the patient for a consultation with a hematologist in person or remotely.

A patient with primary manifestations of pathologies of the blood and hematopoietic organs is referred to a hematologist if he contacts specialists of any profile. Patients with blood diseases are subject to dynamic monitoring at the site of attachment.

Dynamic monitoring of patients with blood diseases is carried out by primary health care physicians with the involvement of a hematologist in accordance with the patient management program developed by him in accordance with clinical protocols, and also in case of their absence in accordance with the best medical practices in the field of hematology with the presence of evidence-based criteria

Patients with diseases of the blood and hematopoietic organs requiring hematological care in the form of specialized hematological medical care, high-tech medical services are removed from the register in the following cases: moving to another country or region, when changing their permanent place of residence; changes in diagnosis; death based on the final medical death certificate.

The appointment of studies to monitor the effectiveness of therapy is carried out by a primary health care physician in accordance with the conclusion of a hematologist within the framework of the guaranteed volume of free medical care.

Outpatient drug provision is carried out by primary health care doctors in accordance with the List of Medicines and Medical Devices for free and (or) preferential outpatient provision of certain categories of citizens of the Republic of Kazakhstan with certain diseases (conditions) based on the prescription of a hematologist.

Providing hematological care in inpatient and hospital-replacement conditions:

Hematological care in a hospital setting is provided in specialized departments of city, regional, departmental, and republican health care organizations licensed for the subtype of medical activity "Hematology". Hematological care in inpatient conditions is provided in a district, city clinic, consultative and diagnostic center, as well as in the relevant departments of city, regional, departmental, and republican health care organizations. In primary health care organizations, medical care in inpatient conditions for patients with blood diseases in the absence of a hematologist is provided without chemotherapy and includes the supervision of a primary health care doctor, a therapist, with the implementation of the hematologist's prescriptions for treatment and monitoring its effectiveness. Specialized care in inpatient and hospital-substituting conditions includes the provision of medical services by hematologists in the relevant departments of city, regional, departmental, and republican health care organizations for diseases of the blood and hematopoietic organs requiring hematological care in the form of specialized hematological medical care and high-tech medical services. Chemotherapy, diagnosis and treatment, and transfusion support are carried out by a hematologist. Chemotherapy for lymphoproliferative diseases may be administered by an oncologist. Specialized care is also provided by a general practitioner or oncologist, under the guidance of a hematologist, in cases where there is a shortage of specialized specialists. When providing medical care by general practitioners or oncologists, it is necessary to organize the control of a hematologist over prescriptions, interpretation of studies, development of a therapy program, and evaluation of effectiveness. Drug provision is carried out within the framework of the guaranteed volume of free medical care and (or) in the system of compulsory social health insurance in accordance with the drug formulary of the health care organization, as well as the rules for the development of drug formularies of health care organizations.

When providing hematological care in inpatient and hospital-substituting conditions, medicines purchased in accordance with the List of Medicines and Medical Products for free and (or) preferential outpatient provision for certain categories of citizens of the Republic of Kazakhstan with certain diseases (conditions) are used.

Medical indications for treatment in inpatient and inpatient conditions for patients with blood diseases are: treatment, including chemotherapy, diagnostic studies, including invasive interventions, assessment of the effectiveness of therapy, provision of transfusion support.

The provision of transfusion care in hospital-replacement conditions is carried out in accordance with the standard of transfusion care for the population of the Republic of Kazakhstan.

Surgical treatment of patients with blood diseases is carried out in specialized surgical healthcare organizations or departments, with the exception of minimally invasive interventions, when they are prescribed for health reasons.

The structural unit providing hematological care in inpatient and hospital-replacement conditions carries out: hospitalization and provision of care to patients with blood diseases according to indications in accordance with clinical protocols; providing advisory assistance to doctors and patients with manifestations of disorders of the blood system and hematopoietic organs of other structural units of the medical organization; development and implementation of measures to improve the quality of medical care and reduce hospital mortality from blood diseases; participation in advanced training of medical and nursing staff of a medical organization on the issues of prevention and provision of medical care to patients with diseases of the blood and hematopoietic organs; introduction into clinical practice of new methods of prevention, diagnosis, treatment and rehabilitation of patients with diseases of the blood and hematopoietic organs; carrying out health education work with patients and their relatives; systematic analysis of information on hospitalized patients, maintaining records and reporting documentation.

The minimum list of diagnostic services in the scope of hematological care provided by a medical organization within which a structural unit has been created that provides hematological care in inpatient and hospital-replacement conditions includes: general clinical examination; general clinical blood test, with the ability to manually count blood cells; blood chemistry; coagulogram and determination of blood coagulation factors and inhibitors to them; serological and molecular studies for the presence of infections; immunophenotyping; invasive methods of bone marrow sampling - puncture and trepanobiopsy; cytological examination of bone marrow; histological and immunohistochemical examination of bone marrow; ultrasound examination of internal organs, x-ray diagnostic methods, computed tomography; immunochemical study of blood and urine proteins; cytogenetic studies of blood and bone marrow; molecular biological methods for studying blood and bone marrow; immunological diagnostic methods during transfusion therapy; resuscitation and transfusion care services in the organization of a hospital; providing medical care for anemia and hereditary deficiencies of blood clotting factors.

LITERATURE

- 1 <https://adilet.zan.kz/rus/docs/V2100025880>

Pharmaceutical Sciences

ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЕ ЧИСЛЕННЫХ ПОКАЗАТЕЛЕЙ СЫРЬЯ VICIA NARBONENSIS L.

Т.А. Гаджибейли

Кафедра фармацевтической химии Азербайджанского Медицинского Университета

Д.С. Гафарова

Кафедра фармацевтической химии Азербайджанского Медицинского Университета

Г.Р. Зейналова

Кафедра фармацевтической химии Азербайджанского Медицинского Университета

ул. Анвер Гасымзаде 14. Баку, Аз. 1022

Азербайджанская Республика

Определение числовых показателей сырья является одним из важных условий стандартизации лекарственного растительного сырья. В рамках фармакохимического изучения видов, принадлежащих к широко распространенному во флоре Азербайджана виду *Vicia L.*, важно определить численные показатели с целью стандартизации сырья *Vicia narbonensis L.*

Цель работы: целью данного исследования является изучение численных показателей сырья *Vicia narbonensis L.*

Материал и методы: Использованное для исследования сырье *Vicia narbonensis L.* было заготовлено с Лерикского района в мае 2021 года. Определение числовых показателей (золы, нерастворимой золы в соляной кислоте, влаги и др.) в сырье проводили фармакопейными методами.

Результаты: **Определение золы-** для этого измельчают 1 г растительного сырья. Фарфоровую чашу нагревают, а затем после охлаждения взвешивают на аналитических весах. Сырье добавляют в фарфоровую чашу и тщательно нагревают сначала при низкой температуре, а затем при увеличении пламени. Горение продолжают при условии, что зола не расплавится и не прилипнет к краю чаши. Сжигание продолжают до достижения постоянного веса и, наконец, чашу с золой охлаждают в эксикаторе. Вес фарфоровой чаши определяют вместе с золой, затем путем вычитания веса фарфоровой чаши определяют постоянный вес золы

Определение количества золы, нерастворимой в соляной кислоте:

Для этого к оставшейся золе в фарфоровой посуде добавьте 2-3 мл разбавленной соляной кислоты, после добавления стакан накрывают часовым стеклом, нагревают на кипящей водяной бане в течение 10 мин, приливают 10 мл кипятка и фильтруют через фильтр, помещают обратно в тот же стакан и поджигают, определен его вес.

Определение влажности - для определения влажности растительного сырья 3 г сырья взвешивают на аналитических весах и сушат в ящике при температуре 100-105 °С, процедуру повторяют 3 раза при 30- минутный перерыв, каждую пробу взвешивают отдельно и разница между массами составляет 0,01 г, если она не слишком велика,

считается достигнутым постоянный вес. В результате было определено, что содержание влаги в сырье составило 9.04%. Таким образом, из первого 1 грамма сырья *Vicia narbonensis* после сжигания и превращения в золу получается 0,291 г остатка. При определении количества золы, нерастворимой в соляной кислоте, результат составил 0,284 г. При определении влажности получено 2,712 г сырья, взятого из 3 г, что показало, что количество влаги соответствует норме.

Заключение. Числовые показатели *Vicia narbonensis* L. определяли с целью стандартизации сырья. Определенные числовые показатели будут использованы при составлении фармакопейной статьи на сырье *Vicia narbonensis*, а также при определении идентичности сырья.

ЛИТЕРАТУРА

1. Pastor-Cavada, E., Juan, R., Pastor, J. E., Alaiz, M., Vioque, J. (2009). Fatty acid distribution in the seed flour of wild *Vicia* species from Southern Spain. *Journal of the American Oil Chemists' Society*, 86, 977–983.
2. Бойков А.А., Бабаскина Л.И., Хасаншина А.Р. и др. Изучение аминокислотного состава представителей рода *Vicia* L.// В сб: Тез. докл. XI Российского национального конгресса «Человек и лекарство». М., 2004. - С. 90-91
3. Бойков А.А., Хасаншина А.Р. Изучение химического состава представителей рода *Vicia* L.// В сб. матер, конф. «Лекарственные растения в фармакологии и фармации» 8-9 сентября 2004, Барнаул, 2004 С. So-s2.

Biological Sciences

Влияние условий размораживания на показатели всхожести и энергии прорастания семян полыни гладкой лекарственного

А.М. Муратова

НАО «Каспийский университет технологий и инжиниринга имени Ш.Есенова» Казахстан
г.Актау

Аннотация: Определены оптимальные тары для криоконсервации семян полыни гладкой и проведена оценка развития проростков при различных условиях эксперимента. Проведена оптимизация условий размораживания семенного материала полыни гладкой.

Ключевые слова: Тара, криохранение, прорастание семян

Семенной материал перед заморозкой выдерживали в растворах криопротекторов, после замораживали в жидком азоте.

Контролем выступали семена, замораживаемые без применения криопротекторов.

-быстрое размораживание на водяной бане при температуре 50-60 °С;

-медленное размораживание при комнатной температуре, 20-24 °С.

Определение жизнеспособности семян

После оттаивания семена высаживали в чашки Петри на два слоя фильтровальной бумаги для определения сохранения их жизнеспособности.

Жизнеспособность семян определяли по двум показателям - всхожесть и энергия прорастания [36.37].

Всхожесть определяли как процент проросших семян к общему числу высеянных семян. Подсчет проводили в течение 14 дней.

Энергию прорастания определяли как всхожесть на седьмой день. Данный параметр характеризует дружность прорастания и является одним из показателей сохранения жизнеспособности семенного материала.

Все эксперименты проводили в трех повторностях по 50 семян в каждой.

Изучение влияния тары на всхожесть и энергию прорастания семян полыни гладкой после криоконсервации.

Нами при выполнении исследований исследовались две тары – пластиковые пробирки и пакетики из алюминиевой фольги.

Семена партиями по 30 штук упаковывали в тары и погружали в жидкий азот. Ждали пока азот выпариться. После размораживания высевали на чашки Петри и анализировали всхожесть и динамику прорастания.

Таблица 1 - Влияние тары на всхожесть и энергию прорастания семян полыни гладкой без криопротекторов

Тара	Всхожесть %	Энергия прорастания %
Контроль AS 1	47,5±0,9	35,0±0,2
Пластик AS 2	43,85±0,4	31,25±0,4
Фольга AS 3	43,75±0,5	31,15±0,3

Результаты крио замораживания показали, что тары из пластика и фольги примерно одинаково влияют на всхожесть и энергию прорастания, однако показатели пластика незначительно выше. Но оба показателя несколько ниже контроля.

Рисунок 1 - Динамика всхожести семян полыни гладкой без использования криопротекторов в различных тарях

Влияние условий размораживания на показатели всхожести и энергии прорастания семян полыни гладкой лекарственного

Одним из важнейших условий сохранения жизнеспособности семян после замораживания в жидком азоте является правильное размораживание. Приведем факторы крио повреждения семян при неправильном размораживании:

- внутриклеточная кристаллизация;
- гипер концентрация солей;
- изменение pH;
- дегидратация;
- фазовые превращения биополимеров.

Медленное замораживание может привести к зарождению и росту кристаллов вне клетки, что приводит к образованию микроканалцев с гипер концентрированными растворами.

В присутствии высоких концентраций ионов уменьшается текучесть мембран, повышается ее жесткость и клетки обезвоживаются. Также изменяется pH, поэтому крио протекторные смеси готовят на основе буферного раствора.

Быстрое замораживание может привести к тому, что клетка не будет успеть освободиться от воды, тем самым формируя внутриклеточные кристаллы.

В нашем эксперименте изучены два варианта (таблица 5):

- медленное размораживание при комнатной температуре;
- быстрое размораживание на водяной бане.

Таблица 2 - Всхожесть и энергия прорастания семян полыни гладкой в зависимости от условий размораживания

Условия эксперимента	Всхожесть, %	Энергия прорастания, %
1	2	3
Контроль (семена без замораживания)	47,5±0,9	35,0±0,2
Семена после криоконсервации, заморозка в пластиковой таре, размораживание при комнатной температуре	43,85±0,4	31,25±0,4
Семена после криоконсервации, заморозка в фольговой таре, размораживание при комнатной температуре	43,75±0,5	31,15±0,3
Семена после криоконсервации, заморозка в пластиковой таре, размораживание на водяной бане	37,9±0,4	22,5±0,2
Семена после криоконсервации, заморозка в фольговой таре, размораживание на водяной бане	39,25±0,3	25,7±0,1

Наши результаты показали, что максимальные результаты всхожести получены в варианте опыта при замораживании семян в таре из пластика и размораживании при комнатной температуре – 43,85 %. Семена полыни гладкой после криоконсервации в таре из пластика и размораживании при комнатной температуре

В итоге эксперимента было выяснено что, оптимальными условиями размораживания является применение медленного размораживания (комнатная температура), а замораживание лучше вести в пластиковой таре.

На первом этапе мы производили замораживание без криопротекторов с использованием 2-х видов тары – пластиковые пробирки и конверты из фольги. Контролем служили семена с 1-летним сроком хранения.

На первичном этапе исследования, результаты показали, что тары из пластика и алюминиевой фольги имеют практически одинаково высокие показатели жизнеспособности семян полыни гладкой. Применение тары из фольги оказалось не столь удобным для эксперимента, в дальнейшем согласовав с научным руководителем, было решено оставить в качестве тары только пластик.

Однако, на втором этапе нами проанализировано совместное применение тары и различных условий размораживания при криоконсервации. Данные результаты позволили выявить, что максимальные результаты всхожести и энергии прорастания для семян полыни гладкой зафиксированы в варианте применения пластиковой тары и размораживания при комнатной температуре.

Замораживание семян полыни гладкой в жидком азоте позволило сохранить жизнеспособность семенного материала. Наилучшим вариантом заморозки является замораживание в пластиковой таре.

1. Лучшие результаты всхожести семян полыни гладкой отмечены при медленном размораживании - при комнатной температуре 20-24°C.

2. Использование отдельных криопротекторов и их смесей позволило повысить результаты всхожести и энергии прорастания семян полыни гладкой при криозамораживании. Наилучшие результаты получены в варианте применения глюкозы в концентрации 2,5% и смеси сахарозы 10% и пропиленгликоля 5%.

Полученные в работе результаты могут быть использованы для введения данного эндемичного вида в криогенную коллекцию растений Казахстана.

Список использованных источников.

1 Somme L. Cold adaptation in terrestrial invertebrates // Cold adapted organisms. Biotechnology, Ecology, Physiology, Enzymology and Molecular biology (Margesin R., Schinner F. eds.). – New York: Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg, 1999. – pp. 137-142.

2 Margesin R., Schinner F. Cold adopted organisms. – Germany: Springer, 1999. – 238 p.

3 Zachariassen K. E. Physiology of cold tolerance in insects // *Physiol. Rev.* – 1985. – Vol. 65. – P. 799–832.

4 Duman J.G., Wu D.W., Xu L., Tursman D., Olsen M.T. Adaptations of insects to subzero temperature // *The Quarterly Review of Biology.* – 1991. – Vol. 66. – № 4. – pp. 407-409.

5 Вечернина Н.А., Таварткиладзе О.К., Васина М.А. Микроразмножение гибридов яблони путем регенерации в культуре invitro семядолей // Биология растительных клеток in vitro и биотехнология: тез. докл. VIII межд. конф. (9–13 сентября 2003 г., Саратов). – Саратов, 2003. – С. 343–344.

6 Delinger D.L., Lee R.E., Hallman G.J., Delinger D.L. Physiology of cold sensitivity // Temperature sensitivity in insects and application in integrated pest management. – Boulder: Westview Press, 1998. – pp. 55–95.

7 Лозино-Лозинский Л.К. Очерки по криобиологии. – Л.: Наука, 1972. – 288 с.

Veterinary Sciences

Исследования изменения спроса владельцев домашних животных на услуги по учету питомцев

Бауржанова Асель Бауржановна

Магистр финансов, студент Executive MBA, КазГЮА им. Нарикбаева, Казахстан

В обществе иногда распространяется информация, которая способна вызывать сильные социальные и экономические изменения. В статье будет исследовано поведение потребителей услуг в условиях агрессивного информирования.

По данным информационной системы учета животных TANVA количество поставленных на учет животных в Республике Казахстан составляет 157 250, включая бродячих и безнадзорных особей. Из них 63% составляют собаки, 37% - кошки.

Численность домашних животных, поставленных на учет в стране равна 135 072, что составляет 86% от всех учтенных в РК животных. Из них собак - 60%, кошек - 40%.

Статус владения животными

Рисунок 1. Количество учтенных животных в Казахстане.

Количество поставленных на учет животных в городе Астана составляет 26 366, включая бродячих и безнадзорных особей. Из них собак - 58%, кошек - 42%.

Численность домашних животных, поставленных на учет в столице равна 14 593 особям, что составляет 55% от всех учтенных в Астане животных. 45% из них приходится на собак, 55% - на кошек.

Рисунок 2. Количество учтенных животных в Астане.

С начала июля 2023 года СМИ и мониторинговые агентства стали распространять информацию о том, что согласно закону “Об ответственном обращении с животными”, с 1 сентября 2023 года владельцев собак и кошек обяжут ставить своих питомцев на учет [1]. 9 августа такая же информация появилась на сайте Комитета лесного хозяйства и животного мира Министерства экологии и природных ресурсов Республики Казахстан [2].

Данная новость, а также появившаяся 12 июля на сайте Акимата города Астаны информация о том, что владельцы кошек и собак смогут бесплатно чипировать своих животных до 1 сентября 2023 года [3], спровоцировали стремительный рост спроса владельцев кошек и собак на услуги по чипированию и регистрации своих животных в учетных базах.

С 4 июля по 4 октября в Республике Казахстан владельцы домашних животных поставили на учет 41 856 питомцев в информационной системе “TANBA”, что в 13,6 раз выше, чем в предыдущие 3 месяца.

Самый большой рост услуг по учету домашних животных в стране пришелся на август - 28 213 услуг, что в 8,5 раз больше, чем в июле.

Рисунок 3. Количество учета домашних питомцев в РК.

С 4 июля по 4 октября в городе Астана владельцы домашних животных поставили на учет 10 012 питомцев, что в 5 раз выше, чем в предыдущие 3 месяца.

Самый большой рост услуг по учету домашних животных в столице пришелся на август - 7 200 услуг, что в 5,2 раз больше, чем в июле.

В июне 2023 года доля услуг по учету домашних животных в столице составляла 65% от объема услуг по учету домашних животных по всей стране.

Рисунок 3. Количество учета домашних питомцев в Астане.

Следует отметить, что после августа 2023 года объем услуг по учету домашних животных резко снизился. По всей стране объем упал в 2,9 раз. В столице объем услуг упал 5,2 раза, вернувшись на такой же уровень, как в июле.

Несмотря на то, что наблюдается рост объема учета животных, учитывая численность населения (19 899 377 человек в РК, 1 383 291 - в Астане) и растущий объем ветеринарных услуг (51,7 млрд. тг. в РК, 5,6 млрд. тг. в Астане) в сравнении с количеством поставленных на учет домашних животных, можно сделать заключение, что далеко не все владельцы ставят на учет своих питомцев[4,5].

На основе вышеуказанных данных можно сделать вывод, что информирование населения об обязательном учете собак и кошек побудило людей массово чипировать и регистрировать своих питомцев в учетных базах. Однако, после августа ажиотаж резко спал. Это может свидетельствовать о том, что владельцами кошек и собак не двигал страх получить штраф и понести ответственность. Скорее всего, они не хотели упустить возможность получить услуги по чипированию бесплатно (в городе Алматы действовала подобная акция). Также это может свидетельствовать о недоверии населения к государству, и это небезосновательно. Параллельно с оповещением через информационные ресурсы населения РК о необходимости постановки на учет кошек и собак с 1 сентября 2023 года, в СМИ стала появляться информация о том, что владельцев домашних животных будут привлекать к ответственности и штрафовать за не постановку питомцев на учет. Информационные ресурсы в этих сообщениях цитировали экспертов из государственных органов, которые в свою очередь ссылались на статьи Кодекса Республики Казахстан «Об административных правонарушениях». Однако в этих статьях не указана точная информация о штрафах владельцев животных, не поставивших питомцев на учет. Также на данный момент неизвестно о случаях штрафования владельцев кошек и собак с 1 сентября 2023 года.

На основе вышеописанных сведений можно сделать вывод, что агрессивное и недостоверное информирование населения - неэффективно в долгосрочной перспективе, а лишь может вызвать нужную реакцию на короткий период времени и привести к еще большему росту недоверия со стороны общества.

Список источников

1. Мониторинговое агентство EnergyProm. [Электронный ресурс]. URL: <https://www.energyprom.kz/ru/a/monitoring/s-1-sentyabrya-kazahstancev-obyazhustavit-domashnih-pitomcev-na-uchyot>
2. Сайт министерства экологии и природных ресурсов Республики Казахстан. [Электронный ресурс]. URL: <https://www.gov.kz/memleket/entities/forest/press/news/details/599640?lang=ru>
3. Сайт министерства экологии и природных ресурсов Республики Казахстан. [Электронный ресурс]. URL: <https://www.gov.kz/memleket/entities/astana/press/news/details/460268?lang=ru>
4. Бюро национальной статистики агентства по стратегическому планированию и реформам Республики Казахстан. [Электронный ресурс]. URL: <https://stat.gov.kz/ru/industries/social-statistics/demography/publications/6371/>
5. Мониторинговое агентство EnergyProm. [Электронный ресурс]. URL: <https://www.energyprom.kz/ru/a/monitoring/obyom-veterinarnyh-uslug-v-rk-vyros-na-18-za-god>

Physical and Mathematical Sciences

Спектры комбинационного рассеяния ионно-облученных монокристаллов GGG

Gulnara.Aralbayeva

L.N. Gumilyov Eurasian National University 10000 Kazakhstan, Astana city, 2 Satbaev st.

Zhakyp Karipbayev

L.N. Gumilyov Eurasian National University 10000 Kazakhstan, Astana city, 2 Satbaev st.

Anatoli Popov

Institute of Solid State Physics, University of Latvia, 8 Kengaraga Str., Lv-1063 Riga, Latvia

Kuat Kumarbekov

L.N. Gumilyov Eurasian National University 10000 Kazakhstan, Astana city, 2 Satbaev st.

Оксидные диэлектрики широко используются в качестве оптических материалов. Монокристаллы сложных оксидов, таких как $\text{Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}$ (YAG), YAlO_3 (YAP), $\text{Gd}_3\text{Ga}_5\text{O}_{12}$ (GGG), $\text{Y}_3\text{Fe}_5\text{O}_{12}$ (YIG) и LiNbO_3 (LNO), используются в квантовой и оптоэлектронике, а также в качестве основных матриц для сцинтилляторов и материалов для оптики в хранении информации. Их приложения предполагают высокое оптическое качество этих кристаллов [1, 2], а их пользователям особенно необходимы знания о возможности образования оптически активных центров при облучении. Как известно, эти центры могут снижать характеристики оптических материалов за счет увеличения потерь и образования паразитных каналов передачи энергии возбуждения [3].

С целью частичного устранения этого недостатка в настоящей работе были проведены исследования спектров комбинационного рассеяния монокристаллов GGG, облученных ионами Kr^{+15} с энергией 1,75 МэВ/нуклон, до флюенсов 1×10^{13} , 5×10^{13} , 1×10^{14} ион/см².

В спектрах КР (рис. 1) отчетливо наблюдается диффузное рассеяние с увеличением флюенса. Кроме того, в спектрах КР обоих облученных кристаллов появляется широкая полоса 900–1200 см⁻¹. Кроме того, наблюдается четкая эволюция КР спектров с флюенсом ионов криптона. В частности, в образце, облученном высокой плотностью энергии, полностью исчезла слабовыраженная тонкая структура в области 1350–1550 см⁻¹, а при 100–850 см⁻¹ констатировано несколько значительных изменений. Стоит обратить внимание, что GGG кристаллизуется в объемно-центрированной кубической структуре граната (пространственная группа $Ia\bar{3}d$ или O_h^{10}) с 80 атомами на примитивную элементарную ячейку. Теоретический анализ предсказывает 25 комбинационно-активных фононных мод в центре зоны Бриллюэна (точка Г): A_{1g} (3) E_g (8) и T_{2g} (14) моды симметрии точечной группы O_h^{10} для частот до ~ 900 см⁻¹ [4]. Назначение мод КР, экспериментальные и расчетные частоты комбинационных активных фононов [5], а также наши собственные результаты собраны в таблице 4-4. Частоты комбинационных активных фононов, экспериментально определенные в настоящей работе для GGG, совпадают с таковыми из [4], значения частот уменьшаются в облучаемых образцах в зависимости от флюенса. По мере увеличения флюенса повышается аморфизация поверхности монокристаллов.

Таблица 1. Моды КР, экспериментальные и расчетные частоты комбинационного рассеяния активных фононов (см^{-1}) и их изменение после облучения.

Мод	Эксперимент [5]	Теория [5]	Необлученный	10^{13} ион/ см^2	5×10^{13} ион/ см^2	10^{14} ион/ см^2
E_g	111.8	110.3	112.2	112.2	112.2	112.2
T_{2g}	156.6	147.9	156.8	156.8	156.8	156.8
T_{2g}	170.3	156.1	170.3	170.3	170.3	170.3
T_{2g}	180.3	184.7	179.9	179.9	179.9	179.9
T_{2g}	239.8	225.6	239.5	239.5	239.5	239.5
E_g	261.0	251.4	260.5	260.5	260.5	260.5
T_{2g}	274.0	292.6	273.9	273.9	273.9	273.9
A_{1g}	354.5	319.6	355.5	355.5	355.5	355.5
T_{2g}	381.1	357.0	381.9	381.9	381.9	381.9
T_{2g}	411.8	438.0	412	412	412	412
A_{1g}	525.0	516.8	523.9	523.9	523.9	523.9
T_{2g}	583.0	593	583	584.8	583	583
T_{2g}	598.8	606.1	597.7	597.7	597.7	597.7
T_{2g}	740.4	739.0	741.7	741.7	741.7	741.7
T_{2g}	-	-	888.7	888.7	888.7	888.7

Рисунок 1. Спектры КР необлученных и облученных ионами криптона кристаллов GGG

1. Krasnikov A., Luchechko A., Mihokova E., Nikl M., Syvorotka I. I., Zazubovich S., Zhydachevskii Y. Origin of Bi³⁺-related luminescence in Gd₃Ga₅O₁₂:Bi epitaxial films // Journal of Luminescence. – 2017. – Vol. 190. – P. 81-88.
2. Luchechko A., Kostyk L., Varvarenko S., Tsvetkova O., Kravets O. Green-Emitting Gd₃Ga₅O₁₂: Tb³⁺ Nanoparticles Phosphor: Synthesis, Structure, and Luminescence // Nanoscale Research Letters. – 2017. – Vol. 12, № 1. – P. 1-6.
3. Sun Q., Piao R. Q., Wang Y., Zhang Z. B., Zhang D. L. Optical and Judd-Ofelt spectroscopic study of Er³⁺/Pr³⁺-codoped Gd₃Ga₅O₁₂ crystal // Journal of Alloys and Compounds. – 2019. – Vol. 783. – P. 836-840.
4. Costantini J. M., Miro S., Beuneu F., Toulemonde M. Swift heavy ion-beam induced amorphization and recrystallization of yttrium iron garnet // Journal of Physics: Condensed Matter. – 2015. – Vol. 27, № 49. – P. 496001.
5. Papagelis K., Arvanitidis J., Vinga E., Christofilos D., Kourouklis G. A., Kimura H., Ves S. Vibrational properties of (Gd_{1-x}Y_x)₃Ga₅O₁₂ solid solutions // Journal of Applied Physics. – 2010. – Vol. 107, № 11. – P. 113504-113504.

Culturology

THE ART OF KAZAKHSTAN AND THE CREATIVE INDUSTRY

Mussabayev Kuat

Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor of the Department of "Art Management and Production", T.K. Zhurgenov Kazakh National Academy of Arts, Republic of Kazakhstan, Almaty

In the study of the development of the creativity of the art of our country, it requires increased attention and careful analysis. We are faced with the question of how we can build a strategy to achieve effectiveness and influence the course of the creative economy in Kazakhstan. After all, it is worth noting that without systematic state support for the creation of appropriate programs to ensure the sustainable development of this industry, it is difficult to imagine the development of the creative industry. A thorough analysis is required for the implementation of innovative forms of socio –cultural activities. And here the main role is played by education as a foundation for the development of scientific creativity among young scientists and artists of Kazakhstan.

A new stage in the development of society has begun, the whole world is on the verge of colossal changes. Universities should be one of the pillars of the development of talents and a communicative platform for the interaction of science and the creative industry. On the scale of the state, higher education institutions play the role of custodians, creators and distributors of knowledge, contribute to the enrichment of people and society. And here I would like to touch on the topic of creating a platform for cooperation between universities and organizations of the creative industry. The essence of the interaction is to create a business incubator and an acceleration platform. Within the walls of which work will take place on the creation of products of the creative industry. It is important to develop a platform for closer interaction between creative universities and enterprises of the creative industry of the country. The exchange of scientific knowledge and experience will be useful for compiling an algorithm for scientific research and training highly specialized personnel in the creative industry.

The business incubator's activities are implemented at three interrelated and interdependent levels:

1. Identification implies holding contests of innovative ideas, proposals and projects among students who are potentially capable of innovative and entrepreneurial activity.
2. Development includes assistance in preparing projects for participation in incubation competitions, providing consulting assistance on all aspects of bringing promising ideas and projects to the level of additional training of students
3. The use provides for the implementation of projects, contests of coursework and other research works to ensure obligations to incubated enterprises, as well as the introduction of innovative projects that have passed the competitive selection to the level of self-sufficiency

The incubator's work plan at the initial stage consists of the following areas: Forming an incoming funnel of projects, Accepting applications from potential residents. Further work with residents is divided into the following blocks: Training program for residents, Detailed study of the business model, Mentoring, Internal, expert and investor Pitches, Commercialization, scaling, Release from the business incubator.

The key resources of the university business incubator include: the image of the educational institution, the scientific potential and intellectual developments of the university, the laboratory and research base, the location of the business incubator and the classroom fund of the university, the absence of the need for the maintenance of support staff (Studios, theater, accounting, economic department, etc.), the Society of experts, mentors and industry specialists, Students and undergraduates, future specialists professionals.

The modernization of modern art in Kazakhstan consists in the constant change of the art paradigm, which ensures the continuity of the development of science and scientific creativity. And here it is worth noting the branch of pedagogical science based on the fusion of pedagogy and art – art pedagogy. The pedagogical process formed on the basis of art pedagogy with new methods and processes will give an opportunity to move away from the conservative approach and discover the know-how in creativity. The main point is the complementarity of pedagogy and art, which in turn will increase the effectiveness of modern education. That is, the generator in this case is art, it makes it possible, thanks to artistic and imaginative thinking, to deepen knowledge in any of the sciences. Integration of this level will also help in the process of inclusive education. After all, we must not forget that talent does not choose and does not sort, it prevails in each of us and is waiting in the wings. The task of universities is to launch all the mechanisms of the educational process to create an absolutely new and perfect "creative and innovative space" that meets world requirements under the means of modernization of the education system. By creating the appropriate conditions, we will achieve those requirements of the XXI century that will help us adapt to a rapidly changing world. It is worth noting these skills that we will need in modern society:

1. Critical thinking;
2. Communication;
3. Prompt and high-quality problem solving;
4. Emotional Intelligence;
5. Leadership;
6. Self-regulation;
7. Teamwork;
8. Creativity.

The potential for the development of the creative industry in modern society is very great and the need for divergent thinking individuals has existed at all times. During its formation, our country set not one task for the development of the creative environment, the creation of a real creative force, not subject to imitation, but creating their own individual handwriting. That's what is important to us at the current level of development of art and science. It is worth noting that the monetization of creativity has opened up new opportunities for the creative industry to involve business, which has become a platform for it to create design, cultural and other creative products. After all, in many ways the success of a company depends on high-quality creativity and is also an important tool for achieving the business goals they have built in the future. It should be noted that educational activities play a significant role, which is aimed at popularizing and promoting the achievements of art and science, which in turn will make it possible to increase social interest. But, the subject of the study himself must participate in this process by carrying out a number of activities. At the current level of development in the context of globalization, there are many tools such as information technologies that allow you to efficiently and quickly transfer this or that information. I would like to emphasize that journalism also plays a significant role, which acts as a means of expressing creativity.

The creation of large international platforms for the development of creativity and the possibility of demonstrating both their own and foreign representatives of art, would contribute to the development of creative science. It is important that the dematerialization of the object

(performances and happenings) should involve and fascinate the viewer, a certain underground on the site of art would have made a tremendous success and would remain in memory for a long time. It is necessary to develop, support and broadcast creative opportunities to the whole world.

The artists who set the vector of development and determine the movement of the creative sector of culture undoubtedly have talent and love for their work, contribute to the promotion and popularization of art and science research.

Proceedings of the 4th International Scientific Conference «Academics and
Science Reviews Materials» (October 5-6, 2023). Helsinki, Finland, 2023.
239p

editor@publisher.agency

<https://publisher.agency>

University of Helsinki

Norra Larsmovägen 91,

70800, Helsinki, Finland